

**LIMNOLOGICAL STUDY OF LAKE TANGANYIKA,
AFRICA WITH SPECIAL EMPHASIS ON
PISCICULTURAL POTENTIALITY**

Lambert Niyoyitungiye

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“LIMNOLOGICAL STUDY OF LAKE TANGANYIKA, AFRICA WITH SPECIAL EMPHASIS ON PISCICULTURAL POTENTIALITY”

**A THESIS SUBMITTED TO ASSAM UNIVERSITY FOR
PARTIAL FULFILLMENT OF THE REQUIREMENT
FOR THE DEGREE OF DOCTOR OF PHILOSOPHY
IN LIFE SCIENCE AND BIOINFORMATICS**

By

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from Mizoram University, Aizawl**

Defence date: 17th September, 2019

To
Almighty and merciful God

&

To
My beloved parents with love

DECLARATION

I, **Lambert Niyoyitungiye**, bearing registration number, Ph.D/3038/2016, dated 09.09.2016, hereby declare that the subject matter of the thesis entitled: *“Limnological Study of Lake Tanganyika, Africa with Special Emphasis on Piscicultural Potentiality”* is the record of the work done by me and that the contents of this thesis did not form the basis for award of any degree/ diploma to me or to anybody else to the best of my knowledge. The thesis has not been submitted previously to any other University/ Institute for obtaining any degree. The thesis is being submitted to Assam University for the degree of Doctor of Philosophy in Life Science & Bioinformatics.

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I myself and on behalf of the Co-supervisor **Prof. Bhanu Prakash Mishra**, Department of Environmental Science, Mizoram University, Aizawl, India do certified that the thesis entitled: ***“Limnological Study of Lake Tanganyika, Africa with Special Emphasis on Piscicultural Potentiality”*** for award of the Doctor of Philosophy in Life Science and Bioinformatics is the outcome of a bonafide research work. This work has not been submitted previously for any other degree of this or any other University. It is further certified that the candidate has complied with all the formalities as per the requirement of Assam University. I recommend that the thesis may be placed in front of the examiners for consideration of award of the degree of this University.

Dated **Silchar**

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CONTENTS

	<u>Page Numbers</u>
CHAPTER-I INTRODUCTION.....	1-7
I.1 Background and Motivation of the Study	1
I.2 Objectives of the Study	7
CHAPTER-II REVIEW OF LITERATURE	8-46
II.1 Major African Lakes	8
II.1.1 Great Lakes.....	8
II.1.2 History of Geological formation of African lakes.....	10
II.2 Hydrographical Network of Burundi	11
II.2.1 Lake Tanganyika.....	13
II.2.1.1 Origin and evolution	13
II.2.1.2 Geographical Situation.....	15
II.2.1.3 Watersheds of Lake Tanganyika.....	18
II.2.1.4 Tributaries of Lake Tanganyika.....	20
II.2.1.4.1 Malagarazi River	20
II.2.1.4.2 Rusizi River.....	20
II.2.1.4.3 Other tributaries on Burundian coast	21
II.2.1.5 Climatic Conditions.	21
II.2.1.6 Biotope of Lake Tanganyika.	23
II.2.1.7 Biodiversity of Lake Tanganyika	24
II.2.1.7.1 General Considerations	24
II.2.1.7.2 Ichtyofauna of Lake Tanganyika	27
II.2.1.7.2.1 Cichlids Fish.....	27
II.2.1.7.2.2 Non-cichlids Fish.....	27
II.2.1.8 Fishing typology in Lake Tanganyika.....	27
II.2.1.8.1 Customary Fishing.....	29
II.2.1.8.2 Artisanal fishing	30
II.2.1.8.3 Industrial fishing.....	30

II.2.1.9	Main threats of Lake Tanganyika	30
II.2.1.9.1	Pollution	30
II.2.1.9.1.1	General Considerations	30
II.2.1.9.1.2	Sedimentary Pollution	31
II.2.1.9.1.3	Urban and Industrial wastes.....	33
II.2.1.9.2	Overfishing and use of destructive gears.....	35
II.2.1.9.3	Increase of human population.....	36
II.2.1.9.4	Eutrophication.....	37
II.3	Brief overview on pisciculture concept.....	40
II.3.1	Definition and Background	40
II.3.2	Quality of water suitable for pisciculture	42
II.3.3	Standards of water quality required in fish culture.....	43
CHAPTER-III MATERIALS AND METHODS.....		47-110
III.1	Study area description	47
III.1.1	Geographical situation	47
III.1.2	Climate	48
III.1.3	Morphology, geology and pedology	48
III.1.4	Hydrography.....	48
III.1.5	Description of the sampling stations.....	49
III.1.5.1	Kajaga site.....	50
III.1.5.2	Nyamugari site.....	50
III.1.5.3	Rumonge site	51
III.1.5.4	Mvugo site	52
III.2	Sampling, field data collection and Laboratory analysis	52
III.2.1	Physico-chemical analyses	52
III.2.1.1	Potential of Hydrogen	54
III.2.1.2	Temperature	55
III.2.1.3	Dissolved Oxygen and percent of Oxygen saturation	57
III.2.1.4	Electrical Conductivity.....	58
III.2.1.5	Total Dissolved Solids	59

III.2.1.6	Turbidity.....	59
III.2.1.7	Chlorides Ions.....	60
III.2.1.8	Total Alkalinity	63
III.2.1.9	Total Hardness, Calcium hardness and Magnesium hardness.....	66
III.2.1.10	Chemical Oxygen Demand.....	69
III.2.1.11	Biochemical Oxygen Demand	72
III.2.1.12	Total Carbon, Total Organic Carbon and Total Nitrogen	76
III.2.1.13	Total Phosphorus	79
III.2.1.14	Heavy Metals.....	82
III.2.2	Biological analysis.....	88
III.2.2.1	Determination of Chlorophyll a	88
III.2.2.2	Bacteriological analysis	92
III.2.2.3	Sampling and taxonomic identification of fish species	95
III.2.2.4	Planktonic population analysis.....	97
III.2.2.5	Species biodiversity measurement.....	103
III.2.2.5.1	Alpha diversity.....	103
III.2.2.5.2	Beta diversity	107
III.3	Statistical Analysis.....	109
CHAPTER-IV EXPERIMENTAL FINDINGS.....		111-201
IV.1	Physico-chemical parameters.....	111
IV.1.1	Physical parameters.....	115
IV.1.2	Chemical parameters	118
IV.1.3	General considerations on correlation (r) between variables ..	131
IV.1.3.1	Pearson's correlation among physico-chemical variables	132
IV.1.3.2	Principal Components Analysis (PCA).....	135
IV.1.4	Effect of study stations on the variation of physico-chemical parameters	139
IV.1.5	Determination of trophic and pollution status of the water.....	150

IV.1.5.1	Trophic status	150
IV.1.5.2	Pollution status	156
IV.1.5.2.1	BOD and COD Status	157
IV.1.5.2.2	Use of Organic Pollution Index IPO and the Method of the Institute of Hygiene and Epidemiology.....	159
IV.2	Biological characteristics	162
IV.2.1	Chlorophyll-a	163
IV.2.2	Bacteriological Characteristics	164
IV.2.3	Planktonic population analysis	166
IV.2.3.1	Phytoplanktons analysis	167
IV.2.3.2	Zooplanktons analysis	171
IV.2.3.3	Correspondence Factor Analysis.....	174
IV.2.3.4	Planktons in aquatic food chain	176
IV.2.3.5	Effect of physico-chemical attributes of water on the abundance of Planktonics communities.....	177
IV.2.3.6	Planktonic species diversity analysis	180
IV.2.3.6.1	Alpha diversity study	180
IV.2.3.6.2	Beta diversity study.....	184
IV.2.4	Fish diversity in relation to pollution	186
IV.2.4.1	Taxonomic diversity of fish species in sampling stations..	186
IV.2.4.2	Interaction between sampling stations, physico-chemical and biological parameters.....	193
IV.2.4.2.1	Effect of change in physico-chemical and biological attributes of water on the abundance of fish species.....	193
IV.2.4.2.2	Effect of pollutants on fish diversity, distribution and identification of pollution indicator fish.	195
IV.2.4.2.3	Similarity between fish species richness of sampling stations.....	198
IV.2.4.2.4	Effect of the sampling sites on the abundance of fish species.....	200

CHAPTER-V DISCUSSION	202-230
V.1 Physico-chemistry of waters	202
V.2 Biological community	222
V.2.1 Algal biomass.....	222
V.2.2 Bacterial community	223
V.2.3 Zooplanktons Population.....	225
V.2.4 Phytoplanktons Population.....	228
FINDINGS SUMMARY AND RECOMMENDATIONS.....	231-239
BIBLIOGRAPHY.....	240-267
PUBLICATIONS.....	268-272
CONFERENCES ATTENDED.....	273-274
ANNEXURES.....	I-XXXI

LIST OF TABLES

	<u>Page Numbers</u>
Table 1: Major events of geological changes in Great Lakes Region.	10
Table 2: Burundian Lakes and their geographical locations.....	13
Table 3: Physiographic statistics of Lake Tanganyika.....	16
Table 4: Distribution of the Waters of Lake Tanganyika per country.....	18
Table 5: Biodiversity components of Lake Tanganyika	26
Table 6: Fishing beaches of Lake Tanganyika on Burundian shoreline	28
Table 7: Pollution sources in Lake Tanganyika catchment	31
Table 8: Water quality required in pisciculture	43
Table 9 : Geographical location of the study sites.....	50
Table 10: Analytical methods adopted to determine quality of lake water.	53
Table 11: Influence of temperature on dissolved oxygen	55
Table 12: Maximum concentration of dissolved oxygen according to temperature	58
Table 13: Potential Matrix Modifiers for Graphite furnace AAS.....	88
Table 14: Spatio-temporal variation in physical and chemical characteristics of water.....	112
Table 15: Descriptive statistics of physico-chemical parameters and water quality required for pisciculture.....	113
Table 16 : Average results of physico-chemical parameters in comparison to the Standards of water quality required for pisciculture.....	114
Table 17: Desirable range of heavy metals dose recommended for pisciculture	129
Table 18: Strength of relationship between variables	131
Table 19: Correlation Coefficient (r) among physical and chemical parameters of Lake Tanganyika.....	132

Table 20: One-way ANOVA to assess the effect of the sampling sites on the variation of physico-chemical variables.	140
Table 21 : Tukey's HSD multiple comparison test for the differences of pairwise averages values of the physico-chemical variables among the sampling stations.....	144
Table 22: Tukey's HSD showing Homogeneous subsets of the average values of the physico-chemical variables at sampling Stations	148
Table 23 : Carlson's trophic state index values for lakes classification in comparison with results obtained for Lake Tanganyika.	152
Table 24: Limit values for the trophic status of water according to international classification systems.	153
Table 25: Trophic status of the sampled sites water of Lake Tanganyika in comparison to international classification systems.	154
Table 26 : Trophic status of Lake Tanganyika.	154
Table 27: Pollution status of the sampled stations	159
Table 28: Limit classes of parameters used for IPO calculation.....	160
Table 29: Limit Classes of used Parameters for IHE Calculation.....	160
Table 30: Organic pollution status of the water at the sampling stations.	161
Table 31: Biological characteristics in comparison to the International Standards of water quality suitable for fish culture.	163
Table 32: Qualitative and quantitative results of phytoplankton population... ..	169
Table 33: Qualitative and quantitative results of zooplanktons population.... ..	172
Table 34: Planktonic species diversity indices	181
Table 35: Correlation between zooplankton diversity indices	183
Table 36: Correlation between phytoplankton diversity indices.....	183
Table 37: Jaccard's Similarity Index of Plankton species among sampling stations.....	185

Table 38: Sorensen's Similarity Index of Plankton Species among sampling stations.....	186
Table 39: Fish species diversity at sampling sites	189
Table 40: Correlation between fish species abundance and physico-chemical variables and planktons abundance.	193
Table 41: Identification and distribution of fish species based on acclimation level to pollution.....	196
Table 42: Pollution status of the sampling stations and Fish acclimation level to pollution.....	197
Table 43: Similarity coefficient between fish species composition at sampling stations.....	198
Table 44: ANOVA-I showing the effect of sampling sites on fish species number	201
Table 45 : Tukey's HSD multiple comparison test for the differences of pairwise averages amount of fish species among the sampling stations.....	201
Table 46: Tukey's HSD showing Homogeneous subsets of averages at sampling Stations.	201

LIST OF FIGURES

	<u>Page Numbers</u>
Figure 1: Map showing the African Great Lakes region.....	9
Figure 2: Map showing the hydrographical network of Burundi	12
Figure 3: Geographical situation of Lake Tanganyika.....	17
Figure 4: Map representing the watershed of Lake Tanganyika	19
Figure 5: Graphic representation of the thermal stratification of Lakes.....	22
Figure 6: Categories of life zones in lakes	24
Figure 7: Photo showing the lake sedimentary pollution further to rainy erosion.....	32
Figure 8: Sewage flowing into Lake Tanganyika from AFRITAN Company.	34
Figure 9: Algal blooms with green colour of Lake Tanganyika water	39
Figure 10: Encroachment by <i>Eichhornia crassipes</i> (water hyacinth) on the shores of Lake Tanganyika, in kibenga quarter.....	39
Figure 11: Maps showing the study areas and sampling stations location	49
Figure 12: Measuring of physico-chemical parameters in the laboratory..	54
Figure 13: Measuring of Temperature, pH, Electrical conductivity and Transparency on-spot	54
Figure 14: Evolution of dissolved oxygen as a function of temperature at 960 mbar according to Benson and Krause (1984).	56
Figure 15 : Graph illustrating TC calibration curve obtained with TOC-L/ASI-L	77
Figure 16: Graph illustrating TN calibration curve obtained with TOC-L/ASI-L	78
Figure 17: Graph illustrating TOC calibration curve obtained with TOC-L / ASI-L	78
Figure 18: Basic components of Flame AAS	83

Figure 19: Basic components of a Graphite Furnace AAS	85
Figure 20: Microorganisms counting process	95
Figure 21: Group interview with local fishermen at Kajaga station. The big fish caught is named <i>dinotopterus tanganicus</i> (Isinga).....	96
Figure 22: Planktons collection by filtering through a cloth net.....	97
Figure 23: Sedgwick-Rafter counting cell	102
Figure 24: Lackey's drop method Cell	102
Figure 25: Observation of Plankton cells under light microscope, OLYMPUS BX60.....	102
Figure 26 : Spatio-temporal variation of Turbidity (A), Temperature (B), Transparency(C) and Total Dissolved Solids (D).	117
Figure 27 : Spatio-temporal variation of Oxygen Percent Saturation (A), Chemical Oxygen Demand (B) and Biochemical Oxygen Demand(C).....	126
Figure 28: Spatio-temporal variation of pH (A), Total Alkalinity (B), Electrical Conductivity (C), Chloride (D), Total Hardness (E) and Calcium (F).....	127
Figure 29 : Spatio-temporal variation of Magnesium (A), Iron (B), Total Carbon (C), Total Nitrogen (D), Total Phosphorus (E) and Dissolved Oxygen (F).....	128
Figure 30: Spatio-temporal fluctuation of heavy metals concentration	130
Figure 31: Strength of relationship between variables.....	131
Figure 32: PCA Graph of Sampling sites observations.....	136
Figure 33: PCA Circle of correlations between physico-Chemical parameters	137
Figure 34: PCA biplot showing relation between sampling sites and Physico-chemical parameters.	138
Figure 35: Proliferation of aquatic plants in Lake Tanganyika, indicator of eutrophication.....	155
Figure 36: Water body pollution by untreated wastewaters discharge....	156

Figure 37: Spatio-temporal variation of Chlorophyll-a content	164
Figure 38: Spatial variation of coliforms bacteria amount	166
Figure 39: Relative diversity index of phytoplankton families (A), species richness & Cumulative abundance of phytoplankton individuals (B), density of phytoplankton species (C) and individuals (D) by station and family	168
Figure 40: Relative diversity index of zooplankton families (A), species richness & Cumulative abundance of zooplankton individuals (B), density of zooplankton species (C) and individuals (D) by station and family.	173
Figure 41: CFA plot showing linkages between: (A) Sampling sites and phytoplanktons species; (B) Sampling sites and phytoplanktons families; (C) Sampling sites and zooplanktons species ;(D)Sampling sites and zooplanktons families.	175
Figure 42: Total abundance of plankton species at the sampling sites.....	177
Figure 43: Canonical Correlation Analysis (CCorA) bi-plot showing relationship between the environmental parameters and phytoplankton composition at sampling sites.	178
Figure 44: Canonical Correlation Analysis biplot showing relationship between the environmental parameters and zooplankton composition at sampling sites.....	179
Figure 45: Relative diversity index of families.....	188
Figure 46: Fish species distribution per orders	188
Figure 47: Species richness per sampling sites.....	189
Figure 48: The fish species representing each family and order.	192
Figure 49: Diagrams showing different groups of Coliform bacteria	223
Figure 50: Types of algae depending on the time of year.....	230

ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

°C	: Degree Celsius
AAS	: Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometry
AFNOR	: Association Française de Normalisation
AFRITAN	: African Tannery Company-
ANOVA-1	: One-way ANalysis Of Variance
APHA	: American Public Health Association
ASTM	: American Society for Testing and Materials or American Standards for Testing of Materials
BIS	: Bureau of Indian Standards
BOD	: Biochemical Oxygen Demand
BPW	: Buffered Peptone water
CCorA	: Canonical Correlation Analysis
CFA	: Correspondence Factor Analysis
CFU	: Colony Forming Units
Chl.a	: Chlorophyll a
COD	: Chemical Oxygen Demand
CPUE	: Catch per Unit Effort
CVRB	: Comité de Valorisation de la Rivière Beauport
DC	: District of Columbia (Washington)
Defra	: Department for Environment Food and Rural Affairs
DO	: Dissolved Oxygen
DRC	: Democratic Republic of Congo
EC	: Electrical Conductivity
EDTA	: Ethylene diamine tetra acetic acid
FAAS	: Flame Atomic Absorption Spectroscopy
FAO	: Food and Agricultural Organisation
GFAAS	: Graphite Furnace Atomic Absorption Spectrometry
GFF	: Glass Fiber Filters
HP	: Horsepower
HSD test	: Honestly Significant Difference test

IBGE	: Institut Bruxellois pour la Gestion de l'Environnement
ICAR	: Indian Council for Agricultural Research
IHE	: Institut d'Hygiène et d'Epidémiologie
IHE	: Institute of Hygiene and Epidemiology
IPO	: Organic pollution index
ISI	: Indian Statistical Institute
ISSN	: International Standard Serial Number
MBAS	: Methylene Blue Active Substances
MDDEP	: Ministère du Développement durable, de l'Environnement et des Parcs
MDTEE	: Ministère en charge du Développement Territorial, de l'Eau et de l'Environnement
MINATTE	: Ministère de l'Aménagement du Territoire du Tourisme et de l'Environnement
NA	: Not Applicable
NAS	: National Academy of Science
NEH	: North Eastern Hill
NIST	: National Institute of Standards and Technology (a unit of the U.S. Commerce Department formerly known as the National Bureau of Standards)
NO.L⁻¹	: Number of Organisms per Liter
NR	: Not Recommended
NRAC	: Northeastern Regional Aquaculture Center
NTU	: Nephelometric Turbidity Unit
OD	: Optical Density
OECD	: Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development
OPI	: Organic Pollution Index
p	: p-value: Probability
PA	: Phenolphthalein Alkalinity
PCA	: Plate Count Agar
PCA	: Principal Component Analysis
PCRWR	: Pakistan Council of Research in Water Resources
pH	: Potential of Hydrogen

Ppb	: parts per billion
ppm	: parts per million
RDC	: Democratic Republic of Congo
RN	: Route Nationale
RSC	: Residual Sodium Carbonate
SAR	: Sodium Adsorption Ratio
SD	: Standard Deviation
SDD	: Secchi disc depth
SPSS	: Statistical Package for the Social Sciences
SRAC	: Southern Regional Aquaculture Centre
SRS	: Sum of Residues Squares
TA	: Total alkalinity
TANESCO	: Tanzania Electric Supply Company
TC	: Total Carbon
TDS	: Total Dissolved Solids
TN	: Total Nitrogen
TOC	: Total Organic Carbon
TP	: Total Phosphorus
TSI	: Trophic Status Indices
TSS	: Total Suspended solids
U.S	: United States
UNDP	: United Nations Development Program
UNECE	: United Nations Economic Commission for Europe
USDA	: United States Department of Agriculture
USEPA	: United States Environmental Protection Agency
USGA	: United States Golf Association
US-NGA	: United States National Geospatial-Intelligence Agency
USRSL	: United States Regional Salinity Laboratory
WHO	: World Health Organization
WWF	: World Wide Fund

ABSTRACT

The water of Lake Tanganyika is subject to changes in physicochemical characteristics resulting in the deterioration of water quality to a great pace. The present investigation was carried out on Lake Tanganyika at 4 sampling sites and aimed to assess the water quality with reference to (i) its suitability for fish culture purposes, (ii) determining the trophic and pollution status of the sampled stations, (iii) assessing the qualitative and quantitative pattern of planktons diversity as fish food, (iv) establishing an inventory and taxonomic characterization of fish species diversity and (v) highlighting the effect of pollutants on the abundance and spatial distribution of fish species.

The physico-chemical and biological parameters of water samples were compared to desirable and acceptable international standards for fish culture and the results of comparative analysis indicated that the Lake has a high fish potential as the most important of the water quality parameters were suitable for fish culture. The investigation revealed the occurrence of 75 species belonging to 7 different orders and 12 families in all sampling sites and among the different species recorded, those belonging to the order Perciformes and the family Cichlidae were most dominant.

The values of transparency, chlorophyll a and total phosphorus were indicative of eutrophication phenomenon. Besides, Kajaga and Nyamugari stations were found heavily polluted while Rumonge and Mvugo Stations were moderately polluted and for this purpose, three categories of fish species have been distinguished, depending on their adaptation level to pollution: polluosensitive species, polluotolerant species and polluoresistant species.

With respect to planktons community results, it was found that all the values obtained were within the permissible limits recommended in pisciculture and, the abundance and diversity of phytoplankton species were far greater than those of zooplankton species with 115 species belonging to 7 different families for phytoplanktons against 10 species belonging to 4 families for zooplankton population in all sampling stations.

Keywords: Water quality, Lake Tanganyika, Fish abundance and Planktons diversity.

CHAPTER-I INTRODUCTION

I.1 Background and Motivation of the Study

Life thrives in water and it is not surprising that the first life originated in water where water was the principal external as well as internal medium for the organisms. 71% of the earth is covered by water of which more than 95% is in gigantic oceans. The smallest amount of water is found in rivers (0.00015%) and lakes (0.01%) and includes the most valuable freshwater resources ([Ramachandra et al., 2006](#)). An aquatic ecosystem includes all lotic systems such as rivers and streams and lentic systems like oceans, lakes, bays, swamps, marshes and ponds along with the biota in them.

Aquatic habitats provide the entire gamut of services essential for sustenance of life in it. Aquatic biodiversity is the rich and diverse spinning through all the trophic levels from primary producer algae to tertiary consumers large fishes. Aquatic food webs are complex with intermediaries like zooplankton, small and medium fishes, aquatic insects and amphibians among the most noted ones. In addition, a limited but diverse group of aquatic plants do play important role in the functioning of the aquatic ecosystems.

The quality and diversity of aquatic life forms depend upon the physico-chemical characteristics of the water such as temperature, salinity, oxygenation, flow velocity, light penetration, nature and abundance of nutrients, and last but not the least, the quantity and sustenance of water. Therefore, the species diversity in the ecosystem is the reflection of the

environment quality. The indicators used are species abundance, population density, age and size distribution and/or species composition. The diversity of aquatic environments therefore offers a great diversity of habitats which influences the biodiversity of these environments.

Aquatic ecosystems provide a variety of goods and services to humans, giving them an irreplaceable economic value (Gleick,1993; Costanza et al., 1997). Continental waters, as a source of livelihood, attract dense colonization of human habitats around. Therefore, these habitats require strict management practices to ensure their sustainability. Contrary to this fact, the aquatic resources, particularly the freshwater ecosystems across the world are facing serious pollution problems due to various anthropogenic activities. The indiscriminate disposal of waste effluents, population growth, the rise of industrialization and increasing use of fertilizers and phytosanitary products in agriculture are among the major causes of pollution of water reservoirs (Singh et al., 2004, Vega et al., 1996, Sillanappa et al., 2004).

Among the fresh water resources, the lentic systems are most vulnerable to anthropogenic activities as they act as sinks for sewage and waste disposal while the lotic systems such as streams and rivers act as drains for the removal of waste to the sea. Human economic activities are undoubtedly the single most important cause of stress in aquatic ecosystems (Vazquez and Favila, 1998; Dokulil et al., 2000; Tazi et al., 2001). The distribution of organisms colonizing aquatic environments, as a matter of fact, is a self-evolving process (Vannote et al, 1980, Dolédec et

al., 1999), and anthropogenic disturbances have very strong repercussion on aquatic biodiversity (Sweeney et al., 2004). The changes in communities may be directly related to the introduction or disappearance of species caused directly or indirectly by human activities (Malmqvist and Rundle, 2002; Bollache et al., 2004). These activities, particularly in developing countries, have caused the pollution of surface waters. The degradation of aquatic environments adversely changing the physiology and ecology of aquatic biota (Khanna and Ishaq, 2013), threaten the balance in aquatic ecosystems (Noukeu et al., 2016). Freshwater fish are one of the most threatened taxonomic groups (Darwall and Vie, 2005) because of their high sensitivity to the quantitative and qualitative alteration of their habitats (Laffaille et al., 2005; Kang et al., 2009; Sarkar et al., 2008). It has been realized that anthropogenic activities have driven many fish species to be endangered, reduced in abundance and diversity; and more so, many species have become extinct (Pompeu and Alves,2003; Pompeu and Alves,2005; Shukla and Singh, 2013; Mohite and Samant,2013; Joshi, 2014).

Apart from anthropogenic activities, environmental factors also affect the freshwater quality. Indeed, extensive evaporation of water from the reservoir due to high temperature and low rain enhances the amount of salts, heavy metals and other pollutants, which are conscientious factor for the poor quality of the reservoir ecosystem (Arain et al., 2008). Among environmental pollutants, metals are of particular concern, due to to their potential toxic effect and ability to bioaccumulation in aquatic ecosystems

(Miller et al., 2002). The major ions such as Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Na^+ , K^+ , Cl^- , HCO_3^- and CO_3^{2-} are essential constituents of water and responsible for ionic salinity as compared with other ions (Wetzel, 1983). As the healthy aquatic ecosystem is depending on the physico-chemical and biological characteristics (Venkatesharaju et al 2010), the water quality assessment is essential to identify the magnitude and source of any pollution load. This can provide significant information about the available resources for supporting life in a given ecosystem. Therefore, water quality monitoring is of immense importance for conservation of water resources for fisheries, water supply and other activities. This involves analysis of physico-chemical, biological and microbiological parameters of the water bodies. The study of the various geological, physicochemical and biological aspects of these water bodies comes under the scope of limnology. The term "Limnology" originates from Greek λίμνη = limne (lake) and λόγος = logos (study). Limnology is thus the science of continental waters (Dussart B., 2004) (freshwaters or saltwaters, stagnating or moving waters, rivers, wetlands, etc.) and was originally defined as oceanography of lakes and sometimes incorrectly as the ecology of fresh waters. Francois-Alphonse Forel (1841-1912) was the precursor to define limnology in its study on Lake Lemman. It is subdivided into physical limnology (temperature, transparency, color, pH, turbidity, Total Dissolved Solids, etc.), chemical limnology (Chemical Oxygen Demand, Dissolved Oxygen, Biochemical Oxygen Demand, alkalinity, hardness, etc) and biological limnology

(zooplankton, phytoplankton and bacterial population). Ramsar Convention uses limnology to define and to characterize the wetlands which have an international importance (Kar, 2007 & 2013). However, Limnology involves a great deal of detailed field as well as laboratory studies to understand the structural and functional aspects and problems associated with the aquatic environment from a holistic point of view.

The current limnological study was carried out on Lake Tanganyika at selected stations belonging to Burundian coast. Indeed, many decisions in favor of Lake Tanganyika future have been taken at the time of the first International Conference on Conservation and Biodiversity of Lake Tanganyika, held in Burundi-Bujumbura in 1991, where regional and international scientists were present to discuss about the wealth and increasing threats of Lake Tanganyika (Cohen, 1991). Despite all these initiatives, the lake is still subject to frequent fluctuations in the chemistry of its water and to desiccation (Wetzel, 2001) due to sudden changes in weather conditions. It is facing a serious pollution problem from various sources, such as discharge of domestic sewage, population growth, rise of industrialization, use of pesticides and chemical fertilizers in agriculture, sedimentation and erosion resulting from deforestation. So, the surface waters of Lake Tanganyika are highly polluted by different harmful contaminants from human activities in large cities established on its catchment areas. In the present study, water quality assessment with reference to its eligibility for fish culture will be reviewed for raising awareness of fish farmers and environmentalists about the important water

quality factors impacting on health of the water body and that are required in optimum values to increase the fish yields to meet the growing demands of a growing population across the four neighbouring countries when the food resources are in depletion conditions. Furthermore, the assessment of the current status of fish community structure in Lake Tanganyika and the impact of the physico-chemical characteristics of water on the abundance, diversity, spatial distribution, richness, trophic ecology of the fish species will also be highlighted. The assessment of the water quality of Lake Tanganyika will also help the government of the riparian countries to take the measures for protecting the lake against the conditions that can adversely affect biodiversity life in the lake.

1.2 Objectives of the Study

The global objective of the present study is to assess the limnological parameters (physical, chemical and biological characteristics) of Lake Tanganyika at selected stations, with reference to its suitability for pisciculture purposes. In concomitant to this, the specific objectives of the study include:

1. To assess the water quality of Lake Tanganyika in comparison to the recommended Standards for water quality suitable for pisciculture.
2. To determine the trophic and pollution status of the waters at selected sampling sites
3. To assess the qualitative and quantitative structure of planktons diversity as fish food in Lake Tanganyika.
4. To establish an inventory and taxonomic characterization of all fish species found in the sampling sites.
5. To determine the influence of physico-chemical parameters (effect of pollutants) on the abundance and spatial distribution of fish species in the lake and hence, to identify the pollution indicator fish.

CHAPTER-II REVIEW OF LITERATURE

II.1 Major African Lakes

II.1.1 Great Lakes

The African Great Lakes form a series of lakes constituting the part of the Rift Valley lakes in and around the East African Rift. From north to south, the Great Lakes of Africa are: Turkana, Albert, Edward, Victoria, Kivu, Tanganyika, Rukwa, Mweru and Malawi. Lake Kyoga is part of the Great Lakes network, but is not considered as great lake, because of its size. The Rift fissure separated the African continent into two blocs: The African block at the West and the Somalian block to the East. The lakes Turkana, Albert, Edward, Kivu, Tanganyika, Rukwa and Malawi are the markings of this fissure oriented from North West to the South East (Fermon, 2007). Most of Africa's main lakes lie along a continental fault line called the East African Rift Valley, which crosses the southeastern part of the continent, creating both spectacular mountains like Kilimanjaro and a system of deep lakes collectively called the Great Lakes of Africa. While not quite as large as the North American Great Lakes system, the system nonetheless looms significant in both the physical and economic geography of the continent and that's not to mention its physical beauty and stature (Fermon, 2007). Lake Albert, Lake Victoria and Lake Edward flow into the White Nile. Lake Tanganyika and Lake Kivu both flow into the Congo River system, Lake Malawi is drained by the Shire River into the Zambezi, while Lake Turkana

has no outlet. The Great lakes region is formed by five countries which are the Democratic Republic of the Congo (D.R.C.), Burundi, Rwanda, Republic of the Congo (Congo-Brazzaville) and Uganda. The African Great Lake region is used in a narrow sense for the area lying between the north of Lake Tanganyika, west of Lake Victoria, and lakes Kivu, Edward, and Albert (Fermon, 2007). This area includes Burundi, Rwanda, the north-east of D.R. Congo, Uganda and northwestern Kenya and Tanzania. It is used in a broader sense to extend to all of Kenya and Tanzania, but not as far south as Zambia, Malawi and Mozambique, or as far north as Ethiopia, although these four countries are neighbors of Grand Lake (Fermon, 2007).

Figure 1: Map showing the African Great Lakes region

Source: https://upload.wikimedia.org/wikipedia/commons/thumb/1/17/African_Great_Lakes.svg/220px-African_Great_Lakes.svg.png

II.1.2 History of Geological formation of African lakes

Twelve million years ago, a tectonic fracture occurred on the African continent, giving rise to the Red Sea and large part of the lakes of East Africa. From this fracture were born African lakes to the east, either by filling in the gaps created (lakes Tanganyika and Malawi), or by filling pools created by west and east cleft formations, as in the case of Lake Victoria. These African lakes have lasted a long time, which is unusual in lacustrine ecosystems. Although modern lakes have been formed by glaciation over the last 12,000 years and have always been characterized by frequent fluctuations in the chemical composition of water and desiccation (Wetzel, 1983), the African Great lakes have a long geological existence.

Table 1: Major events of geological changes in Great Lakes Region.

Eras	Phase	Years	Events
Proterozoic	Precambrian	3,300 to 500 millions years	Peneplain crossed by rivers, erosion effect, Rivers flow to West and East with a dividing line located at the East of the actual Lake Victoria....
	Premiocen (Eocene and Oligocene)	70millions years	Very long tectonic calm, Important contacts between the rivers, Distribution of aquatic organisms at a continental level
Tertiary	Miocene	25 years	-Great tectonic movements: fracturing of the continent and formation of the Great Rift Valley; -Rivers are reversed: One part flows into the Atlantic and forms large lakes of the Rift; Multiplication of lacustrine habitats in Africa
	Pliocene	12millions years	Vaste lac dans le bassin du RDC.
	End of Pliocene	1.5millions years	Definitive development of grabens with formation of volcanoes on their edge, Rivers originating in the basin of Lake Victoria flow into lakes of western grabens (Edward and Mobutu) and then to the Nile to the north.
Quaternary	Pleistocene	1millions years	Tectonic movements continue. Ruwenzori massif forms (Quick barriers on Semlicki between Lakes Albert (Mobutu) and Edward
		500,000 years	Western edge of the basin of Lake Victoria rises gradually.
	Holocene	20,000 years to nowadays	Tectonic stability period, Changes in the level of the lake
		14,500 years	Drought period
		12,000years	Climate change: rise in water level
7,000years	Dryness period Climate change: rise in water level		

II.2 Hydrographical Network of Burundi

Burundi country is fed by a large network of rivers, marshes and lakes occupying up to 10% of its surface area. The country's hydrographical network is divided into two major river basins: the Nile basin with an area of 13,800 km² and the Congo River basin with an area of 14,034 km² (Sinarinzi, 2005):

- (i) The Congo basin consists of two sub-basins: (a) the sub-basin located to the west of the Congo Nile ridge drained by Rusizi River and its tributaries and by Lake Tanganyika, (b) the sub-basin
- (ii) Kumoso located in the East of the country which is a tributary of Maragarazi River and its tributaries. The waters of this basin are collected by Lake Tanganyika and flow into Congo River through Lukuga River, which is an overfall for Lake Tanganyika (Nzigidahera, 2012).
- (iii) The Nile Basin comprising of all the tributaries of Ruvubu and Kanyaru Rivers that meet in the North-East of the Country forming thus Kagera river which flows into Lake Victoria and then into the Nile River. It should also be noted that Burundi is sheltering the southernmost source of the Nile River, located in the south of the country, precisely in Rutovu Commune, Bururi Province.

However, beside Lake Tanganyika, Burundi has a large number of natural lakes to the north belonging to the Nile basin and located on the border of Burundi with Rwanda. These lakes offer an impressive natural spectacle

Table 2: Lakes belonging to Burundian territory and their geographical locations.

Province	Lake	Source	Status
Kayanza	1. Lake Rwegura	Nzigidahera (2012)	Artificial
Muyinga	2. Lake Kavuruga	Nzigidahera (2012)	Artificial
Bubanza	3. Lake Kibenga	US-NGA (2006)	Natural
Bujumbura, Rumonge & Makamba	4. Tanganyika	Nzigidahera(2012)	Natural
Cibitoke	5. Lake Nyamuziba	US-NGA (2006)	Natural
	6. Lake Dogodogo	US-NGA (2006)	Natural
Kirundo	7. Lake Inampete	Nzigidahera (2012)	Natural
	8. Lake Gacimirinda	US-NGA (2006)	Natural
	9. Lake Gitamo	US-NGA (2006)	Natural
	10. Lake Kanzigiri	Nzigidahera (2012)	Natural
	11. Lake Mwangere	Nzigidahera (2012)	Natural
	12. Lake Narungazi	Nzigidahera (2012)	Natural
	13. Lake Rwihinda	Nzigidahera (2012)	Natural
	14. Lake Cohoha	Nzigidahera (2012)	Natural
	15. Lake Rweru	Nzigidahera (2012)	Natural

II.2.1 Lake Tanganyika

II.2.1.1 Origin and evolution

Lake Tanganyika was formed about 12 million years ago and its history is not definitively established. Richard And John Hanning Speke were the first Europeans to discover the lake in 1858 and Burton who led the expedition retains its original name, contrary to the practice in force at the time (Kar, 2013). It was in 1871, 10th November on the shores of Lake Tanganyika at Ujiji station that a historic meeting between David Livingstone and Stanley took place. It was on this occasion that Stanley wrote the famous replica “Doctor Livingstone, i presume?” Lake Tanganyika has been formed since the Miocene 20 million years ago (Coulter et al., 1991). Most of the modern lakes have been trained by glaciation during the past 12,000 years and have experienced a history marked by frequent fluctuations in waters chemistry (Wetzel, 1983).

The current version states that during the alpine folding, the African massif was fractured and gave rise to the rift-valley which runs from the Red Sea to the mouth of Zambezi (Nyakageni, 1985). Lake Tanganyika is the longest, widest and oldest of the African Rift Lakes. According to Ntakimazi (1992), the lake is estimated to be between 5 and 20 million years old and for more than half that period; the lake was isolated from other hydrographic networks. Based on sediment accumulation rates in the basin, geologists estimate that Lake Tanganyika has existed about 12 million years (Scholz and Rosendahl, 1988; Cohen et al., 1993).

According to Brichard (1989), three successive phases seem to have contributed to the evolution of Lake Tanganyika:

- Phase I: During this phase, there would have been two lakes separated by a wall of 500 to 600 m in height;
- Phase II: The two lakes would have merged and the depth would have increased up to 700m;
- Phase III: The depth of the lake would have increased up to 900 m.

At this time, Lake Tanganyika occupied a much larger area than today and its northern shore was at least made up of volcanic barrages located in the South of the current Lake Kivu. The collapse phenomena of the plain bottom occurring at Pleistocene and climate changes were responsible for the gradual shoreline exposure of most of the Rusizi plain. But the Rusizi River itself is the result of events that took place much further in north. Indeed, at a much later time, 8-12000 years, the eruption of the Virunga had the effect of barring the flow to the North of a set of streams that

drained the current basin of Lake Kivu to Lake Edward. The waters have accumulated upstream of the created barrage forming the present Lake Tanganyika. The increase of the level continued, the water excess ending up overflowing to the south over an older volcanic barrage in Bukavu Cyangugu region resulting in the formation of Ruzizi river. This evolution has had significant consequences on the separation of species and this story was reflected in the current biogeographical distribution of species. Lake Tanganyika has two natural possibilities of water outflow: Evaporation and Lukuga River emptying the water of the Lake to Congo River and is powered by Rainfall, the waters from Lake Kivu via Ruzizi river, Malagarazi river and others tributaries of its watershed.

II.2.1.2 Geographical Situation.

Located in the Lakes region of East Africa, Lake Tanganyika is housed in the central part of Western graben, in south of Equator at $29^{\circ} 5'$ and $31^{\circ} 15'$ of longitude East over a length ranging from 40 to 80 km and at $3^{\circ}20'$ and $8^{\circ}45'$ of latitude South over a length of 650 km (Moore, 1903). Lake Tanganyika is surrounded by four countries sharing unequally 1,838km of its entire perimeter (Hanek and al., 1993): Burundi in the North-East controlling 159 km (9% of the coast), D R.C to the West with 795 km (43% of the coast), Tanzania to the East and South-East with 669 km (36% of the coast) and Zambia to the south with 215 km (12% of the coast). Seven main towns and cities are established on the edge of Lake Tanganyika such as: Baraka, Kalemie and Uvira in Democratic Republic of Congo,

Bujumbura and Rumonge in Burundi, Kigoma in Tanzania and Mpulungu in Zambia. Lake Tanganyika is one of the largest lakes of Africa and second biggest Lake Considering the area after Lake Victoria. It is also the longest fresh water lake in the world and holds second position in terms of volume and depth after Lake Baïkal (Wetzel, 1983 and Kar, 2013). In fact, Lake Tanganyika has a volume of 18 900km³, covers an area of 34,000 km² with a length of 677 km and a width of 72km and is spread on a watershed of 231,000km². Its altitude rises to 775m; its average depth is 770m with a maximum of 1433m.

Table 3: Physiographic statistics of Lake Tanganyika (Coulter, 1994; Odada et al., 2004).

Physiographic characteristics	Related Data
Riparian Counties	Burundi, Congo, Tanzania and Zambia
Altitude (surface)	773 m
Surface area	32,600 km ²
Volume	18,880 km ³
Maximum depth in southern basin	1 320 m
Maximum depth in Northern basin	1,470 m
Average depth	570 m
Residence time	440 years
Drainage area	223,000 km ²
Population in drainage area	10 million
Population density in drainage area	45/km ²
Length of lake	670 km
Width	12 à 90 Km
Length of shoreline	1,900 km
Latitude (South)	03°20' - 08°48'
Longitude (Est)	29°03' - 31°12'
Age	Environ 12 million d'années
Coastal perimeter	1 838 Km
Water Stratification	Permanent
Depth of the oxygenated zone to the north	- 70 m
Depth of the oxygenated zone in the South	-200m
Salinity	Environ 460 mg/litre
Resilience Time (renewal)	440 Years old

Figure 3: Geographical situation of Lake Tanganyika

Source:<http://geocurrents.info/wp-content/uploads/2012/07/Lake-Tanganyika-Map.gif>

II.2.1.3 Watersheds of Lake Tanganyika

Various factors make Lake Tanganyika an exceptionally rich and interesting ecosystem. It is estimated that more than 10 million people are living in Lake Tanganyika watershed in four riparian countries (Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC), Burundi, Tanzania and Zambia). Most of the waters of Lake Tanganyika extend over DRC with 45% of the lake's surface, followed by Tanzania (41%), then Burundi (8%) and Zambia (6%) (Capart, 1952). Lake Tanganyika, which is both the longest and second deepest lake in the world, contains 17% of the world's fresh water, and according to the same source, Lake Tanganyika's bottom shows:

- The Northern basin (Bujumbura) including the mouth of Rusizi and the bay of Burton with a maximum depth of 450 m.
- Kigoma Basin between Kungwe Peninsula and Kalemie Hill
- Zongwe basin which owns the deepest part of Kungwe up to Mpulungu.

The [table 4](#) shows how Lake Tanganyika waters are shared between four countries while the [figure 4](#) shows the Watershed of Lake Tanganyika.

Table 4: Distribution of the Waters of Lake Tanganyika per country.

Country	Area		Perimeter	
	Km ²	%	Km	%
Burundi	2 600	8%	159	9%
RDC	14 800	45%	795	43%
Tanzania	13 500	41%	669	36%
Zambia	2 000	6%	215	13%
Total	32 900	100%	1 850	100%

Figure 4: Map representing the watershed of Lake Tanganyika

Source: http://www.globalnature.org/bausteine.net/i/21931/Map_LakeTanganyikaBasin.jpg?width=600

II.2.1.4 Tributaries of Lake Tanganyika

Lake Tanganyika is a reservoir estimated at 18,800 km³ of fresh water (Coulter, 1991) and its waters join the Congo basin, then Atlantic Ocean through Rukuga River. According to Nyakageni (1985), Lake Tanganyika is powered by different rivers which have a high rainfall rate. The major tributaries are Rusizi River which drains Lake Kivu located in the north and Malagarazi River, which drains the west of Tanzania, located in the south of Lake Victoria basin. Lukuga River is the only effluent that empties Lake Tanganyika to Congo River then to Atlantic Ocean.

II.2.1.4.1 Malagarazi River

It drains more than half of the surface of the lake basin. With its numerous tributaries, it gathers waters over an area of approximately 130,000 km² to the East of the lake (Patterson and Makin, 1997). Malagarazi forms the border between Burundi and Tanzania over a distance of 156 km. The main tributaries of the Malagarazi River in Burundi are: Rukoziri, Nyakabonda, Mutsindozi, Ndanga, Nyamabuye, Muyovozi, Musasa and Rumpungwe (Ngendakuriyo, 2008).

II.2.1.4.2 Rusizi River

Located to the western side of Burundi, Rusizi River is the way by which Lake Kivu flows into Lake Tanganyika. During its passage over a length of 117km, Rusizi River gathers the waters from many tributaries such as: Luvungi, Nyakagunda, Nyamagana, Muhira, Kajege, Kaburantwa, Kagunuzi, Nyarundari, Mpanda and Ruhwa (Mpawenayo, 1996).

II.2.1.4.3 Other tributaries on Burundian coast

Besides Malagarazi and Rusizi Rivers which are the major tributaries of the lake, it is important to point out other tributaries across the Burundian coast impacting on the water quality of the lake. These rivers are cited here from north to south of the lake such as: Mutimbuzi, Kinyankongwe, Ntakangwa, Muha, Kanyosha, Mugere, Karonge, Nyamusenyi, Nyaruhongoka, Rukamba, Rugata, Ruzibazi, Cugaro, Kirasa, Buzimba, Buhinda, Shanga, Ngonya, Kizuka, Munege, Kirasa, Dama, Mugerangabo, Murembwe (= Siguvyaye + Jiji), Gasangu, Mukunde, Nyengwe, Kazirwe, Muguruka, Kavungerezi and Rwaba.

II.2.1.5 Climatic Conditions

There are broadly two main seasons in the Lake Tanganyika: The rainy season extending from October or November to May, characterized by light winds, high humidity, heavy rainfall and frequent storms and the dry season extending from June to September or October with moderate rainfall accompanied by strong and steady winds from the south. The change of seasons and wind speed result in southern and northern winds that determine the dynamics of the intertropical convergence zone ([Huttula et al., 1997](#)). These major climate patterns and particularly the winds, regulate seasonal thermal regimes of Lake ([Coulter, 1963](#); [Spiegel & Coulter, 1991](#)), evaporation ([Coulter & Spiegel, 1991](#)), vertical mixing and movement of water masses ([Degens et al 1971](#)). These hydro-physical phenomena are the first regulators of spatial and temporal patterns of biological

productivity. Concerning the thermal conditions, Coulter et al. (1991) indicate that Lake Tanganyika is a tropical lake, where the temperature is greater than 25°C with an average difference rarely exceeding 3°C. The same source indicates also that Lake Tanganyika has an intertropical climate with annual precipitations covering almost 8 months per year with a rainfall of 900 mm. There is a thermal stratification where a hot superficial stratum called "**epilimnion**" is superposed on a deep stratum called "**hypolimnion**" which is colder. Another stratum called "**metalimnion**" is interposed between the epilimnion and the hypolimnion and is characterized by a remarkable "thermocline". The figure 5 shows the different thermal strata of lakes.

Figure 5: Graphic representation of the thermal stratification of Lakes

Source: <http://www.sgreen.us/pmaslin/limno/pic/sum.win.GIF>

Indeed, the epilimnion has a temperature ranging from 25 to 27°C and its thickness varies from 50 to 60m depending on the season in the northern basin of the lake. The metalimnion is an intermediate stratum where the temperature changes quickly from 26 to 23.5°C. The hypolimnion is the deepest and the thickest stratum, with stable temperatures varying slightly from 23 to 23.7°C.

II.2.1.6 Biotope of Lake Tanganyika

Regarding the physical and biological criteria associated to the depth and to the profile of the lake, we can distinguish (Coulter, 1991):

A littoral zone made up of very varied habitats whose contours are sometimes invisible. It is located between the surface and the depth of the rooted plants with lower extension (0 to 10 m deep);

A pelagic or sub-littoral zone extending from the littoral limit up to the depth limit of dissolved oxygen (Approximately 100m in the northern basin and 200m in the Southern basin). It is a favourable area for planktons and large biomass of fish.

A deep or profundal zone located under pelagic zone where the light does not exist. It is therefore unsuitable zone for the aerobic life. It occupies alone approximately 70% of the lacustrine basin. According to Poll (1958), the estuarine and wetland biotopes are expansions of rivers, marshes and wetlands around the lake. These are fluvial habitats belonging only to the rivers and tributaries characterized by ecological conditions very different to those of Lake Tanganyika.

Figure 6: Categories of life zones in lakes

Source: https://image.pbs.org/poster_images/assets/lenticcommthub.jpg.resize.710x399.jpg.

II.2.1.7 Biodiversity of Lake Tanganyika

II.2.1.7.1 General Considerations

Lake Tanganyika contains a remarkable fauna and till now, more than 1300 species of organisms have been found in Lake Tanganyika, placing it in second place in terms of diversity recorded in all lakes on earth (Cohen and al., 1993). While all the African Great Lakes are home of several species known world-wide as the cichlid fishes, Lake Tanganyika in addition to the cichlid fish (over 250 species), contains also non-cichlid fish (more

than 145 species) and invertebrates including gastropods (more than 60 species), bivalves (over 15 species), ostracods (over 84 species), decapods (over 15 species), copepods (more than 69species) and sponges (more than 9 species) (Coulter, 1994).

Lake Tanganyika contains more than 1,300 species of plants and animals and is one of the richest freshwater ecosystems in the world. However, more than 600 of these species are endemic in the Lake Tanganyika Basin. With its large number of species, including species, genera and endemic families, it is clear that the lake contributes greatly to the world's biodiversity. This wide biodiversity within a restricted area has allowed for incredible genetic variation and a fascinating species evolution, for example the "evolutionary plasticity" of Tanganyika jaw cichlids. Many species that coexist over a long period of time in an almost closed environment could be expected to illustrate interesting patterns of evolution and behavior. Thus, with morphologically similar but genetically distinct species, genetically similar but morphologically distinct species, species with robust evolutionary armor in response to predation, diversified species in the morphology of the jaws to exploit all available ecological niches and species that have adopted complex strategies of reproductive and parental behavior, including nest development, oral incubation, and reproductive parasitism (Coulter, 1991) for a review of these and other topics. With its many species with complex and derived patterns and behaviors, Lake Tanganyika is a natural laboratory for research on ecological issues, behavior and evolution. Although all the species close to the cichlids of

Lake Tanganyika are known worldwide, two species have attracted more and more human interest: Sardines (Clupeidae) and *Lates stappersii* dominate the biomass and are the target of industrial and artisanal fisheries. Sardine species, as well as their related marine species, are small, numerous, have a short life and are very successful whereas *Lates stappersii* is a large predator. The [table 5](#) shows the inventory of biodiversity component of Lake Tanganyika.

Table 5: Biodiversity components of Lake Tanganyika (Coulter, 1994)

Taxon	Number of Species	% of endemic species
Algae	759	-
Aquatic Plants	81	-
Protozoa	71	-
Cnidarians	02	-
Sponges	09	78
Bryozoans	06	33
Tapeworms	11	64
Roundworms	20	35
Segmented Worms	28	61
Towards Horsehair	09	-
Thorny-Headed Worms	01	-
Pentastomids	01	-
Rotifers	70	07
Snails	91	75
Clams	15	60
Arachnids	46	37
Crustaceans	219	58
Insects	155	12
Fish (Cichlidae Family)	250	98
Fish (Non-Cichlids)	75	59
Amphibians	34	-
Reptiles	29	07
Birds	171	-
Mammals	03	-
Total:	2156	-

II.2.1.7.2 Ichtyofauna of Lake Tanganyika

II.2.1.7.2.1 Cichlids Fish

In Lake Tanganyika, the family of cichlids includes 187 species of which 183 are endemic. This high endemism is due to the fact that these cichlid fish were able to adapt to the salinity, to geoclimatic and physico-chemical changes (Baedle, 1962). According to Patterson and Makin (1997), the number of cichlid fish of Lake Tanganyika in the early 19th century was estimated at 79 species, of which Boulenger (1905) described 60 species.

II.2.1.7.2.2 Non-cichlids Fish

In Lake Tanganyika basin, 21 non-cichlids fish families distributed in 51 different genera are discovered (De Vos and Snoeks, 1994). Among 145 species recorded, 61 species are endemic and the diversity of non-cichlid fish is therefore close to that of cichlid fish, although the number of species recorded for this family can be estimated significantly to 172 species, of which 167 are endemic (Coulter, 1999). The number of genera and species varies slightly from what Coulter has reported as several genera have been renamed in subsequent work and several new species have been described (De Vos and Snoeks, 1994).

II.2.1.8 Fishing typology in Lake Tanganyika

Fishing plays a very important role in the Burundian economy and represents a valuable source of animal protein for populations, especially riparian populations (Evert, 1980). The main fishing beaches of Lake Tanganyika, located on Burundian Coast are listed in the Table 6.

Table 6: Fishing beaches of Lake Tanganyika on Burundian shoreline

Fishing beaches status	Fishing Beaches per Provinces		
	Bujumbura	Rumonge	Makamba
Official	1. Kajaga	1. Rumonge	1. Gasaba
	2. Cadilac	2. Kagongo	2. Gifuruzi
	3. Gitaza	3. Karonda	3. Kabonga
	4. Kabezi	4. Kizuka	4. Muguruka
	5. Kanyosha	5. Minago	5. Nyagatanga
	6. Nyamugari		6. Mvugo
	7. Magara		
Unlawful	8. Cimental	6. Cugaro	7. Nyabigina
	9. Gakombera	7. Gatare	8. Nyengwe
	10. Gakungwe	8. Gatete	9. Rubindi
	11. Gasange	9. Gikumu	
	12. Gatumba	10. Gisenyi	
	13. Gatumba-gaharawe	11. Kayengwe	
	14. Gatumba-kibero	12. Kigwena	
	15. Kibenga	13. Kinani	
	16. Kinindo	14. Makombe	
	17. Makombe	15. Murembwe	
	18. Migera	16. Nyacijima	
	19. Mwambuko	17. Shanga	
	20. Nyamusenyi		
	21. Nyaruhongoka		
	22. Rutunga		
	23. Ruziba		

Source: Author (2018)

Fish related activities occupy a large part of the population living on the shores of Lake Tanganyika (Nahayo, 2010). According to the study carried out by the Department of Water, Fisheries and Aquaculture in 2007, about 8000 Fishermen are employed in fishing sector and and more than 40,000 people work in related activities such as the construction of canoes, fish processing and marketing. Commercial fishing activities are determined by the phase of the moon. Although more than 50 different gears are identified in Lake Tanganyika (Lindley, 2000), the main fishing gears are nets, beach

seines, gillnets and lines. Women are not involved in fishing and fishing activities generally start in the evening and continue through the night and catches are processed during the day.

II.2.1.8.1 Customary Fishing

The Customary Fishing is characterized by a cheaper investment and uses a plank canoe having 3 to 5 meters in length with a limited number of fishermen (Evert, 1980). In the customary fishing, the gears used are varied and it is done during the day and night-time in quiet weather with or without canoe (Breuil, 1995). The most commonly used equipments are:

- ✓ The landing net locally called "urusenga": used during night under the lighting pressure of lamp near the coasts;
- ✓ The dormant gill net locally called "amakira": net installed in the evening to be lifted the next morning near estuaries;
- ✓ The beach seine: installed at a certain distance from the shore and drawn by several fishers toward the beach. Used during the day, it captures almost all encircled fish;
- ✓ The encircling gill net: used during the day in the fishing technique called the strike and locally called "umutimbo". The technique involves circling the fishing area and hitting the water downstream of the net to scare the fish.
- ✓ The Traps fish-traps: Installed during day time at the mouths of rivers.

II.2.1.8.2 Artisanal fishing

It is practiced in the northern part of the lake, especially by catamarans. A typical catamaran unit consists of two mainly wooden hulls with lamps (Hanek, 1994). The catamaran unit is equipped with 4 to 12 lamps, a plaice net of 60 to 80 m in circumference and 4 to 8 fishermen and is propelled by an engine of 15 to 20HP(horsepower). In this type of fishing, the target fish are especially Clupeidae and Centropomidae which are pelagic (Rutozi, 1993).

II.2.1.8.3 Industrial fishing

It has been practiced since 1954. In 1980, purse seiners increased their fishing effort up to 23 active units. It is a modern steel boat system from 15 to 18 meters equipped with a powerful diesel engine from 20 to 25 HP, a winch, a purse seine having a length of 400 m and 100m vertical drop. This system employs 20 to 30 fishermen and the nets are small meshes for catching a mixture of clupeidae and louseflies (Durazzo, 1999).

II.2.1.9 Main threats of Lake Tanganyika

II.2.1.9.1 Pollution

II.2.1.9.1.1 General Considerations

Pollution is a major threat to Lake Tanganyika's sustainability. Industrial and municipal Sewage are not currently treated before entering into the lake and the governments of riparian countries do not have legislation to prevent contamination of the lake. Pollutants include heavy metals, fuel and oil from boats, pesticides and chemical fertilizers (Patterson G. & Makin

J.,1997). The increase of deforestation has amplified the damage caused by erosion leading to sedimentary deposition in the littoral zone (habitat for organisms). Turbidity and changes in substrates can alter habitats, disrupting food chain/web and primary productivity which reducing species diversity (Cohen et al., 1993). The table 7 shows the main Sources of pollution in Lake Tanganyika watershed.

Table 7: Pollution sources in Lake Tanganyika catchment (Patterson and Makin, 1997).

Type of Pollution	Sources
Industrial Sewage	> 80 industries in Bujumbura, Burundi
Sewage of urban households	Bujumbura, Uvira, Kalemie, Kigoma, Rumonge and Mpulungu
Chlorides hydrocarbons, pesticides, Heavy metals	Rusizi plain, Malagarasi plain Waters of the northern basin from industrial waste
Mercury	Malagarasi river
residual ashes	cement processing in Kalemie
nutrient elements associated with fertilizer	Rusizi plain, Malagarazi plain and other basins
organic waste ,sulfuric dioxide, Fuel and oil	sugar processing manufactory near Uvira city, Ports, lacustrine transport of commodities in all 4 countries

II.2.1.9.1.2 Sedimentary Pollution

Siltation is due to erosion in the drainage area further to increased deforestation. In fact, the topsoil is transported to the lake, where it joins chemical fertilizers and pesticides evacuated from the lake drainage area. 100% of the northern drainage area and approximately 50% of the central areas have been cleared of their natural vegetation, leading to increased erosion. Malagarasi and Rusizi Rivers provide an important part of waters flowing into Lake Tanganyika and also the most of the suspended solids

load in Lake. Siltation is the most damaging threat to the lake's biodiversity, especially siltation from the heavily-impacted smaller northern watersheds. Large-scale deforestation and agricultural practices have resulted in a dramatic increase in land erosion overhanging Lake Tanganyika. The freshly eroded sediments entering into the lake affect adversely its biodiversity, not only by decreasing species habitat, but also by making certain essential nutrients more complex as trace elements. The studies carried out by [Cohen and al \(1993\)](#) focused on the impact of increasing river sediment supply on Lake Tanganyika's biodiversity. The impact of eroded sediments entering into the lake can be observed on the [figure 7](#).

Figure 7: Photo showing the lake sedimentary pollution further to rainy erosion.

Source: https://www.consoglobe.com/wp-content/uploads/2017/02/lac-tanganyika-GNF_River-Rusizi-flows-sediment-laden-into-Lake-Tanganyika-e1486394393582.jpg

In fact, the practice of clearing land by large fires without any control has been followed by a conversion of previously forested land or used in subsistence agriculture. Such clearance could lead to quick erosion, river incision and to gully (Bruijnzeel, 1990). Bizimana and Duchafour (1991) have estimated that the rate of soil erosion in Ntakangwa River basin, which has steep and intensely cultivated slopes has increased between 20 and 100 Tons per year and almost all of its sediments flow into Lake Tanganyika.

II.2.1.9.1.3 Urban and Industrial wastes

Discharges of untreated sewage, including industrial and domestic sewage from large cities established on Lake Tanganyika such as Bujumbura in Burundi, Kigoma in Tanzania, Mpulungu in Zambia, Uvira and Kalemie in Congo might contain nutrients, organic matters, heavy metals (mercury, chromium), pesticides and fuel from ports, shipping places and boats, etc. The problem is considered as serious in all urban centers around the lake. Since the lake is an effectively closed system, the emission of non-biodegradable pollutants will result in an accumulation process that could threaten the lake. Urban and industrial pollution are closely linked. Urban centers attract industries and form major market and transportation hubs, which in turn attract more settlements. Indeed, Bujumbura has two major industries (brewery and textile) that release large quantities of sewage into the lake without treatment. Furthermore, there are many other potentially polluting industries such as: Manufacturers of batteries, paints, soap,

pharmaceuticals, slaughterhouse, oil depots and garages. In Uvira, the main industrial products are petroleum products, cotton processing and sugar production. In addition, increasing the amount of waste and household effluents associated with the growth of urban settlements is a problem in all the countries bordering Lake Tanganyika. In Kigoma bay, where water circulation is restricted, there are already signs of eutrophication. The water supplier site for the city is located very close to the untreated sewage disposal points of many settlements and waste entering into lake from TANESCO power station. However, it is often cheaper to reject the by-products into water than to treat them for mitigating their harmfulness. The sulfur is largely rejected as sulfate, but by microbial action, it becomes a toxic sulphide in reducing medium (Evert, 1980).

Figure 8: Sewage flowing into Lake Tanganyika from AFRITAN Company.

Source:<http://www.iwacu-burundi.org/wp-content/uploads/2016/01/Lac-Tanganyika-polu%C3%A9.jpg>

II.2.1.9.2 Overfishing and use of destructive gears

Overfishing and the use of destructive methods alter biological community's structure and food chain, and may have negative socio-economic consequences (Pearce, Petit and Kiyuku, 1995). Studies show that fish stocks have already been drastically reduced through fishing activities (Pearce, Petit and Kiyuku, 1995). Annual fish catches recorded on Lake Tanganyika have been on an upward trend since 1970, currently at around 200 000 tonnes. Recent estimates by country indicate a yield of about 21,000 tons for Burundi in 1992 (94.5kg/ha/year), 55,000 tons for Tanzania in 1994-1995 (60 kg/ha/year), 12,900 tons for Zambia (69kg/ha/year) and 90,000 tons in Democratic Republic of Congo (34 kg/ha/year). These estimates give an average catch ranging from 54to 66 kg/ha/year for the whole Lake (Lindqvist et al.,1999). The observed fishery yields in Burundi (94.5 and 111.5 kg/ha/year, respectively in 1992 and 1995) are close to the potential yield of 100kg/ha estimated by Coulter (1977).

The evidence of overfishing in Burundian and Zambian waters the downward trend in catch per unit effort (CPUE) for industrial units (purse seiners). The nocturnal CPUE of the commercial units in Burundi decreased from 166 kg in 1994 to 111 kg in 1996, while in Mpulungu it dropped from 877kg in 1994 to 535kg in1996. The decline in catchable stocks of *Luciolates stappersii* around Mpulungu city is not compensated. At the northern extremity of the lake, the commercial units have stopped

their activities and *Luciolates stappersii* represents only around 20% of the commercial catches and the majority of the fish caught are juveniles.

II.2.1.9.3 Increase of human population

All of Lake Tanganyika's threats are linked to anthropogenic sources. Lack of education on Lake resources conservation, rapid population growth and poverty contribute to environmental damage and habitat destruction in the Lake basin. In riparian countries, the annual population growth rate is 2.5-3.1%. In riparian countries, the annual growth rate of the population is between 2.5 and 3.1%. This gradual increase in demographic pressure has forced changes in tropical forest land use to create small agricultural plots located on steep and bare slopes bordering Lake Tanganyika. In addition, infrastructures such as hotels and dwelling houses are being built anarchically in the supra-littoral zone of Lake Tanganyika. These infrastructures built without prior environmental impact assessment on fragile soils are likely to harm the environment of the lake (Manirakiza, 2017). The installation of these infrastructures begins by denudation of the supra-littoral zone, which consists in destroying the vegetation of the lake shores. As a result, the destruction and degradation of the border vegetation reduces the space needed for feeding and reproduction of the lake's biodiversity. In fact, hippopotamus populations can not survive without the vegetation used for pasture and temporary conservation of their babies and crocodiles must also have border vegetation to protect buried eggs (Manirakiza, 2017).

II.2.1.9.4 Eutrophication

According to [OECD \(1982\)](#), eutrophication is an enrichment of water by nutrient salts resulting in structural changes in the ecosystem such as: increased algae production and aquatic plants, fish species depletion, general degradation of water quality and other effects reducing and prohibiting use. Others authors define eutrophication as a typical pollution of certain aquatic ecosystems, occurring when the environment receives a lot of nutrients absorbable by algae and resulting in their proliferation ([figure 9](#)). The major nutrients causing eutrophication phenomenon are phosphorus (contained in phosphates) and nitrogen (contained in ammonium ions, nitrates and nitrites) ([Nzungu, 2017](#)).

In fact, a lake receives naturally and continuously quantities of nutrients brought by torrents and runoff waters. Stimulated by this important substantial supply, some algae grow and multiply excessively. This growth takes place in the surface water layers because plants need light to grow and helps in lowering of oxygen levels and hinder life in lakes ([Evert, 1980](#)). Organic matters have long been considered as the main pollutants of aquatic environments and originate from domestic wastes (household dirt, excrement), agricultural slurries or industrial waste (stationery, tanneries, slaughterhouses, dairies, oil mills, sugar refineries, etc) rejected without prior treatment ([Nzungu, 2017](#)). Eutrophication is observed mostly in ecosystems whose waters are slowly renewing in general and especially in deep lakes and in narrow bays where the waters are not much brewed by

the winds. On the other hand, in lotic ecosystem where the water is constantly renewed and better oxygenated, the algae are constantly washed away by the water flow and therefore, the accumulation of organic matter is not possible. Eutrophication is thus manifested by the appearance of large quantities of algae and other invasive plant species acting by excluding other species in the lake environment. An invasive species representing the most obvious threat to Lake Tanganyika is ***Eichhornia crassipes***, commonly named “water hyacinth” (Figure 10) which grows rapidly and spreads along the shore of Lake Tanganyika as well as in the shallow bays and backwaters of the northern extremity of the lake.

Accordingly, invasive plants can prevent sunlight and oxygen to reach other organisms and cause an increase in evapotranspiration and a sedimentary accumulation. The consequences include a reduction of fishes catch, aquatic biodiversity and loss of aesthetic and recreational value of the invaded areas (Bikwemu and Nzigidahera, 1997). The figure 9 shows the algal proliferation leading to green colour of Lake Tanganyika water occurring recently in September 10, 2018 while the figure 10 shows *Eichhornia crassipes* (water hyacinth) on the shores of Lake Tanganyika, in kibenga quarter.

Figure 9: Algal blooms with green colour of Lake Tanganyika water

Source: <https://bwiza.com/wp-content/uploads/2018/09/Le-lac-vert-Tanganyika-650x325.jpg>

Figure 10: Encroachment by *Eichhornia crassipes* (water hyacinth) on the shores of Lake Tanganyika, in kibenga quarter.

Source: <https://www.iwacu-burundi.org/wp-content/uploads/2019/06/webtv-10june.jpg>

II.3 Brief overview on pisciculture concept

II.3.1 Definition and Background

The word pisciculture originates from the Latin word '**piscis**' meaning '**fish**' and '**culture**' meaning '**rearing**'. Pisciculture alias fish farming is so the breeding, rearing and transplantation of fish by artificial means. It is a scientific technology used for getting maximum fish production from a pond or tank or other water reservoir through the use of available food organisms supplemented by artificial feeding. Pisciculture can also be defined as a branch of animal husbandry dealing with rational deliberate culturing of fish to marketable size in a controlled water body and is the principal form of aquaculture, while other methods may fall under Mariculture (Avault, 1996).

Pisciculture may be confused with Fishery Science, since both deal with the cultivation and harvesting of fish but the major difference is residing in the method of producing fish. Fisheries science includes all aspects of fish culture and harvesting for commercial purposes in brackish water, freshwater and any marine environment while pisciculture involves artificial ways for breeding and cultivation of fish usually in large tanks and enclosures named hatchery (Guerrero, 1997). Fish hatchery is the ability to release young fish into the wild for recreational fishing or to increase the supply of desirable subsistence fishes. In other words, it is a unit where fish eggs are hatched artificially into alevin. Some of the common fish species raised by fish farms include salmon, katla, catfish, tilapia, rohu, mrigal, carp

and cod and the most important worldwide fish species produced in fish farming are carp, tilapia, salmon and catfish (FAO, 2014). The farming of fish includes breeding, rearing of the young and the grow-out of juvenile fish to adult or harvestable fish, to market size of cultured species. The basic principles of fish farming cover the adaptation of fishes to the aquatic environment, their food habits and breeding characteristics (Huet, 1972).

In the farming of tilapias, the culture units used are ponds, tanks and net cages. The production methods vary according to the management applied such as extensive, semi-intensive and intensive systems. Techniques for Induced fish reproduction, monosexual culture, diseases and parasites control, integrated and polyculture farming systems are applied in fish farming to improve seed availability and productivity. Compared with other animal protein producers, fish farming is considered more efficient and more profitable. In 2008, the global revenues from fish farming recorded by FAO amounted to 33.8 million tonnes valued at about USD 60 billion (FAO Yearbook, 2008). With the depletion of global wild fish stocks, aquaculture is expected to produce fish to meet the growing demand for fish and fish protein, resulting in widespread overfishing in wild fisheries. China supplies 62% of world production fish and in 2016, more than 50% of sea foods were produced in aquaculture (Noaa.gov.Retrieved, .2016). Fish culture in natural waters aims to restore and improve fish stocks in rivers, lakes, reservoirs and seas. The increasing human impact on these waters (water pollution) has disturbed the natural regeneration of

fish stocks. Thus, fish farming is necessary for maintaining the life of the existing fish and improving ichthyofauna (Bard, Kimpe et al, 1976).

II.3.2 Quality of water suitable for pisciculture

Water quality is determined by its physical, chemical and biological characteristics and the water quality throughout the world is characterized with wide variability (Hemalatha, Puttaiah, 2014). Nevertheless, the quality of natural water sources used for different purposes should be established in terms of the specific water quality most affecting the possible use of water (Tarzwell, 1957). For helping fish farmers better understand the properties of water impacting on fish culture, Water quality suitable for pisciculture refers to the quality of water propitious to the successful propagation of the desired organisms. The required water quality is determined by the specific organisms to be cultured and has many associated components. Growth and survival of organisms, which together determine the ultimate yield, are influenced by a number of ecological parameters and managerial practices (Sharma, Gupta and Singh, 2013). To succeed in aquaculture of molluscs, fish, crustacean and aquatic plants, the water and soil in which fish are cultivated must have propitious conditions to their growth which, in turn is intimately linked to several physical, chemical and biological characteristics of water and adopted management practices. The choice of an appropriate site has a strong influence on the ultimate success of the aquaculture business and an ideal site should give maximum production at a minimum construction and

management cost. Physical and chemical characteristics of the soil and water will affect the primary and secondary production of the water bodies (Rajesh, Gowda and Mendon, 2002). Thus, the survival and production of fish in a pond are depending on the primary production (which depends on the water quality) and Secondary production (Goldman and Wetzel, 1963). Phytoplanktons produce carbohydrate using sunlight and release oxygen.They are the major source of energy and oxygen in the aquatic ecosystem while zooplanktons feeding on phytoplanktons form the major sources of food for fish.

II.3.3 Standards of water quality required in fish culture

The standards of physico-chemical and biological quality of suitable water for pisciculture are provided in the table 8.

Table 8: Water quality required in pisciculture

Parameters	Recommended Value	Source
Turbidity (NTU)	20 - 30	ICAR(2007)
	≤1000	WWF-Pakistan(2007)
TDS(mg/L)	≤500	USA-EPA(2006)
	10-20	Davis(1993)
TSS(mg/L)	≤80	Wedemeyer(1977); Piper et al.(1982)
	<25(Cold water)	MDTEE (2003)
	<50(Warm water)	MDTEE (2003)
	25 – 30	FAO(2006)
Temperature (°C)	24 - 30	ICAR(2007)
	5<T<20(Cold water)	MDTEE (2003)
	8<T<30(Warm water)	MDTEE (2003)
	6.6 – 8.5(Saline water)	Davis(1993)
Potential of Hydrogen (pH)	6.0 – 9(Fresh water)	Davis(1993)
	7.5 - 8.5(Ideal)	ICAR(2007)
	6.7- 9.5(Suitable)	ICAR(2007)
	6.5 – 8	Wedemeyer(1977); Piper et al.(1982)
	6.6-9	Wedemeyer(1977); Piper et al.(1982)
	6.5-8.5	WWF-Pakistan(2007)
	6-8	NRAC(1993)

	5-9	MDTEE (2003)
BOD(mg/L)	3 – 20	Boyd(2003)
	< 10	ICAR(2007)
	<3 (Cold water)	MDTEE (2003)
	≤8	WWF-Pakistan(2007)
	<5(Warm water)	MDTEE (2003)
COD (mg/L)	< 50	ICAR(2007)
	<20(Cold water)	MDTEE (2003)
	<30(Warm water)	MDTEE (2003)
DO saturation (%)	70(Cold water fish)	Yovita J. M.(2007)
	80(Tropical freshwater fish)	Yovita J. M.(2007)
	75(Tropical marine fish)	Yovita J. M.(2007)
	80-100(Eggs, early fry)	FAO(2006b)
DO(mg/L)	≥ 4	ICAR(2007)
	4-5	NRAC (1993)
	>5(Cold water)	MDTEE (2003), WWF-Pakistan(2007)
	>3(Warm water)	MDTEE (2003)
Free CO₂ (mg/L)	< 5	ICAR(2007)
	≤10	Wedemeyer(1977); Piper et al.(1982)
	≤15	Wedemeyer(1977); Piper et al.(1982)
	<10	NRAC(1993)
Total Hardness (mg/L as CaCO₃)	50-100	WHO (2003)
	>50, preferably>100	NRAC(1993)
	30-180	ICAR(2007)
	50-400	Wedemeyer (1977); Piper et al.(1982)
Calcium (mg/L)	75-150	ICAR(2007)
	10-160	Wedemeyer(1977); Piper et al.(1982)
	>20	SRAC(2013)
Alkalinity (mg/L)	50- 300	ICAR(2007), NRAC(1993)
	10-400	Wedemeyer(1977); Piper et al.(1982)
Salinity(mg/L)	0.5-1(for freshwater fish)	NRAC(1993)
Electrical Conductivity at 25°C (µS / cm)	<350(Cold water)	MDTEE (2003)
	<3000(Warm water)	MDTEE (2003)
	≤1500	WWF-Pakistan(2007)
Sulphates (mg/L)	<200	MDTEE (2003)
Phosphorus (mg/L)	0.01-3	Wedemeyer(1977); Piper et al.(1982)
Chloride(mg/L)	10-25	ICAR(2007)
	>100	SRAC(2013)
Chlorine (mg/L)	0.03	Wedemeyer(1977); Piper et al.(1982)
	<0.02	MDTEE (2003), NRAC(1993)
Cyanide (mg/L)	<0.05	MDTEE (2003)
	≤0.005	WWF-Pakistan (2007)
Fluoride (mg/L)	<0.7	MDTEE (2003)
	≤1.5	WWF-Pakistan (2007)
Nitrate (mg/L as N)	0.1-4.5	ICAR(2007)

	≤3	Wedemeyer(1977); Piper et al.(1982)
Nitrite (mg/L as N)	≤0.1(in soft water)	Wedemeyer(1977); Piper et al.(1982)
	≤0.2(in hard water)	Wedemeyer(1977); Piper et al.(1982)
	≤1	NRAC(1993)
	0.005-0.5	ICAR(2007)
	<0.5	MDTEE (2003)
Ammonia (mg/L as N)	≤ 0.1	ICAR(2007)
	≤1	WWF-Pakistan(2007)
	≤0.0125	Wedemeyer(1977); Piper et al.(1982)
	<0.025	MDTEE (2003)
Ammonium (mg/L as N)	<0.5 (Cold water)	MDTEE (2003)
	<1(Warm water)	MDTEE (2003)
H₂S (mg/L)	≤ 2	ICAR(2007)
	≤0.002	Wedemeyer(1977); Piper et al.(1982)
Ozone (mg/L)	≤0.005	Wedemeyer(1977); Piper et al.(1982)
Ferrous ion (mg/L)	0.00	Wedemeyer(1977); Piper et al.(1982)
Ferric ion (mg/L)	≤0.5	Wedemeyer(1977); Piper et al.(1982)
Silica (mg/L)	4-16	ICAR(2007)
Iron(mg/L)	0.01-0.3	ICAR(2007)
	≤0.15	Wedemeyer (1977); Piper et al.(1982)
	≤0.5	NRAC(1993)
	≤0.3	WWF-Pakistan (2007)
Zinc (mg/L)	0.03-0.05	Wedemeyer (1977); Piper et al.(1982)
	<0.086	WWF-Pakistan(2007)
	<1.3	MDTEE (2003)
Cadmium (mg/L)	<0.005	MDTEE (2003)
	≤0.002	WWF-Pakistan (2007)
Copper(mg/L)	<0.04	MDTEE (2003)
	≤0.007	WWF-Pakistan (2007)
Arsenic(mg/L)	≤0.05	MDTEE (2003)
Magnesium (mg/L)	(Needed for buffer system)	Wedemeyer (1977); Piper et al.(1982)
Nickel(mg/L)	0.05	WWF-Pakistan(2007)
Boron(mg/L)	<2	MDTEE (2003)
	≤1	WWF-Pakistan(2007)
Lead (mg/L)	<0.03	Wedemeyer (1977); Piper et al.(1982)
	≤0.01	WWF-Pakistan(2007)
	<0.02	MDTEE (2003)
Chromium(mg/L)	≤0.05	MDTEE (2003), WWF-Pakistan(2007)
Selenium (mg/L)	≤0.01	MDTEE (2003)
	0.005	WWF-Pakistan(2007)
Barium (mg/L)	<1	MDTEE (2003)

Mercury (mg/L)	≤0.002	Wedemeyer (1977); Piper et al.(1982)
	0.00005(average)	Wedemeyer (1977); Piper et al.(1982)
	≤0.000012	WWF-Pakistan (2007)
	<0.001	MDTEE (2003)
Silver (mg/L)	<0.003	MDTEE (2003)
Manganese (mg/L)	20-200	ICAR(2007)
	≤0.01	Wedemeyer (1977); Piper et al.(1982)
	≤0.1	MDTEE (2003), WWF-Pakistan(2007)
Phenolphthalein (%)	0.0-25	Wedemeyer (1977); Piper et al.(1982)
Methyl orange (%)	75-100	Wedemeyer (1977); Piper et al.(1982)
Carbonate (%)	0.0-25	Wedemeyer (1977); Piper et al.(1982)
Bicarbonate(%)	75-100	Wedemeyer (1977); Piper et al.(1982)
Pesticides (mg/L)	<0.0001(individual substance)	MDTEE (2003)
	<0.5(in total)	MDTEE (2003)
Polychlorinated Biphenyls(mg/L)	≤0.002	Wedemeyer(1977); Piper et al.(1982)
Anionic Detergents as MBAS(mg/L)	≤0.5	MDTEE (2003), WWF-Pakistan(2007)
Oil and grease (mg/L)	≤2	WWF-Pakistan(2007)
Dissolved hydrocarbons(mg/L)	<0.01	MDTEE (2003)
Aromatic Polycyclic hydrocarbons(mg/L)	<0.0002	MDTEE (2003)
Phenolic Compounds as Phenol(mg/L)	<0.001	MDTEE (2003)
	≤0.01	WWF-Pakistan(2007)
Toxic substances and organic pollutants	The waters shall not contain toxic substances and organic pollutants in quantities that may be detrimental fisheries and other aquatic life or to public health or impair the usefulness of the water for the intended purpose.	WWF-Pakistan(2007)
Planktons (Cells/L)	3000-4500	Bhatnagar and Singh (2010)
	2000-6000(acceptable)	Anita Bhatnagar & Pooja Devi(2013)
	3000-4500(Desirable)	Anita Bhatnagar & Pooja Devi(2013)
Fecal coliforms (CFU/100mL)	≤1000	WWF-Pakistan(2007)
Total Coliform (CFU/100mL)	≤5000	WWF-Pakistan(2007)

CHAPTER-III MATERIALS AND METHODS

III.1 Study area description

The present study on Lake Tanganyika was conducted on stations belonging to the Burundian coastline of Imbo plain. The major geophysical characteristics of Imbo plain are described as follow:

III.1.1 Geographical situation

The Imbo Plain is located between 2° 48' 30" and 4° 20' 43" of Latitude-South and 29° 36' 3" of Longitude-East and is the westernmost and lowest in altitude region of Burundi ([Lewalle, 1972](#)). It spreads unevenly over six provinces like Cibitoke, Bubanza, Bujumbura Rural, Bujumbura town hill, Rumonge and Makamba. It lies between Lake Tanganyika to the west & south and the foothills of Mumirwa to the east and north-east. It extends to the north of Lake Tanganyika to the Democratic Republic of Congo ([Nzigidahera, 2012](#)). The Imbo plain is constituted in the north by vast expanses drained by Rusizi River and to the south by the thin coastal plain along Lake Tanganyika. The lowlands of Imbo plain form a series of plains of varying width from Tanzania in the south to Rwanda in the north. The lowlands are formed by Rusizi plain and the riparian plains of Lake Tanganyika ([Nzigidahera, 2012](#)). The limits of Imbo Plain are located +between 774m of altitude (the average level of the lake) and 1000m of isohypse (beginning of coastal escarpments).

III.1.2 Climate

The Imbo plain is characterized by a rainfall of 800 to 1100 mm distributed over 7 to 8 months but some parts especially in the north show a chronic aridity. The average annual temperature is above 25°C with maxima up to more than 30°C and minima up to below 15°C. The relative humidity is estimated at 70% (Nzigidahera, 2012).

III.1.3 Morphology, geology and pedology

Morphologically, the ecological zone of Imbo is a lacustrine and fluvial sedimentary plain with alluvial deposits to the south. From a geological viewpoint, the relief of Imbo plain is one of the results of the collapse episodes that occurred at the end of the Tertiary era and resulting in the current configuration of the graben (Nzigidahera, 2012). Regarding pedological aspect, the soils of Imbo plain are established on lacustrine sediments and alluvial fluvialite sometimes sandy with a great richness in mineral salts but with variable content in humus. Hence a variable fertility especially as the soils are diversified according to the richness in mineral salts and the depth of the soil horizons. The sandy formations, the saline soils dominating the interfluvies and the vertisols of the poorly drained depressions are distinguished (Nzigidahera, 2012).

III.1.4 Hydrography

The hydrography of the Imbo plain is within the context of that of the Congo Basin and precisely in the sub-basin located to the west of the Congo-Nile ridge. This hydrographic network is formed by Rusizi River with its

tributaries and Lake Tanganyika with its tributaries on the Burundian littoral (Nzigidahera, 2012).

III.1.5 Description of the sampling stations

As the lake has a long perimeter (1838km) shared between four countries (Burundi, Tanzania, Democratic Republic of Congo and Zambia), the data collection on fish species caught in the lake, and water sample for laboratory analyses was carried out at 4 sampling sites (Kajaga, Nyamugari, Rumonge and Mvugo) belonging to the Burundian Littoral and the distance separating the selected sampling sites was at least 20km. The table 9 and figure 11 below show the geographical location of the study areas:

Figure 11: Maps showing the study areas and sampling stations location

Table 9 : Geographical location of the study sites.

Study sites	Geographical Location				
	Province	Commune	Longitude -East	Latitude -South	Altitude
Kajaga	Bujumbura Rural	Buterere	029° 17' 56"	03° 20' 55"	783 m
Nyamugari	Bujumbura Rural	Kabezi	029° 20' 24"	03° 30' 27"	776 m
Rumonge	Rumonge	Rumonge	029° 26' 03"	03° 58' 23"	767 m
Mvugo	Makamba	Nyanza-Lac	029° 34' 06"	04° 17' 42"	810 m

III.1.5.1 Kajaga site

Kajaga site is located exactly at west of Bujumbura city at 12 kilometers far away from the capital of Burundi, in Mutimbuzi commune, Bujumbura province and is located between 03° 20' 55" of Latitude-South and 029° 17' 56" of Longitude-East with an altitude of 783m. Kajaga site belongs to a supra-littoral landing beach of fishermen, covered with a strip of rocky plates (beach rocks) on 5 to 10 meters along Lake Tanganyika.

As located in the north bay of Lake Tanganyika, Kajaga site was selected to assess the impact of industrial and domestic wastewater discharges and urban waste from Bujumbura city on the water quality and the diversity, abundance of fish and planktons population.

III.1.5.2 Nyamugari site

Nyamugari site is located at 14 km far away from Bujumbura city on Bujumbura-Rumonge road (RN3), Ramba zone, Kabezi commune in Bujumbura Rural province. At approximately 400 meters from the Road (RN3) between 029° 20' 24" of longitude East and 03° 30' 27" of Latitude South at 776m of altitude. The corresponding beach is covered by the

vegetation of Papyrus and Reeds with a sandy edge. Around 10 o'clock in the morning, the waves increase and disturb the waters of the lake. During the dry season, the water is generally transparent and has blue color while in the rainy season, the alluvium brought by the rivers flowing into the lake disturb also the waters. Nyamugari station is subject to low influences of polluting human activities compared to other sites but is subject to strong erosion because the catchment area overhanging this station is uninhabited, deforested and completely occupied by grassy vegetation. The choice of this site contributes to evaluate the impact of sediment pollution on the quality of the water and the composition of the fish and coastal plankton community.

III.1.5.3 Rumonge site

Rumonge Site is located on the beach of Rumonge town which is installed near the Lake Tanganyika. The landing site of Rumonge is located in the south of Burundi at 72km far away from Bujumbura City, between 029° 26' 03" of longitude East and 03° 58' 23" of Latitude South at 767 m of altitude. Rumonge town is located at north of Kigoma town in Tanzania and at East of Baraka town in the Democratic Republic of Congo. Rumonge Province which lodges Rumonge site is located in the south-east of Burundi, on the borders of Burundi, Congo-Kinshasa and Tanzania. Therefore, Rumonge province is the home of many inhabitants from these two riparian countries. The Rumonge site was selected to evaluate the impact of urban organic

waste discharged into the lake from Rumonge city on the quality of water and the abundance of fish and plankton along the coast.

III.1.5.4 Mvugo site

The landing site of Mvugo is located in southern Burundi on the Road-RN3 at 115km far away from Bujumbura City, south-west of Makamba province, in Nyanza-Lac commune, between 04° 17' 42" of Latitude South and 029° 34' 06" of Longitude-East at 810m of altitude. Mvugo site was chosen as a control site. It is subject to low influences of polluting human activities compared to other stations. The choice of this site is proved on the one hand by the large number of fishing units that land there compared to other sites in the country and on the other hand, it has been found for a long time that this site provides the largest quantity of fish sold in Burundi.

III.2 Sampling, field data collection and Laboratory analysis

III.2.1 Physico-chemical analyses

During the present investigation, field data collection has lasted 6months, at 3 months per year (January, February and March both for 2017 and 2018) and the various outings were always conducted in the morning time. The water samples for Physical and chemical analyses were collected from different Study sites with plastic containers in the morning time. The containers were thoroughly washed and sterilized to avoid extraneous contamination. All samples were adequately labeled and transported immediately to the laboratory for analyzing of different parameters. Some physical and chemical parameters such as water temperature,

Electrical conductivity, pH and dissolved oxygen have been measured in-situ using Electrometric method (conductivity meter and pH-meter) while the remaining parameters were determined in the “Chemistry and Environmental Analysis Laboratory” of the University of Burundi using the standard methods (APHA, 2005; Trivedy and Goel, 1986). The methods adopted for water quality analysis and the used instruments are listed in the table10 below:

Table 10: Analytical methods adopted to determine quality of lake water.

Parameters	Methods	Equipments
1. Physical Parameters		
Turbidity (NTU)	Turbidity tube method	Jackson's Candle, Turbidimeter, Turbidity tube or Nephelometer
Temperature	Temperature sensitive probe	Mercury thermometer
Total Dissolved Solids	Evaporation method, Electrometric and Gravimetric method	Conductivity meter
Transparency	Secchi Disk Visibility Method	Secchi disk
2. Chemical Parameters		
PH, Electrical Conductivity	Electrometric Method	pH-meter, Conductivity meter
Dissolved Oxygen	Alsterberg Azide Modification of the Winkler's Method.	Dissolved Oxygen meter
Total hardness, Calcium and Magnesium	EDTA Titration Method	-
Chlorides	Titration by AgNO ₃ , Mohr's method.	-
BOD	5 days incubation at 20°C followed by titration	BOD Incubator
Total alkalinity	Titration by H ₂ SO ₄	-
COD	Digestion followed by titration	COD Digestor
Total Carbon, Total Nitrogen	Titrimetric method	-
Total Phosphorus	Digestion and ascorbic acid Spectrophotometric Method	Spectrophotometer
Heavy metals (ppm): Iron (Fe), Lead (Pb), Cadmium (Cd), Chromium (Cr), Copper (Cu), Selenium (Se), Arsenic (As)	Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometric Method	Spectrophotometer

Figure 12: Measuring of physico-chemical parameters in the laboratory

Figure 13: Measuring of Temperature, pH, Electrical conductivity and Transparency on-spot.

The methods adopted for water quality analysis and the equipments used for measuring all the physico-chemical parameters are described in the following section:

III.2.1.1 Potential of Hydrogen (pH)

The pH is measured in situ using a pH meter. The measuring consists of immersion of the electrode in water by stirring it and the correct measured value is noted down after its stability.

III.2.1.2 Temperature

The air temperature is obtained using Mercury thermometer while the water temperature is measured using the electrometric method based on the temperature sensitive electrodes with a Pt-Rh probe coupled to a pH electrode.

Procedure: The instrument was immersed in a perfectly shaken sample of water and the readings in degree Celsius were recorded (Ramteke and Moghe, 1988). In the case of dissolved gas like dissolved oxygen, the temperature has a great influence on the solubility of this gas in water as shown by the values taken from Benson and Krause (1984) at temperature ranging from 20 to 40°C and at constant pressure: 960 mbar or 960 hPa (table11 of oxygen solubility).

Table 11: Influence of temperature on dissolved oxygen (DO)

Temp.in °C	DO in mg/L	DO calculated in mg/L	Residual
20	8.664	8.642	0.022
21	8.435	8.461	-0.026
22	8.272	8.288	-0.016
23	8.115	8.123	-0.008
24	7.963	7.965	-0.002
25	7.815	7.813	0.001
26	7.673	7.6688	0.005
27	7.535	7.528	0.007
28	7.401	7.393	0.007
29	7.271	7.263	0.008
30	7.144	7.137	0.006
31	7.022	7.016	0.006
32	6.902	6.898	0.004
33	6.786	6.784	0.002
34	6.673	6.673	-0.000
35	6.63	6.566	0.064
36	6.455	6.461	-0.006
37	6.35	6.359	-0.009
38	6.248	6.261	-0.013
39	6.148	6.164	-0.016
40	6.049	6.070	-0.021
SRS (Sum of Residues Squares)=		0.007	

Figure 14: Evolution of dissolved oxygen (DO) as a function of temperature at 960 mbar according to [Benson and Krause \(1984\)](#).

This curve is constructed from the tabular values established by [Benson and Krause \(1984\)](#) at temperature ranging from 20 to 40°C. According to this graph, it is reflected that dissolved oxygen is a logarithmic function whose slope is -3.71 and intercept is 19.756. For our case the origin is not zero but it is equal to 20. The function giving the dissolved oxygen (DO) as a function of the temperature ranging from 20°C to 40°C at the pressure of 960 mbar or 960 hPa is defined by:

$$\text{DO (mg/L)} = -3.71 \ln(T) + 19.756, \text{ where } T \text{ is the temperature in } ^\circ\text{C}.$$

It is also realized that the amount of dissolved oxygen in mg /L in this same temperature range decreases of 2.615 mg/L and by recalculating the concentrations of dissolved oxygen using the equation above, the Sum of Residuals squares (SRS) is equal to 0.007 ([Table11](#)), which proves that the

function chosen to estimate the amount of dissolved oxygen as a function of temperature reflects the reality. This equation shows the effect of temperature on the concentration of dissolved oxygen and can be used to calculate dissolved oxygen at a given temperature.

III.2.1.3 Dissolved Oxygen and percent of Oxygen saturation

Dissolved oxygen was measured in situ using a VWR oximeter.

Procedure: The measurement is done after calibration of the device and consists of immersing and stirring the probe in the water to be analyzed. The result is displayed in mg/L and the reading is done when the displayed value is stable. After reading, the probe is rinsed with demineralized water and wiped gently.

For calculating the percentage of oxygen saturation, the measured DO value (in-situ or in laboratory) is compared with the maximum value of dissolved oxygen that the water can contain at the observed temperature (during sampling). These maximum values are known and given in [table12](#). They correspond to the maximum amount of oxygen that can be dissolved in one liter of water at given temperatures.

Dissolved Oxygen saturation (%)

$$= \frac{(\text{mesured value of DO}) \times 100}{\text{Maximum value as per the } \a href="#">\text{table12}}$$

Table 12: Maximum concentration of dissolved oxygen (DO) according to temperature.

Temperature (°C)	Dissolved Oxygen (mg.L ⁻¹)	Temperature (°C)	Dissolved Oxygen (mg.L ⁻¹)
0	14.60	23	8.56
1	14.19	24	8.40
2	13.81	25	8.24
3	13.44	26	8.09
4	13.09	27	7.95
5	12.75	28	7.81
6	12.43	29	7.67
7	12.12	30	7.54
8	11.83	31	7.41
9	11.55	32	7.28
10	11.27	33	7.16
11	11.01	34	7.05
12	10.76	35	6.93
13	10.52	36	6.82
14	10.29	37	6.71
15	10.07	38	6.61
16	9.85	39	6.51
17	9.65	40	6.41
18	9.45	41	6.31
19	9.26	42	6.22
20	9.07	43	6.13
21	8.90	44	6.04
22	8.72	45	5.95

Source: CVRB (2005)

III.2.1.4 Electrical Conductivity

The electrical conductivity (in $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$) was obtained using the conductivity meter calibrated before each manipulation.

Procedure: The probe of the conductivity meter was immersed in the water by shaking slightly and reading on the screen of the device as soon as the value is stable. The device displays the measured value in $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ or in mS/cm . The probe is rinsed with demineralized water and wiped gently with paper after each measurement.

III.2.1.5 Total Dissolved Solids (TDS)

Total Dissolved Solids (in mg/L) of the water was obtained using TDS meter by immersing the electrodes in well-mixed sample water (Ramteke and Moghe, 1988). In the electrometric method, the conductivity measurement is used to calculate Total Dissolved Solids by multiplying conductivity ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$) by an empirical factor ranging from 0.55 to 0.9 based on the soluble constituents and temperature. Total Dissolved Solids (TDS) can be also measured through gravimetric method after filtration:

$$\text{Total dissolved Solids (mg/L)} = \frac{(A-B) \times 1000}{\text{Volume of sample (ml)}}$$

Where: A = weight of dried residue + dish, mg

B = weight of dish, mg.

III.2.1.6 Turbidity

The standard method for measuring turbidity has been based on the Jackson candle turbidity meter. Turbidity meter can be used for sample with moderate turbidity and nephelometer (in NTU) for sample with low turbidity. The measurement of turbidity using the turbidity tube method is based on the visual interpretation of the water turbidity. The visual appearance of the black cross mark at the tube bottom via the open end is used for the measurement of turbidity.

Procedure: Gently agitate sample, wait until air bubbles disappear and pour water sample into cell. Read turbidity directly from instrument display.

For Turbidity tube, water sample is poured into the cleaned turbidity tube that was placed above the white sheet placed on the floor. The open end of the tube was observed to visualize the black markings from the distance of 7 to 10cm. The level of water at which the black mark was noted down.

III.2.1.7 Chlorides Ions

Argentometric method: The chlorides are determined by volumetric titration using silver nitrate (Bougherira et al., 2014) according to the AFNOR T90-014 standard described by Rodier et al. (2009). This method is used for analyzing the chloride ion occurring in natural water. The mercurimetric method is recommended when an accurate determination of chloride is required, particularly at low concentrations. The potentiometric method is only appropriate in case of coloured or cloudy sample. Argentometric method is the simplest one and can be the method of choice for variety of samples.

Principle: The quality of sample for estimation of chloride should be 100mL or a suitable portion diluted to 100mL. The chloride is measured in natural or slightly basic solution by titration method using standard silver nitrate and potassium chromate as an indicator. Silver chloride is precipitated first and then, red silver chromate is formed. The chemical reactions involved in this method are given below:

The end of the reaction is marked by the appearance of the brick-red tint due to the formation of Ag_2CrO_4 .

Apparatus: Porcelain dish of 200mL, Pipettes, Burettes and Glass rod

Reagents and standards:

- ✓ Potassium chromate indicator solution: Dissolve 50g $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$ in a little distilled water and add AgNO_3 solution till the appearance of red precipitate. Let stand for 12 hours, filter and dilute to 1 L with distilled water.
- ✓ Standard silver nitrate titrant 0.0141M (0.0141N): Dissolve 2.395g of AgNO_3 in distilled water and dilute to 1000 mL; (1mL of 0.0141N $\text{AgNO}_3 = 0.5 \text{ mg Cl}^-$) and store in brown bottle.

Standardize against 10 mL standard of NaCl diluted to 100 mL, following the procedure described for the samples:

$$N = 0.0141 * \frac{\text{Volume(ml) of Standard NaCl}}{V - B}$$

Where: N = normality of AgNO_3

V = Volume in mL of AgNO_3 titrant for sample

B = Volume in mL of AgNO_3 titrant for blank

- ✓ Standard Sodium chloride 0.0141M (0.0141N): dissolve 824.1mg of NaCl (dried at 40°C) in distilled water and dilute to 1000mL; (1mL of 0.0141N NaCl = 0.5 mg Cl^-).
- ✓ Special reagents for removal of interferences (Colour and turbidity):
 - Aluminum hydroxide suspension: Dissolve 125g of aluminum potassium sulphate or aluminum ammonium sulphate [$\text{AlK}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 12\text{H}_2\text{O}$ or

$\text{Al}(\text{NH}_4(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 12\text{H}_2\text{O})$ in distilled water and dilute to 1000mL. Warm to 60°C and add 55mL concentrated ammonium hydroxide (NH_4OH slowly) with stirring. Let stand for 1 hour. Transfer to a large bottle and wash precipitate by successive addition with thorough mixing and decanting with distilled water until free from chloride. When freshly prepared, a suspension occupies a volume of approximately 1L.

- Others reagents for removal interferences are: Phenolphthalein indicator solution; Sodium hydroxide 1N; Sulphuric acid 1N; Hydrogen peroxide 30 percent.

Calibration: The silver nitrate solution should be standardized against sodium chloride solution of 0.0141N. It provides the force of silver nitrate solution 1 ml = 0.5 mg of chloride as Cl^-

Procedure:

- Use a sample of 100ml or an appropriate portion diluted up to 100 ml. If the sample is highly colored, add 3 ml of aluminium hydroxide [$\text{Al}(\text{OH})_3$] suspension, mix, let settle and filter. If sulphide, thiosulphate or sulphite is present, add 1 ml hydrogen peroxide, and then shake during 1 minute.
- Adjust sample pH to 7-10 with sulphuric acid or sodium hydroxide if it is not in the range, add 1 mL of potassium chromate (K_2CrO_4) indicator solution and titrate directly with AgNO_3 to a pinkish yellow end point. Titrate using a standard solution of AgNO_3 until the precipitation of Ag_2CrO_4 as a pale red precipitate.

- Establish reagent blank value by titration method. For having best exactness, titrate distilled water (50 ml) following the same manner to obtain a reagent blank. A blank of 0.2 to 0.3mL is usual.

The end of the reaction is marked by the appearance of the brick-red tint due to the formation of Ag_2CrO_4 which is 150 times less soluble than AgCl .

Calculation:

$$\text{Chlorides (mg/L) as } \text{Cl}^- = \frac{(V_1 - V_2) \times N \times 35.45 \times 1000}{\text{Volume(ml) of sample taken}}$$

Where:

V_1 = Volume in ml of silver nitrate (AgNO_3) required for sample

V_2 = Volume in ml of silver nitrate (AgNO_3) required for blank titration

N = Normality of silver nitrate (AgNO_3) Solution used.

III.2.1.8 Total Alkalinity

There are two variants of alkalinity: (i) Phenolphthalein alkalinity (PA) which is measured on samples having a pH higher than 8.3 and used to measure the amount of strong acid needed to lower the pH of sample to 8.3 and (ii) Total alkalinity (TA) or methyl orange alkalinity which is a measure of amount of strong acid needed to lower the pH of sample to 4.5. TA is also the sum of hydroxides, carbonates and bicarbonates.

Both variants of alkalinity (PA and TA) can be determined by volumetric titration with standard sulphuric acid (0.02N) or hydrochloric acid (0.001N) solution at room temperature using phenolphthalein and methyl orange indicator respectively. Titration until Phenolphthalein discoloration indicates entire neutralization of OH^- and half of CO_3^{2-} , whereas sharp change from

yellow to orange of methyl orange which indicates total alkalinity (complete neutralization of OH⁻, CO₃⁻ and HCO₃⁻).

The form of related equation is as follows:

Reagents:

- Distilled Water: the pH of the used distilled water must be greater than 6.0. If the pH of the water is below 6.0, it should be boiled for 15 minutes and allowed to cool to room temperature. Deionized water may be used provided that it has a conductance of less than 2µs/cm and a pH more than 6.0.
- Sulphuric Acid: Dilute 5.6 ml of concentrated sulphuric acid (relative density 1.84) to 1 liter with distilled water.
- Standard solution of sulphuric acid (0.02N)
- Standard solution of hydrochloric acid(0.001N)
- Phenolphthalein indicator: dissolve 0.5g phenolphthalein in 100 ml, water-alcohol mixture 1: 1 (v / v).
- Mixed indicator solution: Dissolve 0.02mg of methyl red and 0.01mg bromocresol green in 100ml, 95 percent, ethyl or isopropyl alcohol.

Procedure with standard sulphuric acid (0.02N):

Pipette 20 ml or an appropriate aliquot of sample into a 100 ml beaker. If the pH of the sample is greater than 8.3, add 2 to 3 phenolphthalein indicators and titrate using a standard solution of sulfuric acid until the

appearance of pink color observed by indicator just disappears (equivalence of pH 8.3). Note down the volume of standard sulfuric acid solution used.

Add 2 to 3 drops of mixed indicator to the solution in which the alkalinity of phenolphthalein was determined. Titrate with standard acid until the appearance of light pink color (equivalence of pH=3.7). Note down the standard acid volume used after phenolphthalein alkalinity

Calculation: Calculate alkalinity in the sample as follows:

$$\text{Phenolphthalein alkalinity (as mg/L of CaCO}_3\text{)} = \frac{A \times N \times 50000}{V}$$

$$\text{Total alkalinity (as mg/L CaCO}_3\text{)} = \frac{(A+B) \times N \times 50000}{V}$$

Where: A= Volume in ml of standard sulphuric acid used to titrate to pH 8.3
(For Phenolphthalein)

B= Volume in ml of standard sulphuric acid used to titrate from pH 8.3 to pH 3.7 (For methyl orange)

N= normality of acid used

V = Volume in ml of sample used for testing

Procedure with hydrochloric acid (0.001N):

Add three drops of phenolphthalein to 100 ml of the sample solution. The mixture is colored pink. Proceed to titration of the mixture with 0.001N HCl until the total discoloration.

Phenolphthalein Alkalinity (meq. /L)

$$= \frac{V_{\text{HCl}} \times N_{\text{HCl}} \times 1000 \times 2}{\text{Volume(ml) of the Sample taken}}$$

$$\text{Total Alkalinity (meq. /L)} = \frac{(V_{\text{HCl}} - 0.5) \times N_{\text{HCl}} \times 1000 \times 2}{\text{Volume(ml) of the Sample taken}}$$

Where: $V_1 \text{ HCl}$ = Volume (ml) of HCl used to determine CO_3^{2-} ions.
 N_{HCl} = Normality or Concentration of the HCl titrant solution.
 $V_2 \text{ HCl}$ = Total volume (ml) of HCl used from the beginning until the end of titration.

III.2.1.9 Total Hardness, Calcium hardness and Magnesium hardness

Hardness is determined by EDTA titrimetric method. In an alkaline condition, EDTA reacts with Ca and Mg to form a soluble chelated complex. Ca and Mg ions lead to the appearance of wine red color when combined with Black Eriochrome T. When EDTA is added as a titrant, Ca and Mg divalent ions get complexed resulting in a sharp change from wine red to blue which indicates end point of the titration. At higher pH, about 12, Mg^{2+} ions precipitate and only Ca^{2+} ions remain in the solution. At this pH, the murexide indicator turns to pink colour when combined with Ca^{2+} . When EDTA is added Ca^{2+} gets complexed resulting in the change from pink to purple, which indicates end point of the reaction.

Reagents:

- Buffer solution: Dissolved 16.9g of ammonium chloride (NH_4Cl) in 143ml of conc. Ammonia solution (NH_4OH). Added 1.25g of magnesium salt of ethylenediaminetetraacetate (EDTA) to obtain a sharp colour change of indicator and dilute to 250ml with distilled water. Store in a plastic bottle stoppered tightly for no longer than one month.

- Complexing agent: Magnesium salt of 1, 2 cyclohexanediaminetetraacetic acid. Add 250mg per 100 mL of sample only if interfering ions are present and sharp end point is not obtained.
- Inhibitor solution: Dissolved 4.5g of hydroxylamine hydrochloride in 100ml of 95% ethyl alcohol or isopropyl alcohol.
- Eriochrome Black T sodium salt (Indicator): Dissolve 0.5 g of dye in 100 mL of triethanolamine or 2 ethylene glycol monomethyl ether. The salt can be used also in the form of dry powder by grinding 0.5g of dye with 100 g of NaCl.
- Standard EDTA titrant 0.01M: Weigh 3.723g di-sodium salt of EDTA, dihydrate, dissolve in distilled water and dilute to 1000mL. Store in polyethylene bottle.
- Murexide indicator: Prepared a ground mixture of 200mg of murexide with 0.2g ammonium purpurate and 40g potassium sulphate.

Standard Calcium Solution: Weigh 1g of anhydrous CaCO_3 in a 500mL flask. Slowly add 1+1 HCl through a funnel until dissolution of all CaCO_3 . Add 200mL of distilled water and boil for a few minutes to expel CO_2 . Cool and add a few drops of methyl red indicator and adjust to the intermediate orange colour by adding 3N NH_4OH or 1+1HCl, as required. Transfer quantitatively and dilute up to 1000 mL using distilled water, 1mL = 1mg CaCO_3

Procedure:

Total Hardness: To 25ml of the well-mixed sample taken in a conical flask, 2ml of buffer solution and 1ml of Sodium hydroxide was added. Add a

pinch of eriochrome black T and titrate immediately with 0.01M EDTA until the bright red colour of the wine changes to blue colour.

Calcium Hardness: To 25ml of the well-mixed sample taken in a conical flask, 1ml of sodium hydroxide was added to raise the pH to 12.0 and titrated immediately with EDTA till the pink colour changes to purple.

The volume of EDTA consumed for total hardness and calcium hardness were noted down (Ramteke and Moghe, 1988).

Magnesium hardness (mg/L as MgCO₃) =

(Total hardness as mg CaCO₃/L - Calcium Hardness as mg CaCO₃/L).

Calculation:

$$\text{Total Hardness (mg/L as CaCO}_3) = \frac{(\text{V1} * \text{N}) \text{ of EDTA} * 1000}{\text{Volume (ml) of Sample taken}}$$

$$\text{Calcium Hardness (mg/L as CaCO}_3) = \frac{(\text{V2} * \text{N}) \text{ of EDTA} * 1000}{\text{Volume (ml) of Sample taken}}$$

Where:

V1 = Volume of EDTA consumed by the sample for total hardness titration

V2: Volume of EDTA consumed by the sample for Calcium hardness titration

N = Concentration of EDTA (mg of CaCO₃ equivalent to 1mL EDTA titrant)

Furthermore, **Total Hardness (mg/L as CaCO₃):**

= Calcium Hardness (mg/L as CaCO₃) + Magnesium hardness (mg/L as CaCO₃).

= 2.50 * Calcium conc. (mg/L as Ca²⁺) + 4.12 * Magnesium conc. (mg/L as Mg²⁺).

Magnesium (mg/L as Mg²⁺) = (Total hardness as mg CaCO₃/L - Calcium Hardness as mg CaCO₃/L) x 0.2427
= Magnesium hardness multiplied by 0.2427

III.2.1.10 Chemical Oxygen Demand

Chemical Oxygen Demand determination is much easier, precise and unaffected by interferences as compared with B.O.D. test and the results can be obtained within 5 hours.

Principle: The organic material occurring in the sample is oxidized by potassium dichromate (K₂Cr₂O₇) in the presence of excess sulfuric acid (H₂SO₄) or silver sulphate (AgSO₄) and mercury sulphate to produce CO₂ and H₂O. The sample is refluxed with a known amount of potassium dichromate (K₂Cr₂O₇) in the sulphuric acid medium and the excess potassium dichromate (K₂Cr₂O₇) remaining after the reaction is then titrated against ferrous ammonium sulphate solution (Fe(NH₄)₂.SO₄)₂. The volume of potassium dichromate consumed for oxidation of organic matter is equivalent to the amount of oxygen required to oxidize the organic matter.

Reagents:

i. **Standard potassium dichromate reagent-digestion solution:** weigh exactly 4.913 g of K₂Cr₂O₇ dried at 103°C during 2 to 4 hours and transfer it to a beaker. Weigh **accurately** 33.3 g of mercuric sulphate and add it to the same beaker. Measure precisely 167 ml of concentrated sulfuric acid

with a clean dry test tube and transfer it to the beaker. Dissolve the contents and cool to room temperature (if not dissolved keep it overnight). Take a 1000 ml standard flask and place a funnel on it. Transfer the contents carefully into 1000 ml standard flask and bring it to 1000 ml with distilled water. This is the standard potassium dichromate solution to be used for digestion.

ii. Sulphuric acid reagent-Catalyst solution: Weigh accurately 5.5g of silver sulphate crystals to a dry clean 1000mL beaker. To this, add carefully about 500mL of concentrated sulphuric acid and allow standing for 24hours so that the silver sulphate crystals dissolve completely

iii. Standard Ferrous Ammonium Sulphate Solution: Weigh accurately 39.2g of Ferrous Ammonium Sulphate $\{(Fe (NH_4)_2. (SO_4)_2.6H_2O)\}$ crystals and Dissolve it in distilled water. Take 1000mL standard measuring flask and place a funnel over it. Transfer the contents carefully to the 1000 ml standard flask and make it up to 1000 ml with distilled water.

iv. Ferroin Indicator: Dissolve 1.485g of 1-10 phenonhtrolene and 0.695g of Ferrous Sulphate ($FeSO_4.7H_2O$) in water and dilute to 100 ml with distilled water.

v. Mercuric sulphate: $HgSO_4$.

Procedure: Take two tubes and put 2.5mL of water sample in one tube and 2.5mL of distilled water in another tube called blank. Add 1.5mL of potassium dichromate to both the tubes and then carefully, add 3.5mL of sulphuric acid reagent to both tubes. Tightly close the tubes kept in COD

digestor at 150°C for 2 hours and after this time, cool the room temperature. Transfer the content of the plank tube to the conical flask and add 2 drops of ferroin indicator, the solution colour becomes bluish green.

Titrate the contents with ferrous ammonium sulphate taken in the burette till the appearance of reddish brown color at the end point of the titration and note down the volume of ferrous ammonium sulphate solution consumed by the blank (V1).

Transfer the content of the sample tube to the conical flask and add 2 drops of ferroin indicator and the solution colour becomes green.

Titrate the contents with ferrous ammonium sulphate taken in the burette till the appearance of reddish brown color at the end point of the titration and note down the volume of ferrous ammonium sulphate solution consumed by the sample (V2). The Chemical Oxygen Demand Concentration is given

$$\text{by: COD (mg/L)} = \frac{(V1 - V2) * N * 8 * 1000}{\text{Volume (ml) of Sample taken}}$$

Where,

V1 = Volume (mL) of Ferrous Ammonium Sulphate required for the blank.

V2 = Volume (mL) of Ferrous Ammonium Sulphate required for the sample

N = Normality of Ferrous Ammonium Sulphate

(Note: 1 mL 1N K₂Cr₂O₇ = 8 mg COD).

III.2.1.11 Biochemical Oxygen Demand

The test is carried out at 20°C for 5 days considered as the standard. Normally two methods are used for the determination of BOD:

- **Direct Method:** BOD is determined by measuring dissolved oxygen of waste water/effluent before and after incubation period of 5 days at 20°C.
- **Seeded Dilution Method:** In seeded dilution method, before the BOD test, dilution water is seeded with proper kind and number of organisms from various sources (Domestic wastewater, unchlorinated or non-disinfected effluents from biological wastewater treatment facilities and surface water receiving sewage discharges contain a lot of microbial populations). It is important that a mixed group of organisms is called 'seed'. In absence of toxic substances all necessary nutrients such as nitrogen and phosphorous should be present.
- **Interference:** Heavy metals and residual chlorine are commonly observed as interference in this process. Residual chlorine can be removed by the addition of equivalent amount of sodium sulphite solution.

Reagents:

i. Phosphate Buffer Solution (pH = 7.2) : Dissolve 8.5g of potassium dihydrogen phosphate (KH_2PO_4); 21.75g of dipotassium hydrogen phosphate (K_2HPO_4) + 33.4 g of disodium hydrogen phosphate ($\text{Na}_2\text{HPO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$); 1.7g of ammonium chloride (NH_4Cl) in water and dilute to 1000 ml with distilled water.

- ii. **Magnesium sulphate solution (2.25%):** Dissolve 22.5g of Magnesium Sulphate ($\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$) in water and dilute to 1000 ml with distilled water.
- iii. **Calcium chloride solution (2.75%):** Dissolve 27.5 g of calcium chloride (CaCl_2) in water and dilute to 1000 ml with distilled water.
- iv. **Ferric Chloride Solution (0.025%):** Dissolve 0.25g of ferric chloride ($\text{FeCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$) in water and dilute to 1000 ml with distilled water.
- v. **Sodium Sulphite Solution (0.025N):** Dissolve 1.575g of sodium sulphite (Na_2SO_3) in water and dilute to 1000ml with distilled water.
- vi. **Potassium iodide KI** (Crystal: AR/GR); **Starch indicator** (0.2%) solution; **Acetic acid** (Glacial acetic acid).

Procedure: Preparation of dilution water

- a. Aerate the required volume of distilled water in a PVC container by bubbling compressed air for 1-2 days to attain saturation: Add 1ml phosphate buffer; 1 ml magnesium sulphate solution; 1 ml calcium chloride solution; 1 ml ferric chloride solution and dilute the solution to 1000 ml with aerated water and mix thoroughly.
- b. In case of waste water/effluent, which are not expected to have sufficient bacterial population, add 2ml seed into dilution water. (Normally, 2 ml settled sewage is considered sufficient for 1000 ml dilution water).
- c. Neutralize the sample to $\text{pH} = 7$ if it is highly alkaline or acidic accordingly.
- d. Removal of residual chloride: Take suitable aliquot of sample in 250 ml beaker/volumetric flask; add 10 ml of 1:1 acetic acid solution; dilute with

distilled water if necessary; add about 1g KI solid (yellow colour appears if R-Cl₂ is present); titrate the content against standard sodium sulphite (Na₂SO₃) solution using starch as an indicator; Calculate the volume of sodium sulphite required for aliquot taken and add calculated volume/amount of sodium sulphite in aliquot sample taken for the determination of BOD.

- e. If samples having high dissolved oxygen i.e. above 9mg/l due to algal, reduce dissolved oxygen by agitating the sample.
- f. Several dilutions of prepared sample are to be done so as to obtain about 50% depletion of Dissolved oxygen in dilution water but not less than 2mg/l dissolved oxygen.
- g. Siphon out seeded dilution water in a volumetric flask/measuring cylinder half the required volume; add required quantity of mixed sample solution and dilute the desired volume by siphoning dilution water and mix thoroughly.
- h. The following dilutions are suggested for better results: For strong trade waste = 0.1% to 1%; Raw or settled sewage= 1% to 5%; Treated effluent= 5% to 15% and River Water= 25% to 100%.
- i. Siphon the dilution prepared as above in 4 labeled BOD bottles (300 ml capacity) and stopped immediately.
- j. Keep one bottle for determination of initial dissolved oxygen and incubate 3 bottles at 20°C for 5 days (**Note:** Confirm that bottles have water sealed).

- k. Prepare a blank in duplicate by siphoning plain dilution of water (without seed) to determine the oxygen consumption in dilution water.
- l. Fix the bottles kept for immediate D.O. determination and blank: Add 2ml of MnSO₄ solution in each bottle; add 2 ml of acid reagent in a mixture solution of NaOH + KI + NaN₃(500g NaOH + 150g KI +10g NaN₃ in 1 liter distilled water).

Calculations: D.O is Determined in the sample and in the blank on initial day and after 5 days of incubation at 20°C:

$$\text{When water dilution is not seeded: BOD}_5 \text{ (mg/L)} = \frac{D_i - D_f}{P}$$

$$\text{When water dilution is seeded: BOD}_5 \text{ (mg/L)} = \frac{(D_i - D_f) - (B_i - B_f)f}{P}$$

Where:

D_i =D.O.of the diluted sample for initial day, immediately after preparation,mg.L⁻¹

D_f = D.O. of the diluted sample after 5days of incubation at 20°C, mg.L⁻¹

B_i = D.O. of the seed control or blank (seeded dilution water) for initial day, after preparation, mg.L⁻¹

B_f = D.O.of the seed control or blank (seeded dilution water) for final day (after 5days of incubation), mg.L⁻¹.

P is the decimal volumetric fraction of sample used (it is the % of sample concentration).

$$\text{So, } P = \frac{\text{Initial volume of the sample(before dilution)}}{\text{Final Voume of the sample(after dilution)}}$$

f is the ratio of seed volume in dilution solution to seed volume in BOD test on seed.

$$\text{So, } f = \frac{\text{Volume of seed in diluted sample}}{\text{Volume of seed in seed control}}$$

III.2.1.12 Total Carbon, Total Organic Carbon and Total Nitrogen

Total Carbon, Total Organic Carbon and Total Nitrogen were measured using a SHIMADZU TOC-meter-TOC-L Model, equipped also with nitrogen measurement unit of TNM-L model. For the analysis of TOC, a preliminary step comprising acidification with 1M HCl followed by degassing remove of all the mineral forms of the carbon. The degassing step can also eliminate volatile organic carbon (also called cleanable organic carbon), if it is present. In natural waters and drinking waters, this content in volatile organic compounds is generally negligible and the analysis can thus access to the entire TOC. Considering the oxidation technique used in organic carbon analyzers (combustion, chemical oxidation, catalytic oxidation, UV irradiation, or coupling of these methods) which allows a quasi-total oxidation of the various organic structures, the major fraction of the Organic matter from natural waters is taken into account in this parameter.

Principle: The carbon compounds contained in the water undergo oxidation that converts them into carbon dioxide (CO₂), which is then measured using an infrared analyzer (NDIR: for our case). Since the carbon of inorganic origin is previously removed by degassing in an acid medium, the determination leads directly to the TOC content of the sample. TC is measured in the same way as TOC but without the addition of acid 1M HCl (Rodier et al., 2009).

Regarding TN, it was measured on the same instrument using TN measuring unit, TNM-L model whose principle consists of an oxidation of a sample containing nitrogen by oxygen to nitrogen oxide (NO_x) at high temperature (720°C for our case).

Quantification of the Total Nitrogen (TN) concentration is done using a chemiluminescent detector that detects NO_x, integrates the surface under the peak and converts the latter into total nitrogen concentration (TN). The concentrations of TC, TOC and TN are obtained by comparing them with the standards EN12260.

The Figures 15, 16 and 17 show the calibration curves obtained with the TOC-meter "TOC-L" for the parameters TC, TN and NPOC (NPOC = TOC for our case).

Figure 15 :Graph illustrating TC calibration curve obtained with TOC-L/ASI-L

Figure 16: Graph illustrating TN calibration curve obtained with TOC-L/ASI-L

Figure 17: Graph illustrating TOC calibration curve obtained with TOC-L / ASI-L

Operating mode: Filter if necessary the sample to be analyzed on a GF/C glass micro filter whose pores diameter is 0.45 μm . Introduce each sample

to be analyzed into a small glass tube and place it on a SHIMDZU automatic sampler, model ASI-L. Place also TC, TN and NPOC standards (NPOC=TOC) on it.

Turn on the air compressor, turn on the Parker brand air purification generator technically called "Zero-air" which heats the air upto 571°C, and turn on the measurement device. Using "TOC-L Controller" software, program these standards and samples by indicating their positions on the autosampler or Autosampler ASI-L and their identifications in a program sheet. When the device is ready, start the measurements. After the analysis, the device gives the results of CT, TN and NPOC (NPOC=TOC) expressed in mg/L. Export and save the results into an Excel work book while encoding them correctly in the work book and proceed to their processing.

III.2.1.13 Total Phosphorus (TP)

Total Phosphorus is measured using spectrophotometer with infrared photo tube at 880nm or filter photometer equipped with a red filter, acid washed glassware using dilute HCl and rinse with distilled water.

Reagents

- a. Phenolphthalein indicator aqueous solution.
- b. Sulphuric acid, H₂SO₄ 10N: Carefully add 300 mL conc H₂SO₄ to approximately 600 ml of distilled water and dilute to 1 litre.
- c. Persulphate: (NH₄)₂S₂O₈ or K₂S₂O₈, solid

- d. Sulphuric acid, H_2SO_4 , 5N: Dilute 70 mL conc. H_2SO_4 to 500 mL with distilled water.
- e. *Potassium antimonyl tartrate solution*: Dissolve 1.3715g K (SbO) $\text{C}_4\text{H}_4\text{O}_6 \cdot 1/2 \text{H}_2\text{O}$ in 400 mL distilled water and dilute to 500 mL, store in glass-stoppered bottle.
- f. *Ammonium molybdate solution*: Dissolve 20g of $(\text{NH}_4)_6\text{Mo}_7\text{O}_{24} \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in 500 mL of distilled Water and stock it in a glass-stoppered flask.
- g. *Ascorbic acid, 0.1M*: Dissolve 1.76g ascorbic acid in 100 mL distilled water, keep at 4°C , and use within a week.
- h. *Combined reagents*: Mix 50 mL 5N, H_2SO_4 , 5 mL potassium antimonyl tartrate, 15 mL Ammonium molybdate solution, and 30 mL ascorbic acid solution, in the order given and at room temperature. Stable for 4 hours.
- i. *Stock phosphate solution*, Dissolve 219.5mg anhydrous KH_2PO_4 in distilled water and dilute to 1 L; 1 mL = $50\mu\text{g PO}_4^{3-}$ - P.
- j. *Standard phosphate solution*: Dilute 50 mL stock solution to 1L with distilled water; 1mL = $2.5\mu\text{g P}$.

Procedure

- a. To 50 mL portion of thoroughly mixed sample add one drop phenolphthalein indicator Solution. If a red colour develops, add 1 mL of 10N H_2SO_4 just to discharge colour and either 0.4 g $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$ or 0.5 g $\text{K}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$.
- b. Boil gently on a preheated hot plate for 30 to 40 min or until a final volume of 10 mL is reached.

- c. Cool, dilute to 30mL with distilled water, add one drop phenolphthalein indicator solution and neutralize to a faint pink colour with NaOH and make up to 100 mL with distilled water. Do not filter the solution if a precipitate is forming at this step. It will redissolve under acid conditions of the colourometric test.
- d. Take 50 mL of the digested sample into a 125 mL conical flask, add 1 drop of phenolphthalein indicator. Discharge any red colour by adding 5N H₂SO₄. Add 8 mL combined reagent and mix.
- e. Wait for 10 minutes, but no more than 30 minutes and measure absorbance of each Sample at 880nm. Use reagent blank as reference.
- f. Correction for turbid or coloured samples: Prepare a sample blank by adding all reagents except ascorbic acid and potassium antimonyl tartrate to the sample Subtract blank absorbance from sample absorbance reading.
- g. Preparation of calibration curve: Prepare calibration from a series of standards between 0.15-1.30 mg P.L⁻¹ ranges (for a 1cm light path) by first carrying the standards through identical persulphate digestion process. Use distilled water blank with the combined reagent. Draw a graph with the absorbance as a function of the phosphate concentration to obtain a straight line. At least, test one phosphate standard with each set of samples.

Calculation: TP as mg.L⁻¹ =
$$\frac{\text{mg P from the calibration curve} \times 1000}{\text{Volume of Sample (ml)}}$$

III.2.1.14 Heavy Metals

A. Techniques and instruments used

For our study case, heavy Metals analysis were performed using Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometry(AAS), which is a technique used for determining the concentration of a particular metal element within a sample. In this method, a light of a specific wavelength is transmitted through the atomic vapor of the desired element and attenuation of the light intensity is measured as a result of absorption. The quantitative analysis using AAS is depending on a precise measurement of the intensity of light and on the assumption that the absorbed radiation is proportional to the concentration of the desired element. AAS can be used to analyze the concentration of over 62 different metals in water. There are two widely used AAS techniques for determining metals in water:

i. Flame Atomic Absorption Spectroscopy (FAAS)

In this method, the sample is aspirated and atomized into a flame through which radiation of a selected wavelength (using a hollow cathode lamp) is sent. A beam of light is directed through the flame into monochromator and detector which measures the quantity of light absorbed by the atomized element through the flame. The quantity of absorbed radiation at the specific wavelength in the flame is proportional to the concentration of the desired element in the sample over a limited concentration range and is the quantitative measure for the concentration of the element to be analyzed. This technique is used for the determination of metals in water where the

requirements are at ppm levels. The basic instruments for Flame Atomic Absorption Spectroscopy comprise four main parts: The light beam from **the light source (Hollow Cathode Lamp)** (1) which passes through the absorption **chamber (flame)** (2) in which the element is brought to the atomic status, before being focused on the entrance slot of **the monochromator** (3) which selects a very narrow range of wavelengths. The optical path ends on the entrance slot of **the detector** (4) as shown on the [figure18](#).

Figure 18: Basic components of Flame AAS

Source: http://www.fisica.unam.mx/liquids/images/tutorials/atomic_abspectro01.gif

ii. Graphite Furnace Atomic Absorption Spectrometry (GFAAS)

It is a highly sensitive spectroscopic technique that provides excellent detection limits for measuring concentrations of metals in water where the requirements are at very low levels (ppb). This method has been used for

the present study and the heavy Metals analyzed are: Iron (Fe), Cadmium (Cd), Chromium (Cr), Copper (Cu), Lead (Pb), Selenium (Se) and Arsenic (As). GFAAS uses the same principle as direct flame atomization, but the difference is that the standard burner head is replaced by an electrically heated graphite atomizer or furnace. A discrete sample volume is dispensed into the graphite sample tube. Generally, the analyses are performed by heating the sample in three or more steps. First, a low current heats the tube to dry the sample. The second or charring stage destroys organic matter and volatilizes other matrix components at an intermediate temperature. Finally, the current heats the tube to incandescence and in an inert atmosphere, atomizes the element being determined. Additional stages frequently are added to aid in drying a charring, and to clean and cool the tube between samples. The resultant ground-state atomic vapour absorbs monochromatic radiation from the source. A photoelectric detector measures the intensity of transmitted radiation.

The inverse of transmittance is related logarithmically to the absorbance, which is directly proportional to the number density of vaporized ground-state atom over a limited concentration range. The basic instruments for Graphite Furnace Atomic Absorption Spectrometry (GFAAS) comprise four main parts as for the Flame AAS except that the burner head producing flame is replaced by the furnace as shown on the [figure 19](#):

Figure 19: Basic components of a Graphite Furnace AAS

Source: <http://rampages.us/gaineskm/wpcontent/uploads/sites/16771/2016/04/gfaas.png>

B. Reagents

- ✓ Reagent water (ASTM type-1)
- ✓ Nitric acid (Suprapure 70%)
- ✓ Standard of metals - stock standard solutions traceable to NIST are available from a number of commercial suppliers (Merck & Sigma) or alternatively prepare from reagent as mentioned in APHA 3111B
- ✓ Air- Air is cleaned & dried through a suitable filter to remove oil, water and other foreign substances. The source may be a compressor or commercially bottled gas. Argon Gas- Minimum purity 99.99%
- ✓ Matrix modifier :
 - Magnesium nitrate-(10g/L): Dissolve 10.5g of $\text{Mg}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in water. Dilute to 100 ml.
 - Palladium nitrate-(4g/L): Dissolve 8.89 g $\text{Pd}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ in water and dilute to 1000 ml.

- Phosphoric acid- (10% v/v): Add 10 ml of conc.H₃PO₄ to water and dilute to 100 ml.
- Nickel nitrate-(10g/L): Dissolve 4.96g of Ni (NO₃)₂. 6H₂O in water and dilute to 100 ml.
- Citric acid-(4%): Dissolve 40g of citric acid in water and dilute to 1Liter.

C. Interference

- ✓ Electrothermal atomization determinations may be subjected to significant interferences from molecular absorption as well as chemical and matrix effect. Molecular absorption may occur when components of sample matrix volatilize during atomization, resulting in broadband absorption. When such phenomena occurs use background correction to compensate for this interference.
- ✓ Matrix modification can be useful in minimizing interference and increasing analytical sensitivity. Chemical modifier generally modifies relative volatilities of matrix and metal. Some modifiers inhibit metal volatilization, allowing use of higher ashing/charring temperatures and increasing efficiency of matrix removal.

D. Programming Furnace:

- ✓ Drying temperature: 110°C during 30seconds
- ✓ Decomposition temperature: 450°C during 20seconds
- ✓ Atomization temperature: 1300°C during 3seconds
- ✓ Washing temperature: 1900°C during 3seconds
- ✓ The absorbance measurement at a wavelength of 228.8nm and 10µl of a solution
- ✓ Matrix modifier is added during the assay.

E. Procedure:

- ✓ **Sample Preparation:** Colorless and transparent water samples with turbidity of <1.0 can be directly analyzed by AAS for total metals after acidifying with concentrated HNO_3 (1.5ml HNO_3/L of water). Sample digestion is not required.
- ✓ **Standard Preparation:** Prepare a series of standard metal solution in the optimum concentration range by appropriate dilution from their stock solution with ASTM type1 water containing 1.5ml concentrated HNO_3/L , using the following dilution calculator equation: $N1.V1 = N2.V2$

Where,

N1: Normality or Concentration of initial solution

V1: Volume of initial Solution

N2: Normality or Concentration of final solution

V2: Volume of final Solution

- ✓ **Determination by instrument:** Inject a measured portion of pretreated sample into the graphite furnace .Use same volume as was used to prepare the calibration curve. Add modifier immediately after adding the sample, preferably using an automatic sampler or a micropipette. Use the same volume and concentration of modifier for all standards and samples as given in the table. Dry, char and atomize according to the preset program in the method. Repeat until reproducible results are obtained. Compare the average absorbance value or the area of the peak with the calibration curve to measure the concentration of the concerned element. Alternatively, the results can be read directly if the instrument is equipped with this feature. If absorbance (or

concentration) or peak area of the sample is greater than absorbance (concentration) or peak area of the most concentrated standard solution, dilute sample and reanalyse.

Table 13: Potential Matrix Modifiers for Graphite furnace AAS.

Modifier	Analyses for which modifier May be Useful
1500 mg Pd/L + 100mg Mg(NO ₃) ₂	Ag, As, Cu, Mn, Hg, Sb, Se, Tl
500-2000 mg Pd/L + Reducing agent (Citric acid 1-2% preferred)	Ag, As, Cd, Cr, Cu, Fe, Mn, Hg, Ni, Pb, Sb
5000 mg Mg(NO ₃) ₂ /L	Co, Cr, Fe, Mn,
100-500 mg Pd/L	As
50 mg Ni/L	As , Se , Sb
2% PO ₄ + 1000mgMg(NO ₃) ₂	Cd , Pb
Use 10µl modifier/ 10 µl sample	

✓ **Calculation:**

Read the concentrations directly from the instrument and multiply by appropriate dilution factor if sample has been diluted. Report the result in mg/L.

Metal concentration in sample (mg/L) = Sample concentration from instrument (mg/L) X Dilution factor (if any).

III.2.2 Biological analysis

III.2.2.1 Determination of Chlorophyll a

Principle: The method consists in filtering of a water sample of known volume on a filter of 20µm mesh size. The filter is salvaged and the chlorophyll pigments are dissolved in a suitable solvent (90% acetone). The amount of Chlorophyll a is determined by spectrophotometric method by measuring the optical densities at the appropriate wavelengths ($\lambda = 665\text{nm}$ and $\lambda = 750\text{nm}$) before and after acidification.

Apparatus:

- Spectrophotometer with cuvette of 1, 4, and 10cm path lengths; Tissue grinder; Clinical centrifuge; Centrifuge tubes of 15 mL graduated with screw cap.
- Fluorometer Sequoia-Turner Model 450 or other equivalent fluorometer
- Filtration equipment: Glass Fiber (or membrane) filters (GFF) of 0.45 μm porosity and 47 mm diameter or Millipore filters of 0.8 μm mesh size in cellulose acetate and cellulose nitrate, vacuum pump, solvent
- Resistant disposable filter assembly of 1.0 μm pore size and 10 mL solvent resistant syringe.
- Sterile polypropylene tubes of 15 ml without additive with 16 to 100 mm caps

Reagents:

- Saturated solution of magnesium carbonate (MgCO_3): add 1g of MgCO_3 finely powdered in 100 mL of distilled water.
- Acetone solution 90% in demineralised water ($\text{H}_2\text{C}=\text{O}=\text{CH}_2$, 90% v/v): Mix 90 parts acetone with 10 parts saturated magnesium carbonate solution. For this, use a graduated cylinder and add 100 ml de-ionized water to 900 ml acetone.
- Mother solution of Chlorophyll-a at 4 mg / Liter of concentration
- Standard solutions of chlorophyll a in acetone 90% at concentrations 1, 2, 5, 10, 20, 50 and 100 μg / Liter.
- Hydrochloric acid (HCl 0.1N): Mix 8.6 ml of HCl with 100ml of De-ionized water.

Procedure:

- **Filtration:** The crude water is filtered immediately after sampling in a 100 ml volumetric flask through a filter of 20 μm mesh size. The algae containing the pigments are retained on this filter and the filtered

volume is selected between 50 ml and 5Liter depending on the transparency of the sample. The crude water sample is then filtered under vacuum, on a 0.8 μm fiberglass membrane on which 2ml of saturated magnesium carbon solution are deposited in order to promote filtration and prevent chlorophyll-a alteration.

- **Pigment extraction:** The filter is folded and placed in a 15ml centrifuge tube containing 10ml of 90% acetone where it dissolves instantly. The use of filters which dissolves completely in acetone simplifies greatly the extraction procedure and allows the extract to be stored in the freezer for a maximum of one month before assaying. The supernatant is recovered and filtered through a syringe filter to separate it from debris. The filter and pigment extract must be protected from light. For this purpose, it is recommended to wrap the tubes in aluminum foil.
- **Measurement:** Cuvettes of 10 to 50 mm optical path are used, depending on the estimated concentration (more or less intense coloration of the extract):
 - ✓ Transfer 3 mL of the supernatant (the 20 μm extract of the sample to be measured) into the spectrophotometer cuvette with a 10 to 50 mm optical path.
 - ✓ Set up the cuvette and ensure its correct positioning and read the absorbances of non-acidified extracts at wavelengths of 665 and 750nm. After the first measurement, acidify the chlorophyllian extracts (10 mm cuvette), by adding 15 μl of hydrochloric acid (1N HCl). Wait for 2 to 3 min and read the crude absorbances of the acidified extracts at 665 and 750 nm.

- **Results Calculation (Formula of Lorenzen):** Subtract the 750nm OD values from the readings before acidification (OD 665nm) and after acidification (OD 665nm) and then, Use the corrected values to calculate chlorophyll a.

Corrected Chlorophyll a ($\mu\text{g/L}$ or mg/m^3):

$$= \frac{26.7 \times [(665b - 750b) - (665a - 750a)]V1}{V2 \times L}$$

$$= \frac{26.7 \times (665b - 665a) \times V1}{V2 \times L}$$

Where:

V1 = Volume of solvent used for extraction in milliliters.

V2 = Volume of filtered water (Sample) in Liters.

L = light path or width of the cuvette used in cm.

665b & 750b = Absorbances at 665 and 750 nm before acidification
(Corrected absorbance based on turbidity before acidification).

665a & 750a = Absorbances at 665 and 750 nm after acidification
(Corrected absorbance based on turbidity after acidification).

665b = Subtract 750 nm values (turbidity correction) from the absorbance at 665 nm before acidification.

665a = Subtract 750 nm values (turbidity correction) from the absorbance at 665 nm after acidification.

OD: Optical Density.

The value 26.7 is the absorbance correction factor and is equal to $A \times K$

Where: **A** = absorbance coefficient for chlorophyll a, at 664nm = 11.0

K = ratio expressing correction for acidification = 2.43

III.2.2.2 Bacteriological analysis: Escherichia coli and Coliforms Test***Equipment and materials***

- a. Mechanical blender, Blender jars.
- b. A weighing scale of a capacity of at least 2 kg and sensitivity of 0.1g
- c. Petri dishes and vials made of glass or plastic
- d. Sterile pipettes of 1ml, 5ml and 10 ml, graduated in 0.1 ml units.
- e. Dilution bottles of 160 ml made of borosilicate glass, with rubber stopper or plastic screw caps equipped with Teflon liners.
- f. Water bath thermostated at $48 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ for tempering agar
- g. Incubator, to maintain $35 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$
- h. Colony counter, dark-field with suitable light source and grid plate.
- i. Autoclave for sterilization at 121°C .

Reagents and Culture medium: Buffered Peptone water (BPW), Plate count Agar (PCA) and Overlay Medium (Agar Medium)

Principle:

The aerobic plate count is used to determine the total number of aerobic organisms in a particular water sample and Plate Count Agar (PCA) is a growth medium commonly used to assess the total or viable bacterial growth of a water sample. A series of dilutions of the sample is mixed with an agar medium in plates and incubated at different temperatures ($35 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$ during $24 \pm 2\text{h}$ for Total Coliform; $44 \pm 0.2^\circ\text{C}$ during $24 \pm 2\text{h}$ for coliform fecal; 37°C during $21 \pm 3\text{h}$ for Escherichia Coli).

The number of microorganisms per milliliter of sample is calculated from the number of colonies obtained on PCA plate from selected dilution. It is

assumed that each visible colony is the result of multiplications of a single cell on the agar surface.

Procedure:

- i. Add 1ml of the water sample to a tube containing 9ml of Buffered Peptone water (BPW) and shake the mixture properly. This results in a dilution 10^{-1} .
- ii. Using separate sterile pipettes, prepare decimal dilutions of 10^{-2} , 10^{-3} , 10^{-4} , etc by transferring 1ml of previous dilutions to 9ml of diluents (Peptone water). Shake all dilutions sufficiently to homogenize the mixture.
- iii. Pour into each Petri plate 15–18 ml of the molten sterilized PCA medium (agar cooled to 44°C - 47°C)
- iv. Inoculate 1ml of the water sample dilution using sterile pipette into sterile petri plates in duplicate in two sets. The petri plates should be labeled with the sample number, date and any other desired information.
- v. Immediately mix sample dilutions and agar medium thoroughly and uniformly to obtain homogenous distribution of inoculums in the medium.
- vi. Allow agar to cool and solidify. In case, where in sample microorganism having spreading colonies is expected, add 4ml of overlay medium onto the surface of solidified plates.
- vii. After complete solidification, invert the prepared plates and incubate promptly under different temperature according to the targeted bacteria

(35±0.5°C during 24±2h for Total Coliform; 44±0.2°C during 24±2h for coliform fecal; 37°C during 21±3h for Escherichia Coli).

- viii. After the ideal period of incubation, count all colonies including pinpoint colonies. Spreading colonies shall be considered as single colony. If less than a quarter of the dish is overgrown, count the colonies on the unaffected side and calculate the corresponding number throughout the dish. If more than one quarter is overgrown by spreading colonies, discard the plate.

Calculation and expression of results:

CFU/mL/plate = (no. of colonies x dilution factor) / volume of culture plate

Case 1: Plates having microbial count between 10 and 300cfu

$$N = \frac{\text{Colonies Plate 1} + \text{Colonies Plate 2}}{2}$$

Case 2: Plates having microbial count less than 10cfu but at least 4, Calculate the results as given in Case 1.

Case3: If microbial load is from 3 to 1 then reporting of results shall be: "Microorganisms are present, but, less than 4 per mL".

Case 4: When the test sample/plates contains no colonies then reporting of results shall be: "Less than 1CFU/mL".

Figure 20: Microorganisms counting process

Source: <https://nptel.ac.in/courses/102103015/module5/lec1/images/3.png>

III.2.2.3 Sampling and taxonomic identification of fish species

The fish species sampling was carried out twice per month during three months (January, February and March both for 2017 and 2018). Fish samples were collected from various sampling sites with the help of local fishermen using different types of nets namely gill nets, cast nets and drag nets and much other valuable information were obtained by physical verification and interview with resident adjacent to the selected sites (Figure 21). All the collected fish specimens were identified at the point of

capture according to the Taxonomic identification keys of Paugy *et al.* (2003), Dutta Munshi and Shrivastava (1988); Talwar and Jhingran (1991), Vishwanath (2002) and Jayaram(1999), Allen (1991), Watson (1992), Allen *et al.* (2000) and Marquet *et al.* (2003). The identification of the scientific names corresponding to the vernacular names cited by the fishermen was made using the Lexicon of Kirundi names established by Ntakimazi, Nzigidahera and Fofu (2007). The taxonomic list of the collected species followed the organization proposed by Nelson (1994), as well as the modifications suggested by Fink & Fink (1981), Lauder & Liem (1983).

Figure 21: Group interview with local fishermen at Kajaga station. The big fish caught is named *dinotopterus tanganicus* (Isinga).

The comparative study of the spatial variations of the diversity of fish population for the studied stations was carried out using two commonly used indices: Jaccard (1908) and Sorensen (1948) coefficients which show the similarity or dissimilarity between fish species recorded in the sampling stations on the basis of the presence-absence of species.

III.2.2.4 Planktonic population analysis

Water sample collection: Planktons are heterogynous group of organisms which include both phytoplankton and zooplankton. Water sample for both phytoplankton and zooplankton analysis was collected using a can of 20 liters volume from the surface with minimal disturbance in the morning time between 7:00 to 9:00 am and for obtaining the maximum of organisms, 100 liters of the collected water were filtered through a cloth net of mesh size 63 μm and diameter 16cm (figure 22). At the lower end of the plankton net, a graduated glass bottle is fitted to retain sedimented planktonic organisms. The final volume of the filtered sample was 125ml and was transferred to another plastic bottle of volume 125ml which was labeled mentioning the time, date and place of sampling.

Figure 22: Planktons collection by filtering through a cloth net

Source: Author (2018).

Sample concentration and preservation: The samples containing zooplanktons in 125ml plastic bottles were preserved by adding 5ml of 4% formalin solution and kept for 24 hours undisturbed to allow the sedimentation of plankton suspended in the water. After 24 hours, the supernatant was removed carefully without disturbing the sediments using a dropper or pipette and the final volume of concentrated sample ready for analysis was 50ml.

Qualitative and quantitative analysis of planktons:

For both qualitative and quantitative planktonic analysis, two methods were used: **(i) Sedgwick-Rafter cell method** and **(ii) Lackey's drop method**. Generally Sedgwick-Rafter cell method is used when the density of plankton and filamentous micro algae are less abundant in the sample whereas Lackey's drop method is being used when high density of plankton population is observed in the sample. The quantitative analysis of plankton is being performed by estimating the numbers of individuals observed under light microscope compounds in each species and the number of organisms was expressed in total organisms per liter using the formula. Many phytoplanktons are multi celled filamentous, others are colonized while some are solitary cell. Hence they are more conveniently expressed as units/Liter in counting. The qualitative analysis consists of Species identification from the sample using light microscope compounds and their taxonomic characterization based on morphological characteristics of each species. The zooplankton were identified up to a

taxonomic precision of species level, family and order in both Cladocera and Copepoda using keys given in [Appendix 6.3](#).

i. Sedgwick-Rafter cell method (was used for zooplanktons analysis).

For zooplanktons, the materials used were a graduated dropper or pipette, compound microscope more preferable inverted microscope and Sedgwick-Rafter cell which is a slide with a rectangular cavity of dimensions 50mm* 20mm *1mm(1000mm³=1ml). After shaking gently by inverting twice or thrice the concentrated sample bottle, a subsample of 1ml was transferred quickly in the cavity of Sedgwick-Rafter cell slide ([Figure 23](#)) using a dropper or graduated pipette and the slide was covered by a cover glass or cover slip of an appropriate and known area. Zooplanktonic organisms were observed and counted under the light microscope ([Dewinter binocular microscope, OLYMPUS BX60 model: Figure 25](#)) to the objective lens 40. Six strips were counted in Sedgwick-Rafter cell and organisms were expressed per liter using the following formula:

Calculation: Zooplanktons (Total organisms per Liter) = $\frac{N \times C}{V}$ With N:

$$\text{Organisms per Liter} = \frac{R \times 1000 \text{ mm}^3 \times 10^3}{L \times D \times W \times S}$$

Where:

N = Number of zooplanktons counted in 1ml of concentrated sample but expressed per liter.

C = Total volume in ml of the concentrated sample (50ml, after removal of the supernatant).

V = Total volume in ml of original sample (100 000ml, before filtration with plankton net).

R = Total number of organisms counted per subsample (in 1ml)

L = length of each strip (mm)

D = depth of a strip (mm)

W = width of a strip (mm). It is corresponding to the diameter of the view field and is measured with a transparent graduated ruler or 1cm² of graph paper instead of the slide.

S = number of strips counted.

ii. Lackey's drop method (was used for Phytoplankton analysis)

For phytoplanktons analysis, the materials used were glass slide, Cover slip or cover glass; graduated medicinal dropper, compound microscope. After sedimentation of phytoplanktonic species with formalin (4%) at the bottom of the flask, the concentrated sample bottle was shaken gently by inverting twice or thrice and after homogenization; a drop (0.1ml) of water sample was taken quickly from the bottom using a pipette or medical dropper. This drop is placed on a glass slide (Figure 24) and a coverslip of an appropriate and known area was carefully put over it. Phytoplanktonic organisms were observed and counted under the light microscope (Dewinter binocular microscope, OLYMPUS BX60 model: Figure 25) to the

objective lens 40. The whole of the cover slip was examined by parallel overlapping strips to count all the organisms in the drop and about 20 strips were examined in each drop. The number of subsamples to be taken was depending on the examining 2 to 3 successive subsamples without any addition of unencountered species when compared to the already examined subsamples in the same sample (APHA, 1985). Phytoplanktons were identified in species and family level using self-made keys as per Mpawenayo (1996) available online through the link given in Appendix 6.1. The species belonging to each group were noted down and number of individuals in each species was counted. The number of organisms was expressed in total organisms per liter using the formula according to Lackey's drop method:

$$\text{Calculation: Phytoplankton (Total organisms per Liter)} = \frac{N \times C}{V}$$

$$\text{With N: Organisms per Liter} = \frac{R \times A_c \times 1000}{A_s \times S \times V_c}$$

Where:

N = Number of phytoplanktons counted in 0.1ml drop of concentrated sample and expressed per liter.

C = Total volume in ml of the concentrated sample (50ml, after removal of the supernatant).

V = Total volume in ml of original sample (100 000ml, before filtration with plankton net).

R = Number of organisms counted per subsample (in 0.1ml)

A_c = Area of coverslip in mm²

A_s = Area of one strip in mm²

S = Number of strips counted

V_c = Volume of sample under the cover slip in ml (V_c = 0.1ml)

Figure 23: Sedgwick-Rafter counting cell

Figure 24: Lackey's drop method Cell

Figure 25: Observation of Plankton cells under light microscope OLYMPUS BX60.

III.2.2.5 Species biodiversity measurement

III.2.2.5.1 Alpha diversity

The various diversity indices help to study the structure of fauna and flora, with or without reference to a concrete spatio-temporal context. They allow a quick assessment of the biodiversity in a single look. The variations of diversity index measurements for samples taken from the same area over time serve in tracking of community structure changes and characterization of its overall evolution over time. The species diversity is a measure of the species composition of an ecosystem in terms of the number of species and their relative abundance (Legendre & Legendre, 1998). The commonly used indices are:

i. Specific richness (S)

The specific richness (S) is the simplest measure of biodiversity and provides simply the total number of species recorded on a site. The observed species richness is a simple index, illustrating the ecological characteristics of an environment. This measure is strongly dependent on samples size and does not take into account the relative abundances of the different species. It measures the most basic diversity, based directly on the total number of species in a site and its ecological value is therefore limited (Travers, 1964). A large amount of species increase species diversity. Two species richness indices are widely used:

Margalef's diversity index (D_{ma}) = $(S-1) / \ln N$

Menhinick's diversity index (D_{me}) = S / \sqrt{N}

Where: **N** = the total number of individuals in the sample

S = the total number of species recorded.

ii. Relative diversity index of a family.

The relative diversity index of a family enables to highlight the relative importance of the large families dominant in a given ecosystem. The diversity of taxa in the community represents the number of species in a family over the total number of species, multiplied by 100. It is expressed as a percentage.

Relative diversity index of a family = $100 * (n_{ef} / N_{te})$

Where: **n_{ef}** = number of species in a family;

N_{te} = total number of species in the sample.

iii. The Shannon Wiener Index (H') (1949).

Also referred as Shannon-Weaver Index, it represents the average information provided by a sample on the stand structure from which the sample originates and how individuals are distributed among different species (Daget, 1976). This index serves as indicator of the environmental equitability based on information theory. It is the most commonly used index in ecology (Frontier, 1983; Gray et al., 1979; Collignon, 1991; Barbeault, 1992) as it considers both abundance and species richness. It is calculated as follows:

Shannon Wiener Index (H') = $-\sum_{i=1}^S [ni/N * \log_2(ni/N)]$

Where: **S**= Total number of species in the sample

ni = Number of individuals of a species in the sample

N= Total number of individuals of all species in the sample

It varies from 0 to infinity. The higher the value of the index H' , the greater the diversity. H' is minimal (= 0) if all individuals in the population belong to a single and same species. H' is also minimal if, in the population each species is represented by a single individual, except one species that is represented by all other individuals of the population. This index is maximal when all individuals are equally distributed over all species (Frontier, 1983 in Grall & Hily, 2003).

iv. Pielou's evenness index (1966) (E).

Shannon index is often accompanied by Pielou's evenness index (1966), also called equidistribution index (Blondel, 1979), which represents the ratio of H' to the theoretical maximum index in the population (H_{\max}). Pielou's evenness index (E) measures thus the equitability (or equidistribution) of the species in the station in comparison with an equal theoretical distribution for all the species. Evenness assessment is useful for detecting changes in community structure. It is calculated according to the following formula:

$$E = H' / H'_{\max} = H' / \log_2 S$$

Where: **H'**= Shannon-Wearver Index,

$$H'_{\max} = \log_2 S,$$

S = Total number of species present

log₂: the logarithm in base 2

The evenness index (E) varies from 0 (single species dominance) to 1 (equidistribution of individuals in the samples. It is maximal when the species have identical abundances in the population and it is minimal when a single species dominates the whole population. It is insensitive to specific richness and is therefore very useful for comparing potential dominance between stations or between sampling dates.

v. Simpson Index (Simpson, 1949)

Simpson Index measures the probability that two individuals randomly selected from the sampled population belong to the same species. This index is even lower than the number of species is large (the more species, the probability of taking 2 individuals of the same species becomes low). The addition of rare species modifies only the D value moderately (Grall & Hily, 2003), moreover, this index does not allow annual comparisons of the same site. This index is calculated as per the formula below:

Where: $D = \lambda = \sum_{i=1}^S (ni/N)^2$ (For an infinite sample)

$D = \sum [ni (ni - 1) / N (N - 1)]$ (For a finite sample)

\sum = is the sum of the obtained results for each species present

S = Total number of species in the sample

ni = Number of individuals of a species in the sample

N = Total number of individuals of all species in the sample

D varies between 0 and 1. This index will have 0 values for indicating the maximum diversity, and 1 to indicate the minimum diversity.

vi. Hill's indices Series (Hill, 1973)

Hill's diversity index is a measure of proportional abundance that associates the Shannon-Weaver and Simpson indices. Hill's index seems to be most relevant insofar as it integrates the other two indices and provides an even more accurate view of diversity. However, it may be useful to use the three indices together to extract as much information as possible and better understand the community structure (Grall & Hily, 2003). This index is given by the following equation:

Hill = (1/D) / e^{H'}, Where:

1/D = Inverse of the Simpson Index, for measuring the number of the most abundant individuals.

e^{H'} = Exponential of the Shannon-Weaver index, for measuring the number of abundant individuals but especially rare species.

The higher Hill's index approaches value 1, the lower the diversity is. For facilitating interpretation, it is then possible to use the inverse of Hill's index (1-Hill), where the maximum diversity will be represented by the value 1, and the minimum diversity by the value 0.

III.2.2.5.2 Beta diversity

Beta diversity refers to the importance of species replacement, or biotic changes, along environmental gradients (Whittaker, 1972). Beta diversity therefore measures the gradient of change in diversity between different habitats, sites or communities. The interest of beta diversity study is to

complete alpha diversity study (specific richness and diversity indices) and to ascertain the diversity at regional scale. Beta diversity can be measured using various indices among which, Jaccard and the Sorensen indices are primarily used.

i. Jaccard Index (1908) and Sorensen Index (1948)

These two indices enable the quantification of similarity between habitats. They are therefore used for comparing the number of common species between 2 sites in relation to the total number of species recorded. The similarity increases with the increase of the index value. It is allowed to use a single index and many authors prefer Jaccard Index than Sorensen Index. They are calculated from the measurements taken on the sampling stations (surveys, inventories, transect) as follows:

$$✓ \text{ Jaccard's Index: } S_j = \frac{C}{A+B+C}$$

This index can be modified to a coefficient of dissimilarity by taking its inverse:

$$\text{Jaccard's dissimilarity coefficient} = 1 - S_j = \frac{A+B}{A+B+C}$$

$$✓ \text{ Sorensen's Index: } S_s = \frac{2C}{2C+A+B}$$

This measure is very similar to Jaccard's measure and can also be modified to a coefficient of dissimilarity by taking its inverse:

$$\text{Sorensen's dissimilarity coefficient} = 1 - S_s = \frac{A+B}{2C+A+B}$$

Where:

S_j = Jaccard's similarity coefficient

S_s = Sorensen's similarity coefficient

C = Number of species common or shared between two sampling station

A = Number of species present only in the first sampling station.

B = Number of species present only in the second sampling station.

These indices vary from 0 to 1. They take the value 0 when the two transects have no similarity (no species in common) and 1 when the similarity is maximal (all the species are in common). From Jaccard or Sorensen indices obtained for each pair of sampling sites, it is possible to create a distance matrix. This matrix illustrates the dissimilarity of the sampling sites between them (distance = $1 - S_j$ or $1 - S_s$) and allows to obtain a dendrogram grouping the sites according to their more or less similarity.

III.3 Statistical Analysis

All the Statistical analyzes were performed using: Microsoft office excel 2007, XLSTAT 2019, PAST 3.06 and SPSS.20.0 at 95% & 99% confidence interval (CI) level. Variances were considered significant at “p-value” less than or equal to 0.05. Those analyzes includes:

- **A descriptive analysis** to describe the minimum, maximum, average and standard deviations corresponding to the biological and physicochemical parameters values.
- **Pearson's correlation analysis** to assess pair wise associations between variables (limnological parameters) and the strength of their relations;
- **One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA-1)** to test the significance of the differences between the mean data found in the study stations,

to show the effect of study sites on the variation of physico-chemical parameters values, and the effect of physico-chemical parameters on the variation of fish species number in sampling stations.

- **Tukey's Honestly Significant Difference test (Tukey's HSD)** which is also the one way ANOVA post hoc non parametric test used to test differences among sample means for significance. The Tukey's HSD is a statistical tool used to determine if the relationship between two sets of data is statistically significant and tests all pairwise differences while controlling the probability of making one or more type I errors.
- **Multivariate analyzes including:** Principal Component Analysis (PCA), Correspondence Factor Analysis (CFA) and Canonical Correlation Analysis (CCorA) Factorial which summarize the data correlation structure described by several quantitative variables by identifying underlying factors common to the variables for explaining a significant portion of the data variability. They are applied to the table of variables and take into account the overall variations in abundance between rows and/or columns. They allow the practitioner to reduce the number of variables and make the information less redundant.

CHAPTER-IV EXPERIMENTAL FINDINGS

IV.1 Physico-chemical parameters

The physico-chemical analysis of water is the first considerations for assessment of water quality for its best utilization like drinking, irrigation and Pisciculture purposes and helpful in the understanding of interaction between the climatic and biological process in the water.

In the present investigation, the physical and chemical parameters evaluated were Turbidity (Tur),Temperature (Te), Potential of Hydrogen (pH), Transparency (Tr),Total Alkalinity (TA), Electrical Conductivity (EC),Total Dissolved Solids (TDS),Chlorides (Cl⁻), Total Hardness (TH), Calcium (Ca²⁺), Magnesium(Mg²⁺), Iron (Fe), Total Carbon (TC), Total Nitrogen(TN), Total Phosphorus (TP), Dissolved Oxygen(DO), % of Oxygen Saturation, Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD), Biochemical Oxygen Demand (BOD) and some heavy metals like Cadmium (Cd), Chromium (Cr), Copper (Cu), Lead (Pb), Selenium (Se) and Arsenic (As).

The water analyzes were carried for a total of six months, at 3 months per year (January, February and March, in both 2017 and 2018) at all sampling stations.

The average quarterly data showing spatio-temporal variation of physico-chemical parameters every year are presented in [table14](#), the descriptive statistics data are presented in [table15](#) while the general average of physico-chemical parameters in comparison to International

Standards of water quality required for pisciculture are presented in the [table16](#).

Table 14: Spatio-temporal variation in physical and chemical characteristics of water.

Parameters	Kajaga		Nyamugari		Rumonge		Mvugo	
	2017	2018	2017	2018	2017	2018	2017	2018
Tur (NTU)	0.52	0.5	10.42	9.8	1.6	1.5	2.08	0.65
Te (°C)	28.1	27.1	27.9	28	28.1	29.8	27.8	29.4
Tr (cm)	190	210	110	130	161	175	143	180
TDS (mg.L ⁻¹)	453.59	443.54	453.59	444.88	448.9	440.86	448.9	442.87
pH	8.85	8.85	8.88	8.88	8.6	8.82	8.7	8.5
TA (mg.L ⁻¹)	349.6	300.5	351	340.6	339	335.6	343.6	355.6
EC (µS/cm)	677	662	677	664	670	658	670	661
Cl(mg.L ⁻¹)	46.15	47	33.73	30.8	37.28	39.25	37.15	35.15
TH (mg. CaCO ₃ .L ⁻¹)	226	210.4	197	189.2	204	211.3	161	172.9
Ca ²⁺ (mg.L ⁻¹)	58.8	54.65	33.2	34.95	42	43.18	36.4	39.22
Mg ²⁺ (mg.L ⁻¹)	19.2	17.93	27.7	24.74	24.06	25.11	17.01	18.19
Fe (mg.L ⁻¹)	0.03	0.021	0.02	0.018	0.17	0.161	0.08	0.089
TC (mg.L ⁻¹)	76.1	80.4	82.43	78.92	75.72	71.32	71.55	79.45
TN (mg.L ⁻¹)	0.29	0.38	0.15	0.15	0.16	0.11	0.23	0.19
TP (mg.L ⁻¹)	1.71	1.57	1.56	1.67	0.93	0.79	0.79	0.69
DO (mg.L ⁻¹)	7.71	7.51	7.47	7.39	7.35	7.16	7.19	7.21
DO (%)	98.7	94.5	95.6	94.66	94.1	94.99	92.06	94.03
COD (mg.L ⁻¹)	60	75	26	30	18	25	15	25
BOD (mg.L ⁻¹)	13	15	10	10.6	7	8	5	7.5
Cd (ppm)	0.003	0.002	0.001	0	0	0	0	0
Cr (ppm)	0.059	0.031	0.038	0.04	0.003	0.002	0	0
Cu (ppm)	0.174	0.162	0.083	0.081	0.098	0.079	0.011	0.008
Pb (ppm)	0.081	0.083	0.059	0.062	0.077	0.079	0.032	0.034
Se (ppm)	0.005	0.006	0.003	0.002	0	0	0	0
As (ppm)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Table 15: Descriptive statistics of physico-chemical parameters and water quality required for pisciculture.

Parameters	Mean per study site				Descriptive Statistical data			
	Kajaga	Nyamugari	Rumonge	Mvugo	Min	Max	G M	SD
Tur (NTU)	0.51	10.11	1.55	1.37	0.51	10.11	3.38	4.17
Te (°C)	27.60	27.95	28.95	28.60	27.60	28.95	28.28	0.57
Tr (cm)	200.00	120.00	168.00	161.50	120.00	200.00	162.38	30.44
TDS (mg.L ⁻¹)	448.57	449.24	444.88	445.89	444.88	449.24	447.14	1.93
PH	8.85	8.88	8.71	8.60	8.60	8.88	8.76	0.12
TA (mg.L ⁻¹)	325.05	345.80	337.30	349.60	325.05	349.58	339.44	10.08
EC (µS/cm)	669.50	670.50	664.00	665.50	664.00	670.50	667.38	2.89
Cl ⁻ (mg.L ⁻¹)	46.58	32.27	38.27	36.15	32.27	46.58	38.31	5.59
TH (mg. CaCO ₃ .L ⁻¹)	218.20	193.10	207.65	166.95	166.95	218.20	196.48	20.56
Ca ²⁺ (mg.L ⁻¹)	56.73	34.08	42.59	37.81	34.08	56.73	42.80	9.18
Mg ²⁺ (mg.L ⁻¹)	18.57	26.22	24.59	17.60	17.60	26.22	21.74	3.98
Fe (mg.L ⁻¹)	0.026	0.019	0.166	0.085	0.019	0.166	0.074	0.063
TC(mg.L ⁻¹)	78.25	80.68	73.52	75.50	73.52	80.68	76.99	2.90
TN(mg.L ⁻¹)	0.33	0.15	0.13	0.21	0.13	0.33	0.21	0.08
TP (mg.L ⁻¹)	1.64	1.62	0.86	0.74	0.74	1.64	1.21	0.45
DO (mg.L ⁻¹)	7.61	7.43	7.26	7.20	7.20	7.61	7.38	0.17
DO (%)	96.60	95.13	94.54	93.04	93.04	96.60	94.83	1.36
COD (mg.L ⁻¹)	67.50	28.00	21.50	20.00	20.00	67.50	34.25	20.77
BOD (mg.L ⁻¹)	14.00	10.30	7.50	6.25	6.25	14.00	9.51	3.18
Cd (ppm)	0.0025	0.0005	0	0	0	0.0025	0.0008	0.0011
Cr (ppm)	0.045	0.039	0.0025	0	0	0.045	0.0216	0.0219
Cu (ppm)	0.168	0.082	0.0885	0.0095	0.0095	0.168	0.0870	0.0600
Pb (ppm)	0.082	0.0605	0.078	0.033	0.033	0.082	0.0634	0.0206
Se (ppm)	0.0055	0.0025	0	0	0	0.005	0.0020	0.0024
As (ppm)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.0000	0.0000

Table 16 : Average results of physico-chemical parameters in comparison to the Standards of water quality required for pisciculture.

Parameters	General average	Conclusion: Suitable for fish culture (Yes or No)	Standards of water quality for pisciculture
Tur (NTU)	3.38	No	20–30NTU(Zweigh,1989)
Te (°C)	28.28	Yes	25°C – 30°C (FAO, 2006)
Tr (cm)	162.38	No	30 – 40 (ICAR,2007)
TDS(mg.L ⁻¹)	447.14	Yes	< 500 (USEPA,2006)
PH	8.76	Yes	6–9 (Davis, 1993)
TA (mg.L ⁻¹)	339.44	No	50–300 (ICAR,2007)
EC (µS/cm)	667.38	Yes	<3000 (MDTEE ,2003)
Cl ⁻ (mg.L ⁻¹)	38.31	No	>100 (SRAC, 2013)
TH (mg CaCO ₃ .L ⁻¹)	196.48	No	30–180 (ICAR, 2007)
Ca ²⁺ (mg.L ⁻¹)	42.80	Yes	>20 (SRAC, 2013)
Mg ²⁺ (mg.L ⁻¹)	21.74	-	NA
Fe (mg.L ⁻¹)	0.074	Yes	0.01–0.3 (ICAR,2007)
TC(mg.L ⁻¹)	76.99	-	NA
TN(mg.L ⁻¹)	0.21	Yes	< 0.3 (UNECE, 1994)
TP (mg.L ⁻¹)	1.21	Yes	0.01–3 (Piper et al, 1982)
DO (mg.L ⁻¹)	7.38	Yes	≥ 4 (ICAR,2007)
(%) DO	94.83	Yes	80 - 125% (CVRB, 2005)
COD(mg.L ⁻¹)	34.25	Yes	< 50 (ICAR,2007)
BOD(mg.L ⁻¹)	9.51	Yes	3 – 20 (Boyd, 2003)
Cd (ppm)	0.0008	Yes	<0.005 (MDTEE ,2003)
Cr (ppm)	0.0216	Yes	<0.05 (MDTEE ,2003)
Cu (ppm)	0.0870	No	<0.04 (MDTEE ,2003)
Pb (ppm)	0.0634	No	<0.03 (MDTEE ,2003)
Se (ppm)	0.0020	Yes	<0.01 (MDTEE ,2003)
As (ppm)	0.0000	Yes	<0.05 (MDTEE ,2003)

Note: A: Not Assigned, GM: general Mean, Min: Minimum, Max: Maximum, SD: Standard Deviation, (%) DO: Percent Saturation of Dissolved Oxygen.

IV.1.1 Physical parameters

Turbidity

During the present study, turbidity values ranged from 0.5 to 10.42 NTU (Table 14) with general average of 3.38 ± 4.17 NTU (Table 15). The mean comparison among sites shows a very highly significant difference in turbidity value ($p=0.00$), especially between Kajaga & Nyamugari, Rumonge & Nyamugari and Mvugo & Nyamugari (Table 20 & 21). The maximum values (10.42 NTU) was recorded at Nyamugari station in 2017 with annual mean of 10.11 NTU (Table 15). The minimum value (0.5 NTU) was recorded at kajaga station in 2018 with annual mean of 0.51 NTU. For Rumonge and Mvugo, Mean turbidity is 1.55 NTU and 1.365 NTU respectively. According to Zweigh (1989), Turbidity between 20 - 30 NTU is suitable for good fish culture but in present study it has been realized that results found are not in accordance with permissible range for pisciculture (Table 16).

Temperature

Temperature values recorded for the present study ranged from 27.1⁰C to 29.8⁰C (Table 14) with a general mean of 28.28 ± 0.57 ⁰C for all stations (Table 15). There is no significant difference in temperature variation for all sampling sites ($p=0.505$). The found values fall within the range of 25⁰C to 30⁰C suitable for optimum yield in fish culture recommend by FAO (2006) (Table 16).

Transparency

The transparency of the waters of Lake Tanganyika varies greatly depending on the location. The highest value recorded was 210cm at Kajaga site in February 2018 and lowest value was 110cm at Nyamugari site in January 2017 (Table 14). Mean data for Transparency are 200cm, 161.5cm, 168cm and 120cm respectively to Kajaga, Mvugo, Rumonge and Nyamugari stations (Table 15). The mean values obtained show significant difference among stations ($p=0.042$), especially between Kajaga & Nyamugari ($p=0.032$) (Table 21 & 22). According to Bhatnagar et al., (2004), transparency range of 30-80 cm is good for fish health; 15-40 cm is good for intensive culture system and transparency less than 12 cm causes stress. According to ICAR (Santhosh and Singh, 2007), the secchi disk transparency between 30 and 40 cm indicates optimum productivity of a pond for good fish culture. So the results found fall out of the standards required for fish culture (Table 16).

Total Dissolved Solids (TDS)

The values of TDS found in the present study fluctuated from 440.86 to 453.59 mg.L⁻¹ (Table 14) with a general mean of 447.14±1.93mg.L⁻¹ (Table 15). All values are close, therefore, no significant difference between stations ($p=0.857$). Maximum value was recorded at kajaga and Nyamugari stations and minimum value was found at Rumonge station. The TDS for all study stations were found in accordance with the standard range (less than 500mg.L⁻¹) suitable for fish farming (Table 16) set by the USA

Environmental Protection Agency (Charkhabi and Sakizadeh, 2006).The spatio-temporal variations of Physical parameters are shown on the figure 26:

Figure 26 : Spatio-temporal variation of Turbidity (A), Temperature (B), Transparency(C) and Total Dissolved Solids (D).

IV.1.2 Chemical parameters

Potential of Hydrogen (pH)

During the present study, pH values ranged from 8.5 to 8.88 (Table 14) with a general mean of 8.76 ± 0.12 (Table 15) and do not shows significant difference considering all sampling sites ($p=0.155$). These results indicated alkaline nature throughout the study period at all study sites and were in harmony with the Standards of water quality required for pisciculture recommended by Davis (1993) (Table 16).

Alkalinity

According to the guidelines established by ICAR (Santhosh and Singh, 2007) for water quality required for fish culture, the desirable value for fish culture range from 50-300 mg.L^{-1} . In the present study, the alkalinity value recorded range from 300.5 to 355.6 mg.L^{-1} (Table 14) with general mean of $339.441 \pm 10.08 \text{mg.L}^{-1}$ (Table 15) and there was no significant difference considering all sampling sites ($p=0.595$). Minimum and maximum were recorded in February 2018 respectively at Kajaga and Mvugo stations. The values obtained are slightly higher than the standards reported by Santhosh and Singh (2007) (Table 16).

Electrical conductivity

Electrical Conductivity recorded during the investigation ranged from 658 to 677 $\mu\text{S/cm}$ (Table 14) and the general average was $667.38 \pm 2.89 \mu\text{S/cm}$ (Table 15). The maximum value was observed at Myamugari and Kajaga stations in January 2017, minimum value is found at Rumonge site in

February 2018. The results are close and do not show significant difference among stations ($p=0.857$). According to (MDTEE, 2003) the suitable Electrical Conductivity value for fish culture is less than 3000 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ which is in accordance with the values found during the investigation (Table 16).

Chloride

Chloride obtained was in the range of 30.8 to 47 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ (Table 14). Kajaga site was found to have maximum value while minimum value was recorded at Nyamugari site. Considering all study sites, mean value was 38.31 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1} \pm 5.59$ (Table 15) and the results indicate a highly significant difference between stations ($p=0.003$), especially between Kajaga & Nyamugari ($p=0.002$) and Kajaga & Mvugo ($p=0.007$) and a significant difference between Kajaga & Rumonge ($p=0.016$) and Nyamugari & Rumonge ($p=0.049$) (Table 20 & 21). According to the Southern Regional Aquaculture Centre (SRAC, 2013), Chloride concentration higher than 100 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ is good for fish farming. So, for all the stations, the findings were very little compared to the standards reported by SRAC (Table 16).

Total hardness

Calcium and magnesium are the principal cations that impart hardness. According to ICAR (2007), the ideal value of hardness for fish culture ranges from 30-180 $\text{mgCaCO}_3 \cdot\text{L}^{-1}$. The hardness recorded in the present investigation ranged from 161 to 226 $\text{mg CaCO}_3\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ (Table 14). Maximum and minimum values were recorded in January 2017 at Kajaga and Mvugo sites respectively. Mean hardness was 196.48 $\pm 20.56\text{mg CaCO}_3\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ for all stations (Table 15) with a significant difference among stations ($p=0.011$),

especially between Kajaga & Mvugo ($p=0.01$) and Rumonge & Mvugo ($p=0.023$) (Table 20 & 21). Kajaga and Rumonge stations showed high hardness with respective averages of 218.2 and 207.65mg CaCO₃.L⁻¹. For all stations, the values found were greater than the standard range recommended by ICAR (2007) (Table 16). This implies that the water is too hard and the amount of water soluble salts is too high. So, decreasing of water hardness to reach the acceptable range is needed. It therefore implies that water pH and hardness can all be changed by adding lime to Lake.

Biochemical Oxygen Demand (BOD)

BOD is an indication of both sewage and industrial pollution. The BOD content of various sampling sites ranged from 5 to 15mg.L⁻¹ (Table 14) with a general mean of 9.5125±3.18mg.L⁻¹(Table 15). Kajaga and Nyamugari stations have high BOD Concentration with respective averages of 14 and 10.3mg.L⁻¹(Table 15). Rumonge and Mvugo stations show low mean value of 7.5 and 6.25mg.L⁻¹ respectively. For all stations, the BOD values recorded show a significant difference ($p=0.010$), especially between Kajaga & Rumonge ($p=0.019$) and Kajaga & Mvugo ($p=0.01$) (Table 20 & 21) but all the values were within the standards range of 3-20 mg.L⁻¹ recommended by Boyd (2003) (Table 16).

Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD)

According to guidelines for water quality management for fish culture in Tripura (ICAR, 2007), the desirable value of COD for fish culture should be

less than 50mg.L⁻¹. In the present study, the COD value ranged from 15-75mg.L⁻¹ (Table 14) and the general mean was 34.25±20.77mg.L⁻¹(Table 15) with a highly significant difference observed between stations (p=0.007), in particular between Kajaga & Rumonge (p=0.009) and Kajaga & Mvugo (p=0.008) (Table 20 & 21). Kajaga station showed high COD value with average of 67.5mg.L⁻¹ which is not desirable for fish farming according to ICAR (2007). Nyamugari, Rumonge and Mvugo stations showed respective mean values of 28mg.L⁻¹, 21.5mg.L⁻¹ and 35mg.L⁻¹ which are within the standards range (<50mg.L⁻¹) recommended by ICAR (2007) (Table 16). Thus, Kajaga station cannot be recommended for fish culture purposes if only COD is considered, while the three others stations are considered suitable for pisciculture.

Dissolved oxygen (DO) and % of oxygen saturation

DO content recorded during the investigation ranged from 7.16 to 7.71mg.L⁻¹ (Table 14) with general mean of 7.38±0.17mg.L⁻¹(Table 15) considering all the stations and from 92.06% to 98.7% of oxygen saturation (Table14) with general average of 94.83+1.36% saturation (Table 15). There is no significant difference in percent of oxygen saturation among the sampling sites (p=0.345) while the Dissolved Oxygen values show significant difference between stations (p=0.046), particularly between Kajaga and Mvugo (p=0.049) (Table 20 & 21). According to guidelines set by (ICAR, 2007) for water quality management for fish culture in Tripura, minimum concentration of DO should be maintained in fish ponds at all

times as suitable for fish culture is 4mg.L^{-1} ($\text{DO} \geq 4\text{mg.L}^{-1}$). Yovita John Mallya(2007) stipulated that Cold water fish require 6 mg.L^{-1} (70% saturation),Tropical freshwater fish need 5mg.L^{-1} (80% saturation), Tropical marine fish need 5 mg.L^{-1} (75% saturation) while 80-100% saturation is suitable for eggs and early fry(FAO, 2006b). According to CVRB (2005), the percent of oxygen saturation of 60 to 79% is acceptable for most of organisms living in running waters, 80 to 125% is excellent for most of running water organisms and 125% or more is too high and can be dangerous for fish. Generally, the values observed in running water should be greater than 80% saturation during the day time and 70% during night time. In a lake or estuary, values of 70% saturation are recommended while in salt water; values of 80% are acceptable. Thus, DO values found in the current investigation were within the desirable limits recommended by (ICAR, 2007) (Table 16). The % saturation of Dissolved Oxygen obtained was suitable for eggs and fry (FAO, 2006b) and excellent for most of organisms living in running water (CVRB, 2005).

Calcium ions

Concentration of Calcium ions indicates the hardness of water and the water hardness with 15mg.L^{-1} is satisfactory for growth of fishes (Rajasekar et al., 2005). SRAC (2013) stated that calcium higher than 20mg.L^{-1} ($>20\text{mg.L}^{-1}$) is suitable for fish Culture. Wurts and Durborow (1992) recommended the range of 25 to 100 mg.L^{-1} for free calcium in culture waters and according to them; the Channel catfish can tolerate minimum level of mineral calcium in their feed but may grow slowly under such

conditions. In the present study, Calcium ions ranged from 33.2 to 58.8 mg.L⁻¹(Table 14) with a general mean of 42.8 ±9.18mg.L⁻¹. Maximum and minimum values were found in January 2017 at Kajaga and Nyamugari stations respectively. Kajaga and Rumonge stations showed high Calcium ions with respective averages of 56.73 and 42.59mg.L⁻¹(Table 15). For all stations, the values found show a highly significant difference (p=0.001), particularly between Kajaga & Nyamugari (p=0.001), Kajaga & Rumonge (p=0.006) and Kajaga & Mvugo (p=0.002) and a significant difference between Nyamugari & Rumonge (p=0.038) (Table 20 & 21) but all the values found were in harmony with the standard range recommended by SRAC (2013), Wurts and Durborow (1992) (Table 16).

Magnesium ions

A specific recommended concentration of Magnesium for fish farming in freshwater and fish pond is not assigned. The United States Geological Survey reported median (middle) concentrations in domestic and public well water as 11mg.L⁻¹ (Desimone et al., 2009) and 10.7 mg.L⁻¹(Toccalino et al., 2010). In the present study, magnesium ions ranged from 17.01 to 27.7mg.L⁻¹ (Table14) with a general mean of 21.74±3.98mg.L⁻¹(Table 15). Maximum and minimum values were found in January 2017 at Nyamugari and Mvugo stations respectively. Nyamugari and Rumonge stations have high Magnesium content with respective averages of 26.22 and 24.59mg.L⁻¹. For all stations, the recorded values show a highly significant difference (p=0.006), especially between Nyamugari & Mvugo (p=0.008) and

significant difference between Kajaga & Nyamugari ($p=0.013$), Kajaga & Rumonge ($p=0.03$) and Rumonge & Mvugo ($p=0.018$) (Table 20 & 21) and it has been reflected that the water can not even serve as domestic and public well water (Table 16).

Iron

According to the guidelines for water quality management for fish culture in Tripura (ICAR, 2007), the suitable value of Iron for fish culture varies from 0.01 to 0.3 mg.L⁻¹. In the present study, Iron concentration ranged from 0.018 to 0.17mg.L⁻¹(Table 14). Maximum and minimum values were respectively recorded at Rumonge site in January 2017 and Nyamugari site in February 2018. Mean value was 0.074 ± 0.063 mg.L⁻¹ for all stations. The average obtained from the sampling sites was 0.026mg.L⁻¹ for Kajaga, 0.019 mg.L⁻¹ for Nyamugari, 0.166mg.L⁻¹ for Rumonge and 0.085mg.L⁻¹ for Mvugo (Table 15) and show a very highly significant difference between Kajaga & Rumonge, Nyamugari & Rumonge and Mvugo & Rumonge($p=0.000$) and a highly significant difference between Kajaga & Mvugo ($p=0.002$) and Nyamugari & Mvugo($p=0.001$) (Table 20 & 21). Thus, the results were in accordance with the standards recommended by ICAR (2007), hence all the stations are favourable to fish culture (Table 16).

Nutrients (TN, TP and TC)

Carbon, Nitrogen and Phosphorus are three vital elements required for algal growth that heavily affects eutrophication process in lakes. However, a specific recommended concentration of Total carbon suitable for fish

farming in freshwater and fish pond is not assigned and in the current study, Total carbon dose ranged from 71.32 to 82.43mg.L⁻¹ with general mean of 76.99±2.9mg.L⁻¹ and the difference among stations in total carbon concentration is not significant (p=0.367). Regarding Total Nitrogen, a Concentration less than 0.3mg.L⁻¹ is desirable for maintaining good aquatic life (UNECE, 1994). In the present study, Total Nitrogen recorded during the investigation ranged from 0.11 to 0.38 mg.L⁻¹(Table 14) with general average of 0.21±0.08mg.L⁻¹. Mean Concentrations per stations were 0.33mg.L⁻¹, 0.15mg.L⁻¹, 0.13mg.L⁻¹ and 0.21mg.L⁻¹ respectively for kajaga, Nyamugari, Rumonge and Mvugo stations (Table 15) and show significant difference (p=0.022), especially between Kajaga & Nyamugari (p=0.031) and Kajaga & Rumonge (p=0.023) (Table 20 & 21). Apart Kajaga site which showed Total Nitrogen value slightly greater than the standard range, the values obtained from others stations were within desirable limits for fish culture (Table 16) recommended by UNECE (1994). Regarding Total phosphorus, Piper et al. (1982) stated that the range of 0.01-3mg.L⁻¹ is suitable for pisciculture. Stone and Thomforde (2004) stated that phosphate level of 0.06 mg .L⁻¹ is desirable for fish culture. Bhatnagar et al. (2004) suggested 0.05-0.07mg.L⁻¹ as optimum and productive phosphorus range for fish farming. In the present study, Total Phosphorus values ranged from 0.69 to 1.71mg.L⁻¹(Table 14) with general average of 1.21±0.45mg.L⁻¹. The highest Total Phosphorus concentrations were observed at Kajaga and Nyamugari stations with respective averages of 1.64 and 1.62mg.L⁻¹ (Table15).The values found from all stations show a

highly significant difference ($p=0.001$), particularly between Kajaga & Rumonge ($p=0.003$), Kajaga & Mvugo ($p=0.002$), Nyamugari & Rumonge ($p=0.004$) and Nyamugari & Mvugo ($p=0.002$) (Table 20 & 21); and all the values were in accordance with the standards range reported by Piper et al. (1982), hence suitable for fish culture (Table 16).The spatio-temporal variations of chemical parameters are shown on the figure 27; 28 and 29:

Figure 27 : Spatio-temporal variation of Oxygen Percent Saturation (A), Chemical Oxygen Demand (B) and Biochemical Oxygen Demand(C).

Figure 28: Spatio-temporal variation of pH (A), Total Alkalinity (B), Electrical Conductivity (C), Chloride (D), Total Hardness (E) and Calcium (F).

Figure 29 : Spatio-temporal variation of Magnesium (A), Iron (B), Total Carbon (C), Total Nitrogen (D), Total Phosphorus (E) and Dissolved Oxygen (F).

Heavy Metals

The present study has only focused on Cadmium, Chromium, Copper, Lead, Selenium, and Arsenic. According to (i) MDTEE, (2003), (ii) Uzuoku (2013) and (iii) Piper et al. (1982), the heavy metals concentration range recommended for fish culture is described as follows:

Table 17: Desirable range of heavy metals dose recommended for pisciculture:

Heavy metal	Desirable range (mg.L ⁻¹)	Source
Chromium	<0.05	MDTEE (2003)
Selenium	<0.01	MDTEE (2003)
Arsenic	<0.05	MDTEE (2003)
Copper	<0.04	MDTEE (2003)
Cadmium	<0.01	Uzuoku (2013)
Lead	<0.03	Piper et al. (1982)

For the present study, **Cadmium** concentration was found very low with mean values of 0.0025mg.L⁻¹ and 0.0005mg.L⁻¹ at Kajaga and Nyamugari stations respectively. At Rumonge and Mvugo stations, cadmium concentration was found nil or zero. **Chromium** value was recorded as zero at Mvugo station while mean concentration was 0.045mg.L⁻¹ for Kajaga site, 0.039mg.L⁻¹ for Nyamugari site and 0.0025mg.L⁻¹ at Rumonge Site (Table 15). **Copper and Lead** was present at all study stations with slightly high concentrations. Indeed, mean values of copper are 0.168mg.L⁻¹, 0.082mg.L⁻¹, 0.0885mg.L⁻¹ and 0.0095mg.L⁻¹ respectively for Kajaga, Nyamugari, Rumonge and Mvugo stations (Table 15). Regarding **Lead**, averages concentration are 0.082mg.L⁻¹ for Kajaga site, 0.0605mg.L⁻¹ for Nyamugari site, 0.078mg.L⁻¹ for Rumonge site and

0.033mg.L⁻¹ for Mvugo site (Table 15) .Selenium was absent or nil at Rumonge and Mvugo stations but showed very low mean concentrations of 0.0055mg.L⁻¹ and 0.0025mg.L⁻¹ at Kajaga and Nyamugari stations respectively. Arsenic was totally absent or nil at all study sites. The heavy metals fluctuation in the sampling stations is presented on the Figure 30.

Figure 30: Spatio-temporal fluctuation of heavy metals concentration.

For all heavy metals analysed, it has been realized that the Concentration ranges of Cadmium, Chromium, Selenium and Arsenic were within the standards required for fish culture at all study stations although they show significant difference (respectively p*=0.020; p*=0.020 ; p**=0.001) (Table 20) except for Arsenic concentration which is same and equal to zero at all stations. Copper and lead Concentrations show a very highly significant difference among stations (p=0.000) (Table 20) and apart

from Mvugo station where Copper concentration was in harmony with the standards range, Copper and lead concentrations were found slightly high and polluting as they fall out of the ranges suitable for pisciculture for all study sites.

IV.1.3 General considerations on correlation (r) between variables

The statistical correlation is measured by correlation coefficient(r). Its numerical value ranges from +1 to -1 (or $-1 \leq r \leq +1$) and gives an indication of the strength of relationship between variables. The [table18](#) and the [figure 31](#) show the relationship strengthness between variables.

Table 18: Strength of relationship between variables

Strength of relationship	Value of Correlation coefficient (r)	
	Negative	Positive
Perfect	$r = -1$	$r = +1$
Strong	$-1 \leq r < -0.5$	$+0.5 < r \leq +1$
Moderate	$r = -0.5$	$r = +0.5$
Weak	$-0.5 < r < 0$	$0 < r < +0.5$
None	$r = 0$	$r = 0$

Figure 31: Strength of relationship between variables

Source: <https://image.slidesharecdn.com/mbaiqtunit-3correlation-150117014034-conversion-gate02/95/mba-i-qt-unit3correlation-45-638.jpg>

In general, $r > 0$ indicates positive linear relationship, $r < 0$ indicates negative linear relationship while $r = 0$ indicates no relationship (the variables are independent and not related). $r = +1$ describes a perfect positive correlation and $r = -1$ describes a perfect negative correlation.

IV.1.3.1 Pearson’s correlation (r) among physico-chemical variables

In the present study the correlation coefficient (r) between every parameter pairs is computed by taking the average values as shown in table 19.

Table 19: Correlation Coefficient (r) among physical and chemical parameters of Lake Tanganyika.

Plot	Tur	Te	Tr	PH	TA	EC	TDS	Cl-	TH	Ca ²⁺	Mg ²⁺	TC
Tur	1											
Te	-0.259	1										
Tr	-0.904*	-0.134	1									
PH	0.549	-0.778	-0.144	1								
TA	0.460	0.476	-0.776	-0.482	1							
EC	0.590	-0.932*	-0.227	0.852	-0.221	1						
TDS	0.590	-0.932*	-0.227	0.852	-0.221	1**	1					
Cl-	-0.734	-0.392	0.954*	0.156	-0.909*	0.051	0.051	1				
TH	-0.153	-0.383	0.479	0.660	-0.907*	0.256	0.256	0.654	1			
Ca ²⁺	-0.658	-0.458	0.917*	0.263	-0.946*	0.134	0.134	0.994**	0.722	1		
Mg ²⁺	0.730	0.160	-0.683	0.461	0.187	0.135	0.135	-0.571	0.244	-0.495	1	
TC	0.721	-0.848	-0.411	0.793	-0.023	0.979*	0.979*	-0.150	0.097	-0.069	0.218	1
Fe	-0.457	0.928*	0.151	-0.650	0.117	-0.949*	-0.949*	-0.077	-0.034	-0.132	0.142	-0.935*
TN	-0.504	-0.694	0.754	0.217	-0.671	0.393	0.393	0.842	0.332	0.835	-0.754	0.235
TP	0.474	-0.920*	-0.054	0.962*	-0.486	0.944*	0.944*	0.245	0.560	0.341	0.226	0.875
% DO	0.054	-0.766	0.370	0.864	-0.854	0.655	0.655	0.625	0.887	0.708	0.122	0.506
DO	0.107	-0.923*	0.327	0.854	-0.751	0.809	0.809	0.593	0.707	0.669	-0.049	0.675
COD	-0.282	-0.817	0.658	0.590	-0.868	0.576	0.576	0.846	0.683	0.886	-0.383	0.4
BOD	0.058	-0.904*	0.375	0.837	-0.787	0.774	0.774	0.633	0.736	0.707	-0.066	0.632
Cd	-0.237	-0.847	0.621	0.615	-0.844	0.617	0.617	0.817	0.664	0.860	-0.372	0.447
Cr	0.401	-0.952*	0.023	0.933*	-0.523	0.944*	0.944*	0.316	0.554	0.406	0.127	0.863
Cu	-0.129	-0.649	0.522	0.753	-0.939*	0.489	0.489	0.738	0.945*	0.808	0.055	0.319
Pb	-0.127	-0.284	0.423	0.628	-0.859	0.183	0.183	0.585	0.992**	0.653	0.332	0.035
Se	0.029	-0.943*	0.392	0.781	-0.741	0.797	0.797	0.640	0.638	0.704	-0.186	0.658

Plot	Fe	TN	TP	%DO	DO	COD	BOD	Cd	Cr	Cu	Pb	Se
Fe	1											
TN	-0.526	1										
TP	-0.818	0.425	1									
%DO	-0.492	0.553	0.860	1								
DO	-0.720	0.690	0.926*	0.952*	1							
COD	-0.565	0.892	0.709	0.869	0.920*	1						
BOD	-0.684	0.705	0.906*	0.961*	0.998**	0.935*	1					
Cd	-0.608	0.890	0.738	0.871	0.934*	0.999**	0.946*	1				
Cr	-0.842	0.512	0.995**	0.868	0.951*	0.766	0.932*	0.794	1			
Cu	-0.328	0.575	0.736	0.978*	0.891	0.874	0.912*	0.864	0.750	1		
Pb	0.060	0.219	0.497	0.834	0.627	0.589	0.657	0.567	0.481	0.9	1	
Se	-0.753	0.779	0.889	0.909	0.990**	0.951*	0.989**	0.964*	0.926	0.852	0.545	1

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (1-tailed)

* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (1-tailed)

The correlation coefficient (r) between any two parameters x and y is calculated for all parameters excepted arsenic which has nil value in all study stations.

A perfect positive correlation has been observed between Total Dissolved Solids and Electrical Conductivity ($r=1$, $p<0.01$) and each parameter is perfectly and positively correlated to itself ($r=1$, $p<0.01$).

A significant and strong positive correlation at the 1% level (1-tailed) is established between: Chloride and Calcium ($r=0.994$, $p<0.01$), Total Hardness and Lead($r=0.992$, $p<0.01$), Dissolved Oxygen and Biochemical Oxygen Demand ($r=0.998$, $p<0.01$), Selenium and Dissolved Oxygen ($r=0.990$, $p<0.01$), Cadmium and Chemical Oxygen Demand ($r= 0.999$, $p<0.01$), Biochemical Oxygen Demand and Selenium ($r=0.989$, $p<0.01$) and Chromium and Total phosphorus($r=0.995$, $p<0.01$).

A significant and strong positive correlation at the 5% level (1-tailed) is observed between: Temperature and Iron ($r=0.928$, $p<0.05$), Transparency and Chloride ($r=0.954$, $p<0.05$), Calcium and Transparency ($r=0.917$, $p<0.05$), pH and Chromium ($r=0.933$, $p<0.05$), Electrical Conductivity and Chromium ($r=0.944$, $p<0.05$), Total Dissolved Solids and Chromium ($r=0.944$, $p<0.05$), pH and Phosphorus ($r=0.962$, $p<0.05$), Copper and Total Hardness ($r=0.945$, $p<0.05$), Phosphorus and Biochemical Oxygen Demand ($r=0.906$, $p<0.05$), Dissolved Oxygen and Chromium ($r=0.951$, $p<0.05$), Cadmium and Dissolved Oxygen ($r=0.934$, $p<0.05$), Chemical Oxygen Demand and Dissolved Oxygen ($r=0.920$, $p<0.05$), Biochemical Oxygen Demand and Chemical Oxygen Demand

($r=0.935$, $p<0.05$), Chemical Oxygen Demand and selenium ($r=0.951$, $p<0.05$) Copper and Biochemical Oxygen Demand ($r=0.912$, $p<0.05$), Chromium and Biochemical Oxygen Demand ($r=0.932$, $p<0.05$) Cadmium and Biochemical Oxygen Demand ($r=0.946$, $p<0.05$), selenium and cadmium ($r=0.964$, $p<0.05$), chromium and selenium ($r=0.926$, $p<0.05$), Electrical Conductivity and Total phosphorus ($r=0.944$, $p<0.05$), Total Dissolved Solids and Total phosphorus ($r=0.944$, $p<0.05$), Electrical Conductivity and Total Carbon ($r=0.979$, $p<0.05$), Total Dissolved Solids and Total Carbon ($r=0.979$, $p<0.05$), Dissolved Oxygen and Total phosphorus ($r=0.926$, $p<0.05$).

Percent of Oxygen Saturation showed a significant and strong positive correlation at the 5% level (1-tailed) with Biochemical Oxygen Demand ($r=0.961$, $p<0.05$), Dissolved Oxygen ($r=0.952$, $p<0.05$), Copper ($r=0.978$, $p<0.05$) and Selenium ($r=0.909$, $p<0.05$).

A significant and strong negative correlation at the 5% level (1-tailed) is observed between: Turbidity and Transparency ($r=-0.904$, $p<0.05$), Electrical Conductivity and Iron ($r=-0.949$, $p<0.05$), Total Dissolved solids and Iron ($r=-0.949$, $p<0.05$), Total carbon and Iron ($r=-0.935$, $p<0.05$).

At the 5% level (1-tailed), Temperature showed a significant and strong negative correlation with Electrical Conductivity ($r=-0.932$, $p<0.05$), Total Dissolved Solids ($r=-0.932$, $p<0.05$), Dissolved Oxygen ($r=-0.923$, $p<0.05$), Chromium ($r=-0.952$, $p<0.05$), Selenium ($r=-0.943$, $p<0.05$), Biochemi

cal Oxygen Demand ($r=-0.904$, $p<0.05$) and Total phosphorus ($r=-0.920$, $p<0.05$).

Likewise, Total Alkalinity at the 5% level (1-tailed) showed a significant and strong negative correlation with Chloride ($r=-0.909$, $p<0.05$), Calcium ($r=-0.946$, $p<0.05$), Total Hardness ($r=-0.907$, $p<0.05$) and Copper ($r=-0.939$, $p<0.05$). In fact, the positive correlation between two variables means that the increase in value of one leads to the increase in value of the other. For the negative correlation, the increase in value of one leads to the decrease in value of the other.

IV.1.3.2 Principal Components Analysis (PCA)

Principal Component Analysis (PCA) is one of the most widely used multivariate data analysis methods for analyzing and visualizing multidimensional data sets consisting of individuals described by several quantitative variables. The principle of this method is to describe the data contained in a table of individuals and characters (or variables). This table or data matrix consists of rows representing individuals or observations and columns designated as variables. For obtaining a better data representation, the first principal components (also called dimensions or axes or Factors) given by the two best eigenvalues in terms of percentage are used. That is, the choice of axes F1 and F2 or F1 and F3 or F1 and F4 depends on their ability to represent the maximum of information compared to others. This information is called inertia or variability. The horizontal axis (F1) is the first dimension of PCA while the Vertical axis is the second

dimension of the PCA. In normed PCA, the variables projected on each factorial plane are within a circle of unit radius. The red vectors represent the variables studied. The more a variable is projected towards the edge of the circle, the better it is represented. In addition, two variables that are well represented and close to each other are positively correlated while two opposing variables are negatively correlated. Orthogonality between two variables indicates the absence of linear correlation.

For all the graphs (Figure 32, 33 and 34), F1 axis represents 62.17% of the initial information while F2 axis represents 26.26% of the initial information. Both F1 and F2 axis represent 88.43% of the initial information.

Figure 32: PCA Graph of Sampling sites observations

The figure 32 represents the observations chart indicating the proximity links between the sampling sites. Kajaga and Nyamugari sites seem to

have the same environmental characteristics and are opposed to Rumonge and Mvugo sites which are very close and seem also to have the same environmental conditions.

Figure 33: PCA Circle of correlations between physico-Chemical parameters.

The [figure 33](#) represents the circle of correlations between physico-chemical variables where the red vectors represent the variables studied. The physico-chemical variables forming acute angles ($\alpha < 90^\circ$) are positively correlated; the right angles ($\alpha = 90^\circ$) are formed by uncorrelated physico-chemical variables and the physico-chemical variables forming obtuse angles ($90^\circ < \alpha < 180^\circ$) are negatively correlated. The smaller the angle, the stronger the correlation between variables.

Figure 34: PCA biplot showing relation between sampling sites and Physico-chemical parameters.

The [figure 34](#) represents the biplot graph showing both the relationships between physico-chemical variables and shows how the sampling sites are described by the physico-chemical variables. The more a variable is closer to the sampling station point, the more the concentration of that variable is higher in that station. For example, the highest value of Temperature is recorded at Rumonge site while its minimum value is at Kajaga site. Likewise, the values of Cd, COD and Cu are higher at Kajaga Site than at other sites.

As a matter of principle, the PCA reduces the size of multivariate data to two or three principal components, which can be graphically visualized by removing the data redundancy and losing as little information as possible. It serves thus in positioning of individuals or groups of

individuals in the new space and to identify with the maximum of precision, the information hidden in a dataset, the relations of proximity (similarities) and of remoteness (oppositions) between the variables and the responsible phenomena of these relations.

IV.1.4 Effect of study stations on the variation of physico-chemical parameters

The One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA-1) at 5% level was performed to assess the effect of the sampling sites on the variation of physico-chemical parameters values. The results of one-way Analysis of variance (ANOVA-I) presented in the Table 20 indicated that the influence of the sampling stations on the variation of limnological parameters was:

Very highly significant ($p < 0.001$) for the parameters: Lead, Copper, Iron and Turbidity (for all, $p = 0.000$).

Highly significant ($0.001 \leq p < 0.01$) for the parameters: Chloride ($p = 0.003$), Calcium ($p = 0.001$), Magnesium ($p = 0.006$), Total Phosphorus ($p = 0.001$), Chemical Oxygen Demand ($p = 0.007$) and Selenium ($p = 0.001$).

Significant ($0.01 \leq p \leq 0.05$) for the parameters: Transparency ($p = 0.042$), Total Hardness ($p = 0.011$), Total Nitrogen ($p = 0.022$), Dissolved Oxygen ($p = 0.046$), Biochemical Oxygen Demand ($p = 0.01$), Cadmium ($p = 0.02$) and Chromium ($p = 0.02$).

Indeed, the very highly significant, highly significant and significant effect of the sampling stations on the variation of the physico-chemical parameters values means that the sampling stations have respectively a very strong,

strong and simple influence on the variation of limnological parameters value.

Not significant ($p>0.05$) for the parameters: Temperature ($p=0.505$), pH ($p=0.155$), Total Alkalinity ($p=0.595$), Electrical Conductivity ($p=0.857$), Total Dissolved Solids ($p=0.857$), Total Carbon ($p=0.367$) and % of Oxygen Saturation ($p= 0.345$). It means that the changes in the concentration of these parameters are not influenced by the sampling sites.

Table 20: One-way ANOVA to assess the effect of the sampling sites on the variation of physico-chemical variables.

Dependent Variables	Variation Source	Sum of Squares	Freedom Degree	Mean Square	F Test	p-value
Turbidity	between Study sites	121. 878	3	40.626	133.216***	0.000
	Within Study sites	1.220	4	0.305		
	Total Variance	123.098	7			
Temperature	between Study sites	2.245	3	0.748	0.927 ^{NS}	0.505
	Within Study sites	3.230	4	0.808		
	Total Variance	5.475	7			
Transparency	between Study sites	6487.375	3	2162.458	7.315*	0.042
	Within Study sites	1182.500	4	295.625		
	Total Variance	7669.875	7			
Potential of Hydrogen	between Study sites	0.101	3	0.034	3.053 ^{NS}	0.155
	Within Study sites	0.044	4	0.011		
	Total Variance	0.145	7			
Total Alkalinity	between Study sites	710.997	3	236.999	0.708 ^{NS}	0.595
	Within Study sites	1338.211	4	334.553		
	Total Variance	2049.208	7			
Electrical Conductivity	between Study sites	58.375	3	19.458	0.251 ^{NS}	0.857
	Within Study sites	309.500	4	77.375		
	Total Variance	367.875	7			
Total Dissolved Solids	between Study sites	26.205	3	8.735	0.251 ^{NS}	0.857
	Within Study sites	138.935	4	34.734		
	Total Variance	165.139	7			
Chloride	between Study sites	219.040	3	73.013	33.983**	0.003
	Within Study sites	8.594	4	2.149		
	Total Variance	227.634	7			
Total Hardness	between Study sites	2959.945	3	986.648	15.815*	0.011
	Within Study sites	249.550	4	62.387		
	Total Variance	3209.495	7			
Calcium	between Study sites	589.951	3	196.650	53.095**	0.001
	Within Study sites	14.815	4	3.704		
	Total Variance	604.766	7			
Magnesium	between Study sites	110.769	3	36.923	22.952**	0.006
	Within Study sites	6.435	4	1.609		

	Total Variance	117.204	7			
Total Carbon	between Study sites	58.856	3	19.619	1.394 ^{NS}	0.367
	Within Study sites	56.290	4	14.073		
	Total Variance	115.146	7			
Iron	between Study sites	0.028	3	0.009	299.254 ^{***}	0.000
	Within Study sites	0.000	4	0.000		
	Total Variance	0.028	7			
Total Nitrogen	between Study sites	0.050	3	0.017	10.885*	0.022
	Within Study sites	0.006	4	0.002		
	Total Variance	0.056	7			
Total Phosphorus	between Study sites	1.389	3	0.463	57.388**	0.001
	Within Study sites	0.032	4	0.008		
	Total Variance	1.422	7			
% of Oxygen Saturation	between Study sites	12.981	3	4.327	1.492 ^{NS}	0.345
	Within Study sites	11.598	4	2.900		
	Total Variance	24.579	7			
Dissolved Oxygen	between Study sites	0.208	3	0.069	6.905*	0.046
	Within Study sites	0.040	4	0.010		
	Total Variance	0.248	7			
Chemical Oxygen Demand	between Study sites	3020.5	3	1006.83	20.653**	0.007
	Within Study sites	195	4	48.750		
	Total Variance	3215.5	7			
Biochemical Oxygen Demand	between Study sites	70.904	3	23.635	16.286*	0.010
	Within Study sites	5.805	4	1.451		
	Total Variance	76.709	7			
Cadmium	between Study sites	0.000	3	0.000	11.333*	0.020
	Within Study sites	0.000	4	0.000		
	Total Variance	0.000	7			
Chromium	between Study sites	0.003	3	0.001	11.368*	0.020
	Within Study sites	0.000	4	0.000		
	Total Variance	0.004	7			
Copper	between Study sites	0.025	3	0.008	129.673 ^{***}	0.000
	Within Study sites	0.000	4	0.000		
	Total Variance	0.025	7			
Lead	between Study sites	0.003	3	0.001	378.841 ^{***}	0.000
	Within Study sites	0.000	4	0.000		
	Total Variance	0.003	7			
Selenium	between Study sites	0.000	3	0.000	54.667**	0.001
	Within Study sites	0.000	4	0.000		
	Total Variance	0.000	7			

Note:

*****:** Very highly significant if the probability value is less than 0.001 ($p < 0.001$).

****:** Highly significant if the probability value ranges from 0.001 to 0.01 excluded ($0.001 \leq P < 0.01$).

***:** Significant if the probability value ranges from 0.01 to 0.05 ($0.01 \leq p \leq 0.05$).

NS: Not significant if the probability value is greater than 0.05 ($p > 0.05$).

Indeed, the results of ANOVA-1 indicate only whether or not there are differences in the averages between the sampling stations for a given variable, but in case the difference is detected, the ANOVA-1 does not show exactly where the difference is. However, to verify where this difference lies, Tukey's HSD multiple comparison test was performed to check the differences of pairwise average values of the physico-chemical variables among the sampling stations and the results (Table 21) showed that the difference was:

Very highly significant ($p < 0.001$): (i) for turbidity between Kajaga & Nyamugari, Rumonge & Nyamugari and Mvugo & Nyamugari ; (ii) for Iron between Kajaga & Rumonge, Nyamugari & Rumonge and Mvugo & Rumonge; (iii) for Lead between Kajaga & Mvugo, Nyamugari & Mvugo and Rumonge & Mvugo and (iv) for Copper between Kajaga & Mvugo (for all, $p = 0.000$).

Highly significant ($0.001 \leq p < 0.01$): (i) for Chloride between Kajaga & Nyamugari ($p=0.002$) and Kajaga & Mvugo ($p=0.007$); (ii) for Calcium between Kajaga & Nyamugari ($p=0.001$), Kajaga & Rumonge ($p=0.006$) and Kajaga & Mvugo ($p=0.002$); (iii) for Magnesium between Nyamugari & Mvugo ($p=0.008$); (iv) for Iron between Kajaga & Mvugo ($p=0.002$) and Nyamugari & Mvugo ($p=0.001$); (v) for Total Phosphorus between Kajaga & Rumonge ($p=0.003$), Kajaga & Mvugo ($p=0.002$), Nyamugari & Rumonge ($p=0.004$) and Nyamugari & Mvugo ($p=0.002$); (vi) for Chemical Oxygen Demand between Kajaga & Rumonge ($p=0.009$) and Kajaga & Mvugo ($p=0.008$); (vii) for Copper between Kajaga & Nyamugari ($p=0.002$),

Kajaga & Rumonge ($p=0.002$), Nyamugari & Mvugo ($p=0.003$) and Rumonge & Mvugo ($p=0.002$); (viii) for Lead between Kajaga & Nyamugari ($p=0.001$) and Nyamugari & Rumonge ($p=0.001$); and for Selenium between Kajaga & Rumonge ($p=0.001$) and Kajaga & Mvugo ($p=0.001$).

Significant ($0.01 \leq p \leq 0.05$): (i) for Transparency between Kajaga & Nyamugari ($p=0.032$); (ii) for Chloride between Kajaga & Rumonge ($p=0.016$) and Nyamugari & Rumonge ($p=0.049$); (iii) for Total Hardness between Kajaga & Mvugo ($p=0.01$) and Rumonge & Mvugo ($p=0.023$); (iv) for Calcium between Nyamugari & Rumonge ($p=0.038$); (v) for Magnesium between Kajaga & Nyamugari ($p=0.013$), Kajaga & Rumonge ($p=0.03$) and Rumonge & Mvugo ($p=0.018$); (vi) for Total Nitrogen between Kajaga & Nyamugari ($p=0.031$) and Kajaga & Rumonge ($p=0.023$); (vii) for Dissolved Oxygen between Kajaga & Mvugo ($p=0.049$); (viii) for Chemical Oxygen Demand between Kajaga & Nyamugari ($p=0.016$); (ix) for Biochemical Oxygen Demand between Kajaga & Rumonge ($p=0.019$) and Kajaga & Mvugo ($p=0.01$); (x) for Cadmium between Kajaga & Rumonge ($p=0.025$) and Kajaga & Mvugo ($p=0.025$); (xi) for Chromium between Kajaga & Rumonge ($p=0.043$) and Kajaga & Mvugo ($p=0.035$); (xii) and for Selenium between Kajaga & Nyamugari ($p=0.013$), Nyamugari & Rumonge ($p=0.025$) and Nyamugari & Mvugo ($p=0.025$).

Table 21 : Tukey's HSD multiple comparison test for the differences of pairwise averages values of the physico-chemical variables among the sampling stations.

Dependent Variable	Study site(I)	Study site (J)	Mean Difference (I-J)	p-value
Turbidity	Kajaga	Nyamugari	-9.6***	0.000
		Rumonge	-1.04	0.36
		Mvugo	-0.855	0.492
	Nyamugari	Rumonge	8.56***	0.000
		Mvugo	8.745***	0.000
Rumonge	Mvugo	0.185	0.985	
Temperature	Kajaga	Nyamugari	-0.35	0.977
		Rumonge	-1.35	0.512
		Mvugo	-1	0.702
	Nyamugari	Rumonge	-1	0.702
		Mvugo	-0.65	0.883
Rumonge	Mvugo	0.35	0.977	
Transparency	Kajaga	Nyamugari	80*	0.032
		Rumonge	32	0.368
		Mvugo	38.5	0.256
	Nyamugari	Rumonge	-48	0.151
		Mvugo	-41.5	0.216
Rumonge	Mvugo	6.5	0.979	
Potential of Hydrogen	Kajaga	Nyamugari	-0.03	0.991
		Rumonge	0.14	0.593
		Mvugo	0.25	0.223
	Nyamugari	Rumonge	0.17	0.462
		Mvugo	0.28	0.17
Rumonge	Mvugo	0.11	0.736	
Total Alkalinity	Kajaga	Nyamugari	-20.7845	0.69
		Rumonge	-12.27	0.903
		Mvugo	-24.541	0.588
	Nyamugari	Rumonge	8.5145	0.963
		Mvugo	-3.7565	0.996
Rumonge	Mvugo	-12.271	0.903	
Electrical Conductivity	Kajaga	Nyamugari	-1	0.999
		Rumonge	5.5	0.919
		Mvugo	4	0.965
	Nyamugari	Rumonge	6.5	0.877
		Mvugo	5	0.937
Rumonge	Mvugo	-1.5	0.998	
Total Dissolved Solids	Kajaga	Nyamugari	-0.67	0.999
		Rumonge	3.685	0.919
		Mvugo	2.68	0.965
	Nyamugari	Rumonge	4.355	0.877
		Mvugo	3.35	0.937
Rumonge	Mvugo	-1.005	0.998	
Chloride	Kajaga	Nyamugari	14.31**	0.002
		Rumonge	8.31*	0.016
		Mvugo	10.425**	0.007
	Nyamugari	Rumonge	-6*	0.049

		Mvugo	-3.885	0.172
	Rumonge	Mvugo	2.115	0.539
Total Hardness	Kajaga	Nyamugari	25.1	0.106
		Rumonge	10.55	0.591
		Mvugo	51.25*	0.01
	Nyamugari	Rumonge	-14.55	0.374
		Mvugo	26.15	0.094
	Rumonge	Mvugo	40.7*	0.023
Calcium	Kajaga	Nyamugari	22.65**	0.001
		Rumonge	14.135**	0.006
		Mvugo	18.915**	0.002
	Nyamugari	Rumonge	-8.515*	0.038
		Mvugo	-3.735	0.341
	Rumonge	Mvugo	4.78	0.202
Magnesium	Kajaga	Nyamugari	-7.655*	0.013
		Rumonge	-6.02*	0.03
		Mvugo	0.965	0.868
	Nyamugari	Rumonge	1.635	0.614
		Mvugo	8.62**	0.008
	Rumonge	Mvugo	6.985*	0.018
Iron	Kajaga	Nyamugari	0.0065	0.673
		Rumonge	-0.14***	0.000
		Mvugo	-0.059**	0.002
	Nyamugari	Rumonge	-0.1465***	0.000
		Mvugo	-0.0655**	0.001
	Rumonge	Mvugo	0.081***	0.000
Total Carbon	Kajaga	Nyamugari	-2.425	0.912
		Rumonge	4.73	0.628
		Mvugo	2.75	0.879
	Nyamugari	Rumonge	7.155	0.352
		Mvugo	5.175	0.569
	Rumonge	Mvugo	-1.98	0.948
Total Nitrogen	Kajaga	Nyamugari	0.184*	0.031
		Rumonge	0.2011*	0.023
		Mvugo	0.12325	0.108
	Nyamugari	Rumonge	0.0171	0.969
		Mvugo	-0.06075	0.488
	Rumonge	Mvugo	-0.07785	0.324
Total Phosphorus	Kajaga	Nyamugari	0.0255	0.991
		Rumonge	0.782**	0.003
		Mvugo	0.9015**	0.002
	Nyamugari	Rumonge	0.7565**	0.004
		Mvugo	0.876**	0.002
	Rumonge	Mvugo	0.1195	0.593
Percent of Oxygen Saturation	Kajaga	Nyamugari	1.47	0.824
		Rumonge	2.055	0.655
		Mvugo	3.555	0.296
	Nyamugari	Rumonge	0.585	0.984
		Mvugo	2.085	0.646
	Rumonge	Mvugo	1.5	0.816
Dissolved	Kajaga	Nyamugari	0.1805	0.389
		Rumonge	0.356	0.076

Oxygen		Mvugo	0.411*	0.049
		Rumonge	0.1755	0.407
	Nyamugari	Mvugo	0.2305	0.24
	Rumonge	Mvugo	0.055	0.942
Chemical Oxygen Demand	Kajaga	Nyamugari	39.5*	0.016
		Rumonge	46**	0.009
		Mvugo	47.5**	0.008
	Nyamugari	Rumonge	6.5	0.792
		Mvugo	8	0.685
	Rumonge	Mvugo	1.5	0.996
Biochemical Oxygen Demand	Kajaga	Nyamugari	3.7	0.117
		Rumonge	6.5*	0.019
		Mvugo	7.75*	0.01
	Nyamugari	Rumonge	2.8	0.235
		Mvugo	4.05	0.09
	Rumonge	Mvugo	1.25	0.74
Cadmium	Kajaga	Nyamugari	0.002	0.053
		Rumonge	0.0025*	0.025
		Mvugo	0.0025*	0.025
	Nyamugari	Rumonge	0.0005	0.759
		Mvugo	0.0005	0.759
	Rumonge	Mvugo	0	1
Chromium	Kajaga	Nyamugari	0.006	0.926
		Rumonge	0.0425*	0.043
		Mvugo	0.045*	0.035
	Nyamugari	Rumonge	0.0365	0.069
		Mvugo	0.039	0.056
	Rumonge	Mvugo	0.0025	0.994
Copper	Kajaga	Nyamugari	0.086**	0.002
		Rumonge	0.0795**	0.002
		Mvugo	0.1585***	0.000
	Nyamugari	Rumonge	-0.0065	0.848
		Mvugo	0.0725**	0.003
	Rumonge	Mvugo	0.079**	0.002
Lead	Kajaga	Nyamugari	0.0215**	0.001
		Rumonge	0.004	0.205
		Mvugo	0.049***	0.000
	Nyamugari	Rumonge	-0.0175**	0.001
		Mvugo	0.0275***	0.000
	Rumonge	Mvugo	0.045***	0.000
Selenium	Kajaga	Nyamugari	0.003*	0.013
		Rumonge	0.0055**	0.001
		Mvugo	0.0055**	0.001
	Nyamugari	Rumonge	0.0025*	0.025
		Mvugo	0.0025*	0.025
	Rumonge	Mvugo	0	1

Besides, The comparison of the average values of the physicochemical variables using Tukey's HSD at the 5% level classifies the 4 sampling stations into 3 homogeneous subsets of averages: A, B and C (Table 22).

In fact, for the parameters like: Temperature, pH, Total Alkalinity, Electrical Conductivity, Total Dissolved Solids, Total Carbon and % of Oxygen Saturation, the Tukey's HSD method groups all the sampling sites in the same and single homogeneous subset of averages (A). It means that the sampling site factor has no influence on the variation of the cited limnological variables because the averages values are not significantly different ($p>0.05$).

On the other hand, the overlapping homogeneous subsets of averages (AB) were observed for: Dissolved oxygen, Total Hardness, Biochemical Oxygen Demand, Cadmium and Chromium at Nyamugari station; for Transparency and Dissolved Oxygen at Rumonge station; for Transparency, chloride, Calcium and Total Nitrogen at Mvugo station. The overlap of A and B means that A and B are equal ($A = B$). Indeed, for a given limnological variable, the averages corresponding to the 4 sampling stations and belonging to the same homogeneous subsets of averages (A or B or C) do not diverge significantly. Furthermore (except for the overlap case), the averages belonging to different homogeneous subsets are significantly different, because A, B and C are different.

Table 22: Tukey's HSD showing Homogeneous subsets of the average values of the physico-chemical variables at sampling Stations

Dependent Variable	Factor (Study Sites)	Means for groups in homogeneous subsets for Alpha=0.05			Homogeneous Subsets
		1 (A)	2 (B)	3(C)	
Turbidity	Kajaga	0.51			A
	Rumonge	1.55			A
	Mvugo	1.365			A
	Nyamugari		10.11		B
Temperature	Kajaga	27.6			A
	Nyamugari	27.95			A
	Rumonge	28.95			A
	Mvugo	28.6			A
Transparency	Nyamugari	120			A
	Rumonge	168	168		AB
	Mvugo	161.5	161.5		AB
	Kajaga		200		B
Potential of Hydrogen	Kajaga	8.85			A
	Nyamugari	8.88			A
	Rumonge	8.71			A
	Mvugo	8.6			A
Total Alkalinity	Kajaga	325.04			A
	Nyamugari	345.83			A
	Rumonge	337.31			A
	Mvugo	349.58			A
Electrical Conductivity	Kajaga	669.5			A
	Nyamugari	670.5			A
	Rumonge	664			A
	Mvugo	665.5			A
Total Dissolved Solids	Kajaga	448.565			A
	Nyamugari	449.235			A
	Rumonge	444.88			A
	Mvugo	445.885			A
Chloride	Nyamugari	32.265			A
	Mvugo	36.15	36.15		AB
	Rumonge		38.265		B
	Kajaga			46.575	C
Total Hardness	Mvugo	166.95			A
	Kajaga		218.2		B
	Nyamugari	193.1	193.1		AB
	Rumonge		207.65		B
Calcium	Nyamugari	34.075			A
	Mvugo	37.81	37.81		AB
	Rumonge		42.59		B
	Kajaga			56.725	C
Magnesium	Mvugo	17.6			A
	Kajaga	18.565			A
	Nyamugari		26.22		B
	Rumonge		24.585		B
	Kajaga	0.0255			A

Iron	Nyamugari	0.019			A
	Mvugo		0.0845		B
	Rumonge			0.1655	C
Total Nitrogen	Nyamugari	0.14995			A
	Rumonge	0.13285			A
	Mvugo	0.2107	0.2107		AB
	Kajaga		0.33395		B
Total Carbon	Kajaga	78.25			A
	Nyamugari	80.675			A
	Rumonge	73.52			A
	Mvugo	75.5			A
Phosphorus	Rumonge	0.859			A
	Mvugo	0.7395			A
	Kajaga		1.641		B
	Nyamugari		1.6155		B
% of Oxygen Saturation	Kajaga	96.6			A
	Nyamugari	95.13			A
	Rumonge	94.54			A
	Mvugo	93.04			A
Dissolved Oxygen	Mvugo	7.201			A
	Nyamugari	7.4315	7.4315		AB
	Rumonge	7.256	7.256		AB
	Kajaga		7.612		B
Chemical Oxygen Demand	Nyamugari	28			A
	Rumonge	21.5			A
	Mvugo	20			A
	Kajaga		67.5		B
Biochemical Oxygen Demand	Nyamugari	10.3	10.3		AB
	Rumonge	7.5			A
	Mvugo	6.25			A
	Kajaga		14		B
Cadmium	Nyamugari	0.0005	0.0005		AB
	Rumonge	0			A
	Mvugo	0			A
	Kajaga		0.0025		B
Chromium	Rumonge	0.0025			A
	Mvugo	0			A
	Kajaga		0.045		B
	Nyamugari	0.039	0.039		AB
Copper	Mvugo	0.0095			A
	Nyamugari		0.082		B
	Rumonge		0.0885		B
	Kajaga			0.168	C
Lead	Mvugo	0.033			A
	Nyamugari		0.0605		B
	Rumonge			0.078	C
	Kajaga			0.082	C
Selenium	Rumonge	0			A
	Mvugo	0			A
	Nyamugari		0.0025		B
	Kajaga			0.0055	C

IV.1.5 Determination of trophic and pollution status of the water

IV.1.5.1 Trophic status

To characterize the trophic state of the water of the sampling stations, two methods were applied:

- i. Vollenweider's method which is widely used internationally and accepted protocol by the Organization for Economic Co-Operation and Development OECD (OECD,1982; Ryding and Rast, 1994); Environment Canada (2004); and the Ministry of Sustainable Development in Quebec, MDDEP(2007) and is based on the average values of selected parameters (Vollenweider, 1989).
- ii. Carlson's Trophic Status Indices (TSI) method using a logarithmic transformation (Ln) of the chlorophyll a concentration (Chl. a) in microgram per liter, Secchi disc depth (SDD) in meters and the total phosphorus (TP) in microgram per liter according the following equation (Carlson, 1977):

$$TSI(SD) = 10 * \left(6 - \frac{\ln SD}{\ln 2} \right) = 60 - 14.41 \ln SD \text{ (m)}$$

$$TSI(\text{Chl.a}) = 10 * \left(6 - \frac{2.04 - 0.68 \ln \text{Chl.a}}{\ln 2} \right) = 9.81 \ln \text{Chl.a} \text{ (}\mu\text{g.L}^{-1}\text{)} + 30.6$$

$$TSI(TP) = 10 * \left(6 - \frac{\ln \frac{48}{TP}}{\ln 2} \right) = 14.42 \ln TP \text{ (}\mu\text{g.L}^{-1}\text{)} + 4.15$$

$$\text{Carlson's TSI} = \frac{TSI(\text{Chl.a}) + TSI(TP) + TSI(SD)}{3}$$

These two systems combine information about nutrient status and algal biomass and provide a basis for assessment and the trophic status trend for management. The acquired information allows comparison and

exchange at international level (Bartram et al., 1999). The following parameters are taken into account:

Total phosphorus (PT) which is the nutritive element that usually limits or supports the growth of algae and aquatic plants (Figure 35) in the shallow areas of the lake (shoreline). Total phosphorus is considered as the main nutrient responsible of the eutrophication process and facilitating the detection of the presence of nutritive pollution of a water body. Eutrophic lakes have a high concentration of phosphorus and are often characterized by a high abundance of aquatic plants (macrophytes). There is a link between phosphorus concentration, lake productivity and trophic level.

Chlorophyll a (Chl a) which is an indicator of the biomass (quantity) of microscopic algae present in the lake. The concentration of chlorophyll a has increased with the increasing of nutrients concentration. There is a link between this increase and the trophic level of the lake. Eutrophic lakes produce a large amount of algae.

Transparency (Secchi disc depth) which decreases with the increase of algae amount in the lake. Eutrophic lakes are characterized by low transparency of their water. There is a link between the water transparency and the trophic level of the water body.

However, waters having relatively large supplies of nutrients are termed eutrophic (well nourished), and those having poor nutrient supplies are termed oligotrophic (poorly nourished). Waters having intermediate nutrient supplies are termed mesotrophic (Hutchinson, 1973). Indeed, eutrophic

lake is rich in nutrients and aquatic plants such as accumulation of green blue algae and macrophytes (Figure 35). It is an advanced stage of eutrophication leading to the change in animal communities, to the organic matter increase and to the oxygen deficit in deep waters. In contrast, an oligotrophic lake is a young lake characterized by nutrient-poor, transparent (clear) and well-oxygenated waters as well as by low production of aquatic plants whereas a mesotrophic lake has an intermediate level of aging with relatively clear waters. The table 23 and 24 show respectively the trophic status index categories according to Carlson (1977) and the internationally accepted criteria used for trophic state classification of the water bodies while the table 25 and 26 show the trophic status results obtained for Lake Tanganyika at sampling stations in respective comparison with the standards ranges reported in the tables 24 and 23.

Table 23 : Carlson's trophic state index values for lakes classification (Carlson, 1977) in comparison with results obtained for Lake Tanganyika.

Trophic Status Index Classification system	TSI ranges	Trophic Status
Carlson's Index, 1977	< 30	Oligotrophic
	30 - 40	Oligo- Mesotrophic
	40 - 50	Mesotrophic
	50 - 60	Mesotrophic- Eutrophic
	60 - 70	Eutrophic
	70 – 80	Hypereutrophic
	> 80	Hypereutrophic
Carlson's Index modified by Toledo-Junior et al. ,1983	≤47	Ultraoligotrophic
	47≤52	Oligotrophic
	52≤ 59	Mesotrophic
	59 ≤ 63	Eutrophic
	63≤ 67	Supereutrophic
	≥67	Hypereutrophic

Table 24: Limit values for the trophic status of water according to international classification systems.

Trophic status	Mean TP ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$)	Chl-a ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$)		Transparency (m)		
		Mean	Max.	Min.	Mean	Max.
OECD Criteria (Vollenweider and Kerekes, 1982)						
Ultra-oligotrophic	4<	<1.0	<2.5	>6	>12	
Oligotrophic	<10	<2.5	<8	>3	>6	–
Mesotrophic	10–35	2.5–8	8–25	1.5–3	3–6	–
Eutrophic	35–100	8–25	25–75	0.7–1.5	1.5–3	–
Hypereutrophic	>100	>25	>75	≤ 0.7	≤ 1.5	–
OECD criteria (Ryding and Rast, 1994)						
Ultra-oligotrophic	<4	<1	<2.5	–	>6	>12
Oligotrophic	<10	<2.5	<8	–	>3	>6
Mesotrophic	10–35	2.5–8	8–25	–	1.5–3	3–6
Eutrophic	35–100	8–25	25–75	–	0.7–1.5	1.5–3
Hypereutrophic	>100	>25	>75	–	<0.7	<1.5
Canadian criteria (Environment Canada, 2004)						
Ultra-oligotrophic	<4	<1	<2.5	–	>6	>12
Oligotrophic	4–10	<2.5	<8	–	>3	>6
Mesotrophic	10–20	2.5–8	8–25	–	1.5–3	3–6
Mesotrophic- Eutrophic	20–35	–	–	–	–	–
Eutrophic	35–100	8–25	25–75	–	0.7–1.5	1.5–3
Hypereutrophic	>100	>25	>75	–	<0.7	<1.5
Quebec criteria (MDDEP, 2007)						
Oligotrophic	4–10	1–3	–	–	5–12	–
Mesotrophic	10–30	3–8	–	–	2.5–5	–
Eutrophic	30–100	8–25	–	–	1–2.5	–
Hypereutrophic	–	–	–	–	–	–
Nürnberg criteria (Nurnberg, 2001)						
Oligotrophic	<10	<3.5	–	–	–	–
Mesotrophic	10–30	3.5–9	–	–	–	–
Eutrophic	31–100	9.1–25	–	–	–	–
Hypereutrophic	–	–	–	–	–	–
Swedish criteria (University of Florida, 1983)						
Oligotrophic	<15	<3	–	–	>3.96	–
Mesotrophic	15–25	3–7	–	–	2.43–3.96	–
Eutrophic	25–100	7–40	–	–	0.91–2.43	–
Hypereutrophic	>100	>40	–	–	<0.91	–

Table 25: Trophic status of the sampled sites water of Lake Tanganyika in comparison to international classification systems.

Sampling stations	Mean TP ($\mu\text{g.L}^{-1}$)	Chl-a ($\mu\text{g.L}^{-1}$)		Transparency (m)			Trophic status observed
		Mean	Max	Min	Mean	Max	
Kajaga Site	–	–	–	1.9	2	–	Mesotrophic
	–	–	–	–	2	2.1	Eutrophic
	1641	305	320	–	–	–	Hypereutrophic
Nyamugari Site	–	–	–	1.1	1.2	–	Eutrophic
	1615.5	175	180	–	1.2	1.3	Hypereutrophic
Rumonge Site	–	–	–	1.61	1.68	–	Mesotrophic
	–	–	–	–	1.68	1.75	Eutrophic
	859	215	280	–	–	–	Hypereutrophic
Mvugo Site	–	–	–	–	1.615	–	Mesotrophic
	–	–	–	1.43	1.615	1.80	Eutrophic
	739.5	375	470	–	–	–	Hypereutrophic

Max : Annual maximum value

Min : Annual minimum value

Mean : Annual means value

Table 26 : Trophic status of Lake Tanganyika.

Sampling Stations	Transparency		Chlorophyll a		Total Phosphorus		Carlson's TSI	Trophic status observed
	Values (m)	TSI (SD)	Values ($\mu\text{g.L}^{-1}$)	TSI (Chl.a)	Values ($\mu\text{g.L}^{-1}$)	TSI (TP)		
Kajaga	2	50.012	305	86.716	1641	110.902	82.543	Hypereutrophic
Nyamugari	1.2	57.373	175	81.267	1615.5	110.676	83.105	Hypereutrophic
Rumonge	1.68	52.524	215	83.286	859	101.568	79.126	Hypereutrophic
Mvugo	1.615	53.093	375	88.743	739.5	99.408	80.415	Hypereutrophic

From the [table 25](#), Total Phosphorus and Chorophyll Concentrations revealed that all sampling stations were in Hypereutrophic status while transparency (Secchi disk depth) revealed mesotrophic status at Kajaga, Rumonge and Mvugo sites; Eutrophic Status at all sampling stations and hypereutrophic status at only Nyamugari status. At the same time, the results regarding the trophic status Index presented in the [Table 26](#) reflected that all sampling stations were in Hypereutrophic status. These conditions show in general that the eutrophication process is taking place

and therefore, urgent management of the lake is necessary to control the sources of eutrophication.

The pollution sources include mainly the excessive amounts of nutrients (Total Phosphorus, Total Nitrogen and total carbon) entering lake from rivers and through a variety of human activities such as agricultural fertilizers, industrial and municipal sewage treatment. In fact, the trophic status data obtained in this study cannot be generalized for whole Lake Tanganyika because the transparency and nutrient loadings of the water vary according to the sampling location. The water samples for the current study was taken from surface water at 50 meters far away from the shoreline and was subject to contain a lot of nutrients than the deep waters or the waters taken in the middle of the lake. The [figure 35](#) shows Eutrophication process at a station nearby Bujumbura port.

Figure 35: Proliferation of aquatic plants in Lake Tanganyika, indicator of eutrophication.

IV.1.5.2 Pollution status

Water pollution occurs when untreated waste is thrown into water bodies (figure 36). Polluted water can lead to destruction of plants and organisms living in the aquatic ecosystem and can also be harmful to peoples, plants and animals that use it. The assessment of the pollution status of the sampling stations water was based on the analysis of the major conventional pollutant (Biochemical Oxygen Demand and Chemical Oxygen Demand) which are directly related to organic pollution and the Method of the Institute of Hygiene and Epidemiology (IHE,1986) and Organic pollution index-IPO (Leclercq and Maquet,1987). The figure 36 shows how the discharge of untreated sewage into a water body is polluting it.

Figure 36: Water body pollution by untreated wastewaters discharge

Source: <https://i.pinimg.com/originals/ee/33/bc/ee33bc3e24689ff3ff249cc2b61d03a3.jpg>

IV.1.5.2.1 BOD and COD Status

BOD is similar in function to chemical oxygen demand (COD, since they measure both the amount of organic compounds in water. However, COD is less specific, since it measures everything that can be chemically oxidized, rather than just levels of biodegradable organic matter. COD is useful in terms of water quality by providing a metric to determine the effect that an effluent will have on the receiving body, much like (BOD). COD range in unpolluted surface water is less than or equal to 20 mg.L^{-1} (Chapman, 1997). BOD is widely used as a surrogate of the degree of organic pollution of water (Sawyer et al, 2003); it is one of the most common measures of pollutant organic material in water and is listed as a conventional pollutant in the U.S. Clean water Act. (U.S Clean Water Act. 33, Code1314, Section 304, 2013). BOD values indicate the extent of organic pollution in an aquatic system, which adversely affect the water quality (Jonnalagadda and Mhere, 2001). The BOD of unpolluted waters is less than 1 mg.L^{-1} ; moderately polluted waters have BOD content ranging from 2 to 9 mg.L^{-1} while heavily polluted waters have BOD value more than 10 mg.L^{-1} (Adakole, 2000).

Furthermore, the United Nations World Water Development (2016) states that most pristine rivers have a BOD value below 1 mg.L^{-1} , Moderately polluted rivers have a BOD value in the range of 2 to 8 mg.L^{-1} and Rivers may be considered severely polluted when BOD values exceed 8 mg.L^{-1} (Connor and Richard, 2016).

In the present study, the COD value ranged from 15-75mg.L⁻¹ (Table 14) and the general mean was 34.25±20.77mg.L⁻¹(Table 15). Kajaga station appeared to be polluted by both sewage and industrial wastes as it showed high COD value with average of 67.5mg.L⁻¹. Nyamugari, Rumonge and Mvugo stations show respective mean values of 28mg.L⁻¹, 21.5mg.L⁻¹ and 20mg.L⁻¹(table 15). Since COD in unpolluted surface water is ≤20 mg.L⁻¹ (Chapman, 1997), all stations appeared to be polluted and the pollution stage is reflected by the BOD value. The BOD content of various sampling sites ranged from 5 to 15mg.L⁻¹ (Table 14) with a general mean of 9.51±3.18 mg.L⁻¹(Table 15). Kajaga and Nyamugari stations appeared to be polluted as they have high BOD Concentration with respective averages of 14 and 10.3mg.L⁻¹, Rumonge and Mvugo stations show low mean value of 7.5 and 6.25mg.L⁻¹ respectively (Table 15).

According to Adakole (2000), Connor and Richard (2016), The present study revealed that water of Mvugo and Rumonge stations falls under moderately polluted category, while Kajaga and Nyamugari were under heavily polluted category during the investigation periode. In addition to this, the concentrations of the heavy metals analyzed (Cadmium, Chromium, Copper, Lead and Selenium) at Kajaga and Nyamugari stations were found higher than those recorded at Rumonge and Mvugo stations (figure 30). The table 27 summarizes the pollution status considering COD and BOD values.

Table 27: Pollution status of the sampled stations

Plot	Parameters (mg.L ⁻¹)	Pollution status		
		Unpolluted	Moderately polluted	heavily polluted
Standards values according to pollution level	COD	≤20(Chapman,1997)	>20 (Chapman, 1997)	>20 (Chapman, 1997)
	BOD	<1(Adakole, 2000)	2 - 9(Adakole, 2000) 2-8(Connor & Richard,2016)	>10(Adakole, 2000) >8(Connor & Richard,2016)
Kajaga Site	COD			67.5
	BOD			14
Nyamugari Site	COD			28
	BOD			10.3
Rumonge Site	COD		21.5	
	BOD		7.5	
Mvugo Site	COD		20.05	
	BOD		6.25	

IV.1.5.2.2 Use of Organic Pollution Index IPO (Leclercq & Maquet, 1987) and the Method of the Institute of Hygiene and Epidemiology (IHE, 1986).

They all comprise five classes of water quality corresponding to the generally granted colors:

Zero Pollution in blue Color
Low Pollution in green Color
Moderate Pollution in Yellow Color
Pollution in Orange Color
Very Strong Pollution in Red Color

i. Organic Pollution Index (OPI, Leclercq & Maquet, 1987)

The Organic Pollution Index (OPI) takes into account four parameters (BOD₅, ammonium, nitrites, and Total Phosphorus) .It is calculated according to the method of Leclercq and Maquet (1987) that spreads the values of the pollutant into five classes and determines from its own data, the corresponding class number to each parameter for making the average from them as shown on the table 28.

Table 28: Limit classes of parameters used for IPO calculation

Classes	Parameters			
	BOD ₅ (mgO ₂ .L ⁻¹)	NH ₄ ⁺ (mg N.L ⁻¹)	NO ₂ ⁻ (µg N.L ⁻¹)	Total Phosphorus (µg PO ₄ ⁻ .L ⁻¹)
Class 5	<2	<0,1	5	15
Class 4	2-5	0,1-0,9	6-10	16-75
Class 3	5.1-10	-2,4	11-50	76-250
Class 2	10.1-15	2,5-6,0	51-150	251-900
Class 1	>15	>6	>150	>900

IPO = average number of classes of the 4 parameters (at best):

= 5.0 - 4.6 : no organic pollution

= 4.5 – 4 : low organic pollution

= 3.9 – 3 : moderate organic pollution

= 2.9 – 2 : organic pollution

= 1.9 – 1 : very strong organic pollution

ii. **Method of the Institute of Hygiene and Epidemiology (IHE, 1986)**

This method has the same principle as the organic pollution index (OPI). It is based on the distribution of parameter values into five classes, but with other parameters and other classes. The parameters taken into account are: Percent of Oxygen Saturation, Chemical Oxygen Demand, Biochemical Oxygen Demand, Ammonium, Phosphates and Total Phosphorus (table 29).

Table 29: Limit Classes of used Parameters for IHE Calculation.

Classes	Parameters					
	% Oxygen Saturation	COD (mg-O ₂ .L ⁻¹)	BOD ₅ (mg-O ₂ .L ⁻¹)	NH ₄ ⁺ (mg-N.L ⁻¹)	Phosphates (µg-P.L ⁻¹)	TP (µg-P.L ⁻¹)
Class 5	90-110	≤5	≤1	≤ 0.05	≤50	≤50
Class 4	70-89	5.1-10	1.1-3	0.06-0.5	51-100	51-100
Class 3	50-69	10.1-20	3.1-5	0.51-1	101-200	101-200
Class 2	30-49	20.1-50	5.1-10	1.01-2	201-400	201-400
Class 1	< 30	> 50	> 10	> 2	> 400	> 400

Pollution levels calculated by the method of IHE are given by:

- IHE =5.0 - 4.6: no organic pollution
- =4.5 - 4: low organic pollution
- =3.9 - 3: moderate organic pollution
- =2.9 - 2: organic pollution
- =1.9 - 1: very strong organic pollution

The summary of results reported in the [table 30](#) reflects that the water of Kajaga and Nyamugari stations were facing a very strong organic pollution since these stations are located in the northern bay of Lake Tanganyika which is close to Bujumbura City characterized by a high Industrial and domestic sewage pollution. Contrariwise, Rumonge and Mvugo stations showed a low organic pollution, which indicates that the pollution level of Lake Tanganyika varies gradually by decreasing from northern bay to the southern bay and vice-versa.

Table 30: Organic pollution status of the water at the sampling stations.

Sampling Stations	Method of IPO (Leclercq and Maquet, 1987)		Institute of Hygiene and Epidemiology (IHE, 1986)	
	IPO	Pollution levels	IHE	Pollution levels
Kajaga	1.5	very strong organic pollution	2	organic pollution
Nyamugari	1.5	very strong organic pollution	2.2	organic pollution
Rumonge	2.5	organic pollution	2.5	organic pollution
Mvugo	2.5	organic pollution	2.75	organic pollution

IV.2 Biological characteristics

In this section, the analysis of the biological characteristics of the waters of Lake Tanganyika has focused firstly on the assessment of algal biomass by determining chlorophyll-a content of the water. Secondly, the analysis of Coliforms bacteria (Total coliforms, *Escherichia coli* and fecal coliforms) which are indicators of environmental and Fecal Contamination was performed to determine whether the water of the sampling sites are contaminated and if the amount of total and fecal coliforms are within permissible values in fish culture. Thirdly, the qualitative and quantitative assessment of the planktons population as fish food was performed and finally, taxonomic inventories of the fish species present at the sampling stations as well as the interactions between the fish fauna and the physico-chemical characteristics of water have been highlighted.

Planktons population and bacteriological analyzes were carried out only in 2018, January and February months. The fish species identification and Chlorophylla analysis were achieved during four months (January and February, both for 2017 and 2018). The data showing the spatio-temporal variation of Fish taxa, Chlorophyll a concentration, Microbial organisms, Planktons organisms and the International Standards of water quality suitable for fish culture are presented in the [table 31](#).

Table 31: Biological characteristics in comparison to the International Standards of water quality suitable for fish culture.

Biological Parameters	Year	Sampling Stations				Standards of Water quality suitable for Pisciculture
		Kajaga	Nyamugari	Rumonge	Mvugo	
Phytoplanktons (NO.L ⁻¹)	2018	2482	1031	3450	1506	NR
Zooplanktons (NO.L ⁻¹)	2018	830	219	1152	502	NR
Total Planktons (NO.L ⁻¹)	2018	3312	1250	4602	2008	2000-6000 (Bhatnagar & Pooja, 2013)
Escherichia Coli (CFU.L ⁻¹)	2018	0	4000	20000	30000	NR
Fecal Coliforms (CFU.L ⁻¹)	2018	0	20000	10000	50000	< 20000 (MDTEE, 2003)
Total Coliforms (CFU.L ⁻¹)	2018	90000	140000	600000	50000	< 100000 (USEPA, 1997)
Chlorophyll-a (mg.L ⁻¹)	2017	0.32	0.17	0.15	0.28	<0.0025 (UNECE, 1994)
	2018	0.29	0.18	0.28	0.47	
	Mean	0.305	0.175	0.215	0.375	
Total Number of Fish Taxa	2017	37	26	48	42	NA
	2018	33	30	44	42	
	Mean	35	28	46	42	

NO.L⁻¹: Number of Organisms per Liter

CFU : Colony Forming Units

NR : Not Recommended

NA : Not Applicable

IV.2.1 Chlorophyll-a

Chlorophyll-a having the chemical formula $C_{55}H_{72}MgN_4O_5$ is the principal pigment in plants that makes plants and algae green. This pigment allows plants and algae to make photosynthesis using the sun's **energy** to convert carbon dioxide and water into oxygen and cellular material (Sugar) following this reaction: $Light\ energy + 6CO_2 + 6H_2O \rightarrow C_6H_{12}O_6 + 6O_2$.

According to the United Nations Economic Commission for Europe (UNECE, 1994), Chlorophyll a Concentration in water must be less than

0.0025mg.L⁻¹. In the present study, Chlorophyll a value ranged from 0.15 to 0.47mg.L⁻¹(Table 31). Mean Concentrations per stations were 0.305mg.L⁻¹ for Kajaga site, 0.175mg.L⁻¹ for Nyamugari site, 0.215mg.L⁻¹ for Rumonge site and 0.375mg.L⁻¹ for Mvugo site with General mean of 0.2675mg.L⁻¹. For all study stations, the values obtained were higher than the standards reported by UNECE (1994). The spatio-temporal variation of Chlorophyll-a content is presented on the figure 37.

Figure 37: Spatio-temporal variation of Chlorophyll-a content

IV.2.2 Bacteriological Characteristics

Total coliforms bacteria comprise of fecal coliform and Escherichia Coli. **The presence of Total coliform only** in water sample indicates the environmental contamination. According to USEPA (1997), the total coliforms Concentration less than 100000 Organisms per Liter is

acceptable in freshwater pisciculture. During the present investigation, Total coliforms obtained were in the range of 90×10^3 to 600×10^3 CFU.L⁻¹ (Table 31). Rumonge site was found to have maximum value while minimum value was recorded at Kajaga site. Considering all study sites, mean value was 332.5×10^3 CFU.L⁻¹. Thus, apart from Kajaga site, the results obtained for the three others stations were not in accordance with the acceptable limits for pisciculture recommended by USEPA (1997).

The presence of fecal coliform in water sample is a good indication of recent fecal contamination. In the present study, the fecal coliforms amount ranged from 0 to 50×10^3 CFU.L⁻¹ (Table 31) with 20×10^3 CFU.L⁻¹ in average considering all the stations and Kajaga site appeared not contaminated as fecal coliform amount were nil. According to MDTEE (2003), fecal coliforms Concentration less than 20000 Organisms per Liter ($< 20 \times 10^3$ CFU.L⁻¹) are no harmful for fish culture. The values obtained for Kajaga and Rumonge stations are acceptable for pisciculture while those obtained for Nyamugari and Mvugo stations were found out of the ranges recommended for fish culture.

The presence of *Escherichia coli* in water sample indicates almost always the presence of fecal matter and then the possible presence of pathogenic organisms of human origin (USEPA, 1985). For pisciculture purposes, a specific recommended quantity of *Escherichia coli* is not assigned. During the investigation, the amount of *Escherichia* Coli recorded was ranging from 0 to 30×10^3 CFU.L⁻¹ (Table 31) with an average of 13.5×10^3 CFU.L⁻¹. At Kajaga stations, *Escherichia.coli* amount was 0

and therefore there is no contamination. The spatial variation of coliforms bacteria amount is presented on the figure 38:

Figure 38: Spatial variation of coliforms bacteria amount

IV.2.3 Planktonic population analysis

The term plankton originates from the Greek word *πλαγκτός* (*planktos*), which means wandering or drifter and is referring to minute aquatic organisms drifting, floating or weakly swimming in either marine and fresh water. The planktonic plants are called phytoplankton and planktonic animals are called zooplankton (APHA, 1985; Falkowski & Paul G., 1994). Planktons are recently used as indicators of changes in the aquatic ecosystem as they seem to be strongly influenced by climatic conditions (Beaugrand et al., 2000, Le Fevre-Lehoerff et al., 1995 and Li et al., 2000). During the present investigation, the qualitative analysis has focused on the taxonomic characterization at the family and species level, both for

zooplanktons and phytoplanktons. The quantitative analysis of planktons was performed by quantifying the total number of individuals observed under light microscope compounds per liter

IV.2.3.1 Phytoplanktons analysis

The species composition analysis of the samples has listed 115 species of phytoplanktons belonging to 7 families from all sampling sites (Table 32). The relative diversity index of families (Figure 39) has indicated that **Bacillariophyceae or Diatomophyceae** is the most dominant family in comparison to others families with 50 species (43.4%). The the family **Chlorophyceae** holds second position with 31 species (27%), the the family **Dinophyceae** occupies the third position with 16species (14%), the family **Xanthophyceae** contains 6species (5.2%) and holds the fourth place, the family **Zygophyceae** with 5species (4.3%) holds the fifth position. The family **Myxophyceae** comprised of 4species (3.5%) and occupied the sixth position. The family **Cyanophyceae** was in the last position with 3species (2.6%).

Regarding quantitative data, the results of specific richness(S) and the Cumulative abundance (figure 39) or summed abundance (sum of the abundances of several species) of the sampling sites showed that Rumonge site holds first position with 115species which was the maximum of all species identified comprising 3450 individuals per liter, Kajaga site holds the second position with 107species comprising 2482individuals per liter, Mvugo site in third place with 101species containing 1506individuals

per liter and in the last position was Nyamugari site with 86 species comprising 1031 individuals per liter. The relative abundance (the number of individuals per liter) of each species and the scientific names (Binary names) of all phytoplankton species recorded with their corresponding families are given in details in the table 32.

Figure 39: Relative diversity index of phytoplankton families (A), species richness & Cumulative abundance of phytoplankton individuals (B), density of phytoplankton species (C) and individuals (D) by station and family.

Table 32: Qualitative and quantitative results of phytoplankton population

Family → Species	Acronyms	Kajaga (N.L ⁻¹)	Nyamugari (N.L ⁻¹)	Rumonge (N.L ⁻¹)	Mvugo (N.L ⁻¹)
I. Bacillariophyceae					
1. <i>Amphora coffaeiformis</i>	AC	32	15	43	20
2. <i>Amphora ovalis</i>	AO	35	16	47	22
3. <i>Cocconeis pediculus</i>	CPe	18	9	24	11
4. <i>Cocconeis placentula</i>	CP	16	8	21	10
5. <i>Cyclotella operculata</i>	CO	24	12	32	15
6. <i>Cymatopleura solea</i>	CS	18	9	23	11
7. <i>Epithemia turgid</i>	ET	23	11	31	15
8. <i>Eunotia bilunaris</i>	EB	35	16	47	22
9. <i>Fragilaria Montana</i>	FM	40	18	54	25
10. <i>Gyrosigma attenuatum</i>	GAt	27	13	36	0
11. <i>Gyrosigma nodiferum</i>	GN	30	14	41	19
12. <i>Navicula bahusiensis</i>	NB	31	15	42	19
13. <i>Navicula distinct</i>	ND	18	9	23	11
14. <i>Navicula elliptica</i>	NE	29	14	39	18
15. <i>Navicula gastrum</i>	NG	20	10	27	0
16. <i>Navicula pupula</i>	NP	26	0	35	16
17. <i>Navicula radiosa</i>	NRa	23	0	30	0
18. <i>Navicula rhychocephala</i>	NRh	10	6	12	0
19. <i>Navicula tanganyikae</i>	NTa	10	6	13	7
20. <i>Nitzschia acicularis</i>	NAC	25	12	34	16
21. <i>Nitzschia acula Hantzsch</i>	NAH	24	12	32	15
22. <i>Nitzschia adapta</i>	NA	36	16	48	22
23. <i>Nitzschia bacata</i>	NBa	38	18	52	24
24. <i>Nitzschia Lacustris</i>	NLa	25	12	33	15
25. <i>Nitzschia Lancettula</i>	NL	20	10	26	12
26. <i>Nitzschia nyassensis</i>	NN	22	11	29	14
27. <i>Nitzschia palea</i>	NPa	18	9	24	11
28. <i>Nitzschia rostellata</i>	NR	39	18	53	24
29. <i>Nitzschia sigma</i>	NSi	41	19	56	25
30. <i>Nitzschia speculum</i>	NS	34	16	46	21
31. <i>Nitzschia tubicola</i>	NT	16	8	21	10
32. <i>Rhopalodia gracilis</i>	RG	7	0	9	5
33. <i>Schizostauron crucicula</i>	SC	16	0	21	10
34. <i>Surirella aculeate</i>	SAC	20	10	26	12
35. <i>Surirella acuminata</i>	SA	10	6	13	7
36. <i>Surirella debesi</i>	SD	15	8	19	0
37. <i>Surirella füllebornii</i>	SF	7	4	8	4
38. <i>Surirella gradifera</i>	SG	9	5	11	5
39. <i>Surirella heideni</i>	SH	5	3	5	0
40. <i>Surirella lancettula</i>	SLa	6	4	7	4
41. <i>Surirella latecostata</i>	SL	12	0	15	8
42. <i>Surirella margarifera</i>	SM	10	0	12	6
43. <i>Surirella plana</i>	SP	20	10	26	12
44. <i>Surirella reichelti</i>	SRe	7	4	8	4
45. <i>Surirella rudis</i>	SR	15	8	20	10
46. <i>Surirella spiraloides</i>	SSp	10	0	12	5
47. <i>Surirella striatula</i>	SS	14	7	18	9

48. <i>Surirella striolata</i>	SSt	11	6	14	7
49. <i>Surirella subrobusta</i>	SSu	10	0	13	7
50. <i>Surirella tanganyikae</i>	ST	18	9	23	11
II. Chlorophyceae					
51. <i>Ankistrodesmis nitzschoides</i>	AN	19	9	25	12
52. <i>Ankistrodesmus bernardii</i>	AB	41	19	56	25
53. <i>Botryococcus braunii</i>	BB	27	13	36	17
54. <i>Cerasterias raphidioides</i>	CR	25	12	33	15
55. <i>Chodatella longiseta</i>	CL	18	9	23	11
56. <i>Chodatella subsalsa</i>	CSu	18	9	24	11
57. <i>Closterium leibleinii</i>	CLe	20	10	27	13
58. <i>Crucigenia tetracantha</i>	CT	0	6	14	0
59. <i>Dictyosphaerium pulchellum</i>	DP	31	15	42	0
60. <i>Dimorphococcus lunatus</i>	DL	0	14	39	18
61. <i>Glococystis rehmani</i>	GR	33	15	45	21
62. <i>Gloeocystis gigas</i>	GG	15	8	20	10
63. <i>Hyalotheca mucosa</i>	HM	33	15	44	20
64. <i>Monoraphidium arcuatum</i>	MA	41	18	55	25
65. <i>Monoraphidium circinale</i>	MC	36	16	49	22
66. <i>Monoraphidium griffithii</i>	MG	39	17	53	24
67. <i>Monoraphidium komarkovae</i>	MK	43	19	59	27
68. <i>Nephrocystium lunatum</i>	NLu	27	0	36	17
69. <i>Oocystis lacustris</i>	OL	19	8	25	12
70. <i>Oocystis parva</i>	OP	18	8	23	11
71. <i>Pediastrum boryanum.</i>	PB	27	12	36	17
72. <i>Pediastrum Clathratum</i>	PC	25	11	33	15
73. <i>Pediastrum duplex</i>	PD	36	15	48	22
74. <i>Pediastrum integrum</i>	PI	32	14	43	20
75. <i>Pediastrum simplex</i>	PS	43	19	59	27
76. <i>Pediastrum tetras</i>	PT	22	10	29	14
77. <i>Scenedesmus bijugatus</i>	SB	0	0	33	15
78. <i>Sphaerocystis schroeteri</i>	SSc	0	0	31	15
79. <i>Tetracoccus botryoides</i>	TB	18	9	23	11
80. <i>Tetraedron minimum</i>	TM	15	8	20	10
81. <i>Westella botryoides</i>	WB	18	9	23	11
III. Cyanophyceae					
82. <i>Oscillatoria earlei</i>	OEa	30	14	40	18
83. <i>Oscillatoria angusta</i>	OA	28	13	37	17
84. <i>Oscillatoria pseudogeminata</i>	OPs	45	20	61	28
IV. Dinophyceae					
85. <i>Glenodinium pulvisculus</i>	GP	0	0	9	0
86. <i>Gloeotrichia natans</i>	GNa	0	0	13	7
87. <i>Gomphosphaeria aponina</i>	GA	14	0	18	0
88. <i>Lyngbya limnetica</i>	LL	22	0	29	14
89. <i>Lyngbya perelegans</i>	LP	19	0	25	12
90. <i>Merismopedia aeruginosa</i>	MAe	8	0	10	5
91. <i>Merismopedia elegans</i>	ME	10	0	12	6
92. <i>Merismopedia glauca</i>	MGI	13	0	16	8
93. <i>Merismopedia punctata</i>	MP	10	0	12	0
94. <i>Microcystis elabens</i>	MEI	13	0	17	0
95. <i>Nostoc carneum</i>	NC	7	0	9	0
96. <i>Nostoc piscinale</i>	NPi	15	0	19	10

97. <i>Oscillatoria cortiana</i>	OC	20	0	26	13
98. <i>Oscillatoria princeps</i>	OPr	0	0	14	8
99. <i>Oscillatoria tanganyikae</i>	OTa	14	0	18	10
100. <i>Oscillatoria tenuis</i>	OT	0	0	8	5
V. Myxophyceae					
101. <i>Anabaena tanganyikae</i>	AT	23	11	30	15
102. <i>Anabaenopsis circularis</i>	ACi	19	0	25	13
103. <i>Anabaenopsis Tanganyikae</i>	ATa	26	12	35	17
104. <i>Chroococcus turgidus</i>	CTu	14	0	18	0
VI. Xanthophyceae					
105. <i>Ophiocytium cochleare</i>	OCo	28	13	37	19
106. <i>Ophiocytium elongatum</i>	OE	46	21	62	29
107. <i>Ophiocytium gracilipes</i>	OG	29	13	39	19
108. <i>Ophiocytium majus</i>	OM	25	12	33	16
109. <i>Ophiocytium parvulum</i>	OPa	30	14	41	20
110. <i>Ophiocytium capitatum longispinum</i>	OCL	38	18	52	25
VII. Zygothryxaceae					
111. <i>Closterium aciculare</i>	CA	26	12	33	16
112. <i>Closterium diana pseudodiana</i>	CPs	39	17	51	24
113. <i>Closterium gracile</i>	CG	30	14	41	20
114. <i>Closterium jenniferi</i>	CJ	42	18	54	26
115. <i>Closterium kiitizingii</i>	CK	35	16	46	22
Total number of species		107	86	115	101
Total of Individuals/Liter		2482	1031	3450	1506

Where: NI.L⁻¹: Number of Individuals per Liter

IV.2.3.2 Zooplanktons analysis

During the survey, it has been realized that zooplankton organisms of the lake were very few in number and taxonomic diversity and was consisted of 3 orders: Cyclopoida, Calanoida (Copepods) and Cladocera represented by Diaphanosoma. Indeed, 12species belonging to 4families have been recorded from all study sites. The relative diversity index of families (Figure 40) revealed that the Diaptomidae family was dominant with 5species (41.7%). The Cyclopidae family was in second position with 4species (33.3%), the Sididae family occupied the third position with 2species (16.7%) while the Temoridae family was last with a single species (8.3%)

The results regarding quantitative analysis (Figure 40) showed that Rumonge site was ranked first with respective specific richness (S) and the Cumulative abundance of 11species and 1152individuals per liter, Kajaga and Mvugo site were equal to 10species as same specific richness(S) but with different cumulative abundance of 830 and 502 individuals per liter respectively.This places therefore Kajaga site in second position while Mvugo site was in third position. Nyamugari site was in last position with 8 as specific richness (S) comprising 219 individuals per liter. The table33 shows the qualitative and quantitative results of zooplanktons population while the relative diversity index of families as well as the results of specific richness and Cumulative abundance are shown on the figure 40 respectively.

Table 33: Qualitative and quantitative results of zooplanktons population

Order → Family → Species	Acronyms	Kajaga (NO.L ⁻¹)	Nyamugari (NO.L ⁻¹)	Rumonge (NO.L ⁻¹)	Mvugo (NO.L ⁻¹)
I. Order Cyclopoida					
I.1. Family Cyclopidae					
1. <i>Cyclops nanus</i>	CN	26	0	30	7
2. <i>Cyclops cunningtoni</i>	CC	23	3	31	13
3. <i>Cyclops attenuatus</i>	CA	19	8	27	11
4. <i>Cyclops simplex</i>					
4.1. <i>Cyclops simplex</i> copepodite	CSC	71	21	101	45
4.2. <i>Cyclops simplex</i> female	CSF	58	11	79	34
4.3. <i>Cyclops simplex</i> male	CSM	49	13	70	30
4.4. <i>Cyclops simplex</i> nauplii	CSN	75	17	110	48
II. Order Calanoida,					
II.1. Family Diaptomidae					
5. <i>Diaptomus africanus</i>	DA	37	12	0	15
6. <i>Diaptomus falcifer</i>	DF	46	9	63	26
7. <i>Tropodiaptomus cunningtoni</i>	TC	29	9	52	23
8. <i>Tropodiaptomus burundensis</i>	TB	43	7	65	28
9. <i>Tropodiaptomus simplex</i>					
9.1. <i>Tropodiaptomus simplex</i> copepodite	TSC	67	21	93	41
9.2. <i>Tropodiaptomus simplex</i> female	TSF	54	17	76	33
9.3. <i>Tropodiaptomus simplex</i>	TSM	49	10	70	31

<i>male</i>						
9.4.	<i>Tropodiptomus simplex nauplii</i>	TSN	116	33	171	75
9.5.	<i>Tropodiptomus simplex ovigerous</i>	TSO	59	28	87	39
II.2. Family Temoridae						
10.	<i>Eurytemora sp.</i>	ES	9	0	12	0
III. Order Cladocera						
III.1. Family Sididae						
11.	<i>Diaphanosoma birgei</i>	DBi	0	0	6	0
12.	<i>Diaphanosoma brachyurum</i>	DB	0	0	9	3
Total of Species			10	8	11	10
Total of Individuals per Liter			830	219	1152	502

Where NI.L⁻¹: Number of Individuals per Liter

Figure 40: Relative diversity index of zooplankton families (A), species richness & Cumulative abundance of zooplankton individuals (B), density of zooplankton species (C) and individuals (D) by station and family.

IV.2.3.3 Correspondence Factor Analysis

Correspondence Factor Analysis (CFA) is a descriptive analysis method for studying a contingency table. It consists of replacing a table of data that is difficult to analyze with an approximate simpler tables and unlike the PCA, the CFA offers the particularity of providing a common representation space for variables and individuals by using a reduced table or a frequencies table. It is a tool gathering most of the initial information in a small number of dimensions, focusing not on absolute values but on the correspondence between variables or relative values. CFA explores linkages, similarities and dissimilarities between individuals based on their distances on the factorial planes. CFA therefore studies the association between two qualitative variables as well as the proximities between the modalities of these variables.

For phytoplanktons, the 115 species are distributed in the 4 sampling sites based on their ecological preferences. The species located on the right side of the F1 axis are most abundant at Kajaga and Nyamugari sites where the environmental conditions are favorable for their development than in the other two sites. They probably belong to the families Chlorophyceae, Xanthophyceae, Cyanophyceae, Zygothryxaceae and Bacillariophyceae (Figure 41B). For example, the species SH, NRh, GAt, SD, NG, DP, CG, CA most prefer Kajaga site than OT, OPr, GNa, SSc, SB species that are most abundant at Mvugo site (Figure 41A).

Figure 41: CFA plot showing linkages between: **(A)** Sampling sites and phytoplankton species; **(B)** Sampling sites and phytoplankton families; **(C)** Sampling sites and zooplankton species ;**(D)**Sampling sites and zooplankton families.

Likewise, zooplankton species located on the right side of the F1 axis prefer mostly Kajaga, Nyamugari and mvugo sites which are propitious to their growth. This is the case for species belonging to the family diaptomidae (Figure 41D) such as TSO, TC, TSC, CSC, TSF, CSM and DA

(Figure 41C). On the left side of F1 axis, the species belonging to the family cyclopidae, sididae and temoridae (Figure 41D) like DBi, DB, TSN, CC, CFS TB, TSM, DF, CN and ES are most abundant at Rumonge site (Figure 41C).

IV.2.3.4 Planktons in aquatic food chain

Phytoplanktons are the base of aquatic food webs and energy production is linked to phytoplankton primary production. Zooplanktons are the central trophic link between primary producers and higher trophic levels. In most aquatic food chains, the community interactions are often controlled by abiotic factors or predation at higher levels of food chain. The control of primary production by abiotic factors such as nutrients is called “bottom-up control” whose schematic representation is given as follows:

More available nutrients → more algae → more zooplankton → more planktivorous fish → More piscivorous fish.

As plankton is at the base of the food web, there is a close relationship between plankton abundance and fish production (Smith and Swingle, 1938). According to Bhatnagar and Singh (2010), the desirable range of plankton population in pond fish culture is 3000 to 4500 NI.L⁻¹ and the acceptable range is 2000-6000 NI.L⁻¹. The values of planktons found in the present study fluctuated from 1250 to 4602NI.L⁻¹ with an average of 2793NI.L⁻¹ (Table 31 & Figure 42). Maximum value was recorded at Rumonge site and minimum value was found at Nyamugari station. The

plankton population for all study stations was found in accordance with the acceptable range for fish farming set by [Bhatnagar and Singh \(2010\)](#).

The total abundance of species at the sampling sites is presented on the [figure 42](#).

Figure 42: Total abundance of plankton species at the sampling sites

IV.2.3.5 Effect of physico-chemical attributes of water on the abundance of Planktonics communities.

Physico-chemical parameters play a major role in determining the density, diversity and occurrence of phytoplankton and zooplankton population in a water body. The [figures 43 and 44](#) show respectively the relationship between the environmental factors (Physico-chemical variables) and phytoplanktons and zooplanktons assemblages at the sampling sites using Canonical Correlation Analysis.

Figure 43: Canonical Correlation Analysis (CCorA) bi-plot showing relationship between the environmental parameters and phytoplankton composition at sampling sites.

The results of CCorA presented on [the figure 43](#) show that the abundance and proliferation of phytoplankton species are affected by the physico-chemical parameters concentration. Indeed, the increase in concentration of physico-chemical variables located in the third quadrant (Total carbon, Total Nitrogen, TDS, Conductivity, pH, DO (%), BOD, COD, etc) inhibits the growth and the proliferation of all phytoplankton species located in the first quadrant and the majority of species situated in the fourth quadrant of the trigonometric circle. On the other hand, the growth of phytoplankton species (OT, OPr, GNa, SSc, SB, DL, GP, CT, ACi, OTa, SL, MG, ME,

For Zooplanktons (Figure 44), the Canonical Correlation Analysis (CCorA), shows that apart from *Diaptomus africanus* which is positively affected by Selenium, Dissolved Oxygen, BOD, Cadmium, COD, Total Nitrogen, Chromium, Total Phosphorus, TDS, Conductivity and Total Carbon, all zooplankton species recorded during the present investigation are positively correlated to Hardness, Lead, Iron, Temperature, Copper, DO saturation(%), Calcium, Chloride, Transparency and Magnesium and negatively correlated to Turbidity, Total Alkalinity, pH, Total Carbon, TDS, Electrical Conductivity, Total Phosphorus, Chromium, Selenium, Dissolved Oxygen, BOD, Total Nitrogen, COD and Cadmium. In general, it is realized that all zooplankton species recorded in the present study (except *Diaptomus africanus*) are located in the fourth quadrant of the trigonometric circle. The physico-chemical parameters of the first and fourth quadrant affect positively zooplankton species by accelerating their growth while those belonging the second and the third quadrant act as inhibitors for zooplankton species growth.

IV.2.3.6 Planktonic species diversity analysis

IV.2.3.6.1 Alpha diversity study

Alpha diversity refers to the diversity within a particular area or ecosystem, and is usually expressed by the number of species (specific richness) in that ecosystem (Whittaker, 1972). The comparison of the planktonic species diversity among the sampling stations using diversity indices are given in the table 34.

Table 34: Planktonic species diversity indices

Diversity indices	Planktons	Sampling Stations			
		Kajaga	Nyamugari	Rumonge	Mvugo
1. Shannon Weiner Index (H') = $\sum_{i=1}^S [ni/N * \log_2(ni/N)]$	Pyhto	6.591	6.330	6.670	6.519
	Zoo	2.366	2.042	2.280	2.243
2. Pielou's evenness (E) = $H' / \log_2 S$	Pyhto	0.978	0.985	0.974	0.979
	Zoo	0.712	0.681	0.659	0.675
3. Species richness (S)	Pyhto	107	86	115	101
	Zoo	10	8	11	10
4. Margalef index(D _{ma}) = $(S-1) / \ln N$	Pyhto	13.803	12.395	14.117	13.561
	Zoo	1.447	1.299	1.419	1.339
5. Simpson's index(D) = $\sum [ni. (ni -1) / N.(N-1)]$	Pyhto	0.0108	0.0121	0.0104	0.0110
	Zoo	0.276	0.334	0.294	0.297
6. Hill's diversity index = $(1/D) / e^{H'}$	Pyhto	0.127	0.147	0.121	0.133
	Zoo	0.340	0.389	0.349	0.358

Where: Phyto: Phytoplanktons and **Zoo:** Zooplanktons.

Shannon Weiner Index (H'): Theoretically, Shannon Weiner Index varies from 0 to infinity and increases with diversity increase. For the current investigation, this index is high for phytoplanktons and varies from 6.33 to 6.67 while it is low for zooplanktons with a variation of 2.042 to 2.366. For Both planktons, a great diversity is recorded at Rumonge station while a small diversity is found at Nyamugari station.

Pielou's evenness: It shows the species equidistribution in the population and ranges from 0 to 1. It has 1 value when the species have identical abundances in the population and it is 0 when a single species dominates the whole population. For the present case, it ranges from 0.974 to 0.985 for phytoplanktons and is close to 1 value in all sampling sites which shows that all species have almost the same abundance. For zooplanktons, the Evenness Index varies from 0.659 to 0.712 which are the values close to the average. This event shows that there are some species

in the population tending to dominate others and moreover, the distribution of species in the population is not fair.

Species richness and Margalef's diversity Index: The species richness (S) is the simplest measure of biodiversity and indicates the total number of species recorded at a given location. A large amount of species increases species diversity. Margalef's diversity and Menhinick's diversity indices are two species richness indices commonly but for the present case, only Margalef's diversity index has been used. By direct counting the number of species per stations, Rumonge site occupies the first place with 115 and 11 species, followed by Kajaga site with 107 and 10 species, then Mvugo site with 101 and 10 species and finally Nyamugari site with 86 and 8 species respectively for phytoplanktons and zooplanktons. Margalef's diversity index is ranging from 12.395 to 14.117 for phytoplanktons and from 1.299 to 1.447 for zooplanktons with the same sequence of species richness per stations as observed for direct counting. Apart from Nyamugari station where Margalef's diversity index was low, the other 3 stations have indices a little bit high and close, which show that the environmental conditions propitious to the development of planktons are almost the same.

Simpson's index: In general, Simpson's index decreases with the increase of species, ranges from 0 to 1 and has 0 value for indicating maximum diversity and 1 value to indicate minimum diversity. For the present study, Simpson's Index varies from 0.0104 to 0.0121 and all values are close to zero for phytoplanktons. It varies from 0.294 to 0.334 for

zooplanktons. This event shows that phytoplanktons diversity is greater than zooplanktons diversity.

Hill's diversity index: As the Simpson's index, Hill's diversity Index increases with the decrease of species, varies from 0 to 1 and has 0 value as maximum diversity and 1 value as minimum diversity. For Phytoplanktons, it ranges from 0.121 to 0.147 and from 0.349 to 0.389 for zooplanktons. For both planktons, all values are less than the average (0.5) and are in accordance with the recorded species diversity of the sampling stations.

Correlation between the various diversity Indices:

Table 35: Correlation between zooplankton diversity indices

Plot	SWI	PE	SR	MI	SI	HDI
SWI	1					
PE	0.332	1				
SR	0.828	-0.254	1			
MI	0.911*	0.322	0.759	1		
SI	-0.998**	-0.367	-0.803	-0.890	1	
HDI	-0.996**	-0.256	-0.870	-0.922*	0.989**	1

Table 36: Correlation between phytoplankton diversity indices

Plot	SWI	PE	SR	MI	SI	HDI
SWI	1					
PE	-0.989**	1				
SR	0.999**	-0.993**	1			
MI	0.991**	-0.978*	0.984**	1		
SI	-0.994**	0.988**	-0.990**	-0.998**	1	
HDI	-1**	0.988**	-0.999**	-0.989**	0.992**	1

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (1-tailed)

* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (1-tailed)

SWI: Shannon Weiner Index, **PE:** Pielou's Evenness, **SR:** Species Richness, **MI:** Margalef Index, **SI:** Simpson's Index, **HDI:** Hill's Diversity Index.

For Zooplanktonic diversity indices (Table 35); Shannon Weiner Index is significantly and positively correlated to Margalef Index($r=0.911$, $p<0.05$) and negatively correlated to Simpson's Index($r=-0.998$, $p<0.01$) and Hill's Diversity Index($r=-0.996$, $p<0.01$). Furthermore, Hill's Diversity Index is significantly and negatively correlated to Margalef Index($r=-0.922$, $p<0.05$) and positively correlated to Simpson's Index($r=0.989$, $p<0.01$).

Regarding phytoplanktonic diversity indices (Table 36), apart from Pielous's Evenness and Margalef Index showing a strong and significant negative correlation at 5% level ($r=-0.978$, $p<0.05$), all the remaining diversity indices are strongly and significantly correlated two by two at 1% level ($p<0.01$) with negative and positive correlation and furthermore, Shannon Weiner Index and Hill's Diversity Index are perfectly correlated negatively. In fact, the positive correlation between two variables indicates that the increasing in value of these two variables go hand in hand while negative correlation indicates that the increase in value of one leads to the decrease in value of the other and vice versa.

IV.2.3.6.2 Beta diversity study

Beta diversity refers to the importance of species replacement or biotic changes, along environmental gradients (Whittaker, 1972). Beta diversity therefore measures the gradient of change in species diversity between different habitats, sites or communities and help to ascertain the diversity at regional scale. Beta diversity was measured using Jaccard and Sorensen index.

Indeed, Jaccard and Sorensen's Similarity Index vary usually from 0 (when there is no common species among habitats) to 1 (when all species are shared between habitats). From the [table 37 and 38](#), it has been shown that Jaccard and Sorensen indices give different coefficient values for the same pair of distinct sampling stations but they reflect both, the same information. Indeed, for phytoplanktons, Rumonge x Kajaga pair was top with a high similarity coefficient of 0.96 and 0.93 for Sorensen and Jaccard's index respectively. Considering zooplanktons, the top position is held by Kajaga x Mvugo pair and the similarity coefficients were 0.9 (Sorensen's Index) and 0.82 (Jaccard's Index). This means that the environmental conditions impacting on phytoplanktons and zooplanktons distribution are different. Furthermore, all the values obtained for different pairs of sampling stations were above the average (0.5) and greater than or equal to 0.74, which means that more than half of the total species belonging to each of the sampling sites are commons.

Table 37: Jaccard's Similarity Index of Plankton species among sampling stations

Jaccard's Similarity Index	Kajaga	Nyamugari	Rumonge	Mvugo	Planktons
Kajaga	1	0.77	0.93	0.84	Phytoplankton
Nyamugari		1	0.75	0.73	
Rumonge			1	0.88	
Mvugo				1	
Kajaga	1	0.8	0.75	0.82	Zooplankton
Nyamugari		1	0.58	0.8	
Rumonge			1	0.75	
Mvugo				1	

Table 38: Sorensen's Similarity Index of Plankton Species among sampling stations

Sorensen's Similarity Index	Kajaga	Nyamugari	Rumonge	Mvugo	Planktons
Kajaga	1	0.87	0.96	0.91	Phytoplankton
Nyamugari		1	0.86	0.84	
Rumonge			1	0.94	
Mvugo				1	
Kajaga	1	0.89	0.86	0.9	Zooplankton
Nyamugari		1	0.74	0.89	
Rumonge			1	0.86	
Mvugo				1	

IV.2.4 Fish diversity in relation to pollution

IV.2.4.1 Taxonomic diversity of fish species in sampling stations

The usual sketch in the organism's classification is as follows:

Kingdom → Phylum → Class → Order → Family → Genus → Species.

During Investigation, 75species belonging to 12families and 7Orders were recorded from all study sites and all these species belong to the animal kingdom, Phylum of chordata, class of Actinopterygii.

The relative diversity index of families (Figure 45) has indicated that Cichlidae is the most dominant family compared to others with 45 species (60%). The Claroteidae holds second position with 7species (10%), the Latidae occupies the third position with 6 species (8%), the family Clupeidae contains 4species (5%) and holds the fourth place, the family Alestidae with 3species (4%) holds the fifth position. The families Clariidae, Poeciliidae and Mochokidae occupy the sixth position and comprised of 2species (3%) each.

The families Mastacembelidae, Cyprinidae, Bagridae and Malapteruridae occupy the last position and had only one specie (1%) each

Regarding the fish species distribution per orders ([Figure 46](#)), it has been realized that order Perciformes is the most dominant with 51species(68%), followed by Siluriformes order with 13 species(17%),then Clupeiformes order with 4species(6%). Characiformes order with 3species(4%) and Cyprinodontiformes order with 2species(3%) occupy respectively the fourth and the fifth positions while Synbranchiformes and Cypriniformes order hold last position with one specie(1%) each.

The results regarding the species richness of the study sites ([Figure 47](#)) showed that Rumonge site holds first position with 48 and 44species respectively in 2017and 2018 with an average of 46 species, Mvugo site holds the second position with a constant number of 42 species for both years, Kajaga site in third position with 37 and 33 species in 2017 and 2018 respectively with an average of 35 species while Nyamugari site seemed to be very poor with 26 and 30species in 2017 and 2018 respectively with an average of 28 species. Indeed, after one year, the extinction of 4 fish species was observed at Rumonge and Kajaga stations while 4species were appeared at Nyamugari Stations. The scientific names (Binary names) of all fish species with their corresponding families and orders are listed in the [table 39](#), while the fish species representing each family and order are shown on the [Figure 48](#).

Figure 45: Relative diversity index of families

Figure 46: Fish species distribution per orders

Figure 47: Species richness per sampling sites.

Table 39: Fish species diversity at sampling sites

Order → Family → Species	Rumonge		Mvugo		Kajaga		Nyamugari	
	2017	2018	2017	2018	2017	2018	2017	2018
1. Order: Characiformes								
1.1. Family: Alestidae								
1. <i>Alestes macrophthalmus</i> (Günther, 1867)	X	X	X	X				
2. <i>Hydrocynus forskahili</i> (Cuvier, 1819)					X	X		
3. <i>Hydrocynus goliath</i> (Boulenger, 1898)	X	X			X	X		
2. Order: Perciformes								
2.1. Family: Cichlidae								
4. <i>Neolamprologus pleuromaculatus</i> (Trewavas & Poll, 1952)			X	X				
5. <i>Aulonocranus dewindti</i> (Boulenger, 1899)	X	X					X	X
6. <i>Bathybates fasciatus</i> (Boulenger, 1901)	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
7. <i>Bathybates leo</i> (Poll, 1956)	X	X					X	X
8. <i>Bathybates minor</i> (Boulenger, 1906)	X	X			X	X	X	X
9. <i>Benthochromis tricoti</i> (Poll, 1948)	X	X						
10. <i>Boulengerochromis micolepis</i> (Boulenger, 1899)	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
11. <i>Callochromis macrops macrops</i> (Boulenger, 1898)	X						X	X
12. <i>Callochromis pleurospilus</i> (Boulenger, 1906)							X	X
13. <i>Ctenochromis horei</i> (Günther, 1894)			X	X			X	X
14. <i>Cyathopharynx fulcifer</i> (Boulenger, 1898)			X	X				
15. <i>Cyphotilapia frontosa</i> (Boulenger, 1906)	X	X						
16. <i>Gnathochromis pfefferi</i> (Boulenger, 1898)	X	X	X	X	X	X		

17. <i>Haplochromis burtoni</i> (Günther, 1894)	X	X			X	X	X	X
18. <i>Haplotaxodon microlepis</i> (Boulenger, 1906)					X	X		
19. <i>Hemibates stenosoma</i> (Boulenger, 1901)	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
20. <i>Lamprologus callipterus</i> (Boulenger, 1906)	X	X						
21. <i>Lamprologus lemairii</i> (Boulenger, 1899)	X	X						
22. <i>Lepidiolamprologus attenuatus</i> (Steindachner, 1909)	X	X						
23. <i>Lepidiolamprologus cunningtoni</i> (Boulenger, 1906)	X	X	X	X			X	X
24. <i>Lepidiolamprologus elongarus</i> (Boulenger, 1898)							X	X
25. <i>Limnochromis auritus</i> (Boulenger, 1901)	X	X					X	X
26. <i>Limnotilapia dardenei</i> (Boulenger, 1899)	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
27. <i>Lobochilotes labiatus</i> (Boulenger, 1898)	X		X	X				
28. <i>Neolamprologus brevis</i> (Boulenger, 1899)	X	X						X
29. <i>Neolamprologus Calvus</i> (Poll, 1978)	X	X	X	X	X	X		
30. <i>Neolamprologus compressiceps</i> (Boulenger, 1898)	X	X	X	X				
31. <i>Neolamprologus tetraacanthus</i> (Boulenger, 1899)			X	X				
32. <i>Ophthalmotilapia ventralis</i> (Boulenger, 1898)					X	X		
33. <i>Oreochromis niloticus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	X	X	X	X			X	X
34. <i>Oreochromis tanganycae</i> (Günther, 1894)	X	X	X	X	X	X		
35. <i>Perissodus microlepis</i> (Boulenger, 1898)	X	X	X	X				
36. <i>Reganochromis calliurum</i> (Boulenger, 1901)							X	X
37. <i>Simochromis marginatus</i> (Poll, 1956)			X	X				
38. <i>Telmatochromis temporalis</i> (Boulenger, 1898)	X							
39. <i>Trematocara marginatum</i> (Boulenger, 1899)	X	X	X	X				
40. <i>Trematocara variabile</i> (Poll, 1952)			X	X			X	X
41. <i>Triglachromis otostigma</i> (Regan, 1920)							X	X
42. <i>Tropheus brichardi</i> (Nelissen and Thys van den Audenaerde, 1975)			X	X				
43. <i>Tylochromis polylepis</i> (Boulenger, 1900)			X	X			X	X
44. <i>Xenotilapia boulengeri</i> (Poll, 1942)	X	X	X	X				
45. <i>Xenotilapia burtoni</i> (Poll, 1951)	X	X			X	X		
46. <i>Xenotilapia flavipinnis</i> (Poll, 1985)	X	X					X	X
47. <i>Xenotilapia longispinis burtoni</i> (Poll, 1951)					X	X		
48. <i>Xenotilapia sima</i> (Boulenger, 1899)	X	X	X	X			X	X
2.2. Family: Latidae								
49. <i>Lates angustifrons</i> (Boulenger, 1906)					X			
50. <i>Lates mariae</i> (Steindachner, 1909)	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
51. <i>Luciolates stappersii</i> juv. (Boulenger, 1914)	X	X	X	X	X	X		
52. <i>Lates microlepis</i> (Boulenger, 1898)					X	X		
53. <i>Luciolates microlepis</i> (Boulenger, 1914)	X	X	X	X	X	X		X
54. <i>Luciolates stappersi</i> (Boulenger, 1914)	X	X	X	X	X	X		

3. Order: Siluriformes								
3.1. Family: Mochokidae								
55. <i>Synodontis lacustricolus</i> (Poll, 1953)					X			
56. <i>Synodontis multipunctatus</i> (Boulenger, 1898)			X	X				
3.2. Family: Malapteruridae								
57. <i>Malapterurus electricus</i> (Gmelin, 1789)	X	X	X	X	X	X		
3.3. Family: Bagridae								
58. <i>Bagrus docmac</i> (Forsskal, 1775)			X	X				
3.4. Family: Clariidae								
59. <i>Clarias gariepinus</i> (Burchell, 1822)	X	X	X	X	X	X		X
60. <i>Dinotropterus tanganicus</i> (Boulenger, 1906)	X	X	X	X	X	X		
3.5. Family: Claroteidae								
61. <i>Auchenoglanis occidentalis</i> (Valenciennes, 1840)					X	X		
62. <i>Bathybagrus stappersii</i> (Boulenger, 1917)	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
63. <i>Chrysichthys brachynema</i> (Boulenger, 1900)	X	X						
64. <i>Chrysichthys platycephalus</i> (Worthington and Ricardo, 1937)	X				X			
65. <i>Chrysichthys sianenna</i> (Boulenger, 1906)	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
66. <i>Chrysichthys stappersi</i> (Boulenger, 1917)			X	X	X	X		
67. <i>Lophiobagrus cyclurus</i> (Worthington and Ricardo, 1937)			X	X	X			
4. Order: Clupeiformes								
4.1. Family: Clupeidae								
68. <i>Limnothrissa miodon</i> (Boulenger, 1906)	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
69. <i>Stolothrissa Limnothrissa</i> (Regan, 1917)					X	X		
70. <i>Stolothrissa Limnothrissa juv</i> (Regan, 1917)	X	X	X	X				
71. <i>Stolothrissa tanganicae</i> (Regan, 1917)	X	X	X	X			X	X
5. Order: Cypriniformes								
5.1. Family: Cyprinidae								
72. <i>Barbus paludinosus</i> (Fowler, 1935)					X	X		
6. Order: Synbranchiformes								
6.1. Family: Mastacembelidae								
73. <i>Aethiomastacembelus ellipsifer</i> (Boulenger, 1899)	X	X	X	X	X	X		X
7. Order: Cyprinodontiformes								
7.1. Family: Poeciliidae								
74. <i>Aplocheilichthys pumilus</i> (Boulenger, 1906)					X	X		
75. <i>Lamprichthys tanganicanus</i> (Boulenger, 1898)	X	X	X	X	X	X		
Total: 7 Orders, 12 Families and 75 Species	48	44	42	42	37	33	26	30

1. *Aethiomastacembelus ellipsifer* :
Synbranchiformes, Mastacembelidae

2. *Bagrus docmac* : Siluriformes,
Bagridae

3. *Barbus paludinosus* :
Cypriniformes, Cyprinidae

4. *Dinotopterus Tanganicus* :
Siluriformes, Clariidae

5. *Luciolates stappersi* :
Perciformes, Latidae

6. *Lamprichthys tanganicus* :
Cyprinodontiformes, Poeciliidae

7. *Limnothrissa miodon* :
Clupeiformes, Clupeidae

8. *Hemibates stenosoma* :
Perciformes, Cichlidae

9. *Chrysichthys brachynema* :
Siluriformes, Claroteidae

10. *Malapterurus electricus* :
Siluriformes, Malapteruridae

11. *Synodontis multipunctatus* :
Siluriformes, Mochokidae

12. *Alestes macrophthalmus* :
Characiformes , Alestidae

Figure 48: The fish species representing each family and order.

IV.2.4.2 Interaction between sampling stations, physico-chemical and biological parameters.

IV.2.4.2.1 Effect of change in physico-chemical and biological attributes of water on the abundance of fish species.

For checking the link established between the water quality and the abundance of fish species, Pearson's correlation analysis was performed. The results (Table 40) showed that the amount of fish species is negatively correlated to eighteen parameters and positively correlated to eleven parameters; with strong and weak relation.

Table 40: Correlation between fish species abundance and physico-chemical variables and planktons abundance.

Limnological Variables	Correlation Coefficient (r)	p-value	Strength of relationship (Table 18 and Figure 31)
1. Turbidity	-0.759	0.121	Strong
2. Temperature	0.823	0.089	Strong
3. Transparency	0.450	0.275	Weak
4. pH	-0.812	0.094	Strong
5. Total Alkalinity	0.011	0.494	Weak
6. Electrical Conductivity	-0.972*	0.014	Strong
7. Total Dissolved Solids	-0.972*	0.014	Strong
8. Chlorides	0.185	0.407	Weak
9. Total Hardness	-0.114	0.443	Weak
10. Calcium	0.101	0.449	Weak
11. Magnesium	-0.284	0.358	Weak
12. Total carbon	-0.998**	0.001	Strong
13. Iron	0.908*	0.046	Strong
14. Total Nitrogen	-0.179	0.410	Weak
15. Total Phosphorus	-0.876	0.062	Strong
16. % of Oxygen saturation	-0.508	0.246	Strong
17. Dissolved Oxygen	-0.661	0.170	Strong
18. COD	-0.368	0.316	Weak
19. BOD	-0.617	0.191	Strong
20. Cadmium	-0.415	0.293	Weak
21. Chromium	-0.858	0.071	Strong
22. Copper	-0.318	0.341	Weak
23. Lead	-0.060	0.470	Weak
24. Selenium	-0.635	0.182	Strong
25. Chlorophyll a	0.384	0.308	Weak
26. NPS	0.841	0.080	Strong
27. NPI	0.703	0.148	Strong
28. NZS	0.927*	0.037	Strong
29. NZI	0.751	0.124	Strong

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (1-tailed)

* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (1-tailed)

NPS : Number of Phytoplankton Species

NPI : Number of Phytoplankton Individuals

NZS : Number of Zooplankton Species

NZI : Number of Zooplankton Individuals

From the [table 40](#) above, it is obvious that some physico-chemical parameters are factor influencing or affecting the abundance and distribution of fish species in sampling sites. Indeed, it has been found that the increasing of fish species amount in the sampling stations is:

Significantly and strongly linked to the decreasing in value for Total Carbon ($r=-0.998$, $p<0.01$), Electrical Conductivity ($r=-0.972$, $p<0.05$), Total Dissolved Solids ($r=-0.972$, $p<0.05$); Strongly linked to the decreasing in value of Total Phosphorus ($r= -0.876$), Turbidity ($r=-0.759$), pH($r=-0.812$), Dissolved Oxygen ($r=-0.661$), Biochemical Oxygen Demand ($r=-0.617$), Chromium ($r=-0.858$), Selenium ($r=-0.635$) and % of Oxygen saturation($r=-0.508$) ; Weakly linked to the decreasing in value of Chemical Oxygen Demand ($r=-0.368$), Cadmium($r=-0.415$), Copper($r=-0.318$), Total Hardness ($r=-0.114$), Magnesium Hardness ($r=-0.284$) and Total Nitrogen($r=-0.179$).

Significantly and strongly related to the increase in value of Iron ($r=0.908$, $p<0.05$); strongly related to the increase in Temperature ($r=0.823$), phytoplanktonic species number ($r=0.711$), phytoplankton individuals number ($r=0.567$), zooplankton individuals number ($r=0.612$) and zooplankton species number with significant relation ($r=0.927$) ; weakly

related to the increase in value of Transparency($r=0.45$), Chlorophyll a ($r=0.384$), Chlorides ($r=0.185$) and Calcium hardness ($r=0.101$).

Lastly, a very weak positive and negative relationship is established between the fish species amount and Total Alkalinity ($r=0.011$) and Lead ($r= - 0.060$) respectively, which shows that these two parameters have almost no influence on the abundance of fish species in the sampling stations.

IV.2.4.2.2 Effect of pollutants on fish diversity, distribution and identification of pollution indicator fish.

As discussed previously, it has been realized that waters of Mvugo and Rumonge stations were moderately polluted, while waters at Kajaga and Nyamugari sites were heavily polluted during the investigation period. Furthermore, the annual specific richness of the sampled sites showed a great difference and that difference in specific richness and species taxonomic composition observed between sampling sites are influenced by both intrinsic community interactions and forcing environmental factors. For instance, the local diversity of a community can be affected over relatively short periods of time by at least 4 types of factors: (i) the concentration of deleterious substances or physiologically severe conditions in the environment, (ii) the abundance of key resources, (iii) the abundance of key consumers or disturbances, and (iv) specific features of the local environment (Valiela, 1995). The [table 41](#) shows the identification and distribution of fish species according their acclimation level to pollution while the [table 42](#) summarizes the pollution status of the sampling stations

and the acclimation level to pollution of the fish species inhabiting the respective stations

Table 41: Identification and distribution of fish species based on acclimation level to pollution.

Polluotolerant species	Polluosensitive species	Polluoresistant species
1. <i>Aethiomastacembelus ellipsifer</i>	1. <i>Alestes macrophthalmus</i>	1. <i>Aplocheilichthys pumilus</i>
2. <i>Aulonocranus dewindti</i>	2. <i>Bagrus docmac</i>	2. <i>Auchenoglanis occidentalis</i>
3. <i>Bathybagrus stappersii</i>	3. <i>Benthochromis tricoti</i>	3. <i>Barbus paludinosus</i>
4. <i>Bathybates fasciatus</i>	4. <i>Chrysichthys brachynema</i>	4. <i>Callochromis pleurospilus</i>
5. <i>Bathybates leo</i>	5. <i>Cyathopharynx fulcifer</i>	5. <i>Haplotaxodon microlepis</i>
6. <i>Bathybates minor</i>	6. <i>Cyphotilapia frontosa</i>	6. <i>Hydrocynus forskahili</i>
7. <i>Boulengerochromis micolepis</i>	7. <i>Lamprologus callipterus</i>	7. <i>Lates angustifrons</i>
8. <i>Callochromis macrops</i>	8. <i>Lamprologus lemairii</i>	8. <i>Lates microlepis</i>
9. <i>Chrysichthys platycephalus</i>	9. <i>Lepidiolamprologus attenuatus</i>	9. <i>Lepidiolamprologus elongatus</i>
10. <i>Chrysichthys sianenna</i>	10. <i>Lobochilotes labiatus</i>	10. <i>Ophthalmotilapia ventralis</i>
11. <i>Chrysichthys stappersi</i>	11. <i>Neolamprologus compressiceps</i>	11. <i>Reganochromis calliurum</i>
12. <i>Clarias gariepinus</i>	12. <i>Neolamprologus pleuromaculatus</i>	12. <i>Stolothrissa Limnothrissa</i>
13. <i>Ctenochromis horei</i>	13. <i>Neolamprologus tetracanthus</i>	13. <i>Synodontis lacustricolus</i>
14. <i>Dinotopterus tanganicus</i>	14. <i>Perissodus microlepis</i>	14. <i>Triglachromis otostigma</i>
15. <i>Gnathochromis pfefferi</i>	15. <i>Simochromis marginatus</i>	15. <i>Xenotilapia longispinis burtoni</i>
16. <i>Haplochromis burtoni</i>	16. <i>Stolothrissa Limnothrissa juv.</i>	
17. <i>Hemibates stenosoma</i>	17. <i>Synodontis multipuctatus</i>	
18. <i>Hydrocynus goliath</i>	18. <i>Telmatochromis temporalis</i>	
19. <i>Lamprichthys tanganicus</i>	19. <i>Trematocara marginatum</i>	
20. <i>Lates mariae</i>	20. <i>Tropheus brichardi</i>	
21. <i>Lepidiolamprologus cunningtoni</i>	21. <i>Xenotilapia boulengeri</i>	
22. <i>Limnochromis auritus</i>		
23. <i>Limnothrissa miodon</i>		
24. <i>Limnotilapia dardennei</i>		
25. <i>Lophiobagrus cyclurus</i>		
26. <i>Luciolates microlepis</i>		
27. <i>Luciolates stappersii juv.</i>		
28. <i>Luciolates stappersi</i>		
29. <i>Malapterurus electricus</i>		
30. <i>Neolamprologus brevis</i>		
31. <i>Neolamprologus Calvus</i>		
32. <i>Oreochromis niloticus</i>		
33. <i>Oreochromis tanganicæ</i>		
34. <i>Stolothrissa tanganicæ</i>		
35. <i>Trematocara variable</i>		
36. <i>Tylochromis polylepis</i>		
37. <i>Xenotilapia flavipinnis</i>		
38. <i>Xenotilapia sima</i>		
39. <i>Xenotilapia burtoni</i>		

Table 42: Pollution status of the sampling stations and Fish acclimation level to pollution

Plots	Kajaga (H.P)	Nyamugari (H.P)	Rumonge (M.P)	Mvugo (M.P)	Nyamugari +Kajaga (H.P)	Rumonge +Mvugo(M.P)
Kajaga (H.P)	Resistant	Resistant	Tolerant	Tolerant	Resistant	Tolerant
Nyamugari (H.P)		Resistant	Tolerant	Tolerant	Resistant	Tolerant
Rumonge (M.P)			Sensitive	Sensitive	Tolerant	Sensitive
Mvugo (M.P)				Sensitive	Tolerant	Sensitive
Nyamugari +Kajaga (H.P)					Resistant	Tolerant
Rumonge +Mvugo (M.P)						Sensitive

H.P: Heavily Polluted; **M.P:** Moderately Polluted.

The present investigation has revealed the occurrence of 75 species in all sampling stations (Table 39 & 41) and the pollution status of the sampling sites has contributed to distribute the species in three categories based on their adaptation level to pollution:

Sensitive Species to pollution or Polluosensitive species:

Species living exclusively at Mvugo and Rumonge station which are moderately polluted. In this category, 21 (or 28%) species have been recorded and the presence of these species can be used as indicators of slightly polluted environment.

Resistant Species to pollution or Polluoresistant species:

Species exclusively inhabiting at Kajaga and Nyamugari stations which are heavily polluted. In this category, 15 (or 20%) species have been identified and the presence of these species is indicative of highly polluted environment.

Tolerant Species to pollution or Polluotolerant species: Species adapted for living in all sampling stations, both heavily and moderately polluted. In this category, 39 (or 52%) species have been identified.

IV.2.4.2.3 Similarity between fish species richness of sampling stations

The similarity between fish species recorded in the sampling stations was determined using similarity indices. The most used indices are similarity coefficients of [Jaccard \(1908\)](#) and [Sorensen \(1948\)](#). These indices are intended to compare objects on the basis of the presence-absence of species and are so very simple measures of beta biodiversity, ranging from 0 (when there are no common species between two communities) to 1 (when the same species exist in both communities). A smaller index indicates less similarity in species composition between different habitats ([Condit et al.2002](#); [Nshimba. 2008](#)). The [table 43](#) shows Similarity Index between the fish species composition of sampling stations, calculated using Jaccard and Sorensen's Method.

Table 43: Similarity coefficient between fish species composition at sampling stations.

Plots	Kajaga	Nyamugari	Rumonge	Mvugo	Similarity Index
Kajaga	1	0.23	0.41	0.36	Jaccard's Index
Nyamugari		1	0.38	0.31	
Rumonge			1	0.50	
Mvugo				1	
Kajaga	1	0.37	0.58	0.53	Sorensen's Index
Nyamugari		1	0.55	0.47	
Rumonge			1	0.67	
Mvugo				1	

From the [table 43](#), it is obvious that Jaccard and Sorensen indices give different coefficient values for the same pair of distinct sampling stations but they reflect both, the same information. Indeed, Rumonge x Mvugo pair occupies the first position with a high similarity coefficient of 0.67 and 0.5 for Sorensen and Jaccard's index respectively. This means that many fish species are common or shared between Mvugo and Rumonge stations which are moderately polluted and shows that these two stations have almost the same environmental conditions or characteristics.

Rumonge x Kajaga, Rumonge x Nyamugari and Mvugo x kajaga pairs occupy respectively the second, third and fourth rank with respective Sorensen's similarity coefficients of 0.58, 0.55 and 0.53. The respective Jaccard Indices are 0.41, 0.38 and 0.36. These three indices are so close in value and are close to the average (for Sorensen's index) compared to the extreme values (ranging from 0 to 1). This shows the presence of tolerant fish species to the environmental conditions prevailing in all sampling stations, which are moderately and heavily polluted.

The similarity between fish species composition of Nyamugari x Mvugo and Nyamugari x Kajaga site pairs is very low. It occupies the fifth and sixth position which is the last with respective Sorensen's similarity indices of 0.47 and 0.37, the respective Jaccard's indices are 0.31 and 0.23. This shows that the environmental conditions prevailing in Kajaga, Nyamugari and Mvugo stations are very different and apart from the status pollution of sampling sites, there are some else factors that strongly

influence the similarity or dissimilarity of the specific composition of sampling sites such as the presence or absence of sufficient planktonic nutrients.

IV.2.4.2.4 Effect of the sampling sites on the abundance of fish species

Tukey's Honestly Significant Difference test (Tukey's HSD) and One-way ANalysis of Variance (ANOVA-1) both at the 5% level were performed respectively to make the averages comparison and to assess the effect of study sites on the abundance of fish species. The results of one-way Analysis of variance (ANOVA-I) (Table 44) indicated that the influence of the study stations on the abundance of fish species is highly significant ($p=0.007$). It means that the variation of fish species in number depends on the environmental conditions.

The differences among pairwise averages number of fish species from the sampling stations are shown by Tukey's HSD multiple comparison test in the table 45 and it has been reflected that the mean difference of fish species amount between stations is significant ($p<0.05$) for Kajaga and Rumonge sites ($p=0.036$), Nyamugari and Rumonge sites ($p=0.006$), Nyamugari and Mvugo sites ($p=0.016$).

The comparison of the average number of fish species using Tukey's HSD at the 5% level classifies the 4sampling stations into 3homogeneous subsets of averages A, B and C (Table 46). Indeed, the averages belonging to the same homogeneous subset are not significantly different (e.g: Nyamugari and Kajaga or Kajaga and Mvugo or Rumonge and Mvugo stations) whereas the averages belonging to different

homogeneous subsets are significantly different because the subsets A, B and C are different.

Table 44: ANOVA-I showing the effect of sampling sites on fish species number.

Variable	Variation Source	Sum of Squares	Freedom Degree	Mean Square	F Test	p-value
Fish species amount	between study sites	377.5	3	125.833	20.972**	0.007
	within study sites	24	4	6		
	Total Variance	401.5	7			

Table 45 : Tukey's HSD multiple comparison test for the differences of pairwise averages amount of fish species among the sampling stations.

Dependent Variable	Sampling stations (I)	Sampling stations (J)	Mean Difference (I-J)	p-value
Fish species amount	Kajaga	Nyamugari	7	0.142
		Rumonge	-11*	0.036
		Mvugo	-7	0.142
	Nyamugari	Rumonge	-18*	0.006
		Mvugo	-14*	0.016
	Rumonge	Mvugo	4	0.455

Table 46: Tukey's HSD showing Homogeneous subsets of averages at sampling Stations.

Dependent Variable	Factor (Sampling Stations)	Means for groups in homogeneous subsets for Alpha=0.05			Homogeneous Subsets
		1 (A)	2 (B)	3(C)	
Fish species amount	Nyamugari	28			A
	Kajaga	35	35		AB
	Mvugo		42	42	BC
	Rumonge			46	C

CHAPTER-V DISCUSSION

V.1 Physico-chemistry of waters

Transparency measures the depth of light penetration into the water and shows how clear are the water. It is fundamental because aquatic plants require sunlight to perform photosynthesis. In a water body, transparency varies according to the abundance of suspended particles (clay, silt...) and phytoplankton (Balvay, 1985). The transparency of the waters of Lake Tanganyika varies greatly depending on the location. The highest value was recorded at Kajaga site and the lowest value at Nyamugari site. Lower transparency observed at Nyamugari site can be attributed on the one hand to the strongest and most frequent winds at the time of sampling, causing thus turbulence which resuspends the sediment particles, on the other hand to the wastewater discharges from Mugere hydroelectric dam and surface run-off filled with organic matter (soil, dead leaves etc.,) from the watershed and other effluents into Lake Tanganyika. The clear water phase observed at Kajaga station is attributed to the abundance of zooplankton communities (Jabari, 1998), which contribute significantly to the clarification of water in the lake through phytoplankton grazing (Tuzin and Mason, 1996).

Turbidity is the suspension of particles in water interfering with the passage of light. Turbidity measures the light-transmitting properties of water and is comprised of suspended and colloidal material. The different

classes of turbidity according to the visual quality of the water are as follows:

- NTU<5 : colorless water
- 5<NTU<30 : slightly cloudy water
- NTU>50 : Cloudy water

High turbidity of water can decrease fish productivity as it will reduce light penetration into the water and thus oxygen production by the water plants. During the present investigation, turbidity ranged from 0.5 to 10.42NTU with an annual average of 3.38 ± 4.17 NTU. The maximum value was recorded at Nyamugari station and minimum value was recorded at kajaga station. Apart from Nyamugari station which showed the highest water turbidity, other values are close to 0.32 and 0.33 NTU recorded by [Plisinier et al., \(1999\)](#) respectively at Bujumbura and Mpulungu stations. The highest turbidity recorded at Nyamugari station can be explained by a large influx of solid particles from the soils leaching of the watershed ([Gonzalez et al., 2004](#)), discharges of wastewater from Mugere hydroelectric dam through Mugere river and surface run-off filled with organic matter (soil, dead leaves etc.,) and other effluents into Lake Tanganyika.

Temperature expresses the level of coldness or hotness in living organism body either on earth or in water ([Lucinda and Martin, 1999](#)). It is a primary environmental factor that affects and governs the biological activities and solubility of gases in water. Any increase in water temperature decreases gases concentration such as oxygen, carbon

dioxide and sulfur (Blanc, 2000). Temperature values recorded for the present was varying from 27.1⁰C to 29.8⁰C with an average of 28.28±0.57⁰C and there was no significant difference in temperature variation for all sampling sites. These values of temperature are close to 25.8⁰C recorded by Plisnier et al.(1999) at Bujumbura and Uvira. Considering the average data per study site, Kajaga and Nyamugari sites have a temperature close to 28 ⁰C while Rumonge and Mvugo sites have a temperature close to 29⁰C. This shows that atmospheric or air conditions prevailing at sites bearing the same temperature are almost the same. The little bit difference of temperature recorded may be due to the temporary warming of the surface water by high radiation at the time of sampling and mixing of water probably by internal waves resulting from upward movement of the deeper water to the surface.

Total Dissolved Solids (TDS) represent the remaining residue obtained after evaporation of the water and drying the residue at 103⁰C to 105⁰C up to a constant weight. The analysis of TDS has great implications in the control of biological and physical waste Water treatment processes. The values of TDS found in the present study fluctuated from 440.86 to 453.59. Maximum value was recorded at Kajaga and Nyamugari stations and minimum value was found at Rumonge station. In average, Kajaga and Nyamugari sites have almost the same TDS value close to 449mg.L⁻¹ whereas TDS value recorded at Rumonge and Mvugo sites was close to 445mg.L⁻¹. High TDS values observed at Kajaga and Nyamugari stations imply the increased nutrient status of water body which leads to

eutrophication of aquatic bodies. Primary sources for high TDS on these sites are agricultural and residential runoff, clay rich mountain waters, leaching of soil contamination and point source water pollution discharge from industrial or sewage treatment stations. The most common chemical constituents of TDS are calcium phosphates, nitrates, sodium, potassium and chloride which are found in nutrient runoff. Pesticides from surface runoff are more exotic and harmful elements of TDS. Some total dissolved solids occurring naturally come from weathering and dissolution of rocks and soils.

Potential of hydrogen (pH) indicates the intensity of basic or acidic character of a solution at a given temperature and is expressed by the negative logarithm of hydrogen ion concentration ($\text{pH} = -\log [\text{H}^+]$). pH values ranging from 0 to 7 are decreasingly acidic whereas the values ranging from 7 to 14 are increasingly alkaline. At 25⁰C, pH =7 is neutral, where the activities of the hydrogen and hydroxyl ions are equal and it corresponds to 10⁻⁷ moles/L. The pH of natural water is usually ranging from 4.4 to 8.5 and is greatly influenced by the concentration of carbon dioxide which is an acidic gas (Boyd, 1979).

In the present study, pH values obtained ranged from 8.5 to 8.88 with an average of 8.76±0.12. These results indicated alkaline pH at all study sites. These pH values are close to those measured by Coulter (1994) which ranged from 8.6 to 9.2 and those of Lwikitcha (2012) ranging from 7.3 to 8.9 in Lake Tanganyika. In February the pH is generally similar to each station and is often ranging between 9.0 at the surface and 8.7 to

300m with significant pH variation from September to December (Plisnier et al., 1999). Mean pH value obtained for Kajaga and Nyamugari sites was higher than the pH value recorded for Rumonge and Mvugo stations. The high values may be attributed to sewage discharged by surrounding city (Bujumbura) into the Lake and agricultural fields of the hills overhanging Nyamugari station. The pH of water affects many chemical and biological processes in water. In fact, for the majority of freshwater species, a pH ranging from 6.5 to 9 is appropriate, but most of marine animals are not tolerant to a wide range of pH as freshwater animals, thus the optimal pH ranges generally between 7.5 and 8.5 (Boyd, 1998). Below pH 6.5, some species show slow growth (Lloyd, 1992). At lower pH, the capacity of organism to preserve its salt equilibrium is affected (Lloyd, 1992) and reproduction stops. At $\text{pH} \leq 4$ and $\text{pH} \geq 11$, most of species die. Some species are very sensitive to the sudden variation of pH like freshwater shrimp, which can die at pH greater than 9.5, so it is imperative to stabilize the pH. This can be achieved by making sure that calcium hardness is close in value to total alkalinity. Prawn farmers often add a source of calcium to their ponds (such as calcium chloride or gypsum, calcium sulfate) to elevate calcium hardness up to the total alkalinity concentration in the pond water.

Alkalinity of water is its acid neutralizing capacity and it measures the amount of strong acid needed to lower the pH of a sample to 8.3, which gives free alkalinity (phenolphthalein alkalinity) and to a pH 4.5 gives total alkalinity (Ramachandra et al., 2006). Alkalinity serves as a buffer to

prevent drastic change in pH and expresses the total concentration of bases in water body including carbonates, bicarbonates, hydroxides, phosphates, borates, dissolved calcium, magnesium and other compounds in the water. In the present study, Total alkalinity of the water samples ranged from 300.5 to 355.6 mg.L⁻¹ with an average of 339.44±10.08 mg.L⁻¹. Highest alkalinity was recorded at Mvugo site and the lowest at Kajaga site. The previous studies at Kigoma bay have reported the average surface alkalinity of 293 mg.L⁻¹ CaCO₃ and 255.5 mg.L⁻¹ CaCO₃ at 100m (Ismael *et al.*, 2000). Lime leaching out of concrete ponds or calcareous rocks, photosynthesis, denitrification and sulphate reduction is mainly responsible for increasing alkalinity while respiration, nitrification and sulphide oxidation decrease or consume alkalinity (Stumm and Morgan, 1981; Cook *et al.*, 1986) and to a lesser degree it increases due to evaporation and decomposing organic matter. Ponds with low alkalinity benefit from the addition of lime.

Electrical conductivity expresses the ability of an aqueous solution to carry electrical current and this aptitude depends on the number of free ions present in water (such as Ca²⁺, Mg²⁺, HCO₃⁻, CO₃⁻, NO₃⁻ and PO₄⁻), their total concentration, mobility, valence and relative concentrations and on the temperature of measurement. Conductivity is thus indicative of the total ionic content and freshness level of the water (Ogbeibu and Victor, 1995). The more salts are dissolved in the water; the higher is the value of the electrical conductivity. Conductivity will always increase at a given temperature, when the number of free ions is increased. Most of the solids

remaining in the water after a sand filter are dissolved ions. In the water, Sodium chloride is found in the form of Na^+ and Cl^- . Water with High purity, without salts or minerals has a very low electrical conductivity. In the present study, the Electrical Conductivity values ranged from 658 to $677\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ and the average was $667.38\pm 2.89\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$. These values are very close to those recorded by [Plisnier et al. \(1999\)](#): $659\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ at Bujumbura-Uvira, $654\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ at Kigoma and $662\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ at Mpulungu and those recorded by [Ismael et al. \(2000\)](#): 670 to $681.5\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ at the surface at Kigoma station. The maximum value was observed at Nyamugari and Kajaga stations in January 2017, minimum value is found at Rumonge site in February 2018. In Lake Tanganyika, conductivity increases normally with the increase in depth because the bottom water is rich in nutrients that exist dissolved in the water column. For the current investigation, the sample was taken from surface water which is poor in nutrients.

Chloride is commonly found in streams and wastewater and is useful for fish to maintain their osmotic equilibrium ([Bhatnagar A .and Pooja D., 2013](#)). Chloride can enter surface water from various sources including: industrial and municipal wastewater, sewage from water softening, salt deposits dissolution, agricultural runoff and produced water from gas and oil wells. In the present study, chloride obtained was in the range of 30.8 to $47\text{mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$. Kajaga site was found to have maximum value which can be attributed to high industrial pollution since the station is the closest to Bujumbura city while minimum value was recorded at Nyamugari site. Chloride is the same element in the form of a salt since Chloride (Cl^-) and

sodium (Na^+) form together common salt (sodium chloride). Chloride should not be confused with the gas chlorine (Cl_2) which is a highly reactive compound used as a disinfectant. While chlorine is very lethal to fish, chloride is a component of most waters and is essential in helping fish maintain their osmotic balance. In commercial catfish production, chloride in the form of salt is often added to water to obtain a minimum concentration of 100 mg.L^{-1} . This is done because catfish and certain other species are susceptible to “brown blood” disease, caused by excess nitrite in the water. Maintaining a chloride to nitrite ratio of 10:1 prevents nitrite from entering the fish, thus reducing the occurrence of nitrite poisoning. Chloride concentration may be increased by addition of salt mixture to the water.

The hardness of water is the sum of the concentrations of metal cations present in water, with the exception of those of alkali metals (Na^+ , K^+). In most cases, the hardness is generally due to calcium and magnesium cations concentration in water (Sekerka I. and Lechner J.F., 1975) and is depending on the dissolved solids and pH. Calcium and magnesium are fundamental for metabolic reactions of fish like bone and scale formation. According to Bhatnagar *et al.*,(2004) hardness values less than 20ppm causes stress, 75-150 ppm is optimum for fish culture and >300 ppm is lethal to fish life as it increases pH, resulting in non-availability of nutrients. Certainly, some euryhaline species may have high hardness tolerance limits. The hardness in the present study ranged from 161 to 226 $\text{mg CaCO}_3.\text{L}^{-1}$. Maximum and minimum values were recorded at Kajaga

and Mvugo sites respectively and the average hardness was 196.48 mg CaCO₃.L⁻¹. For all stations, the values found were greater than the standard range recommended by ICAR (2007) for fish culture. This implies that the water is too hard and the amount of water soluble salts is too high. These high values of hardness may be due to the addition of calcium and magnesium salts. The increase in hardness can be also attributed to the decrease in water volume and increase in the rate of evaporation at high temperature. Indeed, hardness is inversely proportional to water volume and directly proportional to rate of evaporation. When the concentration of calcium and magnesium ions is less than 40 ppm, it is considered as soft water and if the concentration is greater than 40ppm it is hard water.

Hujare (2008) reported that the total hardness was high in summer compared to the rainy season and the winter season. So, decreasing of water hardness to reach the acceptable range is needed. It implies that water pH and hardness can all be changed by proper liming of the water and heavy rainfall can lead to sudden variations in the hardness. It is therefore important to avoid the runoff water to bring lot of silt into the fish pond.

Chemical oxygen demands (COD) and biochemical oxygen demand (BOD) are important parameters for oxygen required to degradation of organic matter. In fact, BOD reflects the dissolved oxygen amount needed by aerobic organisms to breakdown organic matter occurring in water at a given temperature for a specified time, while COD determines the oxygen amount needed for oxidizing the biodegradable and

non-biodegradable organic matter in water by a strong chemical oxidant (Mahananda et al., 2010) under specific conditions of oxidizing agent, temperature and time. In the present study, the COD value ranged from 15-75mg.L⁻¹ and the average was 34.25±20.77mg.L⁻¹. Since COD range in unpolluted surface water is ≤20mg.L⁻¹ (Chapman, 1997), mean values showed that all stations were polluted with high pollution at Kajaga station. The BOD content of various sampling sites ranged from 5 to 15mg.L⁻¹ with an average of 9.51±3.18mg.L⁻¹. Kajaga and Nyamugari stations appeared to be polluted by sewage and industrial wastes as they have high BOD Concentration while Rumonge and Mvugo stations show low mean BOD value. The BOD of water in fish ponds can be decreased by removing hardness and by keeping the water at optimum temperature. Excess entry of cattle, industrial and domestic sewage from non-point sources and increased phosphate in the lake can be attributed to high organic load, resulting in higher level of BOD. Clerk (1986) reported that BOD range of 2 to 4 mg.L⁻¹ does not show pollution while levels beyond 5mg.L⁻¹ are indicative of serious pollution. According to Bhatnagar et al.,(2004) ,the BOD level between 3.0-6.0ppm is optimum for normal activities of fishes; 6.0-12.0 ppm is sublethal to fishes and >12.0ppm can usually cause fish kill due to suffocation. Santhosh and Singh (2007) recommended that the optimal level of BOD in aquaculture should be below 10mg.L⁻¹, but the water having BOD content of less than 10-15 mg.L⁻¹ may be considered for pisciculture. Bhatnagar and Singh (2010) suggested that the BOD less than 1.6mg.L⁻¹ is suitable for pond fish culture and according to Ekubo and

Abowei (2011), aquatic system with BOD levels between 1 and 2mg.L⁻¹ is considered clean; 3mg.L⁻¹ is fairly clean; 5mg.L⁻¹ is doubtful and 10mg.L⁻¹ definitely bad and polluted.

Dissolved oxygen (DO) determines the gaseous oxygen amount dissolved in water serving as fundamental role in the life of cultured organisms (Dhawan and Karu, 2002). DO affect the growth, survival, distribution, behaviour and physiology of shrimps and other aquatic organisms (Solis, 1988). The main source of oxygen in water is atmospheric air and photosynthetic planktons. Oxygen depletion of water results in poor fish nutrition, starvation, reduced growth, and increased mortality of fish, either directly or indirectly (Bhatnagar and Garg, 2000). DO content recorded during the investigation ranged from 7.16 to 7.71mg.L⁻¹ with an average of 7.38±0.17mg.L⁻¹. This dissolved oxygen value is close to 8.33mg.L⁻¹ recorded by Ismael et al.(2000) at the surface of Lake Tanganyika in Kigoma Bay, Tanzania. For fish culture, a saturation level in Dissolved Oxygen of at least 5 mg/L is required. Thus; DO values found were within the desirable limits recommended by ICAR (2007) and all the sampling sites were suitable for pisciculture. Oxygen is sensitive to high temperature. Rani et al. (2004) have also reported lower dissolved oxygen values in summer, due to the high rate of organic matter decomposition and the limited flow of water in low holding environment due to high temperature. Indeed, during this period, aquatic plants compete for dissolved oxygen in the water for respiration although this can be gotten back as a product of photosynthesis during the day time. However, during

the raining season, the dissolved oxygen increases as a result of dissolved atmospheric oxygen from rain water and high wind current. Warm water holds less dissolved oxygen than cool water because every 10⁰C rise in temperature doubles the rate of metabolism, chemical reaction and oxygen consumption in general. The low level of dissolved oxygen is the main parameter limiting the quality of water in aquaculture systems. An extremely low level of dissolved oxygen occurs in water body, especially when algal proliferation decline and subsequently break down of algal blooms, which can lead to stress or mortality of pink shrimp in ponds. Chronically low dissolved oxygen levels can reduce growth, feeding and molting frequency. The most common cause of low dissolved oxygen in an aquaculture operation is a high concentration of biodegradable organic matter in water.

Calcium and magnesium are two most common constituents of hardness. Hardness caused by calcium is called calcium hardness, while hardness caused by magnesium is called magnesium hardness. Since calcium and magnesium are normally the only significant minerals that cause hardness, it is generally assumed that Calcium hardness (mg/L as CaCO₃) and Magnesium Hardness (mg/L as CaCO₃) are summed for obtaining total Hardness (mg/L as CaCO₃).

A specific recommended concentration of Magnesium for fish farming in freshwater and fish pond is not assigned. In waters with a high bicarbonate concentration, calcium and magnesium tend to precipitate as the soil water

concentrates. Calcium is found in all the natural waters and its main source is weathering of rocks from which it leaches out. Calcium is an essential element for fish, and moderate calcium levels in aquaculture water help in fish osmoregulation during stressful periods. Calcium is also important for egg and larvae development. Most well water contains enough calcium for hatcheries; 80% of domestic well water sampled by the United States Geological Survey had between 7 and 95 mg.L⁻¹ of calcium (DeSimone et al., 2009). However, certain aquifers may have very low levels. Calcium concentrations greater than 400 mg.L⁻¹ may be detrimental to crustaceans and fish. In the present study, Calcium ranged from 33.2 to 58.8 mg.L⁻¹ with an average of 42.8 ±9.18mg.L⁻¹. Water with free calcium concentrations as low as 10 mg.L⁻¹ can be tolerated by rainbow trout, if pH is above 6.5. At least 5 mg.L⁻¹ of calcium hardness is needed in catfish hatchery water, and more than 20 mg.L⁻¹ is desirable (SRAC, 2013). Fish can absorb calcium from water or food. For example, the concentration of calcium in water sources for catfish hatcheries is essential because low calcium content will decrease the hatching rate of eggs and the survival of fry (SRAC 2013). The quantity of Calcium hardness is fundamental in pond fertilization because higher rates of phosphorus fertilizer are needed for higher calcium hardness contents.

Iron occurs mainly in the surface water in the ferric form as divalent state. Tucker and Robinson (1985) reported that iron concentrations less than 0.5 mg.L⁻¹ would be appropriate for hatcheries and channel catfish

and other warm water species while the optimal iron concentration for cold water temperature is less than 0.15 mg.L^{-1} but Meade (1989) conservatively recommends a general standard of less than 0.01 mg/l . In the present study, Iron concentration ranged from 0.018 to 0.17 mg.L^{-1} . Maximum and minimum values were respectively recorded at Rumonge and Nyamugari sites. Mean value was $0.0736 \pm 0.068 \text{ mg.L}^{-1}$. Thus, the results were in accordance with the standards recommended by ICAR (2007) and all stations were found to be favourable for fish culture. However, ferrous iron (Fe^{2+}) may contribute significantly to groundwater hardness levels. Spring and well waters can contain high levels of iron (ferrous iron) and manganese, while remaining clear to the eye. When the water in the well is exposed to oxygen, the iron turns into rust (ferric iron), which gives the water a rusty brown color. Water with high iron dose should be treated before using it in a fish hatchery. Typically, well water is aerated to oxidize the iron and then, the water is passed through a sand filter to remove the floc (small clumps). Alternatively, well water is pumped into a settling pond for settlement and oxidation before its use in a hatchery.

Nutrients (TN, TP and TC): Carbon, Nitrogen and Phosphorus are three vital elements required for algal growth that heavily affects eutrophication process in lakes. Excess of C and N has a significant impact on eutrophication in lakes through being a nutrient for algal blooms (Nie et al., 2016). Phosphorus is essential element for life and a key limiting nutrient in freshwater systems (Elser J., 2012). Excessive amounts of

Phosphorus entering lakes from rivers and through a variety of human activities such as aquaculture, industry and municipal sewage treatment lead to eutrophication and algal blooms in lakes (Wang et al., 2006). Nutrients may also lead to the growth of nuisance aquatic plants (macrophytes) and filamentous algae, and in rare cases can lead to the presence of some algal species that can produce compounds harmful to wildlife and humans. Some pond owners desire clear water, which requires that nutrient inputs be strictly controlled. According to the USEPA (2000), a total phosphorus concentration of more than 0.01mg.L^{-1} and a total nitrogen concentration of more than 0.15mg.L^{-1} provide sufficient nutrients for algae blooms in the growing season. National background levels in streams for waters with no human disturbance were estimated by the U.S. Geological Survey to be 0.034mg.L^{-1} total phosphorus and 0.58mg.L^{-1} total nitrogen (Dubrovsky et al., 2010). However, a specific recommended concentration of Total carbon suitable for fish farming in freshwater and fish pond is not assigned. In the current study, Total carbon dose ranged from 71.32 to 82.43mg.L^{-1} with an average of $76.99\pm 2.9\text{mg.L}^{-1}$; Total Nitrogen value ranged from 0.11 to 0.38mg.L^{-1} with $0.21\pm 0.08\text{mg.L}^{-1}$ in average; Total Phosphorus values ranged from 0.69 to 1.71mg.L^{-1} with an average of $1.21\pm 0.45\text{mg.L}^{-1}$ and the values found for Total Nitrogen and Total Phosphorus from all stations were in accordance with the standards ranges suitable for fish culture. By comparing the mean concentrations for total phosphorus between stations, the values found at Kajaga and Nyamugari sites (1.64mg.L^{-1} and 1.62mg.L^{-1} respectively) are almost double of each of

the values recorded at Rumonge and Mvugo sites (0.86mg.L^{-1} and 0.74mg.L^{-1} respectively). This suggests that the different activities leading to the increase of these nutrients in the water would be more intense at the sampling sites close to Bujumbura city. In fact, Bujumbura is the largest city on the coast of Lake Tanganyika, sheltering a variety of potentially polluting industries and activities (Bakevya et al., 1998). The extent of degradation of organic origin on Bujumbura side would thus be caused by domestic discharges, agricultural leaching and certain activities (car mechanics, vehicle maintenance stations, oil distributors and various industries) that directly reject their wastewater in the sanitation system, which in turn discharges them into the lake (Ogutu et al., 1997; Pas, 2000; Kelly, 2001).

The N/P ratio, which indicates nutrient deficiency, is often used to explain the dynamics of planktonic communities (Sommer, 1989). The ratio of dissolved N/dissolved P for which one of the elements is considered limiting is variable according to the authors. According to the studies carried out by Guilford and Hecky (2000), nitrogen is limiting when the ratio of total nitrogen (TN) to total phosphorus (TP) is less than 20 and phosphorus limitation is effective when this ratio is greater than 50. However, according to Descy et al. (2006), Nitrogen is considered limiting when the ratio $\text{TN/TP} < 30$ and phosphorus is limiting when this ratio is > 30 . According to Ryding and Rast (1994), if the mass ratio of N / P concentrations $\{ \text{N/P} = [\text{N} = (\text{NO}_2^- + \text{NO}_3^- + \text{NH}_4)] / [\text{P} = \text{PO}_4^{3-}] \}$ is less than 7, nitrogen will probably become the limiting factor and if the ratio is greater than 7, it will be rather phosphorus. If the ratio is approximately 7, the two

elements or even other factors such as light or temperature could be limiting. According to Barroin (2000), nitrogen or phosphorus is limiting in environment when the N / P ratio is <7 or > 10, respectively. But according to Redfield (1934) referring to the average elemental composition of the phytoplankton organisms biomass that develop without limitation by nutrients, nitrogen or phosphorus is respectively limiting depending on whether the ratio N/P is < or >16. In the present study, the TN/TP ratio is very <30 in all sampling stations which indicates that Nitrogen is the lacking element, limiting for algal growth.

Heavy metals are among the important indicators for aquatic pollution. The term heavy metal refers to any metallic chemical element having a relatively high density compared to water or having a specific gravity greater than 5 g/cm³ (Fergusson J.E,1990) and is toxic or poisonous even at low concentrations. Heavy metals are also considered as trace elements due to their presence in trace concentrations (ppb range to less than 10ppm) in various environmental matrices (Kabata- Pendia A., 2001). Contamination of the aquatic environment by heavy metals, whether as a consequence of chronic or toxic events, is an additional source of stress for aquatic organisms. Aquatic environments are very sensitive to trace elements through the coexistence of two phenomena of bioaccumulation and biomagnification through which trace elements are concentrated as they are absorbed into the food chain (water → plankton → herbivorous fish → carnivorous fish → human). Heavy metals accumulate in sediments and can eventually be mobilized into the lake

during the rainy season. Heavy metals entering the aquatic environment are on the one hand of natural sources, the most important of which are volcanic activities, weathering of continents and forest fires (Biney et al.,1994) and on the other hand from anthropogenic sources such as industrial processes (metals smelting, iron and steel industries), use of fossil fuels (eg, coal-fired electrical power stations, industrial boilers, cement furnaces), transports (road and non-road vehicles and engines, watercraft), waste incineration (electrical switches, dental amalgam, fluorescent lighting), Mineral extraction effluents, domestic effluents and urban storms runoff, leaching of metals from household garbage dumps and solid residues, Inputs of metals from rural areas (metals contained in pesticides) and petrochemical activities (Biney et al.,1994).

The present study has only focused on Cadmium, Chromium, Copper, Lead, Selenium and Arsenic. The results of analysis showed that Copper and Lead were present at all sampling stations with slightly high concentrations. This is due to the widespread use of these two elements making them omnipresent in the environment and in addition, lead is also used as an additive in gasoline and is often found in automobile transport emissions. Cadmium was found nil or zero at Rumonge and Mvugo stations and in low concentration at Kajaga and Nyamugari stations. The main sources of anthropogenic emissions of cadmium are the metal industries, waste incineration and smoking (IBGE, 2005). Chromium was present at three stations (Kajaga, Nyamugari and Rumonge) and absent (zero value) at Mvugo station. The quantities of chromium detected in the

hydrosphere are mainly related to industrial emissions. Selenium was absent at Rumonge and Mvugo stations but showed very low concentration at Kajaga and Nyamugari stations. Arsenic was totally absent or nil at all sampling sites. Its total absence can be explained by the absence of its main sources near Lake Tanganyika such as mining, ores melting and coal-fired electrical power stations.

Trophic and pollution status of the water at sampling stations:

Referring to the system developed by [OECD \(1982\)](#), based on the ranges of total phosphorus, chlorophyll a and transparency, the results have shown that the waters were in eutrophic and hypereutrophic status. This finding clearly shows that the sampled sites are affected by domestic, agricultural, urban and /or industrial discharges. Many authors ([Ansa-Assar et al., 2000](#); [Kotak et al., 2000](#); [Downing et al., 2001](#); [Sondergaard et al., 2003](#); [Li et al., 2009](#); [German et al., 2010](#)) declare unanimously that many anthropogenic activities involve a concentration of nutrients, especially phosphorus on a limited number of watersheds. Indeed, deforestation, intensive agriculture and urbanization are recognized as the main factors contributing to the increase of phosphorus and nitrogen in lakes ([Carignan et al., 2000](#); [Prepas et al., 2001](#); [Quinlan et al., 1998](#)) and in the present study, we consider that the same factors (with special emphasis on urbanization) would justify the high phosphorus levels at Kajaga and Nyamugari sites. Furthermore, urbanization leads to an increase and densification of the human population involving the import of nutrients produced in other watersheds, resulting in a concentration of sewage and

detergent discharges (Moss, 1980) in the aquatic environment. This phenomenon has the effect of unbalancing the natural mechanisms of nutrients recycling (Sondergaard et al., 2003) and leads to eutrophication and proliferation of macrophytes. However, the invasion of the water body by the seagrass creates quickly unfavourable conditions for fishing, the fishing gears are entangled and fish eventually die (Galvez-Cloutier R., 2002). Macrophytes accelerate considerably the filling of the lacustrine bowl especially as they proliferate when the depth is too short. Excess plant production leads to deoxygenation of the water and thus contributes to reducing the chances of the animal species survival and even if they do not die, the fish get a taste and smell unsuitable for eating.

Regarding the pollution status of the sampling sites, the Biochemical Oxygen Demand (BOD) and the Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD), which are directly related to the organic pollution, were used and it was found that pollution was very high in the northern areas of Lake Tanganyika which are close to Bujumbura City. In fact, Kajaga and Nyamugari sites were heavily polluted and had high total phosphorus concentrations compared to Rumonge and Mvugo sites, which were moderately polluted with low total phosphorus concentrations. This statement shows that there is a relationship between trophic and pollution status and this is also confirmed by the strong positive correlation observed between total phosphorus concentrations and Biochemical Oxygen Demand ($r = 0.906$) and Chemical Oxygen Demand ($r = 0.709$).

In other words, the pollution level decreases gradually from the northern part of the lake to the southern side of the lake and vice versa.

V.2 Biological community

V.2.1 Algal biomass

Chlorophyll a is an indicator of the microscopic algae biomass present in the lake and its concentration increases with the increase of nutrients concentration. During our investigation, the measurement of Chlorophyll-a concentration distribution showed that Kajaga and Mvugo sites have the highest average concentrations (0.305mg.L^{-1} and 0.375mg.L^{-1} , respectively) compared to other sites. This high level of chlorophyll-a, which reflects the presence of a large phytoplankton biomass is typical of eutrophic environments (Galvez-Cloutiers et al., 2002). The increase in algal biomass at these sites is mainly related to high inputs of nitrogen and phosphorus. This phenomenon of increased algal biomass can lead to changes in assemblages of fish and invertebrates and thus promote the development of undesirable species, such as tolerant species to pollution, some of which may be invasive (Dodds, 2006). This seems to be the case of the water hyacinth (*Eichhornia crassipes*) which swarms at Bujumbura Port station which is close to Kajaga site. The same observations proving that chlorophyll-a concentration peaks are due to urban wastewater discharges were made by Ekou et al. (2011) in their study of the temporal variations of physicochemical and biotic parameters of two aquatic ecosystems of a West African lagoon.

V.2.2 Bacterial community

Coliform bacteria are organisms occurring in the environment and in the faeces of all warm-blooded animals and humans. There are three different groups of coliform bacteria such as Total coliform, Fecal coliform and *Escherichia coli* as shown on the figure 49.

Figure 49: Diagrams showing different groups of Coliform bacteria

Source: <https://www.doh.wa.gov/portals/1/images/4200/coliform.png>

In fact, **total coliform bacteria** are commonly found in the environment and are generally harmless. If only total coliform bacteria are detected in water sample, the source is probably environmental.

Fecal coliform bacteria are a sub-group of total coliform bacteria and originate from faeces produced by human and warm-blooded animals. The presence of fecal coliform in a water sample indicates often a recent fecal contamination and the possible presence of potentially pathogenic bacteria, viruses and protozoa.

Escherichia coli are a sub-group of fecal coliform group and most of *Escherichia coli* bacteria are harmless and are found in large numbers in the intestines of humans and warm-blooded animals. However, detection of

the *Escherichia Coli* in a sample is the indisputable evidence of the occurrence of recent faecal contamination and is indicative of potential presence of enteric pathogens (Payment et al., 2003; Leclerc et al., 2001; Tallon et al., 2005; Wade et al., 2003).

In the present study, both faecal coliforms and *Escherichia Coli* which are good indicators of fecal contamination were absent at Kajaga site and were detected in quantities ranging from 4×10^3 to 50×10^3 CFU.L⁻¹ at Nyamugari, Rumonge and Mvugo stations (Table 31). The minimum value was recorded at Nyamugari site whereas maximum was found at Mvugo site. The presence of this faecal contamination is attributed in part to the nocturnal fishing activity leading fishermen to defecate in the lake while they are fishing. Besides, Rumonge and Mvugo stations are close to human settlements contributing to the release of faecal coliforms into the lake through the raw sewage or partially treated sewage being discharged into the lake as well as the runoff and subsurface flow from the urban area.

Local communities interviewed on spot reported a water-borne cholera outbreak during the rainy season in populations living around and using the water of Lake Tanganyika for domestic purposes, which is also evidence of faecal contamination. The presence of faecal coliforms and *Escherichia Coli* at Nyamugari station where there are no human settlements is also due to faeces released by nocturnal fishermen who defecate on spot while they are fishing. Besides, field observation revealed that women and youths cooking for fishermen spend several hours gathering firewood and the fishermen themselves resting during the

daytime may all defecate anywhere around Nyamugari site, since there are no sanitation facilities available. The total absence of Faecal coliforms and *Escherichia coli* at Kajaga site during our investigation does not necessarily indicate the no contamination and good sanitary quality of the water of this station because these bacteria are in general more sensitive to disinfection of laboratory equipment than more chlorine-resistant pathogens such as viruses (Payment et al., 1997) and cryptosporidium oocysts like Cryptosporidium spp. (Mac Kenzie et al., 1994). Total coliforms have been detected in all sampling stations and ranged from 90×10^3 to 600×10^3 CFU.L⁻¹. Minimum score was recorded at Kajaga site while maximum was found at Rumonge station. The presence of total coliforms indicated both environmental and fecal contaminations which were mainly due to diffuse pollution from runoff, shortcomings in land management of the catchment, human activities and settlements, household sewage, livestock dung and open air defecation.

V.2.3 Zooplanktons Population

The word zooplankton is derived from the Greek *ζῷον* (zoon) meaning "animal", and *πλαγκτός* (planktos) meaning wanderer (Thurman H.V., 1997). The freshwater zooplanktons comprise mainly of six groups such as Protozoa, Rotifers, Crustaceans, Cladocerans, Copepods and Ostracods (Ramachandra et al., 2006) and fish eggs, larvae of larger animals such as annelids and fish. Zooplanktons constitute an important link in food chain as grazers (primary and secondary consumers) and serve as food for fish

directly or indirectly. Therefore any adverse effect to them will be indicated in the wealth of the fish populations and monitoring them as biological indicators of pollution could act as a forewarning for fisheries especially when the food chain is affected by pollution (Mahajan, 1981). In fact, the use of zooplankton for ecological biomonitoring of the water bodies helps in the analysis of water quality trends, development of cause-effect relationships between water quality and environmental health and judgement of the adequacy of water quality for various uses. Zooplankton population of Lake Tanganyika was composed of 3 orders such as: Cyclopoida, Calanoida (Copepods) and Cladocera represented by the Diaphanosoma.

Apart from the shortage of Jellyfish during the present study, the results obtained were in accordance with those found by Coulter (1991) and Bwebwa (1996) who found that the northern pelagic zooplankton community of Lake Tanganyika is dominated by the crustacean copepods consisting mainly of *Tropodiatomus simplex* and cyclopoid while the minor constituents in the pelagic environment are the jellyfish represented by *Limnognathia tanganyicae* and some scarce rotifers. In the present investigation, jellyfish and rotifers have not been identified due to the use of the large mesh size net (63 μm) which lets a large amount of rotifers pass through the net, since this group consists of smaller individuals. On the other hand, this could be explained by a low sampling frequency which decreases the possibilities of capturing the jellyfish, which is a scarce species of Lake Tanganyika, but also by the possible daily migrations that

have been reported in several zooplankton groups (Dussard, 1989; Bwebwa, 1996; Isumbiso et al., 2006). The presence of *Diaphanosoma* (Cladocerans) at only Rumonge and Mvugo sites can be explained by the fact that there are no cladocerans in the lake itself, probably because of the high predation. The Cladoceran species found in the Lake Tanganyika basin were all found in the near-shore area and adjacent waters of the lake. No species was found in pelagic habitat (Patterson and Makin, 1998). The *Diaphanosoma* identified from these two sites would likely come from coastal lagoons. On the other hand, the presence of Copepoda in almost all sampling sites may be a function of several characteristics related to the organisms themselves.

The first is their ability to accept highly variable environmental conditions (Amoros and Chessel, 1985). The second is their resistance to more or less rapid fluctuations in the physical, chemical and biological characteristics of the environment (Dussart, 1989; Arfi et al., 1981, 1987). Finally, the possibility of surviving at the state of resting stages allows some species in this group to be transported from one habitat to another and thus to have a wider range (Amoros and Chessel, 1985; Khalki et al., 2004). Certainly, the variability observed in the distribution of zooplankton is due to abiotic parameters (e.g Climatic or hydrological parameters such as salinity, temperature, advection and stratification), to biotic parameters (e.g. limitation of food, competition, predation) or to a combination of both (Beyst et al., 2001, Christou, 1998, Escribano and Hidalgo, 2000 and Roff et al., 1988). Even if zooplanktons are present in a wide range of

environmental conditions, many species are still limited by dissolved oxygen, temperature, salinity and other physicochemical factors.

V.2.4 Phytoplanktons Population

Derived from the Greek words *φυτόν*(*phyton*) meaning "plant" and *πλαγκτός* (*planktos*) meaning "wanderer" or "drifter"(Thurman,H.V.,1997), phytoplanktons are microscopic organisms wandering with the water current, performing photosynthesis and living in the upper illuminated waters of all aquatic ecosystems. Phytoplanktons form the very basis of aquatic food chain. Phytoplankton survey indicates the trophic status and the presence of organic pollution in the ecosystem. Nutrient enrichment in water bodies leads to eutrophication, which is a common phenomenon manifested by algal proliferation.

The common freshwater phytoplankton families include Cyanophyceae (cyanobacteria or blue-green algae), Chlorophyceae (Green algae), Bacillariophyceae (Diatoms), Dinophyceae (Dinoflagellates), Euglenophyceae and Coccolithophyceae (Reynolds, 2006). The qualitative and quantitative fluctuations of phytoplankton found in Lake Tanganyika are primarily related to warm climatic conditions. It is well known that with the increase of seasonal temperatures from 10°C to 30°C, phytoplanktons group grow rapidly and a qualitative change is performed in such a way that diatoms will be replaced by chlorophyceae and then by cyanobacteria (Reynolds, 1997,2006). During the present investigation, 115 species of phytoplankton belonging to 7 families have been recorded in all sampling

sites. Diatoms and green algae were shown to be more abundant than other algae encountered with 50 and 31 species respectively. This is due to the fact that the investigation was conducted in February month until early March, which are the most favorable periods for the development of diatoms, reputed to be most abundant in the spring-time, precisely in February where water is fresh and chlorophyceae that are known to be most abundant in March (Figure 50). Dense phytoplankton helps in producing 10times more oxygen than it consumes and plays therefore an important role in compensating for respiratory losses without increasing further energy expenditures.

The dinoflagellates were also abundant with 16 species. However, large and rapid variations in abundances of dinoflagellates bloom are observed during the summer. The latitudinal distribution of dinoflagellate cysts in marine sediments is related to the surface waters temperature (Wall et al., 1977; Harland,1983; Edwards & Andrieu,1992), while their offshore distribution is depending on other factors such as salinity, hydrodynamics and mineral salts. Indeed, temperatures between 22°C and 30°C are necessary for the growth of dinoflagellates (Chang et al.,2000; Simoni et al, 2003) and this is in accordance with the results obtained for temperature in the present study which ranged from 27.1°C to 28.95°C throughout the study period. The families Xanthophyceae, Zygothryxaceae and Myxophyceae were shown to be very less abundant and comprised of 6; 5 and 4species respectively.The family Cyanophyceae was in the last position with 3species. The very low presence of cyanobacteria is due to

environmental conditions that were not propitious to their development during the survey period (January-March). Indeed, the temperature rise and the warming of the waters of Lake Tanganyika finally occur at the end of the dry season (September), leading to the proliferation of cyanobacteria and thus causing algal bloom. The algal development is therefore seasonal as shown on the Figure 50.

Figure 50: Types of algae depending on the time of year

Source : <https://www.rappel.qc.ca/IMG/jpg/Image-Lac5-3.jpg>

FINDINGS SUMMARY AND RECOMMENDATIONS

■ Findings Summary

The freshwater resources in the world are facing serious pollution problems due to various anthropogenic activities such as the population growth, the expansion of industrialization, the increasing use of fertilizers and pesticides in agriculture (Singh et al., 2004; Vega et al., 1996).

The degradation of water resources is focusing mainly on changes in water quality which in turn is determined by various physico-chemical and biological factors (Malmqvist and Rundle, 2002). However, all living organisms have tolerable limits of water quality parameters in which they operate their vital functions optimally. An increase beyond these limits has adverse effects on their body functions (Davenport, 1993; Kiran, 2010). The optimum fish production is totally depending on physico-chemical and biological characteristics of water as they may directly or indirectly affect the water quality and hence its suitability for the distribution and production of fish and other aquatic animals (Moses, 1983). Thus, maintaining all the environmental factors at favourable thresholds becomes essential to obtain maximum yield in a fish reservoir and therefore, water quality monitoring is vital for conservation of water resources and their sustainable use for drinking water supply, irrigation, fish farming and other economic activities.

The water of Lake Tanganyika is subject to changes in physico-chemical and biological characteristics resulting in the deterioration of water quality to a great pace. Increasing urbanization and consequent

discharge of harmful effluents from large cities established in Lake Tanganyika watershed is continually altering the water quality and productivity of the Lake, jeopardizing its sustainability (Wetzel, 2001).

The present investigation conducted on Lake Tanganyika was undertaken to assess the water quality with reference to its suitability for fish culture purposes, to determine the trophic and pollution status of the water at sampled stations, to evaluate the qualitative and quantitative structure of planktonic diversity as fish food, to establish an inventory and taxonomic characterization of fish species diversity and to highlight the effect of pollutants on the abundance and spatial distribution of fish species.

Indeed, the results of the comparative analysis revealed that Lake Tanganyika has a high fish potential as most of the analyzed parameters were within permissible limits for pisciculture and the fish productivity of the study areas can be improved, if all physical, chemical and biological parameters are maintained at required levels. However, among 30 physico-chemical and biological parameters evaluated, it has been reflected that the values of:

- ⇒ 19 parameters (63%) were found within the permissible limits recommended in fish farming, such as: Temperature, pH, Electrical Conductivity, Total Dissolved Solids, Calcium, Iron, Total Nitrogen, Total Phosphorus, Percent of Oxygen Saturation, Dissolved Oxygen, Chemical Oxygen Demand, Biochemical Oxygen Demand, Cadmium, Chromium, Selenium, Arsenic, Plankton organisms, Fecal coliforms and Total Coliforms.

- ⇒ 8 parameters (27%) like: Turbidity, Transparency, Total Alkalinity, Chloride, Total hardness, Chlorophyll a, Copper and Lead were found inappropriate for pisciculture.
- ⇒ The standard values recommended in pisciculture for Total Carbon, Magnesium and Escherichia Coli (10%) are not available till date.

The results of Tukey's Honestly Significant Difference test (Tukey's HSD) and One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA-1) at the 5% level revealed that water quality varies considerably depending on the sampling stations location since the effect of the sampling sites was found **very highly significant ($p < 0.001$)** on the variation of Lead, Copper, Iron and Turbidity; **Highly significant ($0.001 \leq p < 0.01$)** on the change of Chloride, Calcium, Magnesium, Total Phosphorus, Chemical Oxygen Demand and Selenium ; **Simply Significant ($0.01 \leq p \leq 0.05$)** on the variation of Transparency, Total Hardness, Total Nitrogen, Dissolved Oxygen, Biochemical Oxygen Demand, Cadmium and Chromium and **not significant ($p > 0.05$)** on the variation of Temperature, pH, Total Alkalinity, Electrical Conductivity, Total Dissolved Solids, Total Carbon, % Saturation of Dissolved Oxygen and Chlorophyll a.

The results obtained regarding the taxonomy and abundance of fish species revealed the occurrence of 75 species belonging to 7 Orders and 12 families in all sampling sites and among them, species belonging to order Perciformes and the family Cichlidae were the most dominant. The relative diversity index of families has indicated that Rumonge site holds

first position with an average of 46 species distributed into 9 families, followed by Mvugo site with 42 species distributed into 11 families, then Kajaga site with an average of 35 species distributed into 11 families and lastly Nyamugari site appeared as the poorest with an average of 28 species distributed into 6 families. Besides, Similarity index between sampling stations proved that Rumonge and Mvugo pairwise have a high similarity coefficient (Sorensen index=0.67) which indicated that most of the fish species are common or shared between Mvugo and Rumonge stations and therefore the environmental conditions prevailing in these two stations are almost the same. On the other hand, Karl Pearson's correlation coefficient calculated between physico-chemical parameters values and the number of fish species showed a strong positive correlation with Temperature and a strong negative correlation with Turbidity, PH, Electrical Conductivity, Total Dissolved Solids, Total carbon, Iron, Dissolved Oxygen, Biochemical Oxygen Demand, Chromium and Selenium, which revealed that physico-chemical parameters have a high influence on the increase and the decrease of fish species amount in the study environment and at the same time, one-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA-I) and Tukey's Honestly Significant Difference test (Tukey's HSD) have showed that the influence of the study stations on the abundance of fish species is highly significant (p -value= 0.007).

Regarding the trophic status, the values of Transparency, Chlorophyll a, Total phosphorus and Trophic Status Index revealed clearly that the waters at sampling stations were in hypereutrophic status which

indicates eutrophication phenomenon. Furthermore, it has been proved that Kajaga and Nyamugari stations were heavily polluted while Rumonge and Mvugo Stations were moderately polluted and for this purpose, three categories of fish species have been distinguished, based on their adaptation level to pollution: (i) 21 species (28%) were sensitive to pollution, (ii) 15 species (20%) were resistant to pollution and (iii) 39 species (52%) were found tolerant to pollution and adapted for living in all sampling stations, both heavily and moderately polluted.

The results regarding bacteriological community revealed the presence of total coliforms in the range of 9×10^4 to 6×10^5 CFU.L⁻¹ with an average of 332.5×10^3 CFU.L⁻¹ in all sampling sites which indicates the environmental contamination. The presence of faecal coliforms and *Escherichia coli* has not been detected at Kajaga site but has been detected at Nyamugari, Rumonge and Mvugo sites with 5×10^4 CFU.L⁻¹ at maximum which indicates faecal Contamination due to open defecation.

With respect to planktons community results, it was found that all the values obtained were within the permissible limits recommended in pisciculture and, the abundance and diversity of phytoplankton species were far greater than those of zooplankton species. In fact the species composition analysis of phytoplanktons from all sampling sites has listed 115 species belonging to 7 families: Bacillariophyceae, Chlorophyceae, Dinophyceae, Xanthophyceae, Zygothryxaceae, Myxophyceae and Cyanophyceae. The species richness and the Cumulative abundance

showed that Rumonge site holds first position with 115 species which was the maximum of all species identified comprising 3450 individuals per liter, followed by Kajaga site with 107 species comprising 2482 individuals per liter, then Mvugo site with 101 species containing 1506 individuals per liter and in the last position was Nyamugari site with 86 species comprising 1031 individuals per liter.

Zooplankton organisms of Lake Tanganyika were found very few in number and in taxonomic diversity and were comprising of 12 species belonging to 4 families: Diaptomidae, Cyclopidae, Sididae and Temoridae and to 3 orders: Cyclopoida, Calanoida (Copepods) and Cladocera represented by Diaphanosoma. The results regarding quantitative analysis showed that Rumonge site was ranked first with respective species richness and the Cumulative abundance of 11 species and 1152 individuals per liter, Kajaga and Mvugo site were found to have same species richness (10 species) but with different cumulative abundance of 830 and 502 individuals per liter respectively. This places therefore Kajaga site in second position while Mvugo site was in third position. Nyamugari site was in last position with 8 as species richness comprising 219 individuals per liter.

■ Recommendations

Many chemical substances emitted into the environment from anthropogenic sources pose a threat to the functioning of aquatic ecosystems and to the use of water for various purposes. Considering the results of the present study, it is imminent that the water quality, biodiversity and natural resources of Lake Tanganyika are increasingly threatened. The necessity of strict measures to prevent and control the release of these substances into the aquatic environment has resulted in the development and implementation of water management policies and strategies for the sustainable management and exploitation of Lake Tanganyika resources. The following strategies are advisable generally to the governments of riparian countries and especially to the peoples living in the catchment of Lake Tanganyika:

- Establishing of a monitoring program for the continuous analysis of the quality of the lake's coastal waters as well as the rivers and streams flowing into the lake.
- The politico-administrative authorities must use all necessary means to enforce the texts relating to the management of effluents, industrial and domestic wastewater, but also the texts regulating the allocation of land on the shore of Lake Tanganyika.
- To determine the impassable boundaries for buffer zones around Lake Tanganyika and prohibit the construction of dwelling houses and hotels in the buffer zones of Lake Tanganyika;

- Rehabilitation of existing sewage treatment stations and construction of new stations as human populations is ever-increasing in the northern riparian towns of Lake Tanganyika.
- Sustainable land management:
 - ✓ The practice of sustainable agriculture using anti-erosion systems by developing fields in platforms and installing contour lines with anti-erosion hedges made of fodder plants, promoting sustainable agro-forestry practices on watersheds, using animal manure and planting leguminous trees.
 - ✓ The fight against deforestation in Lake Tanganyika watershed by promoting alternatives solutions to firewood, lumber wood, construction wood and charcoal.
 - ✓ Improving of forest management, afforestation and reforestation should be a national priority.
- Pollution mitigation:
 - ✓ Reduction of urban and industrial pollution by establishing harmonized regional and international standards for water quality as well as plans for the collection and treatment of wastewater and solid waste.
 - ✓ Minimize the use of pesticides and fertilizers in the Lake Tanganyika catchment and promote sustainable alternatives strategies.
 - ✓ Reduction of pollution resulting from lake traffic by monitoring of transport conditions and storage of dangerous goods such as oil,

- acids of various categories and other toxic substances and collect solid and liquid waste from ships.
- Prevention of eutrophication and reducing of concentrations and external inputs of nutrients:
 - ✓ Limiting the nutrients inputs to water bodies, particularly the supply of phosphorus and nitrates from water runoff, erosion and leaching of fertilized agricultural land leading to an increase of nutrients stock in hydrosystems.
 - ✓ Make an inventory of the major sources of nutrient pollution in the watershed; analyze the cultural practices (ploughing techniques, use of plant cover, soil type...) as well as the processes of phosphorus flow to Lake Tanganyika for treating the problem upstream.
 - Fighting against invasive species especially water hyacinth (***Eichornia crassipes***) which is one of the invading species representing the most obvious threat on Lake Tanganyika.
 - To conduct a study on the determination of Heavy metals concentration accumulated in fish tissue and some macro-invertebrates to prevent the health risks to human consumers, as the present study has detected the presence of slightly high concentrations of heavy metals in the northern areas of Lake Tanganyika (Kajaga and Nyamugari stations) which are heavily polluted.

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Quantitative and qualitative analysis of phytoplankton population in relation to environmental factors at the targeted sampling stations on the Burundian littoral of Lake Tanganyika

Lambert Niyoyitungiye, Anirudha Giri and Bhanu Prakash Mishra

Abstract

The present study was conducted at 4 sampling sites of Lake Tanganyika and was intending to identify and estimate the spatial abundance of phytoplankton in relation to physico-chemical attributes. The species composition analysis of the samples has listed 115 species of phytoplanktons belonging to 7 families from all sampling sites. The relative diversity index of families has indicated that Bacillariophyceae is the most dominant family in comparison to others families with 50 species (43.4%) followed by the family Chlorophyceae with 31 species (27%). The family Cyanophyceae was found very scarce with 3 species (2.6%).

Regarding quantitative data, the results of species richness and the Cumulative abundance of the sampling sites showed that phytoplankton species and density were variable among stations. Rumonge site holds first position with 115 species which was the maximum of all species identified comprising 3450 individuals per liter followed by Kajaga site with 107 species comprising 2482 individuals per liter, then Mvugo site with 101 species containing 1506 individuals per liter and in the last position was Nyamugari site with 86 species comprising 1031 individuals per liter. Furthermore the results of Canonical Correlation Analysis (CCorA) between the environmental parameters and phytoplankton composition at sampling sites have shown that the abundance and proliferation of some phytoplankton species are negatively or positively affected by the physico-chemical parameters concentration because, some physico-chemical variables were found either inhibitors or accelerators for phytoplankton species growth.

Keywords: Phytoplankton, quantitative and qualitative analysis, physico-chemical attributes, Lake Tanganyika

1. Introduction

Considered as the basic component of an aquatic food chain, Phytoplanktons are the source of oxygen and the main autochthonous primary producers of all types of water bodies ^[1]. Phytoplanktons constitute the basis of nutrient cycle of an ecosystem; hence play an important role in maintaining equilibrium between living organisms and abiotic factors ^[2]. Since phytoplanktons are the primary producers forming the first trophic level of food chain in aquatic system, the qualitative and quantitative studies are of great importance to assess the water quality ^[3-6]. Their standing crops and their species composition show the water quality in which they are growing ^[7]. Phytoplanktons are the producers, the basis of the aquatic ecosystem and therefore are sought as the main component of any freshwater system. They play an important role in solving various environmental problems, production of useful substances and understanding the aquatic ecosystem ^[8]. As species composition of phytoplanktons community changes in response to the environmental variations ^[9], a thorough knowledge of phytoplankton abundance and its quality in relation to environmental condition is essential for fish culture. The dominance, community structure and seasonality of phytoplankton in tropical wetlands are strongly variable and are depending on nutrient status, morphometry of the underlying substrate, water level and other regional factors ^[10-12]. Phytoplankton is the main biological elements used to assess the ecological status of surface water bodies and the change in biotic parameters and gives a good indication of energy turnover in aquatic environments, due to its sensitivity to any change in the environment ^[13, 14],

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RESEARCH ARTICLE**EFFECT OF PHYSICO-CHEMICAL ATTRIBUTES ON THE ABUNDANCE AND SPATIAL DISTRIBUTION OF FISH SPECIES IN LAKE TANGANYIKA, BURUNDIAN COAST.**Lambert Niyoyitungiye^{1,2}, Anirudha Giri¹ and Bhanu Prakash Mishra³.

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Abstract

The water of Lake Tanganyika is subject to changes in physical and chemical characteristics and resulting in the deterioration of water quality to a great pace. The current study was carried out to assess the physical and chemical characteristics of water at 4 sampling stations of Lake Tanganyika and intended, firstly to make an inventory and a taxonomic characterization of all fish species found in the study sites, secondly to determine the pollution status of the selected sites and the impact of physico-chemical parameters on the abundance and spatial distribution of fish species in the Lake.

The results obtained regarding the taxonomy and abundance of fish species showed that a total of 75 fish species belonging to 12 families and 7 orders existed in the 4 selected sampling stations. Besides, it has been proved that Kajaga and Nyamugari stations were heavily polluted while Rumonge and Mvugo Stations were moderately polluted. Karl Pearson's correlation coefficient calculated between physico-chemical parameters values and the number of fish species showed strong positive and negative correlation which revealed that physico-chemical parameters have respectively a high influence on the increase and on the decrease of fish species amount in the study environment and at the same time, one way ANOVA and Tukey's Honestly Significant Difference test (Tukey's HSD) showed that the influence of the sampling stations on the abundance of fish species is highly significant (P= 0.007).

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Introduction:-

The healthy aquatic ecosystem is depending on the physico-chemical and biological characteristics (Venkatesharaju et al., 2010). Freshwater resources across the world are facing serious pollution problems due to various anthropogenic activities, mainly the indiscriminate disposal of waste effluents, population growth, the rise of industrialization and the increasing use of phytosanitary products (fertilizers and pesticides) in agriculture. These activities, particularly in developing countries, have caused the degradation of aquatic environments which change the physiology and ecology of aquatic biota (Khanna and Ishaq, 2013), threaten the balance of aquatic ecosystems, animal and plant communities (Noukeu et al., 2016). Consequently, an intensification of eutrophication resulting in

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Assessment of Physico-Chemical Characteristics of Water at Selected Stations of Lake Tanganyika, Africa with Special Emphasis on Pisciculture Purposes

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Abstract—The current limnological study was carried out on Lake Tanganyika in 4 sampling sites to assess the physico-chemical properties and trophic status for pisciculture purpose. The estimated values of physical and chemical parameters of water samples were compared to the desirable, permissible and acceptable ranges for pisciculture recommended standards. In this regards, 9 physico-chemical parameters have been analyzed and the results of the comparative analysis showed that most of the water quality parameters were suitable for fish culture because 7 important parameters (77.8%) were within the permissible limits and 2 parameters (22.2%) were found inappropriate for pisciculture. The values of transparency, chlorophyll a and Total phosphorus revealed clearly that all sampling stations were in hypereutrophic status which indicate eutrophication phenomenon.

Keywords: Limnology, Lake Tanganyika, Pisciculture.

1. INTRODUCTION

Water quality is the major limiting factor in the productivity of aquatic ecosystems, including fish resources. The health of an aquatic ecosystem depends on its physicochemical and biological characteristics (Watson and John, 2003; Venkatesharaju et al., 2010). Adverse changes in water quality of aquatic ecosystems are reflected in the biotic community structure and the most sensitive species often act as sentinels of water quality. Therefore, water quality monitoring is vital for conservation of water resources and their sustainable use for drinking water supply, irrigation and fish farming.

Lake Tanganyika is one of the largest lakes of Africa which is second largest in terms of area following Lake Victoria. At the world level, Lake Tanganyika is the longest freshwater lake and holds second position in terms of volume and depth after Lake Baikal (Wetzel, 1983). It serves as the life support for the four neighboring African countries namely Burundi, Democratic Republic of Congo, Tanzania and Zambia sharing its entire perimeter. Apart from many economic activities, Lake Tanganyika supports the livelihood to a vast majority of the population of these countries through fishing. It has been estimated that Lake Tanganyika provides up to 60% of the animal protein to the people of the region (Jensen, 2016; McGrath, 2016) with up to 200000 tons of fish catch (Jensen, 2016).

Climate change driven rise in global temperature over the years has been identified as one of the major causes for the rapid decline in the productivity of Lake Tanganyika (O'Reilly et al., 2003). Besides, increasing urbanization and consequent discharge of harmful effluents from large cities is continually altering the quality water and productivity of Lake Tanganyika (Wetzel, 2001) jeopardizing its sustainability. In the present study we have analyzed the water quality at four selected locations with varying human activities along the cost of Burundi. The study is limited to physico-chemical characteristics and the findings are compared to reference values recommended for fish farming.

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 Dr. G.C. Mishra President, Krishi Sanskriti (Conference Chair)		
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Venue: University of Science and Technology, Meghalaya

CERTIFICATE OF BEST PAPER PRESENTATION AWARD (ORAL CATEGORIE)

Certified that Prof./Dr./ Mr./Mrs./Ms. Lambert Niyoyitungiye of Dept. of Life Science and
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Award (Oral Categorie) titled Assessment of Physico-Chemical characteristics of water at
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Pisciculture Purposes
The paper was authored by Niyoyitungiye Lambert, A. Giri and B.P. Mishra

 Dr. G.C. Mishra President, Krishi Sanskriti (Conference Chair)		
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Annexures

Appendix 1: Water quality required for various uses

I. Standards required for Irrigation Water quality

Parameters	Recommended Value	Source
TDS(mg/L)	≤1000 (Fine textured soils)	WWF-Pakistan(2007)
	≤2000 (for Coarse textured soils)	WWF-Pakistan(2007)
	≤1500 (Medium textured soils)	WWF-Pakistan(2007)
	<160(Excellent)	USRSL(1954) and FAO (2013)
	160-500(Good)	USRSL(1954) and FAO (2013)
	500-1500(Medium)	USRSL(1954) and FAO (2013)
	1500-2500(Bad)	USRSL(1954) and FAO (2013)
	>2500(Very Bad)	USRSL(1954) and FAO (2013)
Electrical Conductivity (µs/cm) at 25°C	≤1500 (for Fine textured soils)	FAO(2006),BIS-10500(1991), WWF-Pakistan(2007)
	≤2300 (for Medium textured soils)	FAO(2006),BIS-10500(1991), WWF-Pakistan(2007)
	≤3000 (for Coarse textured soils)	WWF-Pakistan(2007)
	<250 (Excellent)	Aamir S. and Muhammad A., 2017
	250-750 (Good)	USRSL(1954) and FAO (2013)
	750-2250 (Medium)	USRSL(1954) and FAO (2013)
	2250-4000 (Bad)	USRSL(1954) and FAO (2013)
SAR (mEq/l)	>4000 (Very Bad)	USRSL(1954) and FAO (2013)
	≤5.0(agricultural irrigation and livestock watering and industrial cooling waters)	WWF-Pakistan(2007)
	≤8 (for Fine textured soils and for Medium textured soils)	WWF-Pakistan(2007)
	≤10(for Coarse textured soils)	WWF-Pakistan(2007)
	<10 (Excellent)	USRSL(1954) and FAO (2013)
	10-18 (Good)	USRSL(1954) and FAO (2013)
	18-26 (Medium)	USRSL(1954) and FAO (2013)
	>26 (Bad)	USRSL(1954) and FAO (2013)
RSC (mEq/l)	>26 (Very Bad)	USRSL(1954) and FAO (2013)
	≤2.3(for medium textured soils)	WWF-Pakistan(2007)
	≤2.5(for Coarse textured soils)	WWF-Pakistan(2007)
	≤1.25(for Fine textured soils)	WWF-Pakistan(2007)
	≤1.25 (Excellent)	USDA(2008)
	1.25-2.5 (Good)	USDA(2008)
2.5> (Medium)	USDA(2008)	

Sodium Percentage (%)	<20 (Excellent)	Wilcox LV(1955)
	20-40 (Good)	Wilcox LV(1955)
	40-60(Medium)	Wilcox LV(1955)
	60-80 (Doubtful)	Wilcox LV(1955)
	>80 (Unsuitable)	Wilcox LV(1955)
pH	6.5 – 8.4	FAO(2006), BIS-10500(1991), WWF-Pakistan(2007)
BOD(mg/L)	8≤(agricultural irrigation and livestock watering, and industrial cooling waters)	WWF-Pakistan(2007)
DO (mg/L)	>4.0(agricultural irrigation and livestock watering, and industrial cooling waters)	WWF-Pakistan(2007)
Magnesium (mEq/L)	0 – 5	FAO(2006), BIS-10500(1991)
Calcium (mEq/L)	0 – 20	FAO (2006), BIS-10500(1991)
Phosphates(mg/L)	0 – 2	FAO (2006),BIS-10500(1991)
Chloride(mg/L)	≤100	WWF-Pakistan(2007)
Cyanides (mg/L)	≤1.0	WWF-Pakistan(2007)
Fluorides (mg/L)	≤1.0	NAS(1972), WWF-Pakistan (2007)
Nitrate (mg/L)	0-10	FAO(2006), BIS-10500(1991)
Ammonia(mg/L)	0-5	FAO(2006), BIS-10500(1991)
Iron(mg/L)	≤5.0	NAS(1972), WWF-Pakistan(2007)
	2.4-4(Desirable)	Duncan,R.R.,R.N.Carrow, and M.Huck.(2000)
Lithium(mg/L)	≤2.5	NAS(1972), WWF-Pakistan(2007)
Vanadium(mg/L)	≤0.10	NAS(1972), WWF-Pakistan(2007)
Zinc (mg/L)	≤1 (soil pH < 6.5)	Stephanie T.,Andrew P. et al.(2014)
	≤5.0 (soil pH > 6.5)	Stephanie T.,Andrew P. et al.(2014)
	≤2.0	NAS (1972)
	<0.3(Desirable)	Duncan,R.R., R.N.Carrow, and M.Huck.(2000)
Cadmium(mg/L)	≤2.0	WWF-Pakistan(2007)
	≤0.02	Defra (2002)
Copper(mg/L)	≤0.01	WWF-Pakistan(2007)
	≤0.50	Defra (2002)
Arsenic(mg/L)	≤0.20	WWF-Pakistan(2007)
	≤0.04	Defra (2002)
Boron	≤0.10	WWF-Pakistan(2007)
	≤1.0	WWF-Pakistan(2007)
Lead (mg/L)	≤2.0(Desirable)	Duncan,R.R., R.N.Carrow, and M.Huck.(2000)
	0.5 – 6.0	Stephanie T.,Andrew P. et al.(2014)
	≤2.00	Defra (2002)
Cobalt (mg/L)	≤5.0	NAS(1972)
	≤0.1(for Livestock)	WWF-Pakistan(2007)
Chromium (mg/L)	≤0.05	WWF-Pakistan(2007)
Chromium (mg/L)	≤2.00	Defra (2002)
	≤0.10	NAS(1972)

	≤0.01	WWF-Pakistan(2007)
Selenium (mg/L)	≤0.02	Defra (2002), NAS(1972), WWF-Pakistan(2007)
Beryllium (mg/L)	≤0.10	NAS(1972), WWF-Pakistan(2007)
Uranium	≤0.01	Stephanie T.,Andrew P. et al.,2014
Mercury (mg/L)	≤0.01(Livestock)	WWF-Pakistan(2007)
Molybdenum (mg/L)	≤0.03	Defra (2002)
	≤0.01	NAS(1972)
	≤0.01	WWF-Pakistan(2007)
Nickel(mg/L)	≤0.15	Defra (2002)
	≤0.20	NAS(1972)
	≤0.20	WWF-Pakistan(2007)
Manganese (mg/L)	≤0.20	NAS(1972), WWF-Pakistan(2007)
Aluminium(mg/L)	≤5.0	WWF-Pakistan(2007)
Fecal coliforms (CFU/100mL)	≤100	Stephanie T.,Andrew P. et al.,2014
	1000 (agricultural irrigation and livestock watering, and industrial cooling waters)	WWF-Pakistan(2007)
Total coliforms (CFU/100mL)	≤1000	Stephanie T.,Andrew P. et al.,2014

NAS: National Academy of Sciences

II. Safe limits for Electrical Conductivity for Irrigation Water (µmhos/cm at 25°C) (U.S. Salinity Laboratory Staff, 1954)

Nature of soil	Crop growth	Upper permissible safe limit (µmhos / cm at 25°C)
Deep black soil and alluvial soils having clay content more than 30% soils that are fairly to moderately well drained.	Semi-tolerant	1500
	Tolerant	2000
Heavy textured soils having clay contents of 20-30% soils that are well drained internally and have good surface drainage system.	Semi-tolerant	2000
	Tolerant	4000
Medium textured soils having clay 10-20% internally very well drained and having good surface drainage system.	Semi-tolerant	4000
	Tolerant	6000
Light textured soils having clay less than 10% soil that have excellent internally and surface drainage system.	Semi-tolerant	6000
	Tolerant	8000

III. Guidelines for evaluation of quality of irrigation water (U.S. Salinity Laboratory Staff, 1954)

Water class	Sodium (Na %)	Electrical Conductivity at 25°C (µs/cm)	Alkalinity hazards	
			SAR (meq/L)	RSC(meq/L)
Excellent	<20	<250	<10	<1.25
Good	20-40	250-750	10-18	1.25-2.0
Medium	40-60	750-2250	18-26	2.0-2.5
Bad	60-80	2250-4000	>26	2.5-3.0
Very bad	>80	>4000	>26	>3.0

IV. Standards required for Drinking water quality

Parameters	Recommended Value	Source
Organoleptic and Physical Parameters		
Turbidity (NTU)	≤1 (Desirable), ≤5 (Permissible)	BIS-10500(2012)
pH	≤10 6.5 – 8.5	BIS-10500(1991) WHO(2004), BIS-10500(2012)
Taste	Agreeable	BIS-10500(2012)
Odour	Agreeable	BIS-10500(2012)
Colour (Hazen Units)	≤5 (Desirable), ≤15 (Permissible)	BIS-10500(2012)
TDS (mg/L)	≤20 ≤800 ≤1000 ≤500 (Desirable), ≤2000 (Permissible)	WWF-Pakistan(2007) WWF-Pakistan(2007) WHO(2004) BIS-10500(2012)
Temperature	The maximum water temperature change shall not exceed 3C° relative to an upstream control point.	WWF-Pakistan(2007), PCRWR, 2007
Chemical Parameters		
BOD (mg/L)	≤2 ≤3 (for water for requiring treatment before use)	WWF-Pakistan(2007) WWF-Pakistan(2007)
DO (mg/L)	> 6 >4 > 4(for water for requiring treatment before use)	WWF-Pakistan(2007) WHO(2004), BIS-10500(1991) WWF-Pakistan(2007)
Total Hardness (mg/L as CaCO ₃)	≤300 ≤500 ≤200 (Desirable) ≤600 (Permissible)	WWF-Pakistan(2007) WHO(2004) BIS-10500(2012)
Magnesium (mg/L)	≤30 (Desirable), ≤100(Permissible) ≤50	BIS-10500(2012) WHO(2004)
Calcium (mg/L)	≤75 (Desirable)	WHO(2004), BIS-10500(1991)

	≤200 (Permissible)	WHO(2004), BIS-10500(1991)
Alkalinity(mg/L)	≤200(Desirable)	WHO, BIS-10500(1991)
	≤600 (Permissible)	BIS-10500(1991)
Electrical Conductivity (µS / cm)	≤1250	WWF-Pakistan(2007)
	≤1400	WHO(2004)
Bicarbonate (mg/L)	≤200 (Desirable), ≤600 (Permissible)	BIS-10500(1991)
	≤250	WHO(2004)
Sulphates(mg/L)	≤200 (Desirable), ≤400 (Permissible)	BIS-10500(2012)
	≤250	WHO(2004), BIS-10500(1991)
Chloride(mg/L)	≤250 (Desirable)	WHO(2004), BIS-10500(2012),
	≤1000 (Permissible)	WWF-Pakistan(2007)
Sodium (mg/L)	≤200	WHO(2004)
Potassium (mg/L)	≤10	WHO(2004)
Aluminium (mg/L)	≤0.03 (Desirable)	BIS-10500 (1991)
	≤0.2 (Permissible)	WWF-Pakistan(2007)
	≤10	WWF-Pakistan(2007)
Nitrate (mg/L)	≤45	WHO(2004), BIS-10500 (1991)
	≤50	WHO(2004)
	≤45 (Desirable)	BIS-10500 (1991)
	≤100 (Permissible)	BIS-10500 (1991)
Nitrite(mg/L)	≤1	WWF-Pakistan(2007)
NH₃(mg/L)	≤0.5	WHO(2004), BIS-10500(1991)
Arsenic (mg/L)	≤0.05 (Desirable), ≤0.01 (Permissible)	BIS 10500(2012)
	0.01-0.05	USEPA(2006)
Cadmium (mg/L)	≤0.01	BIS-10500 (1991)
	≤0.003	BIS-10500 (2012)
	≤0.005	WWF-Pakistan(2007)
Chromium(mg/L)	≤0.05	BIS-10500 (2012) WWF-Pakistan(2007)
Boron (mg/L)	≤0.5 (Desirable), ≤1 (permissible)	BIS-10500 (2012)
Selenium (mg/L)	≤0.01	BIS-10500(1991), WWF-Pakistan(2007)
Copper(mg/L)	≤0.05 (Desirable)	BIS-10500(1991)
	≤1.5 (permissible)	BIS-10500(1991), WWF-Pakistan(2007)
Iron(mg/L)	≤0.3 (Desirable)	BIS-10500(1991), WWF-Pakistan(2007)
	≤1.0 (Desirable)	BIS-10500(1991)
Lead (mg/L)	≤0.01	USEPA(2006)
	≤0.05	BIS-10500(1991), WWF-Pakistan(2007)
Mercury (mg/L as N)	≤0.002	USEPA(2006)

	≤0.001(Desirable)	BIS-10500(1991), WWF-Pakistan(2007)
Manganese(mg/L)	≤0.1	BIS-10500(1991), WWF-Pakistan(2007)
	≤0.3	BIS-10500(1991)
Molybdenum(mg/L)	≤0.07	BIS-10500 (2012)
Silver (mg/L)	≤0.1	BIS-10500 (2012)
Barium(mg/L)	≤0.1	WWF-Pakistan(2007)
Nickel(mg/L as N)	≤0.1	WWF-Pakistan(2007)
	≤0.02	BIS-10500 (2012)
Zinc(mg/L)	≤5 (Desirable)	BIS-10500(1991), WWF-Pakistan(2007)
	≤15 (Permissible)	BIS-10500(1991)
Chlorine (mg/L)	≤0.2 (Desirable), ≤1 (Permissible)	BIS-10500(2012)
Chloramines(as mg Cl₂/L)	≤4	BIS-10500(2012)
Cyanides (mg/L)	≤0.05	BIS-10500(1991), WWF-Pakistan(2007)
	≤4	USEPA(2006)
Fluorides (mg/L)	≤1 (Desirable) ≤1.5 (Permissible)	BIS-10500(2012)
	≤1.9(Permissible)	BIS-10500(1991)
Trihalomethanes(mg/L):	≤0.1	BIS-10500(2012)
(i). Bromoform		
(ii). Dibromochloromethane	≤0.1	BIS-10500(2012)
(iii). Bromodichloromethane	≤0.06	BIS-10500(2012)
(iv). Chloroform	≤0.2	BIS-10500(2012)
Polychlorinated biphenyls (mg/L)	0.0005	BIS-10500(2012)
Polynuclear aromatic hydrocarbons as PAH(mg/L)	≤0.0001	BIS-10500(2012)
Anionic detergents as MBAS (mg/L)	≤0.2(Desirable)	BIS-10500 (1991), WWF-Pakistan(2007)
	≤1(Permissible)	BIS-10500 (1991)
	≤1(for water requiring treatment before use)	WWF-Pakistan(2007)
Phenolic Compounds as Phenol(mg/L)	≤0.001 (Desirable)	BIS-10500 (1991), WWF-Pakistan(2007)
	≤0.002(Permissible)	BIS-10500 (1991)
	≤0.002(for water requiring treatment before use)	WWF-Pakistan(2007)
Mineral oil and grease (mg/L)	≤0.01(Desirable)	BIS-10500 (1991), WWF-Pakistan(2007)
	≤0.03(Permissible)	WWF-Pakistan(2007)
	≤0.1(for water for requiring treatment before use)	WWF-Pakistan(2007)
Toxic substances and organic pollutants	The waters shall not contain other toxic substances and organic pollutants in quantities that may be detrimental to public health or impair the usefulness of the water as	WWF-Pakistan(2007)

	a source of domestic water supply	
Radioactive Materials		
Alpha emitters (Bq/L)	≤0.1	BIS-10500(2012)
Beta emitters (pci/L)	≤1	
Pesticides (mg/L)		
	≤0.001(permissible)	BIS-10500 (1991)
Alachlor (µg/L)	≤20	BIS-10500(2012)
Atrazine(µg/L)	≤2	BIS-10500(2012)
Aldrin/ Dieldrin (µg/L)	≤0.03	BIS-10500(2012)
Alpha HCH (µg/L)	≤0.01	BIS-10500(2012)
Beta HCH (µg/L)	≤0.04	BIS-10500(2012)
Butachlor (µg/L)	≤125	BIS-10500(2012)
Chlorpyriphos (µg/L)	≤30	BIS-10500(2012)
Delta HCH (µg/L)	≤0.04	BIS-10500(2012)
2,4-Dichlorophen oxyacetic acid (µg/L)	≤30	BIS-10500(2012)
DDT(o,p and p,p-Isomers of DDT,DDE and DDD) (µg/L)	≤1	BIS-10500(2012)
Endosulfan (alpha, beta, and sulphate) (µg/L)	≤0.4	BIS-10500(2012)
Ethion (µg/L)	≤3	BIS-10500(2012)
Gamma-HCH (Lindane) (µg/L)	≤2	BIS-10500(2012)
Isoproturon (µg/L)	≤9	BIS-10500(2012)
Malathion (µg/L)	≤190	BIS-10500(2012)
Methyl parathion (µg/L)	≤0.3	BIS-10500(2012)
Monocrotophos (µg/L)	≤1	BIS-10500(2012)
Phorate (µg/L)	≤2	BIS-10500(2012)
Bacteriological quality		
	≤10	BIS-10500(1991)
Fecal coliforms (MPN/100mL)	≤20	WWF-Pakistan(2007)
	≤1000 (for water requiring treatment before use)	WWF-Pakistan(2007)
	≤10	BIS-10500(1991)
Total coliforms (MPN/100mL)	≤50	WWF-Pakistan(2007)
	≤5000 (for water for requiring treatment before use)	WWF-Pakistan(2007)
	Must not be detectable in any 100ml sample	BIS-10500(2012)
Escherichia Coli (MPN/100mL)	Must not be detectable in any 100ml sample	BIS-10500(2012)

MBAS: Methylene Blue Active Substances

V. Standards required for recreational water quality

Waters for this class are intended to be for primary contact recreation such as bathing, swimming, skin diving, etc.

Parameters	Recommended Value	Source
A. Physical parameters		
Turbidity(NTU)	≤5 (Desirable)	BIS-10500(1991), WWF-Pakistan(2007)
	≤10(Permissible)	BIS-10500(1991)
TDS (mg/L)	≤1000	WWF-Pakistan(2007),
Taste	Agreeable	BIS-10500(1991)
Odour	Unobjectionable	BIS-10500(1991)
Colour (Hazen units)	≤20	WWF-Pakistan(2007),
	≤5(Desirable)	BIS-10500(1991)
	≤25(Permissible)	BIS-10500(1991)
Temperature	The maximum water temperature change shall not exceed 3C° relative to an upstream control point.	WWF-Pakistan(2007),
B. Chemical parameters		
pH	6.5 – 8.5	USEPA(2006),WHO(2003), BIS-10500(1991), WWF-Pakistan(2007)
BOD (mg/L)	≤8	WWF-Pakistan(2007)
DO(mg/L)	≤4	WWF-Pakistan(2007)
Total Hardness (mg/L as CaCO ₃)	≤300	WWF-Pakistan(2007)
	≤200	WHO(2003), BIS-10500(1991)
	≤500	WHO(2003)
	200-600	ISI
	≤300(Desirable)	BIS-10500(1991)
	≤600(Permissible)	BIS-10500(1991)
Magnesium (mg/L)	≤30 Max. IS-10500	WHO(2003), BIS-10500(1991)
	≤50	WHO(2003)
	30-100	ISI Permissible (acceptable)
Calcium (mg/L)	≤75 (Desirable)	WHO(2003), BIS-10500(1991)
	≤200(Permissible)	WHO(2003), BIS-10500(1991)
Alkalinity (mg/L)	≤200(Desirable)	WHO(2003), BIS-10500(1991)
	≤600(Permissible)	BIS-10500(1991)
Electrical Conductivity (µS/cm)	≤1500	WWF-Pakistan(2007)
Sulphates (mg/L)	≤400	WWF-Pakistan(2007)
Chloride (mg/L)	≤250	WHO(2003), BIS-10500(1991)
	≤250 (Desirable)	USEPA(2006), WHO(2003) ; BIS-10500(1991),

	≤1000(Permissible)	WWF-Pakistan(2007)
Sodium (mg/L)	≤200	WHO(2003)
Potassium (mg/L)	≤10	WHO(2003)
Chlorine (mg/L)	≤0.2	BIS-10500(1991)
Cyanides (mg/L)	≤0.05	WWF-Pakistan(2007)
Fluorides (mg/L)	≤1.5	WWF-Pakistan(2007)
Aluminium (mg/L)	≤0.03(Desirable)	BIS-10500 (1991)
	≤0.2(Permissible)	BIS-10500 (1991)
Nitrate (mg/L)	≤10	WWF-Pakistan(2007)
	≤45	WHO(2003), BIS-10500 (1991)
	≤50	WHO(2003)
	≤45 (Desirable)	BIS-10500 (1991)
	≤100(Permissible)	BIS-10500 (1991)
Nitrite (mg/L)	≤1	WWF-Pakistan(2007)
NH₃ (mg/L as N)	≤1	WWF-Pakistan(2007)
Arsenic (mg/L)	≤0.05	BIS-10500(1991), WWF-Pakistan(2007)
Cadmium(mg/L)	≤0.01	WWF-Pakistan(2007)
Chromium (mg/L)	≤0.05	WWF-Pakistan(2007)
Copper (mg/L)	≤1.5	WWF-Pakistan(2007)
Boron (mg/L)	≤1	WWF-Pakistan(2007)
Iron(mg/L)	≤0.3(Desirable)	BIS-10500(1991), WWF-Pakistan(2007)
	≤1.0(Desirable)	BIS-10500(1991)
Lead (mg/L)	≤0.01	USEPA(2006), WWF-Pakistan(2007)
Mercury (mg/L as N)	≤0.001	BIS-10500(1991), WWF-Pakistan(2007)
Manganese(mg/L)	≤0.1	BIS-10500(1991), WWF-Pakistan(2007)
	≤0.3	BIS-10500(1991)
Selenium (mg/L)	≤0.05	WWF-Pakistan(2007)
Barium (mg/L)	≤1.0	WWF-Pakistan(2007)
Nickel(mg/L as N)	≤0.1	WWF-Pakistan(2007)
Zinc(mg/L)	≤15 (Desirable)	BIS-10500(1991), WWF-Pakistan(2007)
Anionic detergents as MBAS (mg/L)	≤0.5	WWF-Pakistan(2007)
Phenolic Compounds as Phenol(mg/L)	≤0.01	WWF-Pakistan(2007)
Oil and grease (mg/L)	≤2.0	WWF-Pakistan(2007)
Pesticides (mg/L)	≤0.001(permissible)	BIS-10500 (1991)
Toxic substances and organic pollutants	The waters shall not contain toxic substances and organic pollutants.	WWF-Pakistan(2007)
C. Biological parameters		
Fecal coliforms (MPN/100mL)	≤200	WWF-Pakistan(2007)
Total coliforms (MPN/100mL)	≤1000	WWF-Pakistan(2007)

Appendix 2: Schematic representation of the anatomical structure of freshwater Zooplanktons.**Figure 1: Schematic representation of Rotifera**

Source : http://wgbis.ces.iisc.ernet.in/energy/water/paper/Tr-115/app1_list_clip_image002.jpg

Figure 2: Schematic representation of Ostracoda

Source : https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Rishiram_Ramanan/publication/234135702/figure/fig15/AS:668621491691540@1536423194828/Ventral-view-of-cyclopid_W640.jpg

Figure 3: Dorsal view of Copepoda (Calanoid and cyclopid)

Source : http://wgbis.ces.iisc.ernet.in/energy/water/paper/Tr-115/app1_list_clip_image002_0001.jpg

Figure 4: Ventral view of cyclopoid

Source : http://wgbis.ces.iisc.ernet.in/energy/water/paper/Tr-115/app1_list_clip_image002_0002.jpg

Figure 5: Schematic representation of Cladocera

Source : http://wgbis.ces.iisc.ernet.in/energy/water/paper/Tr-115/app1_list_clip_image002_0000.jpg

**Legend for the anatomical structure of freshwater zooplanktons
(Figure 1-5)**

S.No	Structure name	S.No	Structure name
1.	Eye	37.	Optical ganglion
2.	Head/Cephalic segment	38.	Post abdomen
3.	Antennae	39.	Caudal/Furcal rami
4.	Antennules	40.	Genital segment
5.	Ovary	41.	Metasomal wing
6.	Ciliary wrath	42.	Metasomal spine
7.	Tactile style	43.	Caudal setae
8.	Gangilion	44.	Maxillule
9.	Styligerous prominence	45.	Maxilla
10.	Mastax	46.	Maxilliped
11.	Trophi	47.	Mandible
12.	Gastric glands	48.	Maxillary gland
13.	Stomach	49.	Maxillary gland
14.	Longitudinal muscle	50.	Mandibular setae
15.	Oviduc	51.	4 th leg
16.	Lateral canal	52.	6 th leg
17.	Contractile vessel	53.	5 th leg
18.	Sperms	54.	Ovisac
19.	Intestine	55.	Spermatheca
20.	Rectum	56.	Telson
21.	Cloaca	57.	Food
22.	Foot glands	58.	Furca
23.	Foot	59.	Dorsal skin
24.	Toe	60.	Subterminal claw
25.	Fornix	61.	Terminal claw
26.	Rostrum	62.	Terminal setae
27.	Cervical depression	63.	Thoracic leg
28.	Heart	64.	Branchial setae of maxillae
29.	Shell gland	65.	Branchial plate of mandible
30.	Cerebral gangilion	66.	Mandibular projection
31.	Legs	67.	Mandibular pulp
32.	Claw	68.	Natatory setae of antennae and antennules
33.	Post abdominal setae/process	69.	Labrum
34.	Posterior spine	70.	Mouth
35.	Brood chamber	71.	Labium
36.	Ocellus		

Appendix 3: Schematic representation of Taxonomic classification of freshwater Zooplanktons.

Source: http://wgbis.ces.iisc.ernet.in/energy/water/paper/Tr-115/app3_clip_image001.gif

Source: http://wgbis.ces.iisc.ernet.in/energy/water/paper/Tr-115/app3_clip_image001_0000.gif

Appendix 4: Taxonomic Classification of Freshwater Zooplankton.

TAXA	ROTIFERA	CLADOCERA	COPEPODA	OSTRACODA
Kingdom	Animalia	Animalia	Animalia	Animalia
Phylum	Rotifera Triploblastic, bilateral, unsegmented blastocoelomates. Body divided into head, trunk and foot. Locomotion by the means of coronary cilia. With protonephridia for osmoregulation. No special organs for circulatory or gas exchange system.	Arthropoda Bilateral, triploblastic coelomates. Body segmented into head, abdomen and post abdomen. Locomotion by the means of antennae. Circulatory system is open, dorsal heart present. Gas exchange through body or gill like structure. Males present, both sexual and asexual reproduction.	Arthropoda Bilateral, triploblastic coelomates. Body segmented into head, abdomen and post abdomen. Locomotion by the means of antennae. Circulatory system is open, dorsal heart present. Gas exchange through body or gill like structure. Males present, both sexual and asexual reproduction.	Arthropoda Bilateral, triploblastic coelomates. Body segmented into head, abdomen and post abdomen. Locomotion by the means of antennae. Circulatory system is open, dorsal heart present. Gas exchange through body or gill like structure. Males present, both sexual and asexual reproduction.
Subphylum	-	Crustacea body divided into head and trunk, which may be divided into thorax and abdomen. Head has eye, antennules, antennae, mandibles and maxillae. Antennae uniramous or biramous. Head is surrounded by carapace except for copepods. Both ocelli and compound eye occur in all taxa. Excretion by maxillary glands and antennal glands.	Crustacea body divided into head and trunk, which may be divided into thorax and abdomen. Head has eye, antennules, antennae, mandibles and maxillae. Antennae uniramous or biramous. Head is surrounded by carapace except for copepods. Both ocelli and compound eye occur in all taxa. Excretion by maxillary glands and antennal glands.	Crustacea Body divided into head and trunk which may be divided into thorax and abdomen. Head has eye, antennules, antennae, mandibles and maxillae. Antennae uniramous or biramous. Head is surrounded by carapace except for copepods. Both ocelli and compound eye occur in all taxa. Excretion by maxillary glands and antennal glands.
Class	Digononta Has paired ovaries no lorica or tubes Monogononta Lorica may be present or absent. Benthic, free swimming and sessile forms. Females with single ovary and a vitellarium.	Branchiopoda Limbs usually phyllopodous. Antennules simple and reduced. Mandible without palp. Maxillae reduced or absent.	Copepoda No carapace. Antennules uniramous. The body has nine appendages usually. Six pairs of biramous limbs. Presence of caudal rami. Twenty genera have been reported in India.	Ostracoda Carapace forms a bivalved shell. Antennules uniramous. Not more than five pairs of limbs behind mandibles. One to three pairs of limbs before mandible.
Order	The class Digononta has 2 orders, namely : Bdelloidea and Seisonidea , but both the orders are primarily benthic and epizoic forms. The class Monogononta has 3 orders namely: Ploimida , Gnesiostrocha and Collothecaceae .	Cladocera Carapace large bivalved enclosing trunk but not head. Antennae large biramous used for swimming. Eyes sessile, ocellus present. Trunk limbs 4 to 6 pairs.	The copepoda has three orders namely Calanoida , Cyclopoida and Harpacticoida .	The Class Ostracoda has a order Podocopa The order Podocopa consists of five families namely Cyprididae, Cyclocypridae, Notodromadidae, Eucandonidae and Ilyocyprididae. In India, 61 species of Ostracods have been reported.

<p style="text-align: center;">Family</p>	<p>There are 26 families reported in India:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Epiphanidae This family has 3 genus namely: <i>Epiphanes</i>, <i>Mikrocodides</i>, <i>Liliferotrocha</i> • Brachionidae This family has 5 genus namely: <i>Brchionus</i>, <i>Keratella</i>, <i>Platonus</i>, <i>Anuraeopsis</i> <i>Platyas</i>, <i>Notholca</i>. • Euchlanidae The family has 6 genus namely: <i>Euchlanis</i>, <i>Pseudoeuchlanis</i>, <i>Dipleuchlanis</i>, <i>Tripleuchlanis</i>, <i>Beauchampiella</i>, <i>Diplois</i> • Mytilinidae This family has 1 genus <i>Mytilina</i> which has 5 species: <i>Mytilina ventralis</i>, <i>Mytilina ventralis brevispina</i>, <i>Mytilina ventralis macracantha</i>, <i>Mytilina mucronata</i>, <i>Mytilina bisulcata</i>. • Trichotridae The family supports 2 genus namely: <i>Trichotria</i>, <i>Macrochaetus</i>. • Colurellidae The family has 3 genus: <i>Colurella</i>, <i>Lepadella</i>, <i>Squatinella</i>. • Lecanidae This family has the single largest genus: <i>Lecane</i> among rotifera with 70 species. • Proalidae This family has single genus with two species namely: <i>Proales decipiens</i> and <i>Proales indirae</i>. • Notommatidae The family is represented by five genus namely: <i>Cephalodella</i>, <i>Esophora</i>, <i>Notommata</i>, <i>Itura</i>, <i>Taphro camp</i> • Scarididae The family has a single 	<p>About 8 families are reported in India:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sididae Trunk and thoracic limbs covered by valves. Body length much greater than the height. Head clearly delimited. Antennae not branched. • Bosminidae 5 to 6 pairs of thoracic limbs, dissimilar. Antennae fused with rostrum. • Chydoridae Antennae not fused with rostrum. Dorsal and ventral rami of antennae three segmented. • Daphnidae Dorsal ramus of antanne 3 and ventral ramus 4 segmented. Antennules immovable and short. • Moinidae Antennae movable and mostly long. Antennules situated in the posterior side of the head. • Macrothricidae Antennule in the anterior side of the head. • Leptodoridae Trunk and thoracic limbs not covered by valves. Head elongated. • Podonidae Trunk and thoracic limbs not covered by valves. Head short. Caudal appendage very short. 	<p>The order calanoida has a single family: Diaptomidae Endopodite of P1 two segmented, endopodite of P2-P4 three segmented and P5 with endopodite in both sexes. Some of the genera reported in India include, <i>Phyllodiaptomus</i>, <i>Heliodiaptomus</i>, <i>Paradiaptomus</i>.....</p> <p>The order cyclopoida has a single family: • Cyclopidae Mandibular palp not well developed, reduced to one segment with three setae. Some of the genera reported from India include, <i>Macrocyclops</i>, <i>Paracyclops</i>, <i>Microcyclops</i>.....</p> <p>The order Harpacticoida has a single family: • Cletodidae Harpacticoid are usually benthic but rarely planktonic. Tapering body with each segment distinct. Female genital segment with a suture dorsally. Maxilliped prehensile. Freshwater planktonic species reported from India include <i>Cletocampus albuquerquensis</i>.....</p>	<p>The order Podocopa has five families: Cyprididae, Cyclocyprididae, Notodromadidae, Eucandondidae and lilyocyprididae.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cyprididae This has 4 subfamilies namely :Cypridinae, Cyprettinae, Stenocyprinae, Cypridosinae. • Cyclocyprididae This family has 1 species namely <i>Physocypria fufuracea</i> . • Notodromadidae This family has 2 genera: <i>Centropypris</i> and <i>Indiacypris</i>. • Eucandondidae. This family has a single species <i>Canadonopsis putealis</i>. • Lilyocyprididae. This family has single species : <i>llyocypris nagamalaiensis</i>
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<p>species namely <i>Scardium longicaudatum</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Linidae The family has a single genus <i>Lindia</i> • Trichocercidae The family has a single genus with 21 species. • Asplanchnidae The family has 4 genus <i>Asplanchna</i>, <i>Asplanchnopus</i>. The genus <i>Asplanchna</i> are predatory rotifers. • Synchaetidae The family has 2 genus namely: <i>Polyarthra</i> and <i>Synchaeta</i> with 6 and 5 species respectively. • Gastropodidae The family has 2 genus <i>Ascotrocha</i> and <i>Gastropus</i>. • Dicranophoridae The family has single genus with 5 species namely: <i>Dicranophorus dolerus</i> <i>Dicranophorus tegillus</i> <i>Dicranophorus epicharis</i> <i>Dicranophorus forcipatus</i> <i>Dicranophorus lutkeni</i> <p>Order Gnesiotrocha</p> <p>This order has 6 families:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Floscularidae The family has 5 genus: <i>Limnias</i>, <i>Floscularia</i>, <i>Beauchampia</i>, <i>Lacinularia</i>, <i>Sinantharina</i> • Conochilidae The family has single genus with five species: <i>Conochilus arboreus</i>, <i>Conochilus ossuarius</i>, <i>Conochilus hippocripis</i>, <i>Conochilus madurai</i> <i>Conochilus natans</i>. • Hexarthridae The family has 1 genus with four species: <i>Hexarthra intermedia</i>, <i>Hexarthra mira</i>, <i>Hexarthra Bulgaria</i>, <i>Hexarthra fennica</i>. • Filinidae The family has 1 genus with 5 species: <i>Filinia longiseta</i>, <i>Filinia opoloensis</i>, <i>Filinia</i> 			
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	<p><i>pejleri</i>, <i>Filinia cornuta</i>, <i>Filinia terminalis</i>.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Testudinellidae The family has 1 genus <i>Testudinella</i> with 6 species. • Trichosphaeridae The family has 1 species namely <i>Horaella brehmi</i> <p>Order Collothecaceae: The order has 1 family:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collothecidae The family has 2 genus with 4 species : <i>Cupelopagis vorax</i>, <i>Collotheca ornate</i> , <i>Collotheca trilobata</i>, <i>Collotheca mutabilis</i>. <p>Order Bdelloida: The order has 1 family with 18 species.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Philodinidae The family has 4 genus: <i>Rotaria</i>, <i>Pseudoembata</i>, <i>Philodina</i> and <i>Macrotrachela</i> 			
Genus		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sididae The family consists of 4 genus: <i>Sida</i>, <i>Pseudosida</i>, <i>Latonopsis</i>, <i>Diaphanosoma</i>. • Daphnidae. The family has 5 genus :<i>Ceriodaphnia</i>, <i>Daphnia</i>,<i>Daphniopsis</i>, <i>S capholeberis</i>, <i>Simocephalus</i>. • Moinidae The family has 2 genus :<i>Moina</i>,<i>Moinodaphnia</i>. • Bosminidae The family has 2genera :<i>Bosmina</i>,<i>Bosminopsis</i>. • Macrothricidae The family has 4 genus :<i>Macrothrix</i>, <i>Echinisca</i>, <i>Streblocerus</i>,<i>Ilyocryptus</i>. • Chydoridae This family has two subfamily: Eurycercinae,Aloninae <p>e: ✓ Eurycercinae</p> <p>The subfamily has 4 genus: <i>Eurycercus</i>, <i>Pleuroxus</i>, <i>Alonella</i>, <i>Chydorus</i>.</p> <p>✓ Aloninae</p>		

		<p>The subfamily has 10 genus: <i>Alona</i>, <i>Acroperus</i>, <i>Camptocerus</i>, <i>Graptoleberis</i>, <i>Leydigia</i>, <i>Biapertura</i>, <i>Oxyurella</i>, <i>Kurzia</i>, <i>Euryalona</i>, <i>Indialona</i>.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Leptodoridae <p>This family has a single genus <i>Leptodora</i></p>		
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Source: Ramachandra et al., 2006

Appendix 5: Basic taxonomic differences among the freshwater Zooplanktons community

ROTIFERA	CLADOCERA	COPEPODA	OSTRACODA
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Body divided into head, trunk and abdomen. • Locomotion by the means of coronal cilia, which gives them the name wheel bearers. • With protonephridia for osmoregulation. • Reproduction by parthenogenesis. • No special organs for circulatory or gas exchange system. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A pair of biramous antennae used for swimming gives them the name cladocera. • Carapace large bivalved enclosing the trunk but not the head. • Eyes sessile, ocellus present. • Trunk limbs 4 to 6 pairs. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No carapace • Antennules uniramous. • The body has nine appendages usually. • Six pairs of biramous limbs. • Presence of caudal rami. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Carapace forms a bivalved shell. • Antennules uniramous. • Not more than five pairs of limbs behind mandible. • One to three pairs of limbs before mandibles.

Source: Ramachandra et al., 2006

Appendix 6: Identification Keys for biological organisms

Appendix 6.1: Identification Keys for phytoplankton population: a large file available online:

1. [http://www.kaowarsom.be/documents/MEMOIRES_VERHANDELINGEN/Sciences_naturelles_medicales/Nat.Sc.\(NS\)_T.23,2_MPAWENAYO,%20B._Le_s%20eaux%20de%20la%20plaine%20de%20la%20Rusizi%20\(Burundi\)-%20les%20milieux,%20la%20flore%20et%20la%20v%C3%A9g%C3%A9tation%20algales_1996.PDF](http://www.kaowarsom.be/documents/MEMOIRES_VERHANDELINGEN/Sciences_naturelles_medicales/Nat.Sc.(NS)_T.23,2_MPAWENAYO,%20B._Le_s%20eaux%20de%20la%20plaine%20de%20la%20Rusizi%20(Burundi)-%20les%20milieux,%20la%20flore%20et%20la%20v%C3%A9g%C3%A9tation%20algales_1996.PDF)
2. <http://nio.org/userfiles/file/biology/Phytoplankton-manual.pdf>
3. http://oceandatacenter.ucsc.edu/home/outreach/PhytoID_fullset.pdf

Appendix 6.2: Identification Keys for fish species: a large file available online:

1. <file:///C:/Users/HP/Desktop/2017-Lamb-W.-Minnesota-Fish-Taxonomic-Key.pdf>
2. <http://bi.chm-cbd.net/chm-burundais/pfinstitut/direction-des-eaux-de-la-peche-et-de-l-aquaculture/projets-et-realisation/documents-de-politiques-et-de-strategies/poisson-du-burundi-lexique-des-noms-en-kirundi>

Appendix 6.3: Identification Keys for zooplanktons commonly occurring in freshwater.

I. ROTIFERA
Class: Monogononta
Order: Ploimida, Flosulariceae and Collothecaceae
i. Order: Ploimida
1. Family: Epiphanidae
Lorica absent, body transparent, sometimes sacciform with true tufts of cilia. Trophi malleate type.
Genus: <i>Epiphanes</i>
a. <i>Epiphanes clavulata</i>: The body expands dorsally towards posterior, ventrally straight. Corona has five styligerous prominences each with fur like arrangement of slender styles. Antennae dorsal, gonod ribbon like and bent as a horseshoe. Foot short with small toe.
b. <i>Epiphanes macrourus</i>: Body saccate with three tufts of cilia. Dorsal antennae present. Foot long and segmented with short toes.
Genus: <i>Mikrocodides</i>
a. <i>Microcodies chlaena</i>: Body cylindrical, gradually narrowing posteriorly. Foot broad, segmented with a prominent spur on the dorsal side near the toe. Toe single, broad and tapering into a point. The organism looks like a shell.
Genus: <i>Liliferotrocha</i>
a. <i>Liliferotrocha subtilis</i>: Body elongate and cylindrical. Dorsal antennae prominent. Toes slender, short, triangular and pointed. The body as such cannot be divided into head trunk and foot. Foot is not prominent and body irregular in shape.
2. Family: Brachionidae
Mostly stout rotifers, planktonic, lorica heavy and dorso-ventrally flattened, often carrying visible spines or projections or ringed foot. Trophi malleate type. The oral opening is funnel like in the buccal field with a simple circumapical band of cilia. Corona lacks hood or lamellae. The body is somewhat rounded in shape with most of the members of the family.

Genus: Anuraeopsis

a. *Anuraeopsis fissa*: Lorica with two plates, dorsal and ventral with lateral sulci. Dorsal plate arched and ventral plate flat. The foot part is lobe shaped with no prominent toe. Prominent dorsal antennae.

Genus: Brachionus

a. *Brachionus angularis*: Lorica stippled, with two very small projections in the occipital margin. Posterior spines absent. No foot part and toes.

b. *Brachionus aculeatus flateralis*: Lorica stippled with four occipital spines of equal length. Posterior lateral spine apart with tooth like projections on the inner side.

c. *Brachionus budapestinensis var punctatus*: Lorica stiff and stippled with four occipital spines of which median are longer than lateral.

d. *Brachionus caudatus*: Lorica with four occipital spines, the lateral slightly longer than the median. Posterior spines are long. The body is slightly oval in shape. The occipital spines are small.

e. *Brachionus diversicornis*: Lorica is elongated (different from other *Brachionus* species) with four occipital spines with lateral spines much longer than the median. Right posterior spine is longer than left. Foot long and toes with characteristic claws.

f. *Brachionus forficula f typicus-urawensis*: Lorica with four occipital spines. Posterior spines stippled and bowed inwards with characteristic knee like swellings at the inner side. This species is similar to *B. aculeatus* in the occipital spine region but differs in shape of body and posterior spines.

g. *Brachionus calyciflorua*: Lorica flexible, smooth. Anterior margin with stout spines, broad at the base and with rounded tips. Median spines slightly longer than the laterals. Posterior spines absent. This species has many polymorphic forms, which have posterior spines.

h. *Brachionus falcatus*: Anterior dorsal margin with six equal spines, the medians long and curved out ward at the end. Posterior spines very long, bent inwards and in some forms almost touch each other at their tips.

Genus: Plationus

a. *Plationus patulas*: Occipital margin with six species of which medians slightly longer than the outer ventral margin with four spines. Posterior lateral spines are longer than the median.

Genus: Keratella

a. *Keratella cochlearis*: Lorica with strong median spine. Dorsum with characteristic median longitudinal line, with symmetrically arranged plaques on either side. Foot is present with toes.

b. *Keratella procurva*: Three median plaques on the dorsum, the posterior one is pentagonal and terminates in a short median line. Posterior margin of lorica is narrower than the anterior. Posterior spines are short and sub equal and sometimes absent. The median spines on the occipital part are longer

than lateral spines.

c. *Keratella quadrata*: Three median plaques on the dorsal side of the lorica, the posterior one has a common border with posterior margin of the lorica. The posterior spines are sub equal. The body is segmented into polygonal shapes.

Genus: *Notholca*

a. *Notholca lebis*: Lorica oval, dorsoventrally flat with six spines at occipital margin, the medians and laterals of same length. Posterior end of lorica with broad blunt process. Posterior margin truncated.

Genus: *Platyas*

a. *Platyas quadricornis*: Lorica firm, stippled, dorsoventrally compressed with regular patterns of facets. Occipital margin with two stout spines having truncated ends. Posterior spines equal in length. At the posterior end there is an antennae like structure. Body is rounded in shape.

3. Family: *Euchlanidae*

Body dorso-ventrally flattened with thin lorica, usually lacking any projections. Two prominent toes are present.

Genus: *Euchlanis*

a. *Euchlanis dialatata*: Lorica with dorsal and ventral plates with longitudinal sulci. Dorsal plate with 'U' shaped notch posteriorly. Mastax with four club shaped teeth on each uncus. Foot slender and two jointed. Toes blade-like and fusiform.

b. *Euchlanis brahmae*: Body truncated anteriorly and rounded behind, triradiate in cross-section. Dorsal plate laterally produced into flanges and with a dorsal median keel extending its entire length. Posterior notch absent. Ventral plate absent, but a thin membrane joins dorso-laterally. Mastax with four clubbed shaped teeth on each uncus. Foot two-jointed. Toes slender parallel sided tapering into points and one-third of the length of the dorsal plate.

Genus: *Dipleuchlanis*

a. *Dipleuchlanis propatula*: Lorica oval, dorsal plate is concave and smaller than the ventral. Both the plates have shallow sinuses at the anterior margin. Toes long, parallel sided and ending in points.

Genus: *Tripleuchlanis*

a. *Tripleuchlanis plicata*: Dorsal plate of lorica with emargination posteriorly. Ventral plate is of same size as the dorsal. Lateral sulci separated by cuticular flange giving bellow like folds laterally. Trophi malleate type with six opposing teeth on each incus, Foot glands long including a pair of accessories. Foot three jointed, first joint covered by cuticular plate. Toes short. Lorica has an ornamented pattern with core shaped foot.

Genus: *Euchlanis*

a. *Euchlanis dialatata*: Lorica with dorsal and ventral plates with longitudinal

sulci. Dorsal plate with 'U' shaped notch posteriorly. Mastax with four club shaped teeth on each uncus. Foot slender and two jointed. Toes blade-like and fusiform.

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Genus: *Pseudoeuchlanis*

a. *Pseudoeuchlanis longipedis*: Dorsal plate of lorica with anterior margin raised in the middle into small non-retractile semicircular plate and without a notch in posterior end. Ventral side is membranous, lateral sulci absent. Foot slender. Long ending in points and three-fourth length of dorsal plate. Trophi malleate, six slender club-shaped teeth on each uncus. Stomach gastric gland and foot glands present.

4. Family: Mytilinidae

Body stout and laterally compressed. In some species, often ringed lorica, cylindrical. Foot with indistinct segments.

Genus: *Mytilina*

a. *Mytilina ventralis*: Body cylindrical, lorica firm with dorsal ridges. Anterior end of the lorica stippled and with curved short spines at the margin, posteriorly with single dorsal and two ventral spines of equal length in the typical form. Foot indistinctly segmented and toes ending in blunt points

5. Family: Trichotridae

Body stout, lorica stiff and stippled, foot with triangular spines in some species. Toes slender and long.

Genus: *Trichotria*

a. *Trichotria tetractis*: Antero lateral margins pointed with the spiny projections. Dorsum stiff, stippled and with usual plates and ridges. Foot joints also stippled. Penultimate foot segment with air of triangular spines. Toes slender, long and ending in points.

6. Family: Collurellidae

Head of these animals in some cases has a semicircular, nonretractable, transparent hood like extension. Lateral eyespot present. In some species, one or two very long spines in the midline of the back are present. One or two very long spines in the midline of the back are present.

Genus: *Colurella*

a. *Colurella bicuspidate*: Lorica with two lateral plates, like mussel shell, smooth and laterally compressed. Lorical plates join an abdominal area leaving long openings near anterior and posterior ends. Foot jointed and toes small and pointed.

Genus: *Lepadella*

a. *Lepadella acuminata*: Lorica oval in shape with a pointed projection at the posterior end. Toes small, narrow and pointed.

7. Family: Lecanidae

Dorso-ventrally flattened, more or less rigid lorica, and divided into dissimilar dorsal and ventral plates connected by a soft sulcus. Mouth opening is not funnel shaped in the buccal field. Foot protrudes through an opening in the ventral plate carrying one or two long toes, in some partially fused toes.

Genus: *Lecane*

a. *Lecane papuana*: Lorica sub-circular, anterior dorsal margin straight and ventral with 'V' shaped sinus. Ventral plate slightly narrower than the dorsal. Second foot joint robust. Toes two, slender, parallel sided ending in claws with basal spicule.

8. Family: Notammatidae

Littoral. Trophi virgate and sometimes asymmetric. Body slender, elongated and soft. Corona is characterized by ventrally tilted buccal field. A small apical field and thin, usually large retractable ciliated ears. Foot short and stout, toes stubby.

Genus: *Cephadella*

a. *Cephalodella catellina*: Body transparent and gibbous. Lateral clefts of lorica parallel sided. Foot small and posterior to the projecting abdomen. Toes short, nearly straight, tapering into acute points.

b. *Notommata copeus*: Body elongate and transparent. Head, neck and abdomen marked by transverse folds. Corona projects as bluntly pointed chin. Tail is characteristic with conical projection ending with blunt point. Toes slender and conical, foot glands long and club shaped. Dorsal antennae stout

and long. Trophi asymmetrical, the left prevails over the right. Manubrium long and curved inwards. Stomach is seen distinctly.

9. Family: *Asplanchnidae*

Cuticle thin and delicate, body sac like or pear or conical shaped. Sometimes wing like side appendages present, trophi incudate, corona reduced to a circumapical band.

Genus: *Asplanchna*

a. *Asplanchna brightwelli*: Body large, saccate and transparent. Intestine, foot and toes are absent. Trophi incudate with rami having horn like projections at outer margins of the base and inner spine at the middle.

10. Family: *Synchaetidae*

Trophi modified virgate or virgate, complex pair of hypopharyngeal muscles sometimes present. Saclike or conical or bell shaped, transparent and soft body.

Genus: *Polyarthra*

a. *Polyarthra indica*: Body illoricate and little squarish. Four groups of lateral paddles inserted dorsally and ventrally in the neck region. Each group with three paddles of equal length extending beyond the posterior end of the body. Accessory pair of ventral paddles present between ventral bundles.

ii. Order: *Flosulariceae*

1. Family: *Hexarthridae*

Body transparent and conical, carries six heavily muscled arm like appendages tipped with feathery setae.

Genus: *Hexarthra*

a. *Hexarthra intermedia*: Body large, ventral arm with one pair of hooks and eight filaments. Unicellular five teeth, lower lip and foot are absent. Indistinct antennae on the dorsal side below the corona. Corona is rounded structure surrounded by cilia. The right arm is longer than the left.

2. Family: *Filiniidae*

Pelagic, body delicate, saclike, three or four appendages present, which can be long spines or stout thorns.

Genus: *Filinia*

a. *Filinia longiseta*: Body oval and transparent with long anterior skipping and a posterior spine on the ventral side. Spine not bulged, foot absent. The body is segmented into head and trunk.

3. Family: *Testudinellidae*

Lorica thin, dorso-ventrally flattened, round or shield like armour, body transparent. In some species foot is absent.

Genus: *Testudinella*

a. *Testudinella mucronata*: Lorica nearly circular, slightly stippled and anterior dorsal margin with a blunt tooth like projection. Foot opening ventral

and at one-third distance from the posterior end. Foot is distinctly segmented with toes.

iii. Order: Collothecaceae

1. Family: Collothecidae

Almost entirely sessile, these rotifers have an expanded funnel shaped anterior end and live mostly in a gelatinous case, attached to the substratum by a long foot and disc. The funnel may cause a variable number of scalloped lobes that are studded with bristles, setae or cilia.

Genus: Collotheca

a. *Collotheca ornate*: Corona with five short blunt lobes arranged pentagonally with long cilia. Posterior part covered by transparent long gelatinous case. Hold fast short. The body narrows down posteriorly into a long tail portion.

II. CLADOCERA

1. Family: Sididae

Genus: *Diaphanosoma*

Head is large, without rostrum and ocellus. Antennules are small and truncated. Dorsal ramus of antennae is two segmented. Post abdomen is without anal spine and claw with three basal spines.

2. Family: Daphnidae

Antennules are small, immobile or rudimentary. Antennae are long and cylindrical. Dorsal ramus consists of 4 segments and 3 ventral segments. Post abdomen distinctly set off from the body, usually more or less compressed and always with anal spines. Claws are mostly denticulate or pectinate. This family consists of five pairs of legs and first two pairs are prehensile and without branchial lamellae.

Genus: *Ceriodaphnia*

Body forms are rounded or oval in shape. Valves oval or round to sub-quadrangle and usually ending posteriorly, sharp spine present. Head small and depressed. Antennules are small and not freely movable.

3. Family: Moinidae

Moinids are characterized by their head with a pair of long and thin cigarette shaped antennules. These arise from ventral surface of the head. Most species have hairs on head region or on shell surface. Ocellus is usually absent. Post abdomen has single row of teeth with no marginal spine.

Genus: *Moina*

Body is thick and heavy. Valves are thin, reticulated or striated. Antennules are large and movable: they originate from the flat surface of the head. Eye is located in the center of the head. Ocellus is rarely present. Post abdomen with bident tooth and 3-16 featured teeth is present.

4. Family: Bosminidae

Body is short and usually oval or rounded in outline. Antennules are large and immovably fixed to head. They have no ocellus, abdominal process consists of six pairs of legs.

Genus: *Bosmina*

Body is usually transparent. Antennules are almost parallel to each other. Antennae with 3 or 4 segmented rami. Post abdomen almost quadrate.

5. Family: Chydoridae

Body is generally oval in shape. Head is completely enclosed with in carapace. Antennules are one segmented and generally not extending beyond the tip of the rostrum. Antennae are short and consist of 3 segmented rami. Post abdomen consists of anal spines and lateral setae.

Subfamily: Chydorinae

Width of the body generally greater than the length. Head pores are separated and situated in the median line of head shield. Anus situated in proximal part of post abdomen.

Genus: *Pleuroxus*

Rostrum is long and pointed. Ocellus is smaller than eye. Post abdominal claws consists of two basal spines.

Subfamily: Aloninae

Head has two or three head pores situated in median line of head with two small pores located at either side. Claws consist of single basal spine or sometimes without basal spines.

Genus: *Alona*

Body subquadrate in outline. Values are rectangular and marked with lines. Three main connected head pores are situated at the median line of the head shield. Rostrum is short and blunt. Anus is situated in proximal part of post abdomen.

III. COPEPODA

i. Order: Calanoida

1. Family: Diaptomidae

Endopodite of P1 two segmented, endopodite of P2-P4 three segmented and P5 with endopodite in both sexes.

ii. Order: Cyclopoida

2. Family: Cyclopoidae

Mandibular palp not well developed, reduced to one segment with three setae.

Source: Ramachandra et al., 2006

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3.	Name of Research Scholar	Lambert Niyoyitungiye
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5.	Name of Degree	Ph.D.
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14.	File Format of thesis and accompanying material, if any (PDF, MPEG etc.)	PDF

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